

Swedish Institute for Social Research

ENGLISH CODEBOOK

Level of Living Survey

2000

This code book includes the variables in the data set by December 2010

TABLE EXPLANATION

1	2		3
X619	GROSS SALARY PER HOUR		jfr Y472, jfr U443, jfr V727, jfr W650
	4	Gross salary in SEK per hour, calculated by adding X611 - X618 converted into hourly wage by using X602. This variable is divided into categories.	
		30-39	3 0,1
		40-49	5 0,2
		50-59	14 0,5
		60-69	62 2,1
		70-79	192 6,4
	5	80-89	477 15,9
		90-99	525 17,6
		100-199	1572 52,6
		200-299	108 3,6
		300-399	24 0,8
		400-499	5 0,2
		500-599	2 0,1
		800-899	1 0,0
		1000-1999	1 0,0
		Total	2991
		9999 No answer	133
		Not employed last week	2018
			5142
		Mean value	116,46
		Standard deviation	55,37
			8
			9

- Variable number.** Every variable has a serial number, which can be used as identification when processing data. Not all numbers from X1 to X1154 exist.
- Variable name.**
- References** to corresponding variables in LNU68, LNU74, LNU81 and LNU91.
Jfr (compare) means that the variable (or question) doesn't have exactly the same construction in the other surveys. Note that the possible answers can be different even if the question that the variable is based on is identical for all years.
- The exact wording of the question** and/or an explanation of the construction of the variable and selection, if any (i.e. information on who the table is valid for).
- The code**, that in this example equals kronor per hour. Some variables, like this one, are divided into categories. Note that the categories can be of different sizes. If the code equals a possible answer (e.g. 1=YES), this is stated.
- Number of respondents.**

7. **Percentage** is calculated based on the number of respondents. Percent is not calculated for decline and the like.
8. The category that is **not selected** and how large this is.
9. **Mean value and Standard deviation.** The Mean value and the Standard deviations for variables divided in categories are calculated based on actual values and not interpolated medians.

VARIABLE LIST

Variable number	Variable name	Identical or comparable variables for LNU 1991/81/74/68
-----------------	---------------	---

INFORMATION ABOUT INTERVIEW

X2	PANEL CODE	
X3	BOX NUMBER	Y2, U2
X4	INTERVIEWER NUMBER	Y3, U3, V2
X5	DATE OF INTERVIEW- MONTH, DAY	Y4, U4, jfr V3, jfr W552
X6	TIME AT START OF INTERVIEW - HOUR, MINUTE	Y5, U5, V5
X7	TIME AT END OF INTERVIEW - HOUR, MINUTE	Y6, U6, V708
X10	TYPE OF INTERVIEW	Y7, U7
X11	INDIRECT INTERVIEW	Y8, U8, V719
X12	INTERVIEW LANGUAGE	

SEX, AGE, OCCUPATION

X8	SEX	Y10, U10, V718, W2
X9	YEAR OF BIRTH	Y11, U11, V815, W533
X14	SEI - OWN EMPLOYMENT STATUS	Jfr Y14, jfr U14, jfr V715, jfr W996
X15	OWN SOCIO-ECONOMIC GROUP	Y13, jfr U13
X16	NYK80 CURRENT OCCUPATION	
X17	NYK85 CURRENT OCCUPATION	
X18	OWN EGP	Y669

CHILDHOOD CONDITIONS

NATIONALITY

X51	BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN	
X52	SWEDISH PARENTS	jfr Y15, jfr U15, jfr V6, jfr W4
X53	BIRTH COUNTRY - FATHER	jfr Y16, jfr U16, jfr V7, jfr W4
X54	BIRTH COUNTRY - MOTHER	jfr Y17, jfr U17, jfr V8, jfr W5
X55	HOME LANGUAGE	jfr Y18, jfr U18, jfr V9, jfr W6
X56	AGE AT IMMIGRATION	jfr Y19, jfr U19, jfr V10, jfr W7
X57	COUNTRY OF ORIGIN	
X58	ABILITY TO SPEAK SWEDISH	
X59	RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION - FATHER	
X60	RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION - MOTHER	

SIBLINGS, PARENTS AND CHILDHOOD FAMILY

X61	NUMBER OF SIBLINGS, TOTAL	jfr Y34, jfr U28, jfr V22, jfr W30
X62	NUMBER OF SIBLINGS ALIVE	
X63	NUMBER OF BROTHERS, TOTAL	
X64	NUMBER OF BROTHERS ALIVE	
X65	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 1	
X66	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 2	
X67	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 3	
X68	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 4	
X69	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 5	
X70	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 6	
X71	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 7	
X72	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 8	
X73	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 9	
X74	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 10	
X75	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 11	
X76	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 12	
X77	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 13	
X78	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 14	
X79	SEX SIBLING 1	
X80	SEX SIBLING 2	
X81	SEX SIBLING 3	
X82	SEX SIBLING 4	
X83	SEX SIBLING 5	
X84	SEX SIBLING 6	
X85	SEX SIBLING 7	
X86	SEX SIBLING 8	
X87	SEX SIBLING 9	
X88	SEX SIBLING 10	
X89	SEX SIBLING 11	
X90	SEX SIBLING 12	
X91	SEX SIBLING 13	
X92	SEX SIBLING 14	
X93	AGE-POSITION AMONG SIBLINGS	
X94	INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY	jfr Y20, jfr U20, jfr V11, jfr W20
X95	RELATIONS WITH PARENT LIVING ELSEWHERE	
X96	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL MOTHER EPISODE 1	
X97	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL MOTHER EPISODE 2	
X98	NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL MOTHER	
X99	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL FATHER EPISODE 1	
X100	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL FATHER EPISODE 2	
X101	NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL FATHER	
X102	AGE LIVING WITH STEPMOTHER EPISODE 1	
X103	AGE LIVING WITH STEPMOTHER EPISODE 2	
X104	NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH STEPMOTHER	
X105	AGE LIVING WITH STEPFATHER EPISODE 1	
X106	AGE LIVING WITH STEPFATHER EPISODE 2	
X107	NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH STEPFATHER	
X108	AGE LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT EPISODE 1	
X109	AGE LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT EPISODE 2	

X110	AGE LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT EPISODE 3	
X111	NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT	
X112	WHO DOES RESPONDENT REGARD AS MOTHER	
X113	WHO DOES RESPONDENT REGARD AS FATHER	
X114	LIVED WITH STEPSIBLINGS	
X115	MOVED FROM PARENTAL HOME YEAR/MONTH	
X116	CONFLICT IN CHILDHOOD FAMILY	jfr Y42, U26, V20, W29
X117	CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENTS	
X118	CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENT AND STEPPARENT	
X119	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL MOTHER	
X120	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL FATHER	
X121	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND STEPMOTHER OR STEPFATHER	
X122	CONFLICT BETWEEN OTHERS, WHO...	
X123	FATHER'S EDUCATION	jfr Y22, jfr U22, jfr V13, jfr W22
X124	MOTHER'S EDUCATION	jfr Y23, jfr U23, jfr V14, jfr W23
X126	SEI FATHER	jfr Y24, jfr U150
X127	NYK80 FATHER	Y25
X128	NYK85 FATHER	
X129	FATHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES	jfr Y27, jfr U152, jfr V16, jfr W25
X130	FATHER FARMER: AREA	Y28, U153, jfr V16, jfr W25
X132	SEI MOTHER	jfr Y29, jfr U159
X133	NYK80 MOTHER	Y30
X134	NYK85 MOTHER	
X135	MOTHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES	jfr Y32, jfr U152
X136	MOTHER FARMER: AREA	Y33, jfr U153
X137	RESPONDENT'S AGE WHEN MOTHER STARTED GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT	
X138	CHILDHOOD FAMILY'S ECONOMY	Y36, U25, V19, W28
X139	PARENTS' CAR-OWNING	Y37
X140	PARENTS' HOME-OWNING	Y39
X141	PARENTS OWNED A SUMMER COTTAGE	Y40
X237	YEAR OF BIRTH – MOTHER	
X238	MOTHER - ALIVE	jfr Y21, jfr U21, jfr V12, jfr W21
X239	YEAR OF DEATH – MOTHER	
X240	CIVIL STATUS – MOTHER	
X241	DISTANCE – MOTHER	
X242	RELATIONS MOTHER	
X243	TELEPHONE CONTACT MOTHER	
X244	YEAR OF BIRTH – FATHER	
X245	FATHER – ALIVE	jfr Y21, jfr U21, jfr V12, jfr W21
X246	YEAR OF DEATH – FATHER	
X247	CIVIL STATUS – FATHER	
X248	DISTANCE – FATHER	
X249	RELATIONS FATHER	
X250	TELEPHONE CONTACT FATHER	

HOME TOWN

X142	NUMBER OF HOME TOWNS	jfr Y44, jfr U30, jfr V24, jfr W9
X143	TYPE OF HOME TOWN	Y46, U32, V26, W11
X144	HOME COUNTY – COUNTRY	Y47, U33, V27, W12
X145	HOME MUNICIPALITY	Y48, U34, V28, W13

CHILD CARE AND SCHOOL

X146	NUMBER OF MONTHS AT DAY-CARE CENTRE	Y51
X147	NUMBER OF MONTHS AT THE HOME OF A CHILDMINDER	jfr Y52
X148	NUMBER OF MONTHS AT KINDERGARTEN	Y53

FAMILY SITUATION

HOUSEHOLD STRUCTURE

X149	CIVIL STATUS ACCORDING TO INTERVIEW	jfr Y57, jfr U90, jfr V68, jfr W36
X150	YEAR/MONTH START OF CURRENT COHABITATION	
X151	NUMBER OF PERSONS IN HOUSEHOLD	Y58, U91, jfr V57, jfr W90
X152	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S SEX	
X153	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S YEAR OF BIRTH	
X154	NUMBER OF CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	
X155	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	jfr Y59, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54
X156	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	jfr Y60, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54
X157	NUMBER OF CHILDREN BORN 1982-2000 IN HOUSEHOLD	
X160	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN BORN 1990-1999 IN HOUSEHOLD	jfr Y81
X161	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999	jfr Y61, jfr U103
X162	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999 BORN 1982-1999	
X163	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999	jfr Y62, jfr U103
X164	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999 BORN 1982-1999	
X165	FAMILY TYPE	
X166	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1	Y63
X167	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2	Y64
X168	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3	Y65
X169	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 4	Y66
X170	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 5	Y67
X171	SEX CHILD 1	
X172	SEX CHILD 2	
X173	SEX CHILD 3	
X174	SEX CHILD 4	
X175	SEX CHILD 5	
X176	LIVES WITH PARENT	Y68
X177	HOUSEHOLD WITH THREE GENERATIONS	Y69
X178	MARRIED/COHABITING 1999 AND 2000	Y71, U110
X179	OTHER CHILDREN 1999, NOT IN HOUSEHOLD 2000	Y70

SPOUSE'S OCCUPATION

X181	EMPLOYMENT STATUS SPOUSE	
X182	SEI SPOUSE	jfr Y72, jfr U117, jfr V711
X183	NYK80 SPOUSE	Y73, U119
X184	NYK85 SPOUSE	
X185	SPOUSE'S EGP	Y672
X186	EMPLOYMENT STATUS SPOUSE	jfr Y74, jfr U118, jfr V710
X187	SPOUSE SELF-EMPLOYED: EMPLOYEES	jfr Y75, jfr U120
X188	SPOUSE FARMER: SIZE	jfr Y76, jfr U121
X189	SPOUSE'S CURRENT WORKING HOURS	Y77, U111

CHILDREN

X200	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN IN MUNICIPAL CHILDCARE	jfr Y82
X201	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN IN PRIVATE CHILDCARE	
X202	COST OF CHILDCARE PER MONTH	Y83
X203	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN MANAGING ALONE	Y85
X204	CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	Y89, U124, jfr V954, jfr W59
X205	NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	Y90, U125, jfr V954, jfr W59
X206	NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	Y91, U126, jfr V958
X207	NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	Y92, jfr U127, jfr V958
X208	NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	Y93, jfr U129, jfr V956, jfr W61
X209	NUMBER OF DECEASED CHILDREN	jfr Y94, jfr U130, jfr V957, jfr W62
X210	NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD WHO LIVES WITH OTHER PARENT	
X220	NUMBER OF COMMON (WITH SPOUSE/PARTNER) CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	
X221	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 1	
X222	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 1	
X223	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 2	
X224	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 2	
X225	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 3	
X226	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 3	
X227	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 4	
X228	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 4	
X229	PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 5	
X230	PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 5	
X231	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 1	
X232	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 2	
X233	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 3	
X234	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 4	
X235	ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 5	
X236	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN WITH ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY	

CIVIL STATUS

X190	PREVIOUSLY COHABITING	Y99
X191	NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS	Y100
X192	NUMBER OF PREVIOUS MARRIAGES	
X193	YEAR/MONTH FOR FIRST COHABITATION	jfr Y101
X194	DURATION FIRST COHABITATION	Y102
X195	CIVIL STATUS FIRST COHABITATION	
X196	YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED	jfr Y103
X197	DURATION LAST COHABITATION	
X198	REASON FOR SEPARATION LAST COHABITATION	Y104
X199	CIVIL STATUS LAST COHABITATION	

MOVES

X19	SAME PLACE OF RESIDENCE SINCE 1991	jfr Y105, jfr U37, jfr V30
X20	YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT PLACE OF RESIDENCE	jfr Y108, jfr U40, jfr V32, jfr W15
X21	REASON FOR LATEST MOVE	jfr Y107, jfr U39, jfr V33
X22	YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT DWELLING	jfr Y111, jfr U42, jfr V35, jfr W96

LIVING CONDITIONS

X23	TYPE OF KITCHEN	Y112, jfr U46, jfr V39, jfr W72
X24	NUMBER OF ROOMS, EXCLUDING THE KITCHEN	Y113, U45, V38, W71
X25	LIVING SPACE M ²	Y114
X26	NUMBER OF APARTMENTS IN THE HOUSE	Y115, U44, V37, W70
X27	MODERN HOME	Y116, jfr U55, jfr V746, jfr W587
X28	BOOKS IN THE HOME	Y117, U65, V55, W88
X29	ENCYCLOPAEDIA IN THE HOME	jfr Y118, jfr U66, jfr V56
X30	DAILY NEWSPAPER IN THE HOME	
X31	COMPUTER IN THE HOME	
X32	INTERNET IN THE HOME	
X33	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE	
X34	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR MAINTENANCE	
X35	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE, NEIGHBOURS	
X36	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: VANDALISM OR CRIME	
X37	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: SCARCITY OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT	
X38	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR OUTSIDE AIR QUALITY	
X39	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR INDOOR AIR QUALITY	
X40	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: AFRAID AT NIGHT	
X41	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: OTHER PROBLEMS	
X42	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: TRAFFIC DANGEROUS FOR CHILDREN	
X43	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR FACILITIES FOR CHILDREN'S PLAY/LEISURE ACTIVITIES	
X44	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: OTHER PROBLEMS FOR CHILDREN	
X45	HOME OWNER/RENTER	Y121, U71, V60, W94
X46	COST OF DWELLING – NOT OWNER/RENTER	Y122, U72, V61

X47	TYPE OF POSSESSION	Y123, jfr U73, jfr V62, jfr W95
X48	OWNER OF BUILDING	Y124, U74
X49	COST OF DWELLING – RENT	Y125, U75, jfr V63, jfr W98
X50	DENSITY STANDARD	Y130, U68, V745, W626

EDUCATION

X261	YEARS OF EDUCATION, RESPONDENT	Y131, U137, V229, W538
X305	HIGHEST EDUCATION	Y165, jfr U138, jfr V230, jfr W537

OCCUPATIONAL BIOGRAPHY

X311	NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT	Y183, U478, V517, W293
X312	EVER WORKED 6 MONTHS	
X313	BEGAN WORKING: YEAR	Y184, jfr U144
X314	STILL AT FIRST JOB	jfr Y185
X315	TIME IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS	Y186, jfr U478
X316	WHEN LAST GAINFULLY EMPLOYED	Y187
X319	WHEN LAST UNEMPLOYED > 2 MONTHS	jfr Y190, jfr U480
X322	YEAR EMPLOYED IN CURRENT JOB	jfr Y193, jfr U350, jfr V400, jfr W229
X323	SENIORITY, CURRENT WORKPLACE, MONTHS	Y195
X324	SENIORITY, CURRENT JOB, MONTHS	Y196
X325	NUMBER OF GAINFUL EMPLOYMENTS, TOTAL	Y197
X326	NUMBERS OF JOBS AS EMPLOYEE	Y198
X329	TIME AWAY FROM GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS	Y202
X336	SEI AGE 25	Y209
X341	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 25	Y213
X342	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 25	Y214
X347	SEI AGE 30	Y215
X352	TYPE OF ACTIVITY AGE 30	Y219
X353	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 30	Y220
X358	SEI AGE 35	Y221
X363	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 35	Y225
X364	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 35	Y226
X369	SEI AGE 40	Y227
X374	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 40	Y231
X375	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 40	Y232
X380	SEI AGE 45	Y233
X385	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 45	Y237
X386	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 45	Y238
X391	SEI AGE 50	Y239
X396	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 50	Y243
X397	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 50	Y244
X402	SEI FIRST JOB	Y245
X403	NYK80 FIRST JOB	Y246

X404	NYK85 FIRST JOB	
X405	EGP FIRST JOB	Y247
X412	SEI CURRENT JOB	Y251
X413	NYK80 CURRENT JOB	Y252
X414	NYK85 CURRENT JOB	
X415	EGP CURRENT JOB	Y253
X416	SNI CURRENT JOB	Y254, jfr U349, jfr V399, jfr W228
X417	WORKPLACE SIZE, CURRENT JOB	jfr Y255
X418	SECTOR, CURRENT JOB	Y256
X419	PERMANENTLY EMPLOYED, CURRENT JOB	
X420	REGULAR EMPLOYMENT	

HEALTH AND USE OF HEALTH CARE

X435	GENERAL HEALTH	Y257
X436	WALK 100 M	Y258, U160, V235, W101
X437	RUN 100 M	Y259, U161, V236, W102
X438	WALK STAIRS	Y260, U162, V237, W103
X439	TURN TAP	Y261
X440	LENGTH IN CM	Y262
X441	WEIGHT IN KG	Y263

MEDICATIONS IN THE LAST 14 DAYS

X442	DIGITALIS OR OTHER CARDIOVASCULAR MEDICATIONS	jfr Y271/Y272, jfr U174/U175, jfr V942/941, jfr W978/977
X443	MEDICINE TO REDUCE BLOOD PRESSURE	Y274
X444	LOSEC OR OTHER GASTRIC ULCER MEDICATIONS	
X445	TRANQUILIZERS	jfr Y268, jfr U171, jfr V246, jfr W112
X446	ANTIDEPRESSANTS	
X447	SLEEPING PILLS	Y269, U172, V247, W113
X448	MEDICINE FOR DIABETES	Y270, U173, V945, W981
X449	HORMONE REPLACEMENT THERAPY	
X450	CONTRACEPTIVE PILLS	Y275, U176, V248, W114
X451	USED OTHER MEDICINES	Jfr Y276, jfr U177, jfr V249, jfr W115

ILLNESSES AND AILMENTS IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS

X452	HEADACHE	Y277, U190, V257, W120
X453	COLD	Y278, U191, V258, W121
X454	POOR VISION	Y279, U192, V259, W122
X455	IMPAIRED HEARING	Y280, U193, V260, W123
X456	CHEST PAIN	Y281, U194, V261, W124
X457	BRONCHITIS	Y282, U195, V262, W125
X458	GOITRE	Y283, U196, V263, W126
X459	TUBERCULOSIS	Y284, U197, V264, W127
X460	ACHES IN SHOULDERS/SHOULDER BLADES	Y285, U198, V265, W128
X461	HEART ATTACK	Y286, U199, V266, W129

X462	STROKE	
X463	CARDIAC WEAKNESS	Y287, U200, V267, W130
X464	HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE	Y288, U201, V268, W131
X465	STOMACH PAINS	Y289, U202, V269, W132
X466	GASTRIC ULCER	Y290, U203, V270, W133
X467	PAIN IN BACK/HIPS	Y291, U204, V271, W134
X468	BILIARY TROUBLE	Y292, U205, V272, W135
X469	KIDNEY TROUBLE	Y293, U206, V273, W136
X470	HAEMORRHOIDS	Y294, U207, V274, W137
X471	TROUBLE WITH URINATION	Y295, U208, V275, W138
X472	MENSTRUATION TROUBLE	Y296, jfr U209, jfr V276, jfr W139
X473	PREGNANCY COMPLICATIONS	Y297, jfr U210, jfr V278, jfr W141
X474	VAGINAL TROUBLE	Y298, U211, V277, W140
X475	INGUINAL HERNIA	Y299, U212, V279, W142
X476	VARICOSE VEINS	Y300, U213, V280, W143
X477	SWOLLEN LEGS	Y301, U214, V281, W144
X478	ACHES IN JOINTS	Y302, U215, V282, W145
X479	GENERAL TIREDNESS	Y303, U216, V283, W146
X480	INSOMNIA	Y304, U217, V284, W147
X481	NERVOUS TROUBLE	Y305, U218, V285, W148
X482	DEPRESSIONS	Y306, U219, V286, W149
X483	MENTAL ILLNESS	Y307, U220, V287, W150
X484	SWEATING	Y308, U221, V288, W151
X485	COUGH	Y309, U222, V289, W152
X486	DIFFICULTY BREATHING	Y310, U223, V290, W153
X487	DIZZINESS	Y311, U224, V291, W154
X488	NAUSEA	Y312, U225, V292, W155
X489	WEIGHT LOSS	Y313, U226, V293, W156
X490	VOMITING	Y314, U227, V294, W157
X491	DIARRHOEA	Y315, U228, V295, W158
X492	CONSTIPATION	Y316, U229, V296, W159
X493	OVEREXERTION	Y317, U230, V297, W160
X494	RASHES	Y318, U231, V298, W161
X495	CANCER	Y319, U232, V299, W162
X496	ANAEMIA	Y320, U233, V300, W163
X497	DIABETES	Y321, U234, V301, W164
X498	OVERWEIGHT	Y322, U235, V302, W165
X499	ORGANIC NERVE DISORDER	Y323, U236, V303, W166
X500	DISCOMFORT AFTER INJURY	Y324, jfr U189
X501	ALLERGY	Y325
X502	URINARY TRACT INFECTION	Y326
X503	OTHER INFECTIONS	jfr Y327, jfr U237, jfr V304
X504	OTHER INFLAMMATIONS	jfr Y328, jfr U238, jfr V305
X505	DENTAL TROUBLE	
X506	METABOLISM TROUBLE	
X507	CIRCULATORY TROUBLE	
X508	OTHER ILLNESSES	

USE OF HEALTH CARE

X509	HOSPITALIZED	Y329, U253, V310, jfr W172
------	--------------	----------------------------

X510	DAYS IN HOSPITAL	jfr Y330, jfr U254, jfr V311, jfr W173
X511	BEEN TO A DOCTOR	Y331, U255, V321, jfr W176
X512	NUMBER OF VISITS TO A DOCTOR	Y332, U256, V322, W176
X513	REFRAINED MEDICAL CARE	
X514	NUMBER OF TIMES REFRAINED FROM MEDICAL CARE DUE TO PATIENT FEE	
X515	VISITED A NURSE	Y333, U257, V323, W177
X516	VISITED A DENTIST	Y334, U261, jfr V328, W182
X517	REFRAINED FROM SEEING A DENTIST	
X518	NUMBER OF TIMES REFRAINED FROM DENTAL CARE DUE TO PATIENT FEE	
X519	CONDITION OF TEETH	Y336, jfr U269, jfr V336, jfr W185
X520	DENTURES GOOD	Y337, U270, V337, W186

DIET, ALCOHOL, TOBACCO

X521	FRESH VEGETABLES	Y339, jfr U276, jfr W198
X522	SMOKING	Y340, jfr U278, jfr V340, jfr W202, W203
X523	SMOKING NUMBER OF YEARS	Y341, U279
X524	SMOKING INDOORS	
X525	DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR ETC	Y343, U280, jfr V341, jfr W204
X526	NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC	
X527	NUMBER OF GLASSES	

PHYSICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH

X528	AGILITY	Y346, U239, V734, W559
X529	INDEX FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING	Y347, U241, V736
X530	PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING	Y348, U242, V737, W573
X531	OLLE'S PSYCHOLOGICAL INDEX	Y349
X532	ACHE IN THE LOCOMOTOR SYSTEM	Y350, U243, V739, W567
X533	OLLE'S INDEX FOR ACHE	Y351
X534	CIRCULATORY SYSTEM	Y352, U244, V740, W566
X535	OLLE'S CIRCULATORY INDEX	Y353
X536	STOMACH TROUBLE	Y354, U245, V741, W568
X537	OLLE'S STOMACH INDEX	Y355
X538	DEFECATION TROUBLE	Y356, U246, V742, W569
X539	ACCUMULATED SYMPTOM SCALE	Y357, U247, V743, jfr W637
X540	ACCUMULATED SYMPTOM SCALE 2	Y358
X542	NUMBER OF YES ON SYMPTOM	Y359, U248, V744, jfr W638
X543	NUMBER OF YES ON SYMPTOM 2	

OCCUPATIONAL SITUATION

LAST YEAR

X544	TOTAL HOURS WORKED 1999	Y360, U283, V789, W940
X545	EMPLOYED FULL-TIME 1999	Y361, U284, V342, jfr W205, W206
X546	WEEKS FULL-TIME 1999	Y362, U285, V343, jfr W205, W206
X547	HOURS PER WEEK FULL-TIME 1999	Y363, U286, V344, jfr W205, W206
X548	EMPLOYED PART-TIME 1999	Y364, U288, V346, jfr W207, W208
X549	WEEKS PART-TIME 1999	Y365, U289, V347, jfr W207, W208
X550	HOURS PER WEEK PART-TIME 1999	Y366, U290, V348, jfr W207, W208
X551	FARM WORK 1999	Y369, U296, V356, jfr W210, W211
X552	FARM WORK WEEKS 1999	Y370, U297, V357, jfr W210, W211
X553	HOURS PER WEEK, FARM WORK 1999	Y371, U298, V358, jfr W210, W211
X554	ASSISTED ON FARM 1999	Y372, U300, V360, jfr W212, W213
X555	WEEKS ASSISTED ON FARM 1999	Y373, U301, V361, jfr W212, W213
X556	HOURS PER WEEK ASSISTED ON FARM 1999	Y374, U302, V362, jfr W212, W213
X557	WORK IN OWN FIRM 1999	Y375, U304, V364, jfr W214, W215
X558	WEEKS IN OWN FIRM	Y376, U305, V365, jfr W214, W215
X559	HOURS PER WEEK IN OWN FIRM 1999	Y377, U306, V366, jfr W214, W215
X560	ASSISTANT IN FIRM 1999	Y378, U308, V368, jfr W216, W217
X561	WEEKS ASSISTANT IN FIRM 1999	Y379, U309, V369, jfr W216, W217
X562	HOURS PER WEEK ASSISTANT IN FIRM 1999	Y380, U310, V370, jfr W216, W217
X563	FREELANCE PROFESSION 1999	Y381, U312, V372, jfr W218, W219
X564	WEEKS IN FREELANCE OCCUPATION 1999	Y382, U313, V373, jfr W218, W219
X565	HOURS PER WEEK IN FREELANCE OCCUPATION 1999	Y383, U314, V374, jfr W218, W219
X566	UNEMPLOYED DURING 1999	Y384, U316, V376, jfr W220
X567	WEEKS UNEMPLOYED 1999	Y385, U317, V377, jfr W220
X568	HOUSEHOLD WORK 1999	jfr Y367, jfr U292, jfr V350, jfr W238
X569	WEEKS HOUSEHOLD WORK 1999	jfr Y368, jfr U293, jfr V351, jfr W238

LAST WEEK

X570	LAST WEEK: FULL-TIME	Y398, jfr U332, jfr V345
X571	LAST WEEK: PART-TIME	Y399, jfr U333, jfr V349
X572	LAST WEEK: FARM WORK	Y400, U336, V359
X573	LAST WEEK: ASSIST ON FARM	Y401, U337, V363
X574	LAST WEEK: OWN FIRM	Y402, U338, V367
X575	LAST WEEK: ASSISTANT IN FIRM	Y403, U339, V371
X576	LAST WEEK: FREELANCE OCCUPATION	Y404, U340, V375
X577	LAST WEEK: LOOKING FOR WORK	Y405, U341, V378
X578	LAST WEEK: PENSION	Y406, U344, V387
X579	LAST WEEK: MILITARY SERVICE	Y407, U345, V390
X580	LAST WEEK: STUDYING	Y408, U346, V393
X581	LAST WEEK: HOUSEHOLD	Y409, U334, V352
X582	LAST WEEK: OTHER	Y410, U347, V396

EMPLOYEES' WORKING CONDITIONS

X583	SEI EMPLOYEES	Y411, jfr U355, jfr V712
X584	NYK80 EMPLOYEES	Y412, jfr U356
X585	NYK85 EMPLOYEES	
X586	PERFORM WORK ASSIGNMENTS: WHERE	
X587	ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, CURRENT JOB	
X588	ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, DIFFERENT EMPLOYERS	
X590	NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES	Y414, jfr U357, jfr V404, jfr W233
X591	EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS	Y415, U358, V405, jfr W234
X592	SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	Y416, U359, V406, jfr W234
X593	LEARNING TIME	Y417
X594	USE OF PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE	Y418
X595	KNOWLEDGE CORRESPONDS TO WORK REQUIREMENTS	
X596	SPECIFIC COMPETENCE	Y419
X597	ON-THE-JOB TRAINING	Y420
X598	NUMBER OF DAYS, ON-THE-JOB TRAINING	Y421
X599	ON-THE-JOB TRAINING: HELP TO ADVANCE	
X600	ON-THE-JOB TRAINING: SPECIFIC/GENERAL	
X645	BOSS' NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES	
X646	SEX OF BOSS	
X647	BOSS BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY	
X648	DIFFICULT TO REPLACE RESPONDENT	
X649	DIFFICULT TO GET NEW JOB	

WORK TIMES LAST WEEK

X601	WORKING HOURS OR SHIFT	Y422, jfr U360
X602	REGULAR WEEKLY WORK HOURS	Y460, U418, V459, W251
X603	SUITABLE WORK TIME	Y461, U420, V468
X604	HOW OFTEN OVERTIME	
X605	OVERTIME PER YEAR	
X606	OVERTIME PER MONTH	
X607	OVERTIME PER WEEK	
X608	OVERTIME HOURS	jfr Y439, jfr U385, jfr V764, jfr W243
X609	COMPENSATION FOR OVERTIME	
X610	WORKED WHEN SICK	
X627	NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK/YEAR	
X651	TRAVELLING TIME MINUTES PER DAY	jfr Y441, jfr U387, jfr V765, jfr W244,

W636

SALARY

X611	FIXED MONTHLY SALARY BEFORE TAX	Y464, U434, V720, jfr W272, W275
X612	WEEKLY WAGE BEFORE TAX	Y465, U435, V721, jfr W272, W275
X613	FIXED HOURLY WAGE	Y466, U436, V722, jfr W272, W275
X614	INDIVIDUAL PIECE-RATE	Y467, U437, jfr V723, V724, jfr W272, W275
X615	GROUP PIECE-RATE	Y468, U438, V725, jfr W272, W275
X616	MONTHLY SALARY W BONUS/COMMISSION	jfr Y469, jfr U439, jfr V726, jfr W272,

X617	COMP. FOR INCONVENIENT WORKING HOURS	W275 Y470, U441, V729, jfr W272
X618	OTHER WAGE FORM SEK/MONTH	Y471, U442, V730, jfr W272
X619	GROSS HOURLY WAGE	jfr Y472, jfr U443, jfr V727, jfr W650
X620	MONTHLY SALARY AFTER TAX	Y473, U433, V490, jfr W276

EXTRA FRINGE BENEFITS

X621	PROFIT SHARE	Y474
X622	COMPANY CAR	Y476
X623	FREE CELLPHONE	jfr Y477
X624	FREE CLEANING ETC	
X625	HOLIDAY HOUSE	Y478
X626	SHAREHOLDER BENEFITS	Y480

AUTONOMY AND INFLUENCE

X628	PUNCTUALITY DEMANDED	Y482, U422, V470, W254
X629	PUNCH CLOCK	Y483, U423, V471, W255
X630	FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS	Y484, U424
X631	CAN GO ON AN ERRAND	Y485, U427, V474, W258
X632	CAN BE VISITED	Y486, U428, V475, W259
X633	CAN DETERMINE PACE OF WORK	Y487, U429
X634	INFLUENCE WHAT TASKS	Y489
X635	INFLUENCE WORKING METHODS	Y490
X636	LEARNS NEW THINGS	Y491
X637	MUST BE CREATIVE	Y492
X638	GETS SUPPORT FROM WORKMATES	Y494
X639	DIRECT SUPERVISION	Y495
X640	MUST FOLLOW RULES	Y497
X641	GROUP RESPONSIBILITY	Y498
X642	PACE OF WORK DETERMINED BY MACHINES	Y499
X643	PACE OF WORK DETERMINED BY FELLOW WORKERS	Y500
X644	PACE OF WORK DETERMINED BY CUSTOMERS	Y501

CONDITIONS FOR THE GAINFULLY EMPLOYED

WORKING ENVIRONMENT

X652	WORKLOAD	
X653	HEAVY LIFTING	Y507, U447, V492, jfr W277
X654	PHYSICALLY DEMANDING	Y508, U448, V493, W278
X655	DAILY SWEATING	Y509, U449, V494, W279
X656	MENTALLY TAXING	Y510, U451, V496, W281
X657	STRESSFUL WORK	Y511, U452, V497, W282
X658	MONOTONOUS WORK	Y512, U453, V498, W283
X659	MENTAL PRESSURE	Y513
X660	MENTAL ACTIVITY	Y514
X661	PHYSICALLY EXHAUSTED	jfr U450, jfr V495, jfr W280

X662	MENTALLY EXHAUSTED	jfr U454, jfr V499, jfr W284
X669	ABSENCE DUE TO ILLNESS	
X663	NOISE	Y515, U456, V501, W286
X664	MONOTONOUS MOVEMENTS	Y517, U465, V511
X665	UNSUITABLE WORK POSITIONS	Y518, U466, V512
X666	GAS, DUST, SMOKE	Y519, U468, V514, jfr W290
X667	DIRTY WORK	jfr U455, jfr V500, jfr W285
X668	TOXIC SUBSTANCES, ACIDS, EXPLOSIVES	Y521, U470, V516, jfr W291
X670	SATISFACTION WITH JOB	Y522
X671	SATISFACTION WITH WAGES	Y523

FARMERS

X672	ARABLE LAND	Y524, U482, V526, W300
X673	WOODLAND	Y525, U483, V527, W301
X674	PERMANENT EMPLOYEES ON FARM	Y526, jfr U484
X675	HOURS DURING BUSIEST PERIOD	Y528, U487, V530, W308
X676	HOURS DURING QUIETEST PERIOD	Y529, U488, V531, W309
X677	NUMBER OF BUSY WEEKS	Y530, U489, V532, W310
X678	VACATION POSSIBILITIES	Y531, U490, V533, W311
X679	VACATION 1999	Y532, U491, V534, jfr W312
X680	VACATION WEEKS 1999	Y533, U492, V535, jfr W312

SELF EMPLOYED

X681	SNI (INDUSTRY) SELF-EMPLOYED	
X684	NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES IN FIRM	Y537, U499, V538, jfr W315
X685	AVERAGE WORKING HOURS	Y542, U501, V540, W317
X686	HOURS BUSY WEEKS	
X687	HOURS QUIET WEEKS	
X688	NUMBER OF BUSY WEEKS	
X689	VACATION 1999	Y543, U503, V542, jfr W319
X690	VACATION WEEKS 1999	Y544, U504, V543, jfr W319

FREELANCE OCCUPATION

X691	SEI FREELANCE OCCUPATION	Y545, jfr U508
X692	NYK80 FREELANCE OCCUPATION	Y546, jfr U509
X693	NYK85 FREELANCE OCCUPATION	
X694	AVERAGE WORKING HOURS	Y548, U511, V547, jfr W323

UNEMPLOYED

X695	SEI UNEMPLOYED	Y549, jfr U516
X696	NYK80 UNEMPLOYED	Y550, jfr U517
X697	NYK85 UNEMPLOYED	
X698	WEEKS UNEMPLOYED	Y551, U525, V559, jfr W345

PENSIONERS

X700	SEI PENSIONERS	Y553, jfr U555
X701	NYK80 PENSIONERS	Y554
X702	NYK85 PENSIONERS	
X703	FORMER FARMER – ARABLE LAND	Y555, U556
X704	FORMER FARMER – WOODLAND	Y556, U557
X705	FORMERLY SELF-EMPLOYED – EMPLOYEES	Y557, U558
X706	WANTS TO WORK	Y558, U559, V586, W363
X707	WANTED WORKING HOURS PER WEEK	Y559, jfr U560-U562
X708	DOES NOT MANAGE TO WORK	Y560, U563, V591
X709	NOT PROFITABLE	Y562, U565, V593

OTHER OCCUPATION

X710	SEI OTHER	Y565
X711	NYK80 OTHER	Y566
X712	NYK85 OTHER	

HOUSEWORK AND FAMILY

X713	HOURS – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES	Y567, jfr U542, jfr V576
X714	HOURS RESPONDENT – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES	Y568, jfr U543, jfr V577
X715	HOURS – CARE OF CLOTHING	Y569, jfr U536, U538, jfr V570, V572
X716	HOURS RESPONDENT – CARE OF CLOTHING	Y570, jfr U537, U539, jfr V571, V573
X717	HOURS – CLEANING	Y571, jfr U540, jfr V574
X718	HOURS RESPONDENT - CLEANING	Y572, jfr U541, jfr V575
X719	HOURS – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	
X720	HOURS RESPONDENT – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE	
X721	HOURS – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE	
X722	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OWN CHILDREN	
X723	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PARENTS	
X724	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER FAMILY MEMBER/RELATIVE	
X725	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM MUNICIPAL HOME-HELP SERVICE	
X726	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PRIVATELY PAID HOME-HELP SERVICE	
X727	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER	
X728	DISTRIBUTION OF HOUSEHOLD'S MONEY	
X729	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK	
X730	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS USE OF MONEY	
X731	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS WHO YOU KEEP COMPANY WITH	
X732	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS CHILD RAISING	
X733	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS	
X734	DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH RESPONDENT WORKS	
X735	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT DROPS CHILDREN OFF	
X736	NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER DROPS CHILDREN OFF	
X737	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE DROPS CHILDREN OFF	
X738	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PICKS CHILDREN UP	
X739	NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PICKS CHILDREN UP	
X740	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PICKS CHILDREN UP	
X741	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT COOKS DINNER	

X742 NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER COOKS DINNER
 X743 NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE COOKS DINNER
 X744 NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PUTS CHILDREN TO BED
 X745 NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PUTS CHILDREN TO BED
 X746 NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PUTS CHILDREN TO BED
 X747 GRANDPARENTS BABY-SITTERS

ECONOMIC RESOURCES

X748	CASH MARGIN	Y574, U576, jfr V602, jfr W375
X749	ACQUIRING CASH	Y575, U577, jfr V602, jfr W375
X750	CAR OWNER	Y576, U586, V611, W422
X751	BOAT OWNER	Y577, U587, V612, W423
X752	SUMMER COTTAGE OWNER	Y578, U588, V613, jfr W424
X753	CARAVAN OWNER	Y579, U589, V614, jfr W424
X754	ECONOMIC DIFFICULTIES	Y584
X755	RECEIVES MAINTENANCE PER MONTH	
X756	PAYS MAINTENANCE PER MONTH	
X757	INHERITANCE	jfr U580, jfr V605, jfr W377
X758	SIZE OF INHERITANCE	jfr U581, jfr V606, jfr W378
X759	INHERITANCE, YEAR	jfr U582, jfr V607, jfr W379
X760	TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT GIVEN	
X761	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	
X762	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	
X763	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	
X764	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	
X765	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK	
X766	TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT RECEIVED	
X767	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	
X768	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK	
X769	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	
X770	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK	
X771	FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK	
X772	HELP WITH REPAIRS/MAINTENANCE/WORKMANSHIP	
X773	HELP WITH MEDICAL EXPERTISE	
X774	HELP WITH FINANCIAL OR LEGAL EXPERTISE	

SAFETY OF LIFE AND PROPERTY

X779	SUFFERED FROM THEFT	Y585, U593, jfr V618
X780	SUFFERED FROM DAMAGE	Y586, U596, V621
X781	VIOLENCE LEADING TO BODILY HARM	Y587, U601, V626
X782	VIOLENCE WITHOUT BODILY HARM	Y588, U602, V627
X783	SERIOUS THREATS	Y589, U603, V628

SPARE TIME AND ORGANIZATIONS

X784	VACATION TRIP 1999	Y590, U611, V636, jfr W614
X785	COTTAGE STAY 1999	Y594, U618, V643, W469

SPARE TIME ACTIVITIES

X786	FISHING OR HUNTING IN SPARE TIME	jfr Y596-597, jfr U621-622, jfr V646-647, jfr W472-473
X787	GARDENING	Y598, U623, V648, W474
X788	GO TO THE CINEMA	Y599, U624, V649, W475
X789	GO TO THE THEATRE	Y600, U625, V650, W476
X790	GO TO A RESTAURANT	Y601, U626, V651, W477
X791	DANCING	Y602, U627, V652, W478
X792	VISIT RELATIVES	Y604, U632, V657, W483
X793	HAVE RELATIVES VISIT	Y605, U633, V658, W485
X794	VISIT FRIENDS AND ACQUAINTANCES	Y606, U634, V659, W484
X795	HAVE FRIENDS VISIT	Y607, U635, V660, W486
X796	READ BOOKS	Y603, U628, V653, W479
X797	STUDY CIRCLE	Y608, U636, V661, W487
X798	PLAY MUSIC OR SING IN A CHOIR	jfr Y610-611, jfr U638, jfr V663, jfr W488
X799	HOBBY ACTIVITY	Y612, U640, V665, W490
X800	SPORTS ACTIVITY	Y613

FRIENDSHIP RELATIONS

X251	NUMBER OF CLOSE FRIENDS	
X252	CLOSE FRIENDS – RELATIVES	
X253	CLOSE FRIENDS – MEN	
X254	CLOSE FRIENDS – BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY	
X255	CLOSE FRIENDS – FELLOW WORKERS	
X256	CLOSE FRIENDS – UNEMPLOYED	
X257	CLOSE FRIENDS – CHILDHOOD FRIENDS	
X258	CLOSE FRIENDS KNOW EACH OTHER	
X259	SEES CLOSE FRIENDS, HOW OFTEN	
X260	TELEPHONE CONTACT WITH CLOSE FRIENDS, HOW OFTEN	
X775	CLOSE FRIEND WHEN ILL	Y614, U699
X776	CLOSE FRIEND AS COMPANY	Y615, U700
X777	SOMEONE TO TALK TO	Y616, U701
X778	SOMEONE TO BORROW MONEY FROM	

UNION AND POLITICAL ACTIVITY

X801	MEMBER OF TRADE UNION	Y617, U648, V666, jfr W491
X802	UNION	Y618, U649, V667, jfr W491
X803	VISITED TRADE UNION MEETING	jfr Y620, jfr U650, jfr V668, jfr W492
X804	UNION REPRESENTATIVE	Y621, U652, V670, W493
X805	UNION ACTIVITY	Y622, U653, V749, W579

X806	PARTY MEMBERSHIP	Y623, U654, V671, W494
X807	VISITED POLITICAL MEETING	jfr Y624, jfr U656, jfr V672, jfr W495
X808	POLITICAL ACTIVITY	Y625, U658, V750, W578
X809	PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION 1998	Y627, U659, V673, jfr W523

OTHER ASSOCIATIONS

X810	OTHER ASSOCIATIONS	Y629, jfr U670, jfr V683, jfr W500
X811	ASSOCIATION ACTIVITIES	Y630
X812	SERVICE LAST YEAR	Y631, U668, V681, jfr W499
X813	SERVICE ACTIVITY	Y632, U669, V682, jfr W499

POLITICAL RESOURCES

X814	TOOK PART IN DEMONSTRATION	jfr Y633, jfr U671, jfr V684, jfr W501
X815	PERSONAL CONTACT	Y634, U672, V685, W502
X816	SPOKEN IN MEETING	Y635, U673, V686, W503
X817	WRITTEN IN NEWSPAPER	Y636, U674, V687, W504
X818	POLITICAL PARTICIPATION	Y637, U675, V751, jfr W580, W599
X819	CAN COMPLAIN	Y638, U678, V689, W506
X820	HELP WHEN COMPLAINING	Y639

EVALUATIONS

X821	AFFINITY TO THE WORKING CLASS	Y640
X822	AFFINITY TO THE MIDDLE CLASS	Y641
X823	AFFINITY TO THE UPPER MIDDLE CLASS	Y642
X824	SOCIETY WITH MORE PRIVATE ALTERNATIVES	jfr Y643
X825	SOCIETY WITH SMALL INCOME DIFFERENCES	Y645
X826	SOCIETY WITH MORE CARE WITHIN THE FAMILY	
X827	SOCIETY WITH GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FAMILY	
X828	TROUBLESHOOTER	Y649
X829	LIFE SATISFACTION	Y650
X830	HARD TO UNDERSTAND	Y651
X831	CONTROL OF OWN LIFE	Y652
X832	RESPONDENT'S EVALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION	Y647, U702
X833	HAS RESPONDENT'S CONDITIONS IMPROVED OR DETERIORATED	Y648, U703

REGISTER INFORMATION AND WEIGHT SYSTEMS

X835	NATIONALITY	Y654, U705
X837	COUNTY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION	Y656, U707
X838	MUNICIPALITY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION	Y657, U708
X839	DISTRICT FOR PARISH REGISTRATION	
X840	TYPE OF LOCALITY	Y659, U710, V820, W610
X841	H-REGION	Y660, jfr U728

X842	CIVIL STATUS	Y661, U715, V814, W704
X843	SPOUSE'S YEAR OF BIRTH	Y663, U716
X844	SPOUSE'S YEAR OF BIRTH FROM INTERVIEW	Y664
X845	RESPONDENT GROUP WEIGHT	jfr Y666, jfr U727, jfr V797, jfr W942
X846	RESPONDENT GROUP WEIGHT B	jfr Y666, jfr U727, jfr V797, jfr W942
X847	RESPONDENT GROUP WEIGHT C	jfr Y666, jfr U727, jfr V797, jfr W942
X848	FATHER'S EGP	Y670
X849	MOTHER'S EGP	Y671

PARTNER: INFORMATION ABOUT INTERVIEW

X1154 P – TODAY'S DATE

PARTNER: SEX, AGE AND PROFESSION

X1002 P – SEX

X1001 P – YEAR OF BIRTH

X1044 P – PRESENT OCCUPATION jfr Y74, jfr U118, jfr V710

PARTNER: CHILDHOOD CONDITIONS

PARTNER: NATIONALITY

X1004 P – BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN

X1005 P – BIRTH COUNTRY – FATHER

X1006 P – BIRTH COUNTRY – MOTHER

X1007 P – HOME LANGUAGE

X1008 P – COUNTRY OF ORIGIN

X1009 P – AGE AT IMMIGRATION

PARTNER: SIBLINGS, PARENTS AND CHILDHOOD FAMILY

X1003 P – NUMBER OF SIBLINGS, TOTAL

X1010 P – FATHER - MOTHER ALIVE

X1011 P – INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY

X1013 P – SEI FATHER

X1014 P – NYK80 FATHER

X1015 P – NYK85 FATHER

X1017 P – SEI MOTHER

X1018 P – NYK80 MOTHER

X1019 P – NYK85 MOTHER

X1022 P – CONFLICTS IN CHILDHOOD FAMILY

PARTNER: EDUCATION

X1023 P – PARTNER'S EDUCATION IN YEARS

X1024 P – HIGHEST EDUCATION jfr Y80, jfr V82, jfr W39

PARTNER: OCCUPATIONAL BIOGRAPHY

X1025 P – NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT
X1026 P – BEGAN WORKING: YEAR
X1031 P – OCCUPATION AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1032 P – SEI AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1033 P – NYK80 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1034 P – NYK85 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1035 P – EGP AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1036 P – YEAR/MONTH STARTED OCCUPATION HELD AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1037 P – YEAR/MONTH LEFT OCCUPATION HELD AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1038 P – SEI AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1039 P – NYK80 AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1040 P – NYK85 AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1041 P – EGP AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1042 P – NUMBER OF TIMES CHANGED OCCUPATION AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION
X1049 P – YEAR/MONTH BEGAN PRESENT OCCUPATION
X1050 P – IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT LAST WHEN
X1051 P – EMPLOYED: PERMANENT EMPLOYMENT

PARTNER: EMPLOYEES' WORKING CONDITIONS

X1059 P – ON-THE-JOB TRAINING
X1060 P – NUMBER OF DAYS ON-THE-JOB TRAINING
X1061 P – OPPORTUNITIES FOR ADVANCEMENT IN CURRENT JOB
X1069 P – EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS
X1070 P – SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL
X1071 P – SUPERVISORY TASKS
X1072 P – NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES

PARTNER: WORKING HOURS LAST WEEK

X1052 P – WORKING HOURS OR SHIFT
X1053 P – REGULAR WEEKLY WORK HOURS jfr Y77, jfr U111
X1054 P – SUITABLE WORK TIME
X1055 P – HOW OFTEN OVERTIME
X1056 P – OVERTIME PER YEAR
X1057 P – OVERTIME PER MONTH
X1058 P – OVERTIME PER WEEK
X1062 P – FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS
X1067 P – TRAVELING TIME MINUTES
X1068 P – NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK: NUMBER OF NIGHTS/YEAR

PARTNER: SALARY

X1073 P – GROSS MONTHLY SALARY
X1074 P – NET MONTHLY SALARY

PARTNER: CONDITIONS FOR GAINFULLY EMPLOYED

PARTNER: WORKING ENVIRONMENT

X1063 P – CAN DETERMINE PACE OF WORK
X1064 P – MENTALLY TAXING
X1065 P – STRESSFUL WORK
X1066 P – MONOTONOUS WORK
X1075 P – PHYSICALLY EXHAUSTED
X1076 P – MENTALLY EXHAUSTED

PARTNER: HOUSEHOLD WORK AND FAMILY

X1095 P – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE
X1096 P – HOURS – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE
X1097 P – HOURS P – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES
X1098 P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES
X1099 P - HOURS CHILDREN – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES
X1100 P – HOURS P – CARE OF CLOTHING
X1101 P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CARE OF CLOTHING
X1102 P – HOURS CHILDREN – CARE OF CLOTHING
X1103 P – HOURS P – CLEANING
X1104 P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CLEANING
X1105 P – HOURS CHILDREN – CLEANING
X1106 P – HOURS P – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE
X1107 P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE
X1108 P – HOURS CHILDREN – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE
X1109 P – RECEIVES HELP WITH HOUSEWORK
X1110 P – HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OWN CHILDREN NOT LIVING AT HOME
X1111 P - HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PARENTS
X1112 P - HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER FAMILY MEMBER/RELATIVE
X1113 P - HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM MUNICIPAL HOME-HELP SERVICE
X1114 P - HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PRIVATELY PAID HOME-HELP SERVICE
X1115 P - HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER
X1116 P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK
X1117 P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS USE OF MONEY
X1118 P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS WHO YOU KEEP COMPANY WITH
X1119 P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS CHILD RAISING
X1120 P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS
X1121 P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH P WORKS

PARTNER: OCCUPATIONAL SITUATION

PARTNER: LAST YEAR

X1077 P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 1999: NUMBER OF WEEKS jfr Y78, jfr U112, jfr V71 jfr W41-43
X1078 P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 1999: HOURS/WEEK

PARTNER: FAMILY SITUATION

PARTNER: CIVIL STATUS

- X1079 P – PREVIOUSLY COHABITING
- X1080 P – NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS
- X1081 P – YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED

PARTNER: CHILDREN

- X1082 P – CHILDREN NOT IN HOME
- X1083 P – NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1084 P – NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1085 P – NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1086 P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1087 P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1088 P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1089 P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 4 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1090 P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 5 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1091 P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 6 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1092 P – RELATIONS CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD
- X1093 P – PAYS MAINTENANCE PER MONTH
- X1094 P – RECEIVES MAINTENANCE PER MONTH

PARTNER: ECONOMIC RESOURCES

- X1122 P – CASH MARGIN
- X1123 P – ACQUIRING CASH

PARTNER: HEALTH

- X1124 P – GENERAL HEALTH

PARTNER: ILLNESSES AND AILMENTS IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS

- X1125 P – HEADACHE
- X1126 P – GENERAL TIREDNESS
- X1127 P – INSOMNIA
- X1128 P – POOR VISION
- X1129 P - IMPAIRED HEARING
- X1130 P – ACHES IN SHOULDERS/SHOULDER BLADES
- X1131 P – STOMACH PAINS
- X1132 P – PAIN IN BACK/HIPS
- X1133 P – OVEREXERTION
- X1134 P – ACHES IN JOINTS
- X1135 P – NERVOUS TROUBLE

- X1136 P – DEPRESSIONS
X1137 P – MENTAL ILLNESS

PARTNER: ALCOHOL

- X1143 P – DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR, ETC
X1144 P – NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC
X1145 P – NUMBER OF GLASSES

PARTNER: PHYSICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH

- X1138 P – INDEX FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING
X1139 P – PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING
X1140 P – OLLE'S PSYCHOLOGICAL INDEX
X1141 P – ACHE IN THE LOCOMOTOR SYSTEM
X1142 P – OLLE'S INDEX FOR ACHE

PARTNER: EVALUATIONS

- X1146 P – SOCIETY WITH MORE PRIVATE ALTERNATIVES
X1147 P – SOCIETY WITH SMALL INCOME DIFFERENCES
X1148 P – SOCIETY WITH MORE CARE WITHIN THE FAMILY
X1149 P – SOCIETY WITH GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FAMILY
X1150 P – AFFINITY TO THE WORKING CLASS
X1151 P – AFFINITY TO THE MIDDLE CLASS
X1152 P – AFFINITY TO THE UPPER MIDDLE CLASS
X1153 P – P:S EVALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION

VARIABLE PRESENTATION

VARIABLE TERMS, WORDINGS OF QUESTIONS,
CONSTRUCTIONS OF VARIABLES, CODES AND SIMPLE
FREQUENCIES

X2	PANEL CODE			
	Respondents with panel code 1 are part of the panel and answered the occupational biography 1991. Respondents with panel code 2 are part of the panel but did not answer the occupational biography 1991. Respondents with panel code 3 are new respondents.			
	1	2840	55,2	
	2	922	17,9	
	3	1380	26,8	
		5142		
X3	BOX NUMBER			Y2, U2
X4	INTERVIEWER NUMBER			Y3, U3, V2
X5	DATE OF INTERVIEW– MONTH, DAY			Y4, U4, jfr V3, jfr W552
	Date – month and day – when the interview was carried out. Only minimum value and maximum value are shown.			
	0103	1	0,0	
	1299	1	0,0	
	No information	1		
X6	TIME AT START OF INTERVIEW – HOUR, MINUTE			Y5, U5, V5
	Interviewers note of time – hour and minute – when the interview started. Only minimum value and maximum value are shown.			
	0705	1	0,0	
	2200	1	0,0	
	No information	7		
X7	TIME AT END OF INTERVIEW – HOUR, MINUTE			Y6, U6, V708
	Interviewers note of time – hour and minute – when the interview ended. Only minimum value and maximum value are shown.			
	30	1	0,0	
	2330	1	0,0	
	No information	102		
X8	SEX			Y10, U10, V718, W2
	The respondent's sex.			
	1 Male	2602	50,6	
	2 Female	2540	49,4	
	Total	5142		
X9	YEAR OF BIRTH			Y11, U11, V815, W533
	The respondent's year of birth.			
	25	58	1,1	
	26	46	0,9	
	27	53	1,0	
	28	57	1,1	

29	67	1,3
30	57	1,1
31	65	1,3
32	56	1,1
33	58	1,1
34	73	1,4
35	67	1,3
36	64	1,2
37	78	1,5
38	82	1,6
39	68	1,3
40	74	1,4
41	80	1,6
42	105	2,0
43	101	2,0
44	85	1,7
45	106	2,1
46	124	2,4
47	106	2,1
48	117	2,3
49	97	1,9
50	108	2,1
51	108	2,1
52	115	2,2
53	84	1,6
54	82	1,6
55	92	1,8
56	88	1,7
57	91	1,8
58	88	1,7
59	90	1,8
60	96	1,9
61	107	2,1
62	100	1,9
63	104	2,0
64	128	2,5
65	109	2,1
66	119	2,3
67	79	1,5
68	114	2,2
69	97	1,9
70	97	1,9
71	113	2,2
72	125	2,4
73	88	1,7
74	87	1,7
75	115	2,2
76	87	1,7
77	110	2,1
78	98	1,9
79	98	1,9

	80	91	1,8
	81	90	1,8
		5142	
X10	TYPE OF INTERVIEW		Y7, U7
	Note if the interview is carried out face-to-face or by phone.		
	1 In person	4296	83,8
	2 By phone	830	16,2
	3 Respondent has filled in the answers	1	0,0
	Total	5127	
	9 No information	15	
		5142	
X11	INDIRECT INTERVIEW		Y8, U8, V719
	Note if the interview is carried out entirely, partly or not at all with the respondent her-/himself.		
	1 Entire interview carried out with respondent	4911	98,9
	2 Parts of interview with respondent	20	0,4
	3 Entire interview with other than respondent	37	0,7
	Total	4968	
	9 No information	174	
		5142	
X12	INTERVIEW LANGUAGE		
	Note if the interview is carried out in Swedish, partly carried out using interpreter, entire interview carried out using interpreter or carried out in English.		
	1 Interview carried out in Swedish	4578	98,4
	2 Interview partly carried out using interpreter	28	0,6
	3 Entire interview carried out using interpreter	45	1,0
	4 Interview carried out in English	2	0,0
	Total	4653	
	9 No information	489	
		5142	

X14	SEI – OWN EMPLOYMENT STATUS		Jfr Y14, jfr U14, jfr V715, jfr W996
	1 Working	3342	65,2
	2 Working in the home	124	2,4
	3 Pensioner	624	12,2
	4 Studying	408	8,0
	5 Long-term unemployed	224	4,4
	6 Early retirement pensioner	285	5,6
	7 Military service	13	0,3
	8 Sick, not working	12	0,2
	9 Parental leave	90	1,8
	Total	5122	
	10 No answer	20	
		5142	

X15	OWN SOCIO-ECONOMIC GROUP		Y13, jfr U13
	Own occupation according to socio-economic classification (SEI)*		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	353	7,0
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	868	17,2
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	549	10,9
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	337	6,7
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	271	5,4
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	75	1,5
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	399	7,9
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	78	1,5
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	943	18,7
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	581	11,5
	57 Professional, upper-level executive**	104	2,1
	60 Self-employed professionals	30	0,6
	71 Self-employed without employees	186	3,7
	72 Self-employed, 1-9 employees	156	3,1
	73 Self-employed, 10-19 employees	28	0,6
	74 Self-employed 20+ employees	40	0,8
	86 Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	7	0,1
	87 Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	23	0,5
	89 Farmer, size of farm unknown	16	0,3
	Total	5044	
	99 Unclassified	98	
		5142	
	* Unemployed, pensioners, students and others not gainfully employed have been coded according to their last occupation that lasted at least 6 months. Homemakers have been coded according to the husband's occupation. Unmarried students under the age of 24 have been coded according to their parent's occupation.		
	** This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.		

X16	NYK80 CURRENT OCCUPATION
	Current profession or occupation coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.

X17	NYK85 CURRENT OCCUPATION
------------	---------------------------------

Current occupation coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.

X18	OWN EGP			Y669
	Own occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP)			
	1 Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	30	0,6	
	2 Ib Higher-grade professionals	725	14,4	
	3 II Lower-grade professionals	966	19,2	
	4 IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	725	14,4	
	5 IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	548	10,9	
	6 IVa Small proprietors with employees	184	3,6	
	7 IVb Small proprietors without employees	186	3,7	
	8 IVc Farmers	23	0,5	
	9 IVd Smallholders	23	0,5	
	10 Vs Supervisors	114	2,3	
	11 Vj Supervisors in primary production	6	0,1	
	12 VIs Skilled manual workers	535	10,6	
	13 VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	14	0,3	
	14 VIIs Unskilled manual workers	943	18,7	
	15 VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	22	0,4	
	Total	5044		
	99 Unclassified	98		
		5142		
X19	SAME PLACE OF RESIDENCE SINCE 1991			jfr Y105, jfr U37, jfr V30
	Did you move to your current place of residence before or after 1991?			
	1 1991 or later	1574	31,1	
	2 Before 1991	3492	68,9	
	Total	5066		
	9 No answer	76		
		5142		
X20	YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT PLACE OF RESIDENCE			jfr Y108, jfr U40, jfr V32, jfr W15
	When did you move to your current place of residence? Only year is shown.			
	Before 1991	3492	68,9	
	91	107	2,1	
	92	101	2,0	
	93	96	1,9	
	94	121	2,4	
	95	142	2,8	
	96	142	2,8	
	97	155	3,1	
	98	239	4,7	
	99	266	5,2	
	2000	204	4,0	
	2001	2	0,0	
	Total	5067		
	9999 No answer	75		

5142

X21**REASON FOR LATEST MOVE****jfr Y107, jfr
U39, jfr V33**

What was the main reason for your moving to your current place of residence? The table is valid for X19 NE 2.

1 Better residence (built a house, gained more room, etc.)	257	16,2
2 Moved closer to family/friends	135	8,5
3 Better area to live in	130	8,2
4 Respondent got new job/better job opportunities	216	13,6
5 Own studies	173	10,9
6 Change of family situation	325	20,5
7 Spouse/partner changed jobs	54	3,4
8 Moved with parents	25	1,6
9 Other	268	16,9
Total	1583	
10 No answer	67	
Not applicable	3492	
	5142	

X22**YEAR AND MONTH MOVED TO CURRENT DWELLING****jfr Y111,
jfr U42, jfr
V35, jfr
W96**

When did you move to your current dwelling? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.

20-29	5	0,1
30-39	15	0,3
40-49	24	0,5
50-59	77	1,5
60-69	220	4,3
70-79	659	12,8
80-89	981	19,1
90	154	3,0
91	154	3,0
92	124	2,4
93	132	2,6
94	176	3,4
95	223	4,3
96	241	4,7
97	336	6,6
98	510	9,9
99	593	11,6
2000	502	9,8
2001	3	0,1
Total	5129	
9999 No answer	13	
	5142	

X23**TYPE OF KITCHEN****Y112, jfr
U46, jfr
V39, jfr
W72**

What kind of kitchen or cooking facilities do you have in your home?

1 Kitchen with dining area	4919	95,8
2 Kitchen or kitchenette without dining area	165	3,2
Other arrangements (cooking recess cupboard or the 3 like)	41	0,8

4 No cooking facilities	7	0,1
5 Living in an institution	1	0,0
Total	5133	
9 No answer	9	
	5142	

X24 **NUMBER OF ROOMS, EXCLUDING THE KITCHEN** **Y113, U45, V38, W71**

How many rooms do you have excluding the kitchen? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.

1	314	6,1
2	817	15,9
3	1037	20,2
4	1142	22,2
5	950	18,5
6	527	10,3
7	213	4,1
8	70	1,4
9	37	0,7
10	14	0,3
11	6	0,1
12	5	0,1
13	4	0,1
14	1	0,0
15	2	0,0
Total	5139	
99 No answer	2	
Living in an institution	1	
	5142	
Mean value		3,95
Standard deviation		1,76

X25 **LIVING SPACE M²** **Y114**

How large is your residence in square meters (m2)? The table is valid for X23 NE 5. This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	1	0,0
10-19	21	0,4
20-29	59	1,2
30-39	105	2,1
40-49	173	3,5
50-59	293	5,9
60-69	455	9,2
70-79	460	9,3
80-89	449	9,0
90-99	353	7,1
100-109	437	8,8
110-119	331	6,7
120-129	417	8,4
130-139	250	5,0
140-149	233	4,7
150-159	240	4,8
160-169	170	3,4
170-179	105	2,1

	180-189	99	2,0
	190-199	36	0,7
	200-299	235	4,7
	300-399	34	0,7
	400-499	7	0,1
	600-699	1	0,0
	Total	4964	
	999 No answer	177	
	Living in an institution	1	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		108,18
	Standard deviation		51,28
X26	NUMBER OF APARTMENTS IN THE HOUSE		Y115, U44, V37, W70
	How many apartments are there in the house where you live, all entrances counted?		
	1 1 apartment (detached house, row house)	2881	56,2
	2 2 apartments	113	2,2
	3 3-10 apartments	456	8,9
	4 11 or more apartments	1671	32,6
	5 Trailer	1	0,0
	6 Living in an institution	1	0,0
	Total	5123	
	9 No answer	19	
		5142	
X27	MODERN HOME		Y116, jfr U55, jfr V746, jfr W587
	Do you have all modern conveniences in your home (i.e. bathroom/shower, indoor toilet, central heating, cooking range (not wood-fired), refrigerator)? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.		
	1 Yes	5104	99,4
	2 No	32	0,6
	Total	5136	
	9 No answer	5	
	Living in an institution	1	
		5142	
X28	BOOKS IN THE HOME		Y117, U65, V55, W88
	Do you have at least two running meters of books, not counting works of reference? If yes: Do you have at least five running meters of books, not counting works of reference? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.		
	11 At least five running meters	2850	55,6
	12 Two to five running meters	1399	27,3
	20 Not two running meters	875	17,1
	Total	5124	
	99 No answer	17	
	Living in an institution	1	
		5142	
X29	ENCYCLOPAEDIA IN THE HOME		jfr Y118, jfr U66, jfr V56
	Is there an encyclopaedia in your home? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.		
	1 Yes	3936	76,6

	2 No	1201	23,4
	Total	5137	
	9 No answer	4	
	Living in an institution	1	
		5142	
X30	DAILY NEWSPAPER IN THE HOME		
	Do you have access to a daily newspaper in your home (or to one that comes every other day or so)? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.		
	1 Yes	3917	76,2
	2 No	1223	23,8
	Total	5140	
	9 No answer	1	
	Living in an institution	1	
		5142	
X31	COMPUTER IN THE HOME		
	Do you have access to a computer at home? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.		
	1 Yes	3600	70,0
	2 No	1540	30,0
	Total	5140	
	9 No answer	1	
	Living in an institution	1	
		5142	
X32	INTERNET IN THE HOME		
	Do you have access to the Internet at home? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.		
	1 Yes	2924	58,3
	2 No	2089	41,7
	Total	5013	
	9 No answer	128	
	Living in an institution	1	
		5142	
X33	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE		
	Do you experience problems with traffic noise where you live?		
	1 Yes	539	10,5
	2 No	4596	89,5
	Total	5135	
	9 No answer	7	
		5142	
X34	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR MAINTENANCE		
	Do you experience problems with poor house/building maintenance where you live?		
	1 Yes	319	6,2

	2 No	4799	93,8
	Total	5118	
	9 No answer	24	
		5142	
X35	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: NOISE, NEIGHBOURS		
	Do you experience problems with noisy neighbours where you live?		
	1 Yes	445	8,7
	2 No	4691	91,3
	Total	5136	
	9 No answer	6	
		5142	
X36	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: VANDALISM OR CRIME		
	Do you experience problems with vandalism or crime where you live?		
	1 Yes	502	9,8
	2 No	4632	90,2
	Total	5134	
	9 No answer	8	
		5142	
X37	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: SCARCITY OF PUBLIC TRANSPORT		
	Do you experience problems with scarcity of public transport where you live?		
	1 Yes	952	18,6
	2 No	4169	81,4
	Total	5121	
	9 No answer	21	
		5142	
X38	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR OUTSIDE AIR QUALITY		
	Do you experience problems with poor outside air quality (caused by e.g. traffic or industries) where you live?		
	1 Yes	260	5,1
	2 No	4875	94,9
	Total	5135	
	9 No answer	7	
		5142	
X39	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR INDOOR AIR QUALITY		
	Do you experience problems with poor indoor air quality where you live?		
	1 Yes	247	4,8
	2 No	4876	95,2
	Total	5123	
	9 No answer	19	
		5142	

X40	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: AFRAID AT NIGHT		
	Are you afraid of going out at night where you live?		
	1 Yes	515	10,0
	2 No	4611	90,0
	Total	5126	
	9 No answer	16	
		5142	
X41	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: OTHER PROBLEMS		
	Do you experience additional problems where you live?		
	1 Yes	345	7,0
	2 No	4612	93,0
	Total	4957	
	9 No answer	185	
		5142	
X42	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: TRAFFIC DANGEROUS FOR CHILDREN		
	Do you experience problems with traffic that is dangerous for children where you live? (If respondent has children 12 years or younger (i.e., born 1988 or after).		
	1 Yes	452	33,9
	2 No	883	66,1
	Total	1335	
	9 No answer	33	
	Not applicable	3774	
		5142	
X43	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: POOR FACILITIES FOR CHILDREN'S PLAY/LEISURE ACTIVITIES		
	Do you experience problems with poor facilities for children's play/leisure activities where you live? (If respondent has children 12 years or younger (i.e., born 1988 or after).		
	1 Yes	231	17,3
	2 No	1101	82,7
	Total	1332	
	9 No answer	36	
	Not applicable	3774	
		5142	
X44	PROBLEM IN HOME/AREA: OTHER PROBLEMS FOR CHILDREN		
	Do you experience other problems for children where you live? (If respondent has children 12 years or younger (i.e., born 1988 or after).		
	1 Yes, long way from friends	23	1,7
	2 Yes, other problems	50	3,8
	3 No	1246	94,5
	Total	1319	
	9 No answer	49	
	Not applicable	3774	
		5142	

X45**HOME OWNER/RENTER****Y121, U71,
V60, W94**

Who owns/rents the place you live in? The table is valid for X23 NE 5.

1 You yourself or your spouse	4729	92,0
2 Parents (own)	293	5,7
3 Own child/children	22	0,4
4 Parents-/ daughter-/ son-in-law	3	0,1
5 Sister/brother	16	0,3
6 Other close friend/relative	14	0,3
7 Other with whom respondent is lodging	24	0,5
8 Other	40	0,8
Total	5141	
Living in an institution	1	
	5142	

X46**COST OF DWELLING – NOT OWNER/RENTER****Y122, U72,
V61**

Do you pay anything for where you live, and if so how much (cost per month (kronor))? The table is valid for X45 NE 1. This variable is divided into categories.

0	221	55,7
400-499	2	0,5
500-599	7	1,8
600-699	1	0,3
700-799	1	0,3
900-999	1	0,3
1000-1099	21	5,3
1200-1299	5	1,3
1300-1399	1	0,3
1400-1499	3	0,8
1500-1599	23	5,8
1600-1699	1	0,3
1700-1799	4	1,0
1800-1899	3	0,8
1900-1999	1	0,3
2000-2099	26	6,5
2100-2199	2	0,5
2200-2299	4	1,0
2300-2399	4	1,0
2400-2499	1	0,3
2500-2599	14	3,5
2700-2799	2	0,5
2800-2899	1	0,3
3000-3099	15	3,8
3100-3199	1	0,3
3200-3299	2	0,5
3300-3399	3	0,8
3400-3499	1	0,3
3500-3599	2	0,5
3700-3799	1	0,3
3800-3899	2	0,5
3900-3999	1	0,3
4000-4099	2	0,5
4100-4199	1	0,3

4400-4499	1	0,3
4500-4599	3	0,8
4600-4699	2	0,5
5000-5099	3	0,8
5300-5399	1	0,3
5500-5599	1	0,3
5700-5799	1	0,3
6000-6999	3	0,8
8000-8999	2	0,5
Total	397	
99999 No answer	16	
Not applicable	4729	
	5142	
Mean value for all		1022,16
Standard deviation		1472,56
Mean value for >0		2305,67
Standard deviation		1389,46

X47	TYPE OF POSSESSION			Y123, jfr U73, jfr V62, jfr W95
	Do you own the house/apartment or is it your own condominium apartment or are you renting? The table is valid for X45 EQ 1.			
	1 Own house	2450	51,8	
	2 Own condominium	752	15,9	
	3 Rent dwelling	1525	32,3	
	4 Trailer	1	0,0	
	Total	4728		
	9 No answer	1		
	Not applicable	413		
		5142		

X48	OWNER OF BUILDING			Y124, U74
	Who owns the building? The table is valid for X47 EQ 3.			
	1 A municipal housing company	730	48,7	
	2 A private housing company/private person	719	47,9	
	3 Another landlord	51	3,4	
	Total	1500		
	9 No answer	25		
	Not applicable	3617		
		5142		

X49	COST OF DWELLING – RENT			Y125, U75, jfr V63, jfr W98
	How much is your rent or charge per month? Add extra cost for fuel or heating if this applies, but do not deduct housing allowance (if any). The table is valid for X47 EQ 2 or 3. This variable is divided into categories.			
	0	3	0,1	
	500-999	8	0,4	
	1000-1999	126	5,6	
	2000-2999	460	20,4	
	3000-3999	594	26,3	
	4000-4999	518	22,9	
	5000-5999	309	13,7	

6000-6999	142	6,3
7000-7999	54	2,4
8000-8999	27	1,2
9000-9999	8	0,4
10000-10999	4	0,2
11000-11999	2	0,1
12000-12999	1	0,0
13000-13999	1	0,0
15000-15999	1	0,0
Total	2258	
99999 No answer	19	
Not applicable	2865	
	5142	
Mean value for all		4020,35
Standard deviation		1558,90
Mean value for >0		4025,70
Standard deviation		1553,02

X50 **DENSITY STANDARD** **Y130, U68, V745, W626**

Index of dwelling space based on the questions about number of rooms in the home and number of persons in the household (X24, X151). The table is valid for X23 NE 5.

1 Very high	485	9,4
2 High	1613	31,4
3 Good	1494	29,1
4 Acceptable	756	14,7
5 Bad	652	12,7
6 Overcrowded	130	2,5
7 Extremely overcrowded	10	0,2
Total	5140	
9 No answer	1	
Living in an institution	1	
	5142	

X51 **BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN**

Were both of your parents born in Sweden? Question not asked to panel.

1 Yes	965	69,9
2 No	415	30,1
Total	1380	
9 Question not asked	3762	
	5142	

X52 **SWEDISH PARENTS** **jfr Y15, jfr U15, jfr V6, jfr W4**

Were both of your parents Swedish citizens at the time of your birth? The table is valid for X51NE 1.

1 Yes	3367	80,7
2 No	124	3,0
3 Both had other citizenship	681	16,3
Total	4172	
9 No answer	5	

	Parents born in Sweden	965	
		5142	
X53	BIRTH COUNTRY – FATHER		jfr Y16, jfr U16, jfr V7, jfr W4
	What is the birth country of your father?		
	1 Sweden	4346	84,5
	2 Denmark, Norway	77	1,5
	3 Finland	175	3,4
	4 Former Yugoslavia (when defining Yug.)	78	1,5
	5 Other Eastern Europe, incl. former East Germany	89	1,7
	6 Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	66	1,3
	7 Spain, Italy, Greece	16	0,3
	8 Other nationalities	293	5,7
	9 Unknown	2	0,0
		5142	
X54	BIRTH COUNTRY – MOTHER		jfr Y17, jfr U17, jfr V8, jfr W5
	What is the birth country of your mother?		
	1 Sweden	4352	84,6
	2 Denmark, Norway	78	1,5
	3 Finland	212	4,1
	4 Former Yugoslavia (when defining Yug.)	74	1,4
	5 Other Eastern Europe, incl. former East Germany	83	1,6
	6 Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	49	1,0
	7 Spain, Italy, Greece	10	0,2
	8 Other nationalities	282	5,5
	9 Unknown	2	0,0
		5142	
X55	HOME LANGUAGE		jfr Y18, jfr U18, jfr V9, jfr W6
	During your childhood and adolescence, i.e., up to your 16th birthday, what language was spoken most in your home? The table is valid for X51 NE 1.		
	1 Swedish	250	28,4
	2 Danish, Norwegian	49	5,6
	3 Finnish	104	11,8
	4 Serbo-Croatian, Serbian, Croatian, Yugoslavian	17	1,9
	5 Other Eastern European languages, incl. Hungarian	104	11,8
	6 German	29	3,3
	7 English	15	1,7
	8 French, Spanish, Italian	33	3,8
	9 Other	248	28,2
	12	1	0,1
	13	5	0,6
	15	3	0,3
	16	1	0,1
	17	1	0,1
	19	5	0,6
	55	1	0,1
	72	1	0,1

78	1	0,1
79	1	0,1
89	1	0,1
98	1	0,1
99	9	1,0
Total	880	
11 No answer	1	
Not applicable	4261	
	5142	
Two digits = a combination of two languages		

X56 **AGE AT IMMIGRATION** **jfr Y19, jfr U19, jfr V10, jfr W7**

Were you born in Sweden or in another country? If another country: How old were you when you came to Sweden? The table is valid for X51NE 1.

10 In Sweden	231	26,2
21 In another country < 7 years	73	8,3
22 In another country, 7-16 years	91	10,3
23 In another country, >16 years	486	55,2
Total	881	
Not applicable	4261	
	5142	

X57 **COUNTRY OF ORIGIN**

In which country were you born? Question not asked to panel.

1 Sweden	1082	78,4
2 Denmark, Norway	11	0,8
3 Finland	29	2,1
4 Yugoslavia	57	4,1
5 Eastern Europe, incl. East Germany	25	1,8
6 Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	12	0,9
7 Spain, Italy, Greece	6	0,4
8 Other	154	11,2
9 Unknown	4	0,3
Total	1380	
0 Question not asked	3762	
	5142	

X58 **ABILITY TO SPEAK SWEDISH**

How would you evaluate your ability to speak Swedish? Do you think your Swedish is quite good, fairly good, fairly bad or quite bad? The table is valid for X51 NE 1, X56 NE 10 or 21, X57 NE 1 and X12 EQ 1.

1 Quite good	77	37,0
2 Fairly good	110	52,9
3 Fairly bad	18	8,7
4 Quite bad	3	1,4
Total	208	
9 No answer	3	
Not applicable	4931	
	5142	

X59

RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION – FATHER

What is/was the religious affiliation of your father? Question not asked to panel.

1 Protestant Christianity	995	75,3
2 Catholic Christianity	57	4,3
3 Orthodox Christianity	47	3,6
4 Islam	128	9,7
5 Judaism	2	0,2
6 Hinduism	3	0,2
7 Buddhism	10	0,8
8 Other	2	0,2
9 No religious affiliation	78	5,9
Total	1322	
98 Doesn't know	53	
99 Doesn't want to report	5	
Question not asked	3762	
	5142	

X60

RELIGIOUS AFFILIATION – MOTHER

What is/was the religious affiliation of your mother? Question not asked to panel.

1 Protestant Christianity	1026	77,0
2 Catholic Christianity	54	4,1
3 Orthodox Christianity	46	3,5
4 Islam	126	9,5
5 Judaism	2	0,2
6 Hinduism	3	0,2
7 Buddhism	9	0,7
8 Other	1	0,1
9 No religious affiliation	66	5,0
Total	1333	
98 Doesn't know	43	
99 Doesn't want to report	4	
Question not asked	3762	
	5142	

X61

NUMBER OF SIBLINGS, TOTAL

Do you have or have you had siblings? If yes: How many?

0	437	8,5
1	1638	31,9
2	1282	24,9
3	755	14,7
4	377	7,3
5	243	4,7
6	165	3,2
7	88	1,7
8	49	1,0
9	38	0,7
10	34	0,7

jfr Y34, jfr
U28, jfr
V22, jfr
W30

11	13	0,3
12	7	0,1
13	9	0,2
14	1	0,0
15	5	0,1
17	1	0,0
	5142	

X62

NUMBER OF SIBLINGS ALIVE

If you have siblings, how many of them are alive?

0	152	3,2
1	1712	36,4
2	1288	27,4
3	713	15,2
4	359	7,6
5	189	4,0
6	150	3,2
7	59	1,3
8	32	0,7
9	23	0,5
10	17	0,4
11	4	0,1
12	4	0,1
13	1	0,0
15	2	0,0
Total	4705	
Does not have siblings	437	
	5142	

X63

NUMBER OF BROTHERS, TOTAL

If you have siblings, how many of them are your brothers?

0	1246	26,5
1	1917	40,7
2	873	18,6
3	382	8,1
4	172	3,7
5	63	1,3
6	31	0,7
7	12	0,3
8	6	0,1
9	2	0,0
13	1	0,0
Total	4705	
Does not have siblings	437	
	5142	

X64

NUMBER OF BROTHERS ALIVE

If you have brothers, how many of them are alive?

0	1458	31,0
1	1899	40,4
2	830	17,6
3	321	6,8
4	131	2,8
5	32	0,7
6	23	0,5
7	10	0,2
8	1	0,0
Total	4705	
Does not have siblings	437	
	5142	

X65

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 1

What is the year of birth of sibling 1? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	13	0,3
10-19	93	2,0
20-29	318	6,9
30-39	562	12,2
40-49	876	19,1
50-59	803	17,5
60-69	927	20,2
70-79	751	16,4
80-89	236	5,1
90-99	13	0,3
Total	4592	
-1 No answer	113	
Does not have siblings	437	
	5142	

X66

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 2

What is the year of birth of sibling 2? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	8	0,3
10-19	60	2,0
20-29	202	6,9
30-39	342	11,6
40-49	544	18,5
50-59	571	19,4
60-69	530	18,0
70-79	424	14,4
80-89	233	7,9
90-99	33	1,1
Total	2947	
-1 No answer	120	
Not applicable	2075	
	5142	

X67

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 3

What is the year of birth of sibling 3? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	5	0,3
10-19	39	2,3
20-29	113	6,8
30-39	224	13,5
40-49	315	18,9
50-59	311	18,7
60-69	305	18,3
70-79	190	11,4
80-89	130	7,8
90-99	32	1,9
Total	1664	
-1 No answer	121	
Not applicable	3357	
	5142	

X68

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 4

What is the year of birth of sibling 4? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	3	0,3
10-19	26	2,8
20-29	72	7,8
30-39	129	14,0
40-49	176	19,1
50-59	176	19,1
60-69	161	17,5
70-79	85	9,2
80-89	76	8,2
90-99	18	2,0
Total	922	
-1 No answer	108	
Not applicable	4112	
	5142	

X69

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 5

What is the year of birth of sibling 5? This variable is divided into categories.

10-19	19	3,4
20-29	45	8,1
30-39	87	15,7
40-49	133	24,0
50-59	94	17,0
60-69	82	14,8
70-79	53	9,6
80-89	28	5,1
90-99	13	2,3
Total	554	
-1 No answer	99	
Not applicable	4489	
	5142	

X70

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 6

What is the year of birth of sibling 6? This variable is divided into categories.

10-19	12	3,6
20-29	26	7,8
30-39	67	20,2
40-49	59	17,8
50-59	62	18,7
60-69	47	14,2
70-79	32	9,6
80-89	18	5,4
90-99	9	2,7
Total	332	
-1 No answer	78	
Not applicable	4732	
	5142	

X71

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 7

What is the year of birth of sibling 7? This variable is divided into categories.

10-19	7	3,7
20-29	16	8,4
30-39	43	22,6
40-49	27	14,2
50-59	30	15,8
60-69	31	16,3
70-79	19	10,0
80-89	13	6,8
90-99	4	2,1
Total	190	
-1 No answer	55	
Not applicable	4897	
	5142	

X72

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 8

What is the year of birth of sibling 8? This variable is divided into categories.

10-19	1	0,9
20-29	12	10,3
30-39	27	23,3
40-49	24	20,7
50-59	13	11,2
60-69	15	12,9
70-79	16	13,8
80-89	7	6,0
90-99	1	0,9
Total	116	
-1 No answer	41	
Not applicable	4985	
	5142	

X73

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 9

What is the year of birth of sibling 9? This variable is divided into categories.

20-29	10	12,5
-------	----	------

30-39	18	22,5
40-49	19	23,8
50-59	11	13,8
60-69	9	11,3
70-79	5	6,3
80-89	7	8,8
90-99	1	1,3
Total	80	
-1 No answer	28	
Not applicable	5034	
	5142	

X74

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 10

What is the year of birth of sibling 10? This variable is divided into categories.

10-19	1	2,0
20-29	7	13,7
30-39	9	17,6
40-49	14	27,5
50-59	9	17,6
60-69	4	7,8
70-79	2	3,9
80-89	3	5,9
90-99	2	3,9
Total	51	
-1 No answer	19	
Not applicable	5072	
	5142	

X75

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 11

What is the year of birth of sibling 11? This variable is divided into categories.

20-29	2	8,7
30-39	5	21,7
40-49	12	52,2
50-59	1	4,3
60-69	1	4,3
70-79	1	4,3
80-89	1	4,3
Total	23	
-1 No answer	13	
Not applicable	5106	
	5142	

X76

YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 12

What is the year of birth of sibling 12? This variable is divided into categories.

20-29	1	7,7
30-39	5	38,5
40-49	5	38,5
50-59	1	7,7
90-99	1	7,7
Total	13	

	-1 No answer	10	
	Not applicable	5119	
		5142	
X77	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 13		
	What is the year of birth of sibling 13? This variable is divided into categories.		
	20-29	1	12,5
	40-49	6	75,0
	90-99	1	12,5
	Total	8	
	-1 No answer	8	
	Not applicable	5126	
		5142	
X78	YEAR OF BIRTH SIBLING 14		
	What is the year of birth of sibling 14?		
	27	1	33,3
	44	1	33,3
	50	1	33,3
	Total	3	
	-1 No answer	4	
	Not applicable	5135	
		5142	
X79	SEX SIBLING 1		
	Is sibling 1 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	2418	51,6
	2 Sister	2264	48,4
	Total	4682	
	9 No answer	23	
	Does not have siblings	437	
		5142	
X80	SEX SIBLING 2		
	Is sibling 2 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	1548	51,0
	2 Sister	1489	49,0
	Total	3037	
	9 No answer	30	
	Not applicable	2075	
		5142	
X81	SEX SIBLING 3		
	Is sibling 3 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	911	51,9
	2 Sister	843	48,1
	Total	1754	

	9	No answer	31	
		Not applicable	3357	
			5142	
X82		SEX SIBLING 4		
		Is sibling 4 a brother or a sister?		
	1	Brother	513	51,2
	2	Sister	489	48,8
		Total	1002	
	9	No answer	28	
		Not applicable	4112	
			5142	
X83		SEX SIBLING 5		
		Is sibling 5 a brother or a sister?		
	1	Brother	295	47,2
	2	Sister	330	52,8
		Total	625	
	9	No answer	28	
		Not applicable	4489	
			5142	
X84		SEX SIBLING 6		
		Is sibling 6 a brother or a sister?		
	1	Brother	176	45,8
	2	Sister	208	54,2
		Total	384	
	9	No answer	26	
		Not applicable	4732	
			5142	
X85		SEX SIBLING 7		
		Is sibling 7 a brother or a sister?		
	1	Brother	122	54,0
	2	Sister	104	46,0
		Total	226	
	9	No answer	19	
		Not applicable	4897	
			5142	
X86		SEX SIBLING 8		
		Is sibling 8 a brother or a sister?		
	1	Brother	63	45,3
	2	Sister	76	54,7
		Total	139	
	9	No answer	18	
		Not applicable	4985	

		5142	
X87	SEX SIBLING 9		
	Is sibling 9 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	43	44,8
	2 Sister	53	55,2
	Total	96	
	9 No answer	12	
	Not applicable	5034	
		5142	
X88	SEX SIBLING 10		
	Is sibling 10 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	33	53,2
	2 Sister	29	46,8
	Total	62	
	9 No answer	8	
	Not applicable	5072	
		5142	
X89	SEX SIBLING 11		
	Is sibling 11 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	17	56,7
	2 Sister	13	43,3
	Total	30	
	9 No answer	6	
	Not applicable	5106	
		5142	
X90	SEX SIBLING 12		
	Is sibling 12 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	10	55,6
	2 Sister	8	44,4
	Total	18	
	9 No answer	5	
	Not applicable	5119	
		5142	
X91	SEX SIBLING 13		
	Is sibling 13 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	8	66,7
	2 Sister	4	33,3
	Total	12	
	9 No answer	4	
	Not applicable	5126	

		5142	
X92	SEX SIBLING 14		
	Is sibling 14 a brother or a sister?		
	1 Brother	3	60,0
	2 Sister	2	40,0
	Total	5	
	9 No answer	2	
	Not applicable	5135	
		5142	
X93	AGE-POSITION AMONG SIBLINGS		
	Respondent's age-position among the siblings.		
	1	2179	42,4
	2	1601	31,1
	3	709	13,8
	4	318	6,2
	5	159	3,1
	6	75	1,5
	7	50	1,0
	8	22	0,4
	9	9	0,2
	10	13	0,3
	11	4	0,1
	12	2	0,0
	15	1	0,0
		5142	
X94	INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY		jfr Y20, jfr U20, jfr V11, jfr W20
	Did you live with both your natural (biological) parents during your whole childhood, i.e. up to age 16? If no: Why not?		
	10 Yes	4120	80,1
	21 Divorce, judicial separation, separation	580	11,3
	22 Parents never lived together	100	1,9
	23 Both parents deceased	12	0,2
	24 Father deceased	132	2,6
	25 Mother deceased	82	1,6
	26 Lived with foster parents	62	1,2
	27 Lived with adoptive parents	42	0,8
	28 Did not grow up with both, no reason	11	0,2
	Total	5141	
	99 No answer	1	
		5142	
X95	RELATIONS WITH PARENT LIVING ELSEWHERE		
	During the period when your parents did not live together, how often did you see the parent with whom you did not mainly live? The table is valid for X94 EQ 21 or 22.		
	1 Several times a week	85	12,7
	2 About once a week	79	11,8

	3	1-3 times a month	148	22,2
	4	Less often	209	31,3
	5	Never	146	21,9
		Total	667	
	9	No answer	13	
		Not applicable	4462	
			5142	
X96	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL MOTHER EPISODE 1			
	From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive mother during childhood (0-16 years). Value 0011 means that the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive mother between 0 and 11 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her mother at the time of the interview. 983 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).			
X97	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL MOTHER EPISODE 2			
	From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive mother a second time during childhood (0-16 years). Value 1214 means that the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive mother a second time during childhood between 12 and 14 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her mother at the time of the interview. 62 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).			
X98	NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL MOTHER			
	Number of years the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive mother during childhood (0-16 years).			
	-1	Lived with both parents during childhood	4120	80,2
	0	Not lived with biological/adoptive mother	43	0,8
	1		17	0,3
	2		22	0,4
	3		22	0,4
	4		21	0,4
	5		17	0,3
	6		21	0,4
	7		13	0,3
	8		18	0,4
	9		12	0,2
	10		31	0,6
	11		20	0,4
	12		29	0,6
	13		28	0,5
	14		38	0,7
	15		32	0,6
	16		636	12,4
		Total	5140	
	99	No answer	2	
			5142	
X99	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL FATHER EPISODE 1			
	From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive father during childhood (0-16 years). Value 0011 means that the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive father between 0 and 11 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her father at the time of the interview. 828 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).			
X100	AGE LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL FATHER EPISODE 2			
	From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive father a second time during childhood (0-16 years). Value 1214 means that the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive father a second time during childhood between 12 and 14 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her father			

at the time of the interview. 64 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X101

NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH BIOLOGICAL FATHER

Number of years the respondent lived with his/her biological/adoptive father during childhood (0-16 years).

-1 Lived with both parents during childhood	4120	80,2
0 Not lived with biological/adoptive father	210	4,1
1	45	0,9
2	38	0,7
3	66	1,3
4	46	0,9
5	43	0,8
6	43	0,8
7	33	0,6
8	32	0,6
9	34	0,7
10	41	0,8
11	41	0,8
12	47	0,9
13	55	1,1
14	49	1,0
15	43	0,8
16	149	2,9
Total	5135	
99 No answer	7	
	5142	

X102

AGE LIVING WITH STEPMOTHER EPISODE 1

From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her stepmother/foster mother during childhood (0-16 years). Value 0011 means that the respondent lived with his/her stepmother/foster mother between 0 and 11 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her stepmother/foster mother at the time of the interview. 158 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X103

AGE LIVING WITH STEPMOTHER EPISODE 2

From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her stepmother/foster mother a second time during childhood (0-16 years). Value 1214 means that the respondent lived with his/her stepmother/foster mother a second time during childhood between 12 and 14 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her stepmother/foster mother at the time of the interview. 6 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X104

NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH STEPMOTHER

Number of years the respondent lived with his/her stepmother/foster mother during childhood (0-16 years).

-1 Lived with both parents during childhood	4120	80,2
0 Not lived with stepmother	862	16,8
1	7	0,1
2	12	0,2
3	11	0,2
4	10	0,2
5	10	0,2
6	20	0,4
7	2	0,0
8	9	0,2

9	10	0,2
10	11	0,2
11	6	0,1
12	5	0,1
13	11	0,2
14	9	0,2
15	11	0,2
16	12	0,2
Total	5138	
99 No answer	4	
	5142	

X105

AGE LIVING WITH STEPFATHER EPISODE 1

From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her stepfather/foster father during childhood (0-16 years). Value 0011 means that the respondent lived with his/her stepfather/foster father between 0 and 11 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her stepfather/foster father at the time of the interview. 368 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X106

AGE LIVING WITH STEPFATHER EPISODE 2

From and to what age the respondent lived with his/her stepfather/foster father a second time during childhood (0-16 years). Value 1214 means that the respondent lived with his/her stepfather/foster father a second time during childhood between 12 and 14 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with his/her stepfather/foster father at the time of the interview. 23 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X107

NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH STEPFATHER

Number of years the respondent lived with his/her stepfather/foster father during childhood (0-16 years).

-1 Lived with both parents during childhood	4120	80,2
0 Not lived with stepfather	653	12,7
1	22	0,4
2	24	0,5
3	18	0,4
4	18	0,4
5	15	0,3
6	23	0,4
7	36	0,7
8	25	0,5
9	26	0,5
10	35	0,7
11	18	0,4
12	25	0,5
13	22	0,4
14	25	0,5
15	17	0,3
16	18	0,4
Total	5140	
99 No answer	2	
	5142	

X108

AGE LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT EPISODE 1

From and to what age the respondent lived with another guardian (e.g. grandparents) during childhood (0-16

years). Value 0011 means that the respondent lived with another guardian (e.g. grandparents) between 0 and 11 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with another guardian at the time of the interview. 141 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X109

AGE LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT EPISODE 2

From and to what age the respondent lived with another guardian (e.g. grandparents) a second time during childhood (0-16 years). Value 1214 means that the respondent lived with another guardian (e.g. grandparents) a second time during childhood between 12 and 14 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with another guardian at the time of the interview. 11 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X110

AGE LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT EPISODE 3

From and to what age the respondent lived with another guardian (e.g. grandparents) a third time during childhood (0-16 years). Value 1516 means that the respondent lived with another guardian (e.g. grandparents) a third time during childhood between 15 and 16 years of age. Value 17 indicates that respondent still lives with another guardian at the time of the interview. 2 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X111

NUMBER OF YEARS LIVING WITH ANOTHER ADULT

Number of years the respondent lived with another guardian (e.g. grandparents) during childhood (0-16 years).

-1 Lived with both parents during childhood	4120	80,2
0 Not lived with another adult	878	17,1
1	12	0,2
2	13	0,3
3	12	0,2
4	13	0,3
5	7	0,1
6	10	0,2
7	6	0,1
8	8	0,2
9	4	0,1
10	7	0,1
11	7	0,1
12	2	0,0
13	7	0,1
14	4	0,1
15	4	0,1
16	24	0,5
Total	5138	
99 No answer	4	
	5142	

X112

WHO DOES RESPONDENT REGARD AS MOTHER

Who do you regard as your mother? (If respondent has lived with a stepmother (or other female guardian)).

1 Biological mother	184	68,7
2 Stepmother/other	83	31,0
3 Does not regard anyone as mother	1	0,4
Total	268	
9 No answer	18	
Not applicable	4856	
	5142	

X113	WHO DOES RESPONDENT REGARD AS FATHER		
	Who do you regard as your father? (If respondent has lived with a stepfather (or other male guardian)).		
	1 Biological father	238	63,8
	2 Stepfather/other	130	34,9
	3 Does not regard anyone as father	5	1,3
	Total	373	
	9 No answer	39	
	Not applicable	4730	
		5142	
X114	LIVED WITH STEPSIBLINGS		
	Have you at any time during your childhood/adolescence lived with a stepbrother or stepsister? The table is valid for X94 NE 10.		
	1 Yes	276	28,0
	2 No	709	72,0
	Total	985	
	9 No answer	37	
	Not applicable	4120	
		5142	
X115	MOVED FROM PARENTAL HOME YEAR/MONTH		
	When did you move away from your parental home for the first time? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.		
	35-39	4	0,1
	40-44	74	1,5
	45-49	186	3,8
	50-54	311	6,4
	55-59	345	7,1
	60-64	427	8,7
	65-69	557	11,4
	70-74	533	10,9
	75-79	454	9,3
	80-84	455	9,3
	85-89	537	11,0
	90-94	508	10,4
	95-99	448	9,2
	2000	44	0,9
	Total	4883	
	0 Has not moved away from home	234	
	9999 No answer	25	
		5142	
X116	CONFLICT IN CHILDHOOD FAMILY		
	Was there any serious friction in your family while you were growing up?		
	1 Yes	610	11,9
	2 Uncertain	147	2,9
	3 No	4366	85,2
	Total	5123	
			jfr Y42, U26, V20, W29

	9 No answer	19	
		5142	
X117	CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENTS		
	Was there any serious friction between your biological parents? The table is valid for X116 NE 2 or 3.		
	1 Yes	458	76,5
	2 No	141	23,5
	Total	599	
	9 No answer	30	
	Not applicable	4513	
		5142	
X118	CONFLICT BIOLOGICAL PARENT AND STEPPARENT		
	Was there any serious friction between a biological parent and a stepparent? The table is valid for X116 NE 2 or 3.		
	1 Yes	54	9,2
	2 No	535	90,8
	Total	589	
	9 No answer	40	
	Not applicable	4513	
		5142	
X119	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL MOTHER		
	Was there any serious friction between you and your biological mother? The table is valid for X116 NE 2 or 3.		
	1 Yes	100	16,9
	2 No	492	83,1
	Total	592	
	9 No answer	37	
	Not applicable	4513	
		5142	
X120	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND BIOLOGICAL FATHER		
	Was there any serious friction between you and your biological father? The table is valid for X116 NE 2 or 3.		
	1 Yes	91	15,5
	2 No	497	84,5
	Total	588	
	9 No answer	41	
	Not applicable	4513	
		5142	
X121	CONFLICT RESPONDENT AND STEPMOTHER OR STEPFATHER		
	Was there any serious friction between you and your stepmother or stepfather? The table is valid for X116 NE 2 or 3.		
	1 Yes	41	7,0
	2 No	547	93,0
	Total	588	

	9 No answer	41	
	Not applicable	4513	
		5142	
X122	CONFLICT BETWEEN OTHERS, WHO...		
	Was there any serious friction between others, who? The table is valid for X116 NE 2 or 3.		
	1 Yes	106	17,9
	2 No	486	82,1
	Total	592	
	9 No answer	37	
	Not applicable	4513	
		5142	
X123	FATHER'S EDUCATION		jfr Y22, jfr U22, jfr V13, jfr W22
	Did your father (foster father) receive any education apart from elementary or compulsory school? If yes: Which of the following best describes your father's level of education?		
	1 Elementary or compulsory school only		
	2 Vocational education above elementary/compulsory level		
	3 Lower secondary school, 2-year social/econ./techn. program at upper secondary level		
	4 Upper secondary school exam (cf. A-level, Abitur, Bac), 3- to 4-year academic program		
	5 University or university college education		
	6 University degree		
	7 Father has not been at school		
	8 Do not know		
	Total		
	9 No answer		
X124	MOTHER'S EDUCATION		jfr Y23, jfr U23, jfr V14, jfr W23
	Did your mother (foster mother) receive any education apart from elementary or compulsory school? If yes: Which of the following best describes your mother's level of education?		
	1 Elementary or compulsory school only		
	2 Vocational education above elementary/compulsory level		
	3 Lower secondary school, 2-year social/econ./techn. program at upper secondary level		
	4 Upper secondary school exam (cf. A-level, Abitur, Bac), 3- to 4-year academic program		
	5 University or university college education		
	6 University degree		
	7 Father has not been at school		
	8 Do not know		
	Total		
	9 No answer		
X126	SEI FATHER		jfr Y24, jfr U150
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your father's (foster father's) main occupation? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".		

11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	803	15,9
12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	433	8,5
21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	891	17,6
22 Skilled manual worker, service production	50	1,0
33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	96	1,9
35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	128	2,5
36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	254	5,0
45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	91	1,8
46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	472	9,3
56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	433	8,5
57 Professional, upper-level executive*	108	2,1
60 Self-employed professionals	14	0,3
71 Self-employed without employees	274	5,4
72 Self-employed, 1-9 employees	308	6,1
73 Self-employed, 10-19 employees	52	1,0
74 Self-employed 20+ employees	79	1,6
86 Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	8	0,2
87 Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	226	4,5
89 Farmer, size of farm unknown	334	6,6
Total	12	0,2
Total	5066	
99 Unclassified	76	
	5142	

*This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.

X127

NYK80 FATHER

Y25

Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your father’s (foster father’s) main occupation? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 (“Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK”). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.

X128

NYK85 FATHER

Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your father’s (foster father’s) main occupation? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 (“Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK”). A list of codes was published by SCB’s Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.

X129

FATHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES

jfr Y27, jfr U152, jfr V16, jfr W25

Was your father at any point during your childhood self-employed?

1 Yes, no employees	451	9,4
2 Yes, 1-9 employees	421	8,7
3 Yes, 10-19 employees	134	2,8
4 Yes, 20 or more employees	144	3,0
5 No	3664	76,1
Total	4814	
9 No answer	328	
	5142	

X130

FATHER FARMER: AREA

Y28, U153, jfr V16, jfr

If father (foster father) was a farmer: How large was the farm?

			W25
	1 Small farm	297	44,3
	2 Average farm	342	51,0
	3 Large farm	31	4,6
	Total	670	
	0 Question not asked (father not farmer)	4455	
	9 No answer	17	
		5142	
X132	SEI MOTHER		jfr Y29, jfr U159
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother's (foster mother's) main occupation? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	318	6,3
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	999	19,7
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	39	0,8
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	167	3,3
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	281	5,5
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	20	0,4
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	191	3,8
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	26	0,5
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	429	8,4
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	175	3,4
	57 Professional, upper-level executive*	10	0,2
	60 Self-employed professionals	63	1,2
	71 Self-employed without employees	58	1,1
	72 Self-employed, 1-9 employees	5	0,1
	73 Self-employed, 10-19 employees	6	0,1
	74 Self-employed 20+ employees	3	0,1
	86 Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	115	2,3
	87 Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	156	3,1
	89 Farmer, size of farm unknown	1	0,0
	92 Homemaker	2019	39,7
	Total	5081	
	99 Unclassified	61	
		5142	
	* This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.		
X133	NYK80 MOTHER		Y30
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother's (foster mother's) main occupation? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.		
X134	NYK85 MOTHER		
	Looking back at your childhood – up to age 16 when you (mostly) were at school – what was your mother's (foster mother's) main occupation? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.		
X135	MOTHER SELF-EMPLOYED: NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES		jfr Y32, jfr U152
	Was your mother at any point during your childhood self-employed ?		

1	Yes, no employees	68	1,9
2	Yes, 1-9 employees	37	1,0
3	Yes, 10-19 employees	4	0,1
4	Yes, 20 or more employees	4	0,1
5	No	3454	96,8
	Total	3567	
9	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	1569	
		5142	

X136

MOTHER FARMER: AREA

**Y33, jfr
U153**

If mother (foster mother) was a farmer: How large was the farm?

1	Small farm	27	48,2
2	Average farm	27	48,2
3	Large farm	2	3,6
	Total	56	
0	Question not asked (mother not farmer)	2936	
9	No answer	2	
	Not applicable	2148	
		5142	

X137

RESPONDENT'S AGE WHEN MOTHER STARTED GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT

If your mother was employed at any time during your childhood, how old were you when you mother began to work outside the home for the first time after your birth?

0		38	3,7
1		185	18,0
2		90	8,8
3		41	4,0
4		28	2,7
5		26	2,5
6		34	3,3
7		40	3,9
8		22	2,1
9		18	1,8
10		22	2,1
11		14	1,4
12		23	2,2
13		17	1,7
14		10	1,0
15		11	1,1
16		2	0,2
17		3	0,3
26		1	0,1
88	Mother was gainfully employed in the home	76	7,4
89	Respondent was over three years old	124	12,1
90	Respondent was under three years old	80	7,8
98	Doesn't know	121	11,8
	Total	1026	
99	No answer	11	
	Not applicable	4105	
		5142	

X138	CHILDHOOD FAMILY'S ECONOMY		Y36, U25, V19, W28
	Did your family experience economic hardship while you were growing up?		
	1 Yes	774	15,1
	2 No	4354	84,9
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	
X139	PARENTS' CAR-OWNING		Y37
	Did your parents own a car during (the greater part of) your childhood?		
	1 Yes	1830	79,8
	2 No	464	20,2
	Total	2294	
	9 No answer	3	
	Question not asked	2845	
		5142	
X140	PARENTS' HOME OWNING		Y39
	Did your parents own their own home (detached, semi-detached, row-house, farmhouse etc.) during (the greater part of) your childhood?		
	1 Yes	1760	76,7
	2 No	534	23,3
	Total	2294	
	9 No answer	3	
	Question not asked	2845	
		5142	
X141	PARENTS OWNING A SUMMER COTTAGE		Y40
	Did your parents own a summer cottage during (the greater part of) your childhood?		
	1 Yes	615	26,8
	2 No	1677	73,2
	Total	2292	
	9 No answer	5	
	Question not asked	2845	
		5142	
X142	NUMBER OF HOME TOWNS		jfr Y44, jfr U30, jfr V24, jfr W9
	In how many places did you live during your childhood, i.e., up to age 16?		
	1	2551	49,8
	2	1249	24,4
	3	683	13,3
	4	315	6,1
	5	156	3,0
	6	69	1,3
	7	39	0,8

8	24	0,5
9	10	0,2
10	15	0,3
11	2	0,0
12	4	0,1
14	1	0,0
15	1	0,0
21	6	0,1
26	1	0,0
35	1	0,0
Total	5127	
99 No answer	15	
	5142	

X143

TYPE OF HOME TOWN

**Y46, U32,
V26, W11**

Where did you live (most of the time) during your childhood (i.e., up to age 16)?

1 In a rural area	1391	27,1
2 Community > 500 inhabitants	1019	19,8
3 Small town < 10 000 inhabitants	412	8,0
4 In a medium size town	1141	22,2
5 In a major town: Sthlm, Gbg, Malmö	775	15,1
6 Abroad	399	7,8
Total	5137	
9 No answer	5	
	5142	

X144

HOME COUNTY – COUNTRY

**Y47, U33,
V27, W12**

In what county did you live (most of the time) during your childhood (i.e., up to age 16)?

1 Stockholms stad	462	9,0
2 Stockholms län	207	4,0
3 Uppsala	113	2,2
4 Södermanlands län	136	2,6
5 Östergötlands län	214	4,2
6 Jönköpings län	178	3,5
7 Kronobergs län	122	2,4
8 Kalmar län	143	2,8
9 Gotlands län	38	0,7
10 Blekinge län	88	1,7
11 Kristianstads län	172	3,3
12 Malmöhus län	357	6,9
13 Hallands län	115	2,2
14 Göteborgs län	422	8,2
15 Älvsborgs län	206	4,0
16 Skaraborgs län	143	2,8
17 Värmlands län	166	3,2
18 Örebro län	182	3,5
19 Västmanlands län	143	2,8
20 Dalarnas län	191	3,7

21 Gävleborgs län	178	3,5
22 Västernorrlands län	174	3,4
23 Jämtlands län	97	1,9
24 Västerbottens län	159	3,1
25 Norrbottens län	168	3,3
30 Norway	45	0,9
31 Finland	104	2,0
32 Former Yugoslavia	76	1,5
33 Eastern Europe, incl. former East Germany	46	0,9
34 Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	34	0,7
35 Spain, Italy, Greece	6	0,1
36 Other countries	256	5,0
Total	5141	
99 No answer	1	
	5142	

X145 HOME MUNICIPALITY Y48, U34, V28, W13

In what municipality did you live (most of the time) during your childhood (i.e., up to age 16)? 5013 respondents have values on this variable (frequency not shown).

X146 NUMBER OF MONTHS AT DAY-CARE CENTRE Y51

If the respondent was born in 1974 or later: Before you began elementary school, were you ever at a day-care centre? If yes: For about how many years and months altogether?

1	1	0,4
6	1	0,4
7	1	0,4
12	32	12,1
18	2	0,8
24	47	17,7
29	1	0,4
30	8	3,0
36	53	20,0
39	1	0,4
42	5	1,9
48	44	16,6
54	6	2,3
60	33	12,5
65	2	0,8
66	10	3,8
69	1	0,4
72	15	5,7
84	2	0,8
Total	265	
88 Has not been at a day-care centre	471	
99 No answer	40	
Not applicable	4366	
	5142	
Mean value		39,66
Standard deviation		18,35

X147 NUMBER OF MONTHS AT THE HOME OF A CHILDMINDER jfr Y52

If the respondent was born in 1974 or later: Before you began elementary school, did you ever spend time at the home of a child minder? If yes: For about how many years and months altogether?

1	3	1,0
2	1	0,3
3	1	0,3
4	1	0,3
5	2	0,6
6	9	2,9
7	1	0,3
9	1	0,3
11	1	0,3
12	50	16,1
18	1	0,3
20	1	0,3
24	80	25,8
29	1	0,3
30	4	1,3
36	41	13,2
37	1	0,3
42	1	0,3
48	32	10,3
50	1	0,3
54	2	0,6
60	20	6,5
66	2	0,6
72	28	9,0
75	1	0,3
78	2	0,6
84	8	2,6
90	1	0,3
91	1	0,3
96	8	2,6
97	4	1,3
Total	310	
Has not been at the home of a child minder	425	
No answer	41	
Not applicable	4366	
	5142	
Mean value		37,57
Standard deviation		24,65

X148

NUMBER OF MONTHS AT KINDERGARTEN

Y53

If the respondent was born in 1974 or later: Before you began elementary school, were you ever at kindergarten or preparatory school? If yes: For about how many years and months altogether?

1	1	0,2
4	1	0,2
6	3	0,6
8	1	0,2
9	3	0,6
10	14	2,7

	11	1	0,2	
	12	420	79,5	
	18	2	0,4	
	24	70	13,3	
	36	9	1,7	
	48	3	0,6	
	Total	528		
	88 Has not been at kindergarten	231		
	99 No answer	17		
	Not applicable	4366		
		5142		
	Mean value		14,08	
	Standard deviation		5,74	
X149	CIVIL STATUS ACCORDING TO INTERVIEW			jfr Y57, jfr U90, jfr V68, jfr W36
	Spouse or partner currently living in household.			
	1 Unmarried	1130	22,0	
	2 Divorced	336	6,5	
	3 Widow(er)	174	3,4	
	4 Cohabitant	1012	19,7	
	5 Married	2490	48,4	
		5142		
X150	YEAR/MONTH START OF CURRENT COHABITATION			
	What year and what month did your current cohabitation start? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.			
	40-49	44	1,3	
	50-59	323	9,2	
	60-69	560	16,0	
	70-79	639	18,3	
	80-89	747	21,4	
	90-99	1083	31,0	
	2000	95	2,7	
	2001	1	0,0	
	Total	3492		
	9999 No answer	10		
	Not cohabiting	1640		
		5142		
X151	NUMBER OF PERSONS IN HOUSEHOLD			jfr Y58, U91, jfr V57, jfr W90
	Number of persons currently living in the household.			
	1	1049	20,40	
	2	1991	38,72	
	3	800	15,56	
	4	889	17,29	
	5	304	5,91	
	6	70	1,36	
	7	23	0,45	
	8	8	0,16	

9	6	0,12
10	1	0,02
12	1	0,02
	5142	
Mean value		2,57
Standard deviation		1,32

X152	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S SEX	
	What is your partner's/cohabitant's sex?	
1	Male	1758 50,2
2	Female	1744 49,8
	Total	3502
	Not cohabiting	1640
		5142

X153	PARTNER'S/COHABITANT'S YEAR OF BIRTH	
	What is your partner's/cohabitant's year of birth? This variable is divided into categories.	
	10-19	8 0,2
	20-29	194 5,5
	30-39	457 13,1
	40-49	759 21,7
	50-59	777 22,2
	60-69	764 21,8
	70-79	524 15,0
	80-89	17 0,5
	Total	3500
99	No answer	2
	Not cohabiting	1640
		5142

X154	NUMBER OF CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD	
	Number of children currently living in the household.	
	0	3172 61,7
	1	729 14,2
	2	864 16,8
	3	284 5,5
	4	61 1,2
	5	19 0,4
	6	7 0,1
	7	5 0,1
	8	1 0,0
		5142
	Mean value for all	0,73
	Standard deviation	1,08
	Mean value for >0	1,89
	Standard deviation	0,92

X155	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD			jfr Y59, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54		
	Number of own children currently living in the household.					
	0	3440	66,9			
	1	681	13,2			
	2	733	14,3			
	3	221	4,3			
	4	45	0,9			
	5	14	0,3			
	6	4	0,1			
	7	2	0,0			
	8	1	0,0			
	10	1	0,0			
		5142				
		Mean value for all	0,61			
	Standard deviation	1,00				
	Mean value for >0	1,83				
	Standard deviation	0,90				
X156	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD			jfr Y60, jfr U92, jfr V949, jfr W54		
	Number of spouse's children currently living in the household.					
	0	5052	98,2			
	1	49	1,0			
	2	34	0,7			
	3	6	0,1			
	5	1	0,0			
		5142				
		Mean value for all	0,03			
		Standard deviation	0,22			
		Mean value for >0	1,56			
		Standard deviation	0,72			
	X157	NUMBER OF CHILDREN BORN 1982-2000 IN HOUSEHOLD				
		Number of children born 1982-2000 currently living in the household.				
0		3386	65,8			
1		679	13,2			
2		757	14,7			
3		242	4,7			
4		53	1,0			
5		13	0,3			
6		8	0,2			
7		2	0,0			
8		1	0,0			
10		1	0,0			
		5142				
		Mean value for all	0,64			
	Standard deviation	1,04				
	Mean value for >0	1,87				

	Standard deviation		0,92
X160	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN BORN 1990-1999 IN HOUSEHOLD		jfr Y81
	Number of younger children born 1990-1999 currently living in the household.		
	0	3966	77,1
	1	603	11,7
	2	469	9,1
	3	87	1,7
	4	11	0,2
	5	6	0,1
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,36
	Standard deviation		0,75
	Mean value for >0		1,60
	Standard deviation		0,71
X161	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999		jfr Y61, jfr U103
	Number of own children living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 1999.		
	0	3551	69,1
	1	640	12,4
	2	686	13,3
	3	189	3,7
	4	49	1,0
	5	17	0,3
	6	8	0,2
	7	1	0,0
	8	1	0,0
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,57
	Standard deviation		0,99
	Mean value for >0		1,84
	Standard deviation		0,91
X162	NUMBER OF OWN CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999 BORN 1982-1999		
	Number of own children born 1982-1999 living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 1999.		
	0	3473	67,5
	1	669	13,0
	2	721	14,0
	3	211	4,1
	4	42	0,8
	5	14	0,3

6	5	0,1
7	2	0,0
8	1	0,0
9	4	0,1
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,60
Standard deviation		1,02
Mean value for >0		1,84
Standard deviation		0,95

X163	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999	jfr Y62, jfr U103
	Number of spouse's or partner's children living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 1999.	
	0	5075 98,7
	1	41 0,8
	2	20 0,4
	3	4 0,1
	4	1 0,0
	5	1 0,0
	5142	
	Mean value for all	0,02
	Standard deviation	0,20
	Mean value for >0	1,52
	Standard deviation	0,80

X164	NUMBER OF SPOUSE'S CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD 1999 BORN 1982-1999	
	Number of spouse's or partner's children born 1982-1999 living in the household during the main part (at least nine months) of 1999.	
	0	5048 98,2
	1	49 1,0
	2	34 0,7
	3	6 0,1
	5	1 0,0
	9	4 0,1
	5142	
	Mean value for all	0,03
	Standard deviation	0,34
	Mean value for >0	1,87
	Standard deviation	1,67

X165	FAMILY TYPE	
	What does your family look like?	
	1 Two cohabitants w common child(ren) only	1462 74,0
	2 Single woman with child(ren)	144 7,3
	3 Single man with child(ren)	54 2,7
	4 Two cohabitants w woman's child(ren) only	40 2,0
	5 Two cohabitants w man's child(ren) only	9 0,5
	6 Two cohabitants w own, and possibly common,	41 2,1

	child(ren)		
	7 Other	226	11,4
	Total	1976	
	Not applicable	3166	
		5142	
X166	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1		Y63
	Year of birth for the youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		
	50-59	7	0,4
	60-69	14	0,7
	70-79	77	3,9
	80-89	655	33,3
	90-99	1126	57,3
	2000	87	4,4
	Total	1966	
	Does not have children	3176	
		5142	
X167	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2		Y64
	Year of birth for the second youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		
	60-69	3	0,2
	70-79	74	6,0
	80-89	556	45,0
	90-99	601	48,7
	2000	1	0,1
	Total	1235	
	Not applicable	3907	
		5142	
X168	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3		Y65
	Year of birth for the third youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		
	60-69	1	0,3
	70-79	23	6,2
	80-89	232	62,2
	90-99	117	31,4
	Total	373	
	Not applicable	4769	
		5142	
X169	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 4		Y66
	Year of birth for the fourth youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		
	70-79	5	5,6
	80-89	66	74,2
	90-99	18	20,2
	Total	89	

	Not applicable	5053	
		5142	
X170	YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 5		Y67
	Year of birth for the fifth youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household. This variable is divided into categories.		
	70-79	2	6,5
	80-89	24	77,4
	90-99	5	16,1
	Total	31	
	Not applicable	5111	
		5142	
X171	SEX CHILD 1		
	Sex of the youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
	1 Male	1025	52,1
	2 Female	941	47,9
	Total	1966	
	Does not have children	3176	
		5142	
X172	SEX CHILD 2		
	Sex of the second youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
	1 Male	657	53,2
	2 Female	578	46,8
	Total	1235	
	Not applicable	3907	
		5142	
X173	SEX CHILD 3		
	Sex of the third youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
	1 Male	184	49,3
	2 Female	189	50,7
	Total	373	
	Not applicable	4769	
		5142	
X174	SEX CHILD 4		
	Sex of the fourth youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
	1 Male	39	43,8
	2 Female	50	56,2
	Total	89	
	Not applicable	5053	
		5142	

X175	SEX CHILD 5		
	Sex of the fifth youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently living in the household.		
	1 Male	14	45,2
	2 Female	17	54,8
	Total	31	
	Not applicable	5111	
		5142	
X176	LIVES WITH PARENT		Y68
	Currently cohabiting with parent.		
	0 No	4857	94,5
	1 Yes	285	5,5
		5142	
X177	HOUSEHOLD WITH THREE GENERATIONS		Y69
	Currently living in a household with three generations.		
	1 Respondent's grandparent	3	21,4
	2 Respondent's child(ren) and parent	3	21,4
	3 Respondent's grandchild(ren)	8	57,1
	Total	14	
	Not living in household with three generations	5128	
		5142	
X178	MARRIED/COHABITING 1999 AND 2000		Y71, U110
	Spouse or partner in household during the main part of 1999 (at least nine months) and during 2000 at time of interview.		
	1 Married-cohabiting 99+00	3289	64,0
	2 Unmarried 99, married 00	208	4,0
	3 Married 99, Unmarried 00	77	1,5
	4 Unmarried 99+00	1563	30,4
	5 Married-cohabiting 99+00 different partner	5	0,1
	Total	5142	
X179	OTHER CHILDREN 1999, NOT IN HOUSEHOLD 2000		Y70
	Sex of the youngest child (own and/or spouse's/partner's) currently not living in the household.		
	1	130	87,8
	2	15	10,1
	3	2	1,4
	4	1	0,7
	Total	148	
	Not applicable	4994	
		5142	
X181	EMPLOYMENT STATUS SPOUSE		

What is your spouse's/partner's employment status?

1	Employed	2144	61,3
2	Self-employed	352	10,1
3	On parental leave (on leave from work)	49	1,4
4	Working in the home	53	1,5
5	Pensioner	439	12,6
6	Studying	176	5,0
7	Unemployed	115	3,3
8	Early retirement pensioner	137	3,9
9	Other	30	0,9
	Total	3495	
11	No answer	7	
	Not cohabiting	1640	
		5142	

X182

SEI SPOUSE

**jfr Y72, jfr
U117, jfr
V711**

What is your spouse's main occupation? (What is his/her position in the workplace called?) Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI". Pensioners and household workers are coded according to their previous occupation.

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	216	6,3
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	556	16,3
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	367	10,8
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	223	6,5
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	153	4,5
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	57	1,7
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	267	7,8
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	41	1,2
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	671	19,7
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	377	11,1
57	Professional, upper-level executive	71	2,1
60	Self-employed professionals	39	1,1
71	Self-employed without employees	153	4,5
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	120	3,5
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	21	0,6
74	Self-employed 20+ employees	19	0,6
79	Self-employed, unknown number of employees	11	0,3
86	Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	10	0,3
87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	32	0,9
89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	3	0,1
	Total	3407	
99	Unclassified	95	
	Not cohabiting	1640	
		5142	

X183

NYK80 SPOUSE

Y73, U119

What is your spouse's main occupation? (What is the term for his/her position in the workplace?) Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.

X184

NYK85 SPOUSE

What is your spouse's main occupation? (What is the term for his/her position in the workplace?) Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.

X185	SPOUSE'S EGP			Y672
	Spouse's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).			
	1 Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	39	1,1	
	2 Ib Higher-grade professionals	467	13,7	
	3 II Lower-grade professionals	684	20,1	
	4 IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	482	14,1	
	5 IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	355	10,4	
	6 IVa Small proprietors with employees	152	4,5	
	7 IVb Small proprietors without employees	153	4,5	
	8 IVc Farmers	32	0,9	
	9 IVd Smallholders	13	0,4	
	10 Vs Supervisors	76	2,2	
	11 Vj Supervisors in primary production	2	0,1	
	12 VIs Skilled manual workers	368	10,8	
	13 VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	2	0,1	
	14 VIIs Unskilled manual workers	567	16,6	
	15 VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	15	0,4	
	Total	3407		
	99 Unclassified	95		
	Not cohabiting	1640		
		5142		

X186	EMPLOYMENT STATUS SPOUSE			jfr Y74, jfr U118, jfr V710
	What is your spouse's/partner's current occupational status?			
	1 Working	2544	73,4	
	2 Working in the home	53	1,5	
	3 Pensioner	439	12,7	
	4 Studying	176	5,1	
	5 Long-term unemployed	115	3,3	
	6 Early retirement pensioner	137	4,0	
	Total	3464		
	9 No answer	38		
	Not cohabiting	1640		
		5142		

X187	SPOUSE SELF-EMPLOYED: EMPLOYEES			jfr Y75, jfr U120
	If spouse/partner is self-employed or a farmer: Does he/she have any employees?			
	1 No employees	229	54,7	
	2 1-9 employees	143	34,1	
	3 10-19 employees	26	6,2	
	4 20 or more employees	21	5,0	
	Total	419		
	9 No answer	4		

	Not applicable	4719	
		5142	
X188	SPOUSE FARMER: SIZE		jfr Y76, jfr U121
	If spouse/partner is a farmer: How large is the farm?		
	1 Small farm	12	19,7
	2 Average farm	44	72,1
	3 Large farm	5	8,2
	Total	61	
	9 No answer	2	
	Not applicable	5079	
		5142	
X189	SPOUSE CURRENT WORKING HOURS		Y77, U111
	If spouse/partner: How many hours per week does your spouse/partner currently work? This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	926	26,9
	1-4	7	0,2
	5-9	13	0,4
	10-14	19	0,6
	15-19	26	0,8
	20-24	137	4,0
	25-29	81	2,3
	30-34	264	7,7
	35-39	182	5,3
	40-44	1372	39,8
	45-49	121	3,5
	50-54	149	4,3
	55-59	37	1,1
	60-64	68	2,0
	65-69	9	0,3
	70-74	19	0,6
	75-79	5	0,1
	80-84	10	0,3
	85-89	1	0,0
	95-98	1	0,0
	Total	3447	
	99 No answer	55	
	Not cohabiting	1640	
		5142	
X190	PREVIOUSLY COHABITING		Y99
	Have you previously been married or cohabiting for at least 6 months?		
	1 Yes	1883	36,6
	2 No	3259	63,4
		5142	
X191	NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS		Y100

Number of times that respondent previously has been cohabiting for at least 6 months.

0	3312	64,5
1	1313	25,6
2	391	7,6
3	92	1,8
4	23	0,4
5	5	0,1
Total	5136	
9 No answer	6	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,48
Standard deviation		0,76
Mean value for >0		1,36
Standard deviation		0,66

X192

NUMBER OF PREVIOUS MARRIAGES

Number of times that respondent has been married previously.

0	1224	72,5
1	446	26,4
2	17	1,0
3	2	0,1
Total	1689	
9 No answer	16	
Question not asked	3437	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,29
Standard deviation		0,48
Mean value for >0		1,05
Standard deviation		0,23

X193

YEAR/MONTH FOR FIRST COHABITATION

jfr Y101

Year and month when respondent first got married or started cohabiting for at least six months for the first time. If respondent has not previously been married or cohabiting the information refers to the current marriage/cohabitation. Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.

40-49	93	2,1
50-59	528	12,0
60-69	903	20,5
70-79	935	21,3
80-89	953	21,7
90-99	941	21,4
2000	46	1,0
Total	4399	
9999 No answer	2	
Not applicable	741	
	5142	

X194

DURATION FIRST COHABITATION

Y102

Number of years or part of a year that the first marriage or cohabitation lasted. If respondent has not been previously married or cohabiting the information refers to how long (number of years) the current

marriage/cohabitation has lasted. This variable is divided into categories.

1-4	1040	23,7
5-9	902	20,5
10-14	466	10,6
15-19	429	9,8
20-24	417	9,5
25-29	364	8,3
30-34	286	6,5
35-39	238	5,4
40-44	151	3,4
45-49	75	1,7
50-54	20	0,5
55-59	3	0,1
Total	4391	
99 No answer	10	
Not applicable	741	
	5142	
Mean value		15,85
Standard deviation		12,71

X195

CIVIL STATUS FIRST COHABITATION

What was your civil status in the first cohabitation?

1 Married	449	41,7
2 Not married	629	58,3
Total	1078	
3 Question not asked	3044	
9 No answer	11	
Not applicable	1009	
	5142	

X196

YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED

jfr Y103

Year and month when respondent's last marriage or cohabitation lasting for at least six months ended. Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.

50-59	19	1,0
60-69	62	3,4
70-79	248	13,7
80-89	461	25,4
90-99	949	52,3
2000	74	4,1
2001	1	0,1
Total	1814	
9999 No answer	15	
Not applicable	3313	
	5142	

X197

DURATION LAST ENDED COHABITATION

Number of years or part of a year that the last marriage or cohabitation lasted. If respondent has not been previously married or cohabiting the information refers to how long (number of years) the current marriage/cohabitation has lasted.

1-4	625	34,5
-----	-----	------

5-9	475	26,2
10-14	226	12,5
15-19	153	8,4
20-24	112	6,2
25-29	80	4,4
30-34	49	2,7
35-39	36	2,0
40-44	24	1,3
45-49	20	1,1
50-54	11	0,6
Total	1811	
99 No answer	18	
Not applicable	3313	
	5142	
Mean value		11,13
Standard deviation		10,60

X198 REASON FOR SEPARATION LAST COHABITATION Y104

Reason the last cohabitation (lasting for at least six months) ended. Was this because of divorce/separation, death or some other reason?

1 Separation	1567	86,3
2 Death	209	11,5
3 Other	40	2,2
Total	1816	
9 No answer	13	
Not applicable	3313	
	5142	

X199 CIVIL STATUS LAST COHABITATION

What was your civil status in the last ended cohabitation?

1 Married	432	40,1
2 Not married	644	59,9
Total	1076	
3 Question not asked	3044	
9 No answer	13	
Not applicable	1009	
	5142	

X200 NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN WITH MUNICIPAL CHILDCARE jfr Y82

Number of younger children (born 1990-2000) with municipal childcare (municipal day-care, after-school leisure centre, or municipal child minder, incl. three-family system)?

0	413	35,1
1	460	39,1
2	281	23,9
3	21	1,8
4	1	0,1
Total	1176	
No younger children	3966	
	5142	

X201**NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN WITH PRIVATE CHILDCARE**

Number of younger children (born 1990-2000) with private childcare (private child minder, parental cooperative or other private day-care or own nanny/au pair)?

0	1097	93,3
1	57	4,8
2	18	1,5
3	4	0,3
Total	1176	
No younger children	3966	
	5142	

X202**COST OF CHILDCARE PER MONTH****Y83**

Total cost of childcare for younger children (born 1990-2000) in the household (in hundreds of kronor per months).

0	354	31,6
1	3	0,3
2	6	0,5
3	22	2,0
4	17	1,5
5	33	2,9
6	27	2,4
7	26	2,3
8	20	1,8
9	32	2,9
10	35	3,1
11	31	2,8
12	27	2,4
13	27	2,4
14	43	3,8
15	41	3,7
16	34	3,0
17	39	3,5
18	34	3,0
19	17	1,5
20	42	3,8
21	21	1,9
22	16	1,4
23	18	1,6
24	24	2,1
25	17	1,5
26	18	1,6
27	8	0,7
28	16	1,4
29	8	0,7
30	17	1,5
31	6	0,5
32	5	0,4
33	4	0,4

34	6	0,5
35	3	0,3
36	1	0,1
37	4	0,4
39	1	0,1
40	8	0,7
41	1	0,1
43	1	0,1
45	1	0,1
46	2	0,2
47	1	0,1
48	1	0,1
50	1	0,1
53	1	0,1
Total	1120	
99 No answer	56	
No younger children	3966	
	5142	

X203

NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN MANAGING ALONE

Y85

Number of younger children (born 1990-2000) in the household who at times manages alone during some part of the day.

0	1047	89,6
1	105	9,0
2	14	1,2
3	2	0,2
Total	1168	
9 No answer	8	
No younger children	3966	
	5142	

X204

CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSHOLD

**Y89, U124,
jfr V954, jfr
W59**

Do you have or have you had children who are not living with you? (Also adoptive- and stepchildren and deceased children – but not foster children if not counted as own).

1 Yes	2162	42,9
2 No	2873	57,1
Total	5035	
9 No answer	107	
	5142	

X205

NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSHOLD

**Y90, U125,
jfr V954, jfr
W59**

How many of your children are not living with you now?

0	108	4,8
1	600	26,4
2	974	42,9
3	408	18,0
4	134	5,9
5	33	1,5

	6	6	0,3
	7	2	0,1
	8	1	0,0
	9	2	0,1
	11	1	0,0
	Total	2269	
	No children living elsewhere	2873	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		2,01
	Standard deviation		1,08
	Mean value for >0		2,11
	Standard deviation		1,00
X206	NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSHOLD		Y91, U126, jfr V958
	Number of children born 1994 or later not living at home.		
	0	2224	98,0
	1	41	1,8
	2	2	0,1
	3	2	0,1
	Total	2269	
	No children living elsewhere	2873	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,02
	Standard deviation		0,17
	Mean value for >0		1,13
	Standard deviation		0,46
X207	NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSHOLD		Y92, jfr U127, jfr V958
	Number of children born 1982-1993 not living in the household.		
	0	2093	92,2
	1	128	5,6
	2	37	1,6
	3	11	0,5
	Total	2269	
	No children living elsewhere	2873	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,10
	Standard deviation		0,39
	Mean value for >0		1,34
	Standard deviation		0,59
X208	NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSHOLD		Y93, jfr U129, jfr V956, jfr W61
	Number of children born 1974-1981 not living in the household.		
	0	1493	65,8
	1	558	24,6
	2	200	8,8
	3	17	0,7

	4	1	0,0	
	Total	2269		
	No children living elsewhere	2873		
		5142		
	Mean value for all		0,45	
	Standard deviation		0,69	
	Mean value for >0		1,31	
	Standard deviation		0,51	
X209	NUMBER OF DECEASED CHILDREN			jfr Y94, jfr U130, jfr V957, jfr W62
	Number of deceased children born 1974 or later.			
	0	2239	98,7	
	1	29	1,3	
	2	1	0,0	
	Total	2269		
	No children living elsewhere	2873		
		5142		
X210	NUMBER OF CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD WHO LIVES WITH OTHER PARENT			
	Number of children who are living with their other parent.			
	0	2105	92,9	
	1	100	4,4	
	2	44	1,9	
	3	14	0,6	
	4	2	0,1	
	5	1	0,0	
	Total	2266		
	9 No answer	3		
	No children living elsewhere	2873		
		5142		
	Mean value for all		0,11	
	Standard deviation		0,44	
	Mean value for >0		1,51	
	Standard deviation		0,76	
X220	NUMBER OF COMMON (WITH SPOUSE/PARTNER) CHILDREN IN HOUSEHOLD			
	Number of children living in the household who are you and your spouse's/partner's mutual children.			
	0	3442	66,9	
	1	679	13,2	
	2	733	14,3	
	3	221	4,3	
	4	45	0,9	
	5	14	0,3	
	6	4	0,1	
	7	2	0,0	
	8	1	0,0	
	10	1	0,0	

	5142	
Mean value for all		0,61
Standard deviation		1,00
Mean value for >0		1,83
Standard deviation		0,90

X221

PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 1

Number of weeks of parental leave with the first child. This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

0	53	3,3
1-9	32	2,0
10-19	8	0,5
20-29	27	1,7
30-39	60	3,8
40-49	104	6,6
50-59	464	29,3
60-69	182	11,5
70-79	234	14,8
80-89	227	14,3
90-99	27	1,7
100-109	69	4,4
110-119	12	0,8
120-129	4	0,3
130-139	10	0,6
140-149	2	0,1
150-159	20	1,3
160-169	6	0,4
170-179	3	0,2
180-189	2	0,1
200-299	15	0,9
300-399	24	1,5
600-699	1	0,1
Total	1586	
993 Currently on leave	83	
999 No answer	87	
Not applicable	3386	
	5142	
Mean value for all		69,77
Standard deviation		46,04
Mean value for >0		72,18
Standard deviation		44,93

X222

PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 1

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the first child.* This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

0	193	12,0
1-9	485	30,2
10-19	68	4,2
20-29	69	4,3
30-39	75	4,7
40-49	61	3,8

50-59	220	13,7
60-69	92	5,7
70-79	219	13,7
80-89	19	1,2
90-99	9	0,6
100-109	40	2,5
110-119	5	0,3
130-139	7	0,4
140-149	1	0,1
150-159	14	0,9
160-169	1	0,1
170-179	1	0,1
180-189	1	0,1
200-299	7	0,4
300-399	17	1,1
Total	1604	
993 Currently on leave	58	
999 No answer	94	
Not applicable	3386	
	5142	
Mean value for all		38,56
Standard deviation		46,66
Mean value for >0		43,83
Standard deviation		47,37

*For fathers only stating 10 days of parental leave the time has been rounded up to two weeks.

X223

PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 2

Number of weeks of parental leave with the second child. This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

0	30	3,0
1-9	14	1,4
10-19	8	0,8
20-29	9	0,9
30-39	25	2,5
40-49	50	5,1
50-59	277	28,1
60-69	118	12,0
70-79	155	15,7
80-89	155	15,7
90-99	18	1,8
100-109	42	4,3
110-119	12	1,2
120-129	7	0,7
130-139	12	1,2
140-149	4	0,4
150-159	12	1,2
160-169	3	0,3
170-179	1	0,1
180-189	6	0,6
200-299	10	1,0
300-399	16	1,6
400-499	1	0,1
600-699	2	0,2

	Total	987	
993	Currently on leave	26	
999	No answer	65	
	Not applicable	4064	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		74,77
	Standard deviation		53,34
	Mean value for >0		77,11
	Standard deviation		52,47

X224

PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 2

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the second child.* This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

	0	114	11,5
	1-9	290	29,3
	10-19	49	4,9
	20-29	28	2,8
	30-39	45	4,5
	40-49	34	3,4
	50-59	133	13,4
	60-69	60	6,1
	70-79	154	15,5
	80-89	15	1,5
	90-99	3	0,3
	100-109	28	2,8
	110-119	3	0,3
	130-139	7	0,7
	150-159	8	0,8
	160-169	1	0,1
	180-189	2	0,2
	200-299	5	0,5
	300-399	12	1,2
	Total	991	
993	Currently on leave	17	
999	No answer	72	
	Not applicable	4062	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		41,02
	Standard deviation		49,33
	Mean value for >0		46,35
	Standard deviation		50,03

*For fathers only stating 10 days of parental leave the time has been rounded up to two weeks.

X225

PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 3

Number of weeks of parental leave with the third child. This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

	0	10	3,6
	1-9	3	1,1
	10-19	3	1,1
	20-29	3	1,1
	30-39	8	2,9

40-49	14	5,1
50-59	77	28,1
60-69	24	8,8
70-79	46	16,8
80-89	41	15,0
90-99	3	1,1
100-109	12	4,4
110-119	1	0,4
130-139	1	0,4
140-149	1	0,4
150-159	7	2,6
170-179	1	0,4
180-189	1	0,4
190-199	1	0,4
200-299	4	1,5
300-399	9	3,3
600-699	4	1,5
Total	274	
993 Currently on leave	17	
999 No answer	30	
Not applicable	4821	
	5142	
Mean value for all		86,14
Standard deviation		87,63
Mean value for >0		89,41
Standard deviation		87,62

X226

PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 3

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the third child.* This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

0	37	13,3
1-9	76	27,3
10-19	16	5,8
20-29	6	2,2
30-39	10	3,6
40-49	10	3,6
50-59	44	15,8
60-69	13	4,7
70-79	42	15,1
80-89	2	0,7
100-109	6	2,2
120-129	1	0,4
150-159	4	1,4
180-189	1	0,4
200-299	2	0,7
300-399	8	2,9
Total	278	
993 Currently on leave	9	
999 No answer	34	
Not applicable	4821	
	5142	
Mean value for all		45,29

Standard deviation	61,57
Mean value for >0	52,24
Standard deviation	63,32

*For fathers only stating 10 days of parental leave the time has been rounded up to two weeks.

X227

PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 4

Number of weeks of parental leave with the fourth child. This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

0	3	4,8
1-9	1	1,6
10-19	1	1,6
30-39	3	4,8
40-49	3	4,8
50-59	22	34,9
60-69	5	7,9
70-79	7	11,1
80-89	3	4,8
100-109	3	4,8
150-159	2	3,2
200-299	2	3,2
300-399	4	6,3
600-699	4	6,3
Total	63	
993 Currently on leave	3	
999 No answer	12	
Not applicable	5064	
	5142	
Mean value for all		118,24
Standard deviation		153,00
Mean value for >0		124,15
Standard deviation		154,44

X228

PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 4

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the fourth child.* This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

0	12	19,4
1-9	15	24,2
20-29	1	1,6
30-39	3	4,8
40-49	2	3,2
50-59	9	14,5
60-69	3	4,8
70-79	6	9,7
90-99	1	1,6
100-109	2	3,2
150-159	2	3,2
200-299	1	1,6
300-399	5	8,1
Total	62	
993 Currently on leave	3	
999 No answer	13	

Not applicable	5064	
	5142	
Mean value for all		61,63
Standard deviation		88,06
Mean value for >0		76,42
Standard deviation		92,19
*For fathers only stating 10 days of parental leave the time has been rounded up to two weeks.		

X229

PARENTAL LEAVE – CHILD 5

Number of weeks of parental leave with the fifth child. This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

30-39	1	6,3
50-59	7	43,8
70-79	2	12,5
80-89	1	6,3
150-159	1	6,3
300-399	1	6,3
600-699	3	18,8
Total	16	
993 Currently on leave	2	
999 No answer	7	
Not applicable	5117	
	5142	
Mean value		188,25
Standard deviation		227,54

X230

PARENTAL LEAVE RESPONDENT – CHILD 5

Number of weeks the respondent was on parental leave with the fifth child.* This variable is divided into categories. Only respondents with children (biological or adopted) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

1-9	3	18,8
20-29	1	6,3
30-39	1	6,3
40-49	1	6,3
50-59	4	25,0
70-79	1	6,3
150-159	1	6,3
300-399	4	25,0
Total	16	
993 Currently on leave	2	
999 No answer	7	
Not applicable	5117	
	5142	
Mean value		113,88
Standard deviation		124,68

*For fathers only stating 10 days of parental leave the time has been rounded up to two weeks.

X231

ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 1

Does the first child have any kind of illness, problem or disability? Only respondents with children (biological, adopted, spouse's/partner's children or other, e.g. foster children) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

1	No	1509	89,0
2	Yes	187	11,0
	Total	1696	
9	No answer	6	
	Not applicable	3440	
		5142	

X232

ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 2

Does the second child have any kind of illness, problem or disability? Only respondents with children (biological, adopted, spouse's/partner's children or other, e.g. foster children) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

1	No	915	90,1
2	Yes	101	9,9
	Total	1016	
9	No answer	5	
	Not applicable	4121	
		5142	

X233

ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 3

Does the third child have any kind of illness, problem or disability? Only respondents with children (biological, adopted, spouse's/partner's children or other, e.g. foster children) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

1	No	264	93,0
2	Yes	20	7,0
	Total	284	
9	No answer	4	
	Not applicable	4854	
		5142	

X234

ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 4

Does the fourth child have any kind of illness, problem or disability? Only respondents with children (biological, adopted, spouse's/partner's children or other, e.g. foster children) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

1	No	60	89,6
2	Yes	7	10,4
	Total	67	
	Not applicable	5075	
		5142	

X235

ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY CHILD 5

Does the fifth child have any kind of illness, problem or disability? Only respondents with children (biological, adopted, spouse's/partner's children or other, e.g. foster children) born 1982 or later and living at home shall answer the question.

1	No	20	90,9
2	Yes	2	9,1
	Total	22	
	Not applicable	5120	
		5142	

X236	NUMBER OF YOUNGER CHILDREN WITH ILLNESS/PROBLEM/DISABILITY		
	Number of children born 1994 or later with any illness, problem or disability.		
	0	4852	94,4
	1	247	4,8
	2	37	0,7
	3	3	0,1
	4	2	0,0
	7	1	0,0
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,07
	Standard deviation		0,31
	Mean value for >0		1,19
	Standard deviation		0,57

X237	YEAR OF BIRTH – MOTHER		
	In what year was your mother born? This variable is divided into categories.		
	1870-1879	2	0,0
	1880-1889	52	1,0
	1890-1899	220	4,3
	1900-1909	642	12,5
	1910-1919	805	15,7
	1920-1929	889	17,3
	1930-1939	847	16,5
	1940-1949	1030	20,1
	1950-1959	472	9,2
	1960-1969	30	0,6
	8888 Doesn't know	143	2,8
	Total	5132	
	9999 No answer	10	
		5142	

X238	MOTHER - LIVING			jfr Y21, jfr U21, jfr V12, jfr W21
	Is your mother alive?			
	1 Yes	3375	65,8	
	2 No	1751	34,1	
	8 Doesn't know	5	0,1	
	Total	5131		
	9 No answer	11		
		5142		

X239	YEAR OF DEATH – MOTHER		
	If your mother is dead, in what year did she die? This variable is divided into categories.		
	20-29	4	0,2
	30-39	18	1,0
	40-49	38	2,2
	50-59	61	3,5
	60-69	141	8,2

70-79	238	13,8
80-89	470	27,2
90-99	663	38,4
2000	54	3,1
8 Doesn't know	39	2,3
Total	1726	
9 No answer	36	
Mother alive (or doesn't know)	3380	
	5142	

X240

CIVIL STATUS – MOTHER

What is your mother's civil status? Respondent living with his/her mother shall not answer the question.

1 Married/cohabiting with father	1576	50,7
2 Married/cohabiting with new partner	352	11,3
3 Single	1171	37,7
4 Doesn't know	9	0,3
Total	3108	
9 No answer	11	
Not applicable	2023	
	5142	

X241

DISTANCE – MOTHER

How far away does your mother live? This variable is divided into categories and refers to kilometres. Respondent living with his/her mother shall not answer the question.

0	425	15,1
1-9	846	30,1
10-99	957	34,0
100-199	222	7,9
200-299	135	4,8
300-399	77	2,7
400-499	60	2,1
500-599	34	1,2
600-699	21	0,7
700-799	10	0,4
800-899	11	0,4
900-999	9	0,3
1000-1999	6	0,2
Total	2813	
9999 No answer	40	
77777 Other country	266	
Not applicable	2023	
	5142	

X242

RELATIONS MOTHER

How often do you usually see your mother? Respondent living with his/her mother shall not answer the question.

1 Several times a week	695	22,4
2 About once a week	681	21,9
3 1-3 times a month	833	26,8
4 Less often	836	26,9

5	Never	64	2,1
	Total	3109	
9	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	2023	
		5142	

X243

TELEPHONE CONTACT MOTHER

How often do you usually talk to your mother on the telephone? Respondent living with his/her mother shall not answer the question.

1	Several times a week	1446	46,5
2	About once a week	958	30,8
3	1-3 times a month	433	13,9
4	Less often	158	5,1
5	Never	114	3,7
	Total	3109	
9	No answer	10	
	Not applicable	2023	
		5142	

X244

YEAR OF BIRTH – FATHER

In what year was your father born? This variable is divided into categories.

1860-1869		3	0,1
1870-1879		17	0,3
1880-1889		110	2,1
1890-1899		353	6,9
1900-1909		723	14,1
1910-1919		804	15,7
1920-1929		838	16,3
1930-1939		803	15,7
1940-1949		961	18,7
1950-1959		280	5,5
1960-1969		10	0,2
8888	Doesn't know	228	4,4
	Total	5130	
9999	No answer	12	
		5142	

X245

FATHER - LIVING

Is your father alive?

1	Yes	2628	51,2
2	No	2466	48,0
8	Doesn't know	39	0,8
	Total	5133	
9	No answer	9	
		5142	

**jfr Y21, jfr
U21, jfr
V12, jfr
W21**

X246

YEAR OF DEATH – FATHER

If your father is dead, in what year did he die? This variable is divided into categories.

20-29		1	0,0
30-39		17	0,7
40-49		51	2,1
50-59		111	4,5
60-69		269	11,0
70-79		506	20,6
80-89		644	26,2
90-99		726	29,6
2000		48	2,0
2001		1	0,0
8	Doesn't know	80	3,3
	Total	2454	
9	No answer	12	
	Father alive (or doesn't know)	2676	
		5142	

X247

CIVIL STATUS – FATHER

What is your father's civil status? Respondent living with his/her father shall not answer the question.

1	Married/cohabiting with mother	1582	65,2
2	Married/cohabiting with new partner	391	16,1
3	Single	429	17,7
4	Doesn't know	24	1,0
	Total	2426	
9	No answer	7	
	Not applicable	2709	
		5142	

X248

DISTANCE - FATHER

How far away does your father live? This variable is divided into categories and refers to kilometres. Respondent living with his/her father shall not answer the question.

0		321	14,9
1-9		604	28,0
10-99		742	34,4
100-199		171	7,9
200-299		114	5,3
300-399		69	3,2
400-499		56	2,6
500-599		30	1,4
600-699		14	0,6
700-799		11	0,5
800-899		10	0,5
900-999		11	0,5
1000-1999		2	0,1
	Total	2155	
9999	No answer	83	
77777	Other country	195	
	Not applicable	2709	
		5142	

X249**RELATIONS FATHER**

How often do you usually see your father? Respondent living with his/her father shall not answer the question.

1	Several times a week	481	19,9
2	About once a week	483	20,0
3	1-3 times a month	635	26,2
4	Less often	713	29,5
5	Never	108	4,5
	Total	2420	
9	No answer	13	
	Not applicable	2709	
		5142	

X250**TELEPHONE CONTACT FATHER**

How often do you usually talk to your father on the telephone? Respondent living with his/her father shall not answer the question.

1	Several times a week	742	30,7
2	About once a week	808	33,4
3	1-3 times a month	448	18,5
4	Less often	273	11,3
5	Never	148	6,1
	Total	2419	
9	No answer	14	
	Not applicable	2709	
		5142	

X251**NUMBER OF CLOSE FRIENDS**

How many close friends do you have? (Include friends at work, neighbours and relatives, but not family members.) This variable is divided into categories.

0		133	2,6
1-4		1110	21,8
5-9		1362	26,7
10-14		1181	23,2
15-19		371	7,3
20-24		435	8,5
25-29		135	2,6
30-34		159	3,1
35-39		18	0,4
40-44		52	1,0
45-49		11	0,2
50-54		88	1,7
60-64		11	0,2
65-69		1	0,0
70-74		2	0,0
75-79		2	0,0
80-84		3	0,1
85-89		1	0,0
90-94		4	0,1
97	More than 99 friends	17	0,3
	Total	5096	
99	No answer	46	

		5142	
	Mean value for all		11,25
	Standard deviation		11,47
	Mean value for >0		11,55
	Standard deviation		11,47

X252

CLOSE FRIENDS – RELATIVES

How many of your close friends are relatives? This variable is divided into categories.

0		2808	56,8
1-4		1428	28,9
5-9		385	7,8
10-14		190	3,8
15-19		66	1,3
20-24		31	0,6
25-29		16	0,3
30-34		7	0,1
35-39		1	0,0
40-44		4	0,1
45-49		1	0,0
50-54		3	0,1
80-84		1	0,0
97	More than 99 friends	2	0,0
	Total	4943	100
99	No answer	66	
	Doesn't have a close friend	133	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		2,03
	Standard deviation		4,68
	Mean value for >0		4,69
	Standard deviation		6,19

X253

CLOSE FRIENDS – MEN

How many of your close friends are men? This variable is divided into categories.

0		927	18,8
1-4		1882	38,2
5-9		1183	24,0
10-14		518	10,5
15-19		199	4,0
20-24		91	1,8
25-29		55	1,1
30-34		31	0,6
35-39		14	0,3
40-44		9	0,2
45-49		6	0,1
50-54		4	0,1
55-59		2	0,0
60-64		2	0,0
65-69		1	0,0
70-74		2	0,0
75-79		1	0,0
80-84		2	0,0

90-94		1	0,0
97	More than 99 friends	3	0,1
	Total	4933	
99	No answer	76	
	Doesn't have a close friend	133	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		5,48
	Standard deviation		7,22
	Mean value for >0		6,75
	Standard deviation		7,46

X254

CLOSE FRIENDS – BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY

How many of your close friends were not born in Sweden? This variable is divided into categories.

0		3476	70,4
1-4		1159	23,5
5-9		162	3,3
10-14		65	1,3
15-19		28	0,6
20-24		22	0,4
25-29		10	0,2
30-34		3	0,1
40-44		2	0,0
45-49		2	0,0
50-54		3	0,1
60-64		1	0,0
70-74		1	0,0
90-94		1	0,0
97	More than 99 friends	1	0,0
	Total	4936	
99	No answer	73	
	Doesn't have a close friend	133	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		1,10
	Standard deviation		3,96
	Mean value for >0		3,73
	Standard deviation		6,58

X255

CLOSE FRIENDS – FELLOW WORKERS

How many of your close friends are present or former fellow workers? This variable is divided into categories.

0		1983	40,2
1-4		2238	45,3
5-9		476	9,6
10-14		142	2,9
15-19		44	0,9
20-24		28	0,6
25-29		9	0,2
30-34		12	0,2
35-39		1	0,0
50-54		1	0,0
70-74		1	0,0
80-84		1	0,0

	Total	4936	
99	No answer	73	
	Doesn't have a close friend	133	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		2,17
	Standard deviation		3,85
	Mean value for >0		3,63
	Standard deviation		4,41

X256

CLOSE FRIENDS – UNEMPLOYED

How many of your close friends are currently unemployed? This variable is divided into categories.

	0	4058	82,6
	1-4	757	15,4
	5-9	62	1,3
	10-14	19	0,4
	15-19	5	0,1
	20-24	7	0,1
	30-34	2	0,0
	50-54	2	0,0
	70-74	1	0,0
	Total	4913	
99	No answer	96	
	Doesn't have a close friend	133	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,44
	Standard deviation		2,08
	Mean value for >0		2,54
	Standard deviation		4,43

X257

CLOSE FRIENDS – CHILDHOOD FRIENDS

How many of your close friends are your friends since childhood? This variable is divided into categories.

	0	2024	40,9
	1-4	2345	47,4
	5-9	358	7,2
	10-14	137	2,8
	15-19	30	0,6
	20-24	22	0,4
	25-29	7	0,1
	30-34	12	0,2
	40-44	1	0,0
	50-54	5	0,1
	70-74	1	0,0
	90-94	1	0,0
97	More than 99 friends	1	0,0
	Total	4944	
99	No answer	65	
	Doesn't have a close friend	133	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		2,06
	Standard deviation		4,19
	Mean value for >0		3,48

Standard deviation

4,97

X258**CLOSE FRIENDS KNOW EACH OTHER**

How many of your close friends know each other?

1 They all know each other	1219	25,3
2 Most of them know each other	2339	48,5
3 Not many of them know each other	1056	21,9
4 None of them know each other	213	4,4
Total	4827	
9 No answer	66	
Doesn't have, or have one, close friend	249	
	5142	

X259**SEE CLOSE FRIENDS, HOW OFTEN**

How often do you usually see some of these close friends (this friend)?

1 Several times a week	1928	38,7
2 About once a week	1369	27,5
3 1-3 times a month	1247	25,0
4 Less often	430	8,6
5 Never	7	0,1
Total	4981	
9 No answer	28	
Doesn't have a close friend	133	
	5142	

X260**TELEPHONE CONTACT WITH CLOSE FRIENDS – HOW OFTEN**

How often do you usually talk to your close friends on the telephone?

1 Several times a week	1992	40,0
2 About once a week	1589	31,9
3 1-3 times a month	1001	20,1
4 Less often	364	7,3
5 Never	34	0,7
Total	4980	
9 No answer	29	
Doesn't have a close friend	133	
	5142	

X261**YEARS OF EDUCATION RESPONDENT****Y131, U137,
V229, W538**

How many years altogether have you been to school or vocational training full-time? (Include all education from elementary school on.)

0	9	0,2
1	2	0,0
2	1	0,0
3	4	0,1
4	14	0,3
5	19	0,4

6	132	2,6
7	381	7,4
8	272	5,3
9	398	7,8
10	320	6,2
11	671	13,1
12	877	17,1
13	472	9,2
14	381	7,4
15	356	6,9
16	300	5,8
17	237	4,6
18	124	2,4
19	61	1,2
20	49	1,0
21	16	0,3
22	13	0,3
23	8	0,2
24	7	0,1
25	6	0,1
27	3	0,1
28	1	0,0
30	1	0,0
Total	5135	
99 No answer	7	
	5142	

X305

HIGHEST EDUCATION

**Y165, jfr
U138, jfr
V230, jfr
W537**

0 No education	36	0,7
1 Elementary school/	644	12,5
2 Compulsory school	352	6,8
3 Short vocational education	1785	34,7
4 Academic program upper secondary education	597	11,6
5 Post-secondary education	1113	21,6
6 University degree	580	11,3
7 Postgraduate education	34	0,7
Total	5141	
Not applicable	1	
	5142	

X311

NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT

**Y183, U478,
V517, W293**

Approximately how many years altogether have you spent in gainful employment? This variable is divided into categories.

0	98	2,0
1-4	561	11,5
5-9	534	10,9
10-14	556	11,4
15-19	498	10,2
20-24	493	10,1
25-29	535	10,9
30-34	511	10,5

35-39	372	7,6
40-44	382	7,8
45-49	218	4,5
50-54	113	2,3
55-59	16	0,3
60-64	2	0,0
Total	4889	
88 Have never been gainfully employed	210	
99 No answer	17	
999 Worked >6 months, to be controlled	26	
	5142	
Mean value for all		21,90
Standard deviation		14,25

X312

EVER WORKED 6 MONTHS

Have you ever had a job that lasted at least 6 months?

1 Yes	4687	95,1
2 No	217	4,4
99	23	0,5
Total	4927	
9 No answer	5	
Not applicable	210	
	5142	

X313

BEGAN WORKING: YEAR

**Y184, jfr
U144**

What year and month did you begin your first job that lasted at least 6 months? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.

35-39	11	0,2
40-44	159	3,4
45-49	247	5,3
50-54	316	6,7
55-59	336	7,2
60-64	403	8,6
65-69	402	8,6
70-74	471	10,0
75-79	465	9,9
80-84	456	9,7
85-89	523	11,2
90-94	384	8,2
95-99	491	10,5
2000	24	0,5
Total	4688	
9999 No answer	4	
Not applicable	450	
	5142	

X314

STILL AT FIRST JOB

jfr Y185

Do you still have the same position at the same workplace today?

1 Yes	1141	26,5
2 No	3172	73,5

Total	4313
9 No answer	7
Not applicable	822
	5142

X315	TIME IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS	Y186, jfr U478
Total number of months in gainful employment from the first job that lasted at least 6 months, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.		
6-99	1000	22,1
100-199	841	18,6
200-299	805	17,8
300-399	777	17,2
400-499	672	14,9
500-599	376	8,3
600-699	49	1,1
700-799	2	0,0
Total	4522	
995 More than 15 jobs	88	
996 Telephone interview	12	
997 Never worked ≥ 6 months	458	
998 Born before 1925 or after 1965	38	
999 No answer	24	
	5142	
Mean value for all		261,05
Standard deviation		166,50

X316	WHEN LAST GAINFULLY EMPLOYED	Y187
Year when respondent was last gainfully employed, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.		
52-59	5	0,1
60-69	6	0,1
70-79	33	0,7
80-89	132	2,8
90-99	1047	22,4
100 2000	3294	70,4
101 2001	165	3,5
Total	4682	
995 More than 15 jobs	13	
996 Telephone interview	1	
997 Never worked ≥ 6 months	441	
999 No answer	5	
	5142	
Mean value for all		98,35
Standard deviation		4,21

X319	WHEN LAST UNEMPLOYED > 2 MONTHS	jfr Y190, jfr U480
If you have ever been unemployed for more than 2 months, when was the (last time) it happened? This variable is divided into categories.		
50-54	2	0,7
55-59	5	1,6

60-64	3	1,0
65-69	8	2,6
70-74	7	2,3
75-79	12	3,9
80-84	23	7,6
85-89	44	14,5
90-94	39	12,8
95-99	103	33,9
2000	56	18,4
2001	2	0,7
Total	304	
9999 No answer	347	
Not applicable	4491	
	5142	

X322 **YEAR EMPLOYED IN CURRENT JOB** **jfr Y193, jfr U350, jfr V400, jfr W229**

Year when respondent was first employed at his/her current job, according to the occupational biography.

51-59	11	0,4
60-69	157	5,1
70-79	416	13,4
80-89	649	20,9
90-99	1509	48,6
100 2000	366	11,8
Total	3108	
994 Not employed at interview	2001	
999 No answer	33	
	5142	
Mean value for all		89,80
Standard deviation		10,22

X323 **SENIORITY, CURRENT WORKPLACE MONTHS** **Y195**

Number of months that respondent has been employed at the current workplace, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.

0	32	1,1
1-99	1784	59,4
100-199	644	21,5
200-299	291	9,7
300-399	196	6,5
400-499	47	1,6
500-599	7	0,2
Total	3001	
994 Not employed at interview	1662	
995 More than 15 jobs	19	
996 Telephone interview	6	
997 Never worked \geq 6 months	441	
998 Born before 1925 or after 1965	7	
999 No answer	6	
	5142	
Mean value for all		104,64
Standard deviation		109,83

X324

SENIORITY, CURRENT JOB, MONTHS

Y196

Number of months that respondent has had his/her current job, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.

0	42	1,4
1-99	2109	70,0
100-199	522	17,3
200-299	214	7,1
300-399	106	3,5
400-499	18	0,6
500-599	2	0,1
Total	3013	
994 Not employed at interview	1662	
995 More than 15 jobs	15	
996 Telephone interview	5	
997 Never worked ≥ 6 months	441	
998 Born before 1925 or after 1965	3	
999 No answer	3	
	5142	
Mean value for all		78,05
Standard deviation		91,70

X325

NUMBER OF GAINFUL EMPLOYMENTS, TOTAL

Y197

Total number of gainful employments from the first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography.

1	361	7,9
2	596	13,1
3	614	13,5
4	625	13,7
5	557	12,3
6	487	10,7
7	378	8,3
8	262	5,8
9	203	4,5
10	135	3,0
11	98	2,2
12	67	1,5
13	58	1,3
14	41	0,9
15	18	0,4
16	13	0,3
17	9	0,2
18	9	0,2
19	5	0,1
20	3	0,1
21	2	0,0
22	1	0,0
23	2	0,0
24	1	0,0
28	1	0,0
Total	4546	
95 More than 15 jobs	88	
96 Telephone interview	4	
97 Never worked ≥ 6 months	458	

98	Born before 1925 or after 1965	38
99	No answer	8

X326

NUMBERS OF JOBS AS EMPLOYEE

Y198

Total number of jobs as employee from the first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography.

0	47	1,0
1	403	8,9
2	635	14,0
3	619	13,6
4	622	13,7
5	560	12,3
6	470	10,3
7	354	7,8
8	252	5,5
9	177	3,9
10	123	2,7
11	84	1,8
12	60	1,3
13	50	1,1
14	34	0,7
15	17	0,4
16	10	0,2
17	8	0,2
18	6	0,1
19	5	0,1
20	5	0,1
22	2	0,0
23	2	0,0
24	1	0,0
Total	4546	
95	More than 15 jobs	88
96	Telephone interview	4
97	Never worked >=6 months	458
98	Born before 1925 or after 1965	38
99	No answer	8

X329

TIME AWAY FROM GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT, MONTHS

Y202

Total number of months without gainful employment since first job that lasted for at least six months, according to the occupational biography. This variable is divided into categories.

0	929	20,6
1-99	2780	61,5
100-199	568	12,6
200-299	157	3,5
300-399	52	1,2
400-499	22	0,5
500-599	8	0,2
600-699	1	0,0
Total	4517	
995	More than 15 jobs	88
996	Telephone interview	9
997	Never worked >=6 months	458

998	Born before 1925 or after 1965	38	
999	No answer	32	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		56,37
	Standard deviation		75,45

X336	SEI AGE 25		Y209
	Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	468	12,2
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	882	23,0
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	581	15,2
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	231	6,0
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	394	10,3
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	58	1,5
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	339	8,8
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	58	1,5
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	502	13,1
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	153	4,0
	57 Professional, upper-level executive*	4	0,1
	79 Self-employed	120	3,1
	89 Farmer	44	1,1
	Total	3834	
	90 Not started working at 25	459	
	91 Not turned 25 at interview	614	
	97 Never worked ≥ 6 months	192	
	99 No answer	43	
		5142	
	* This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.		

X341	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 25		Y213
	Type of main activity at 25 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	10 Employed	2787	74,1
	20 Self-employed	108	2,9
	30 Farmer	41	1,1
	41 Unemployed	73	1,9
	42 Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	174	4,6
	43 Studying	110	2,9
	44 Military service	78	2,1
	45 Parental leave	317	8,4
	46 Housework	36	1,0
	47 Pensioner	22	0,6
	48 Other	17	0,5
		3763	
	49 Not gainfully employed, type of activity missing	2	
	90 Not started working at 25	459	
	91 Not turned 25 at interview	614	
	95 More than 15 jobs	88	
	96 Telephone interview	2	
	97 Never worked ≥ 6 months	192	

	99 No answer	22	
		5142	
X342	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 25		Y214
	Age when respondent was last gainfully employed, at age 25, according to the occupational biography.		
	14	1	0,0
	16	1	0,0
	17	6	0,2
	18	20	0,5
	19	32	0,9
	20	44	1,2
	21	69	1,8
	22	127	3,4
	23	140	3,7
	24	306	8,1
	25	3016	80,2
		3762	
	90 Not started working at 25	459	
	91 Not turned 25 at interview	614	
	95 More than 15 jobs	88	
	96 Telephone interview	2	
	97 Never worked >=6 months	192	
	99 No answer	25	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		24,50
	Standard deviation		1,26
X347	SEI AGE 30		Y215
	Socio-economic group (SEI) for (the last) gainful employment at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	319	8,8
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	753	20,8
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	464	12,8
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	179	4,9
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	317	8,8
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	51	1,4
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	325	9,0
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	63	1,7
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	560	15,5
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	327	9,0
	57 Professional, upper-level executive*	24	0,7
	79 Self-employed	185	5,1
	89 Farmer	53	1,5
	Total	3620	
	90 Not started working at 30	179	
	91 Not turned 30 at interview	1140	
	97 Never worked >=6 months	135	
	99 No answer	68	
		5142	

* This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.

X352 **TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 30** **Y219**

Type of main activity at 30 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

10 Employed	2629	73,4
20 Self-employed	185	5,2
30 Farmer	53	1,5
41 Unemployed	58	1,6
42 Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	77	2,2
43 Studying	54	1,5
44 Military service	91	2,5
45 Parental leave	372	10,4
46 Housework	36	1,0
47 Pensioner	10	0,3
48 Other	16	0,4
	3581	
90 Not started working at 30	180	
91 Not turned 30 at interview	1140	
95 More than 15 jobs	83	
96 Telephone interview	2	
97 Never worked >=6 months	135	
99 No answer	21	
	5142	

X353 **AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 30** **Y220**

Age when respondent was last gainfully employed, at age 30, according to the occupational biography.

16	1	0,0
17	3	0,1
18	2	0,1
19	16	0,4
20	19	0,5
21	30	0,8
22	32	0,9
23	28	0,8
24	44	1,2
25	45	1,3
26	37	1,0
27	68	1,9
28	91	2,6
29	216	6,1
30	2935	82,3
	3567	
90 Not started working at 30	180	
91 Not turned 30 at interview	1140	
95 More than 15 jobs	83	
96 Telephone interview	2	
97 Never worked >=6 months	135	
99 No answer	35	

		5142	
	Mean value for all		29,33
	Standard deviation		1,95
X358	SEI AGE 35		Y221
	Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	250	7,7
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	604	18,7
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	377	11,7
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	161	5,0
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	266	8,2
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	63	2,0
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	279	8,6
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	75	2,3
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	535	16,6
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	307	9,5
	57 Professional, upper-level executive*	44	1,4
	79 Self-employed	207	6,4
	89 Farmer	59	1,8
	Total	3227	
	90 Not started working at 35	82	
	91 Not turned 35 at interview	1651	
	97 Never worked ≥ 6 months	101	
	99 No answer	81	
		5142	
	* This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.		
X363	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 35		Y225
	Type of main activity at 35 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	10 Employed	2449	76,2
	20 Self-employed	234	7,3
	30 Farmer	61	1,9
	41 Unemployed	45	1,4
	42 Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	53	1,6
	43 Studying	25	0,8
	44 Military service	36	1,1
	45 Parental leave	248	7,7
	46 Housework	35	1,1
	47 Pensioner	13	0,4
	48 Other	16	0,5
		3215	
	49 Not gainfully employed, type of activity missing	1	
	90 Not started working at 35	82	
	91 Not turned 35 at interview	1651	
	95 More than 15 jobs	72	
	96 Telephone interview	2	
	97 Never worked ≥ 6 months	101	
	99 No answer	18	

5142

X364**AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 35****Y226**

Age when respondent was last gainfully employed, at age 35, according to the occupational biography.

17	1	0,0
18	1	0,0
19	5	0,2
20	10	0,3
21	17	0,5
22	15	0,5
23	12	0,4
24	22	0,7
25	18	0,6
26	11	0,3
27	21	0,7
28	21	0,7
29	24	0,7
30	25	0,8
31	28	0,9
32	30	0,9
33	46	1,4
34	121	3,8
35	2778	86,7
	3206	
90 Not started working at 35	82	
91 Not turned 35 at interview	1651	
95 More than 15 jobs	72	
96 Telephone interview	2	
97 Never worked >=6 months	101	
99 No answer	28	
	5142	
Mean value for all		34,26
Standard deviation		2,51

X369**SEI AGE 40****Y227**

Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	177	6,5
12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	543	19,8
21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	273	10,0
22 Skilled manual worker, service production	141	5,1
33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	215	7,8
35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	42	1,5
36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	242	8,8
45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	74	2,7
46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	450	16,4
56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	272	9,9
57 Professional, upper-level executive*	53	1,9
79 Self-employed	205	7,5

89 Farmer	54	2,0
Total	2741	
90 Not started working at 40	48	
91 Not turned 40 at interview	2192	
97 Never worked >=6 months	76	
99 No answer	85	
	5142	

* This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.

X374

TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 40

Y231

Type of main activity at 40 years of age, according to the occupational biography.

10 Employed	2165	78,8
20 Self-employed	245	8,9
30 Farmer	59	2,1
41 Unemployed	32	1,2
42 Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	37	1,3
43 Studying	32	1,2
44 Military service	10	0,4
45 Parental leave	109	4,0
46 Housework	18	0,7
47 Pensioner	21	0,8
48 Other	20	0,7
	2748	
90 Not started working at 40	48	
91 Not turned 40 at interview	2192	
95 More than 15 jobs	65	
96 Telephone interview	2	
97 Never worked >=6 months	76	
99 No answer	11	
	5142	

X375

AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 40

Y232

Age when respondent was last gainfully employed, at age 40, according to the occupational biography.

18	1	0,0
19	3	0,1
20	5	0,2
21	8	0,3
22	5	0,2
23	6	0,2
24	7	0,3
25	5	0,2
27	10	0,4
28	8	0,3
29	9	0,3
30	10	0,4
31	12	0,4
32	7	0,3
33	10	0,4

34	6	0,2
35	8	0,3
36	14	0,5
37	20	0,7
38	19	0,7
39	71	2,6
40	2494	91,1
	2738	
90 Not started working at 40	48	
91 Not turned 40 at interview	2192	
95 More than 15 jobs	65	
96 Telephone interview	2	
97 Never worked >=6 months	76	
99 No answer	21	
	5142	
Mean value for all		39,39
Standard deviation		2,69

X380	SEI AGE 45	Y233
Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	149	6,4
12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	440	19,0
21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	221	9,5
22 Skilled manual worker, service production	112	4,8
33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	172	7,4
35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	46	2,0
36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	212	9,1
45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	66	2,8
46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	364	15,7
56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	253	10,9
57 Professional, upper-level executive*	67	2,9
79 Self-employed	173	7,5
89 Farmer	44	1,9
Total	2319	
90 Not started working at 45	23	
91 Not turned 45 at interview	2641	
97 Never worked >=6 months	69	
99 No answer	90	
	5142	
* This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.		

X385	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 45	Y237
Type of main activity at 45 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
10 Employed	1893	80,6
20 Self-employed	223	9,5
30 Farmer	49	2,1
41 Unemployed	34	1,4
42 Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	19	0,8

43 Studying	16	0,7
44 Military service	2	0,1
45 Parental leave	46	2,0
46 Housework	19	0,8
47 Pensioner	25	1,1
48 Other	24	1,0
	2350	
90 Not started working at 45	23	
91 Not turned 45 at interview	2641	
95 More than 15 jobs	49	
96 Telephone interview	2	
97 Never worked >=6 months	69	
99 No answer	8	
	5142	

X386

AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 45

Y238

Age when respondent was last gainfully employed, at age 45, according to the occupational biography.

18	1	0,0
19	3	0,1
20	1	0,0
21	4	0,2
22	1	0,0
23	3	0,1
24	3	0,1
25	1	0,0
27	2	0,1
28	3	0,1
29	5	0,2
30	4	0,2
31	3	0,1
32	2	0,1
33	4	0,2
34	1	0,0
35	2	0,1
36	2	0,1
37	2	0,1
38	4	0,2
39	8	0,3
40	6	0,3
41	10	0,4
42	14	0,6
43	28	1,2
44	32	1,4
45	2189	93,6
	2338	
90 Not started working at 45	23	
91 Not turned 45 at interview	2641	
95 More than 15 jobs	49	
96 Telephone interview	2	
97 Never worked >=6 months	69	

	99 No answer	20	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		44,54
	Standard deviation		2,60
X391	SEI AGE 50		Y239
	Socio-economic group (SEI) for the last gainful employment at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	121	6,6
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	368	19,9
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	175	9,5
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	93	5,0
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	130	7,0
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	40	2,2
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	164	8,9
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	59	3,2
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	285	15,4
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	207	11,2
	57 Professional, upper-level executive*	61	3,3
	79 Self-employed	108	5,9
	89 Farmer	34	1,8
	Total	1845	
	90 Not started working at 50	7	
	91 Not turned 50 at interview	3132	
	97 Never worked >=6 months	65	
	99 No answer	93	
		5142	
	* This category should be checked if it is used separately. Normally it is merged with category 56.		
X396	TYPE OF ACTIVITY, AGE 50		Y243
	Type of main activity at 50 years of age, according to the occupational biography.		
	10 Employed	1542	81,7
	20 Self-employed	170	9,0
	30 Farmer	40	2,1
	41 Unemployed	25	1,3
	42 Employment training (AMS-utbildning)	11	0,6
	43 Studying	4	0,2
	45 Military service	27	1,4
	46 Parental leave	24	1,3
	47 Housework	34	1,8
	48 Pensioner	11	0,6
		1888	
	90 Not started working at 50	7	
	91 Not turned 50 at interview	3132	
	95 More than 15 jobs	38	
	96 Telephone interview	2	
	97 Never worked >=6 months	65	
	99 No answer	10	
		5142	

X397	AGE AT LAST JOB, AGE 50			Y244
	Age when respondent was last gainfully employed, at age 50, according to the occupational biography.			
	18	1	0,1	
	19	1	0,1	
	21	1	0,1	
	22	1	0,1	
	23	2	0,1	
	25	1	0,1	
	27	1	0,1	
	28	2	0,1	
	29	4	0,2	
	30	3	0,2	
	31	1	0,1	
	32	1	0,1	
	35	1	0,1	
	37	1	0,1	
	38	2	0,1	
	39	4	0,2	
	40	1	0,1	
	41	4	0,2	
	42	2	0,1	
	43	8	0,4	
	44	8	0,4	
	45	8	0,4	
	46	6	0,3	
	47	5	0,3	
	48	18	1,0	
	49	26	1,4	
	50	1770	94,0	
		1883		
	90 Not started working at 50	7		
	91 Not turned 50 at interview	3132		
	95 More than 15 jobs	38		
	96 Telephone interview	2		
	97 Never worked >=6 months	65		
	99 No answer	15		
		5142		
	Mean value for all		49,55	
	Standard deviation		2,66	
X402	SEI FIRST JOB			Y245
	Socio-economic group (SEI) for respondent's first job that lasted at least six months, according to the occupational biography.			
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	526	10,2	
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	933	18,2	
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	404	7,9	
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	157	3,1	
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	349	6,8	
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	13	0,3	

36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	198	3,9
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	36	0,7
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	312	6,1
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	141	2,7
57	Professional, upper-level executive*	7	0,1
60	Self-employed professional	7	0,1
71	Self-employed without employees	20	0,4
72	Self-employed, 1-9 employees	9	0,2
73	Self-employed, 10-19 employees	2	0,0
74	Self-employed 20+ employees	1	0,0
79	Self-employed, unknown number of employees	6	0,1
87	Farmer, 21-100 hectares arable land	4	0,1
89	Farmer, size of farm unknown	2	0,0
97	Never worked >=6 months	444	8,6
98	Born before 1925 or after 1965	1567	30,5
	Total	5138	
99	No answer	4	
		5142	

X403

NYK80 FIRST JOB

Y246

Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's first job lasting at least six months, according to the occupational biography. See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.

X404

NYK85 FIRST JOB

Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's first job lasting at least six months, according to the occupational biography. A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.

X405

EGP FIRST JOB

Y247

Class (EGP) for respondent's first job that lasted at least six months, according to the occupational biography.

1 Ia	Self-employed, higher grade professionals	7	0,2
2 Ib	Higher-grade professionals	149	4,8
3 II	Lower-grade professionals	327	10,5
4 IIIa	Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	333	10,6
5 IIIb	Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	773	24,7
6 IVa	Small proprietors with employees	17	0,5
7 IVb	Small proprietors without employees	20	0,6
8 IVc	Farmers	4	0,1
9 IVd	Smallholders	2	0,1
10 Vs	Supervisors	36	1,2
11 Vj	Supervisors in primary production	2	0,1
12 VIs	Skilled manual workers	401	12,8
13 VIj	Skilled manual workers in primary production	9	0,3
14 VIIs	Unskilled manual workers	958	30,6
15 VIIj	Unskilled manual workers in primary production	89	2,8
	Total	3127	
97	Never worked >=6 months	444	
98	Born before 1925 or after 1965	1567	
99	Unclassified	4	
		5142	

X412

SEI CURRENT JOB

Y251

Socio-economic group (SEI) for respondent's current job.

11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	202	5,7
12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	562	15,9
21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	362	10,3
22 Skilled manual worker, service production	219	6,2
33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	166	4,7
35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	59	1,7
36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	287	8,1
45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	53	1,5
46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	685	19,4
56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	457	12,9
57 Professional, upper-level executive*	89	2,5
79 Self-employed	348	9,9
89 Farmer	41	1,2
Total	3530	
99 No answer	10	
93 Not gainfully employed at interview	1602	
	5142	

X413

NYK80 CURRENT JOB

Y252

Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's current job.

0 Scientific and artistic work	0	0,0
1 Architect	38	1,1
2 Electro engineer	82	2,3
3 Mechanical engineer	62	1,8
4 Chemical engineer	14	0,4
5 Mining engineer	3	0,1
6 Other engineering work	34	1,0
7 Cartographer	5	0,1
8 Survey assistant	1	0,0
9 Not specified technical work	60	1,7
11 Chemist	11	0,3
13 Geologist	1	0,0
14 Laboratory assistant	11	0,3
21 Veterinarian	1	0,0
22 Biologist	5	0,1
23 Research and consulting in agriculture	6	0,2
24 Research and consulting in forestry	1	0,0
31 Physician	23	0,7
32 Dentist	5	0,1
40 Nurse	72	2,0
41 Midwife	7	0,2
42 Psychiatric nurse	18	0,5
43 Assistant nurse	169	4,8
44 Dental nurse	17	0,5
46 Pharmacist	6	0,2
47 Physiotherapist	32	0,9
48 Other health care occupations	8	0,2
50 Headmaster	11	0,3
51 University headmaster	35	1,0

52	Theory teacher	47	1,3
53	Class teacher	45	1,3
54	Teacher of music, arts or crafts	26	0,7
55	Vocational studies teacher	8	0,2
56	Pre-primary teacher	50	1,4
57	Educational consulting	9	0,3
58	Other occupations in education	27	0,8
61	Priest	7	0,2
68	Other religious work	3	0,1
72	Prosecutor	3	0,1
73	Practicing lawyers	3	0,1
74	Corporation lawyer	4	0,1
78	Other juridical occupation	0	0,0
81	Sculptor, painter	25	0,7
82	Industrial designer	12	0,3
83	Display decorator	3	0,1
84	Author	1	0,0
85	Journalist	15	0,4
86	Performing artist	8	0,2
87	Musician	6	0,2
88	Other artistic occupation	4	0,1
91	Auditor	10	0,3
92	Social worker	52	1,5
93	Librarian	10	0,3
94	Economist	62	1,8
95	Psychologist	5	0,1
96	Personnel service	35	1,0
97	Programmer	73	2,1
98	Other sci. and hum. occupation	7	0,2
101	Official in public administration	48	1,4
111	General business manager	41	1,2
118	Other business manager	129	3,7
201	Bookkeeper	43	1,2
203	Bank cashier	2	0,1
204	Cashier in shop or restaurant	23	0,7
208	Debt collector	3	0,1
290	Secretary	153	4,3
291	Computer operator	4	0,1
292	Bank clerk	21	0,6
293	Travel agency clerk	12	0,3
294	Shipping agent	6	0,2
295	Property manager	24	0,7
296	Insurance clerk	5	0,1
297	Social insurance clerk	6	0,2
298	Cost accountant	2	0,1
301	Wholesaler	18	0,5
302	Retailer	32	0,9
309	Not specified commercial occupation	1	0,0
311	Insurance salesman	6	0,2
312	Real estate agent	5	0,1
313	Marketing promoter	41	1,2
331	Commercial traveller	128	3,6
332	Shop manager	11	0,3
333	Shop assistant	79	2,2

338	Gasoline salesman	3	0,1
401	Farmers, silvic-, horticulturist	41	1,2
402	Farm supervisor	3	0,1
403	Forestry supervisor	2	0,1
404	Horticultural supervisor	0	0,0
405	Pet breeder	1	0,0
407	Reindeer owner	0	0,0
409	Not specified agricultural work	1	0,0
411	Farm worker	2	0,1
412	Garden worker	12	0,3
418	Other agricultural work	4	0,1
421	Hunter	0	0,0
431	Fisherman	3	0,1
432	Fish breeder	1	0,0
441	Woodman	9	0,3
501	Miner	0	0,0
502	Well-, diamond driller	0	0,0
503	Mineral processing work	0	0,0
504	Other mining work	18	0,5
509	Not specified mining work	1	0,0
601	Ship's master	3	0,1
602	Maritime pilot	0	0,0
603	Engine officer	1	0,0
611	Deck crew	4	0,1
621	Airline pilot	1	0,0
631	Railway engine driver	2	0,1
632	Railway and station personnel	6	0,2
633	Motor vehicle driver	108	3,1
635	Messenger, delivery boy	4	0,1
636	Road traffic assistant	2	0,1
639	Not specified transport occupation	0	0,0
641	Harbour master	0	0,0
642	Air traffic controller	4	0,1
643	Traffic supervisor	3	0,1
644	Road transport supervisor	8	0,2
651	Post-office clerk	8	0,2
653	Telephone operator	17	0,5
655	Telecommunication operator	1	0,0
661	Postman	19	0,5
662	Office messenger	17	0,5
671	Lighthouse-keeper	0	0,0
678	Railway assistant	2	0,1
701	Textile work	11	0,3
711	Tailor	6	0,2
712	Fur-dealer	0	0,0
713	Hat making	0	0,0
714	Upholsterer	1	0,0
715	Cutter	1	0,0
718	Other sewing work	0	0,0
719	Not specified manufacturing work	0	0,0
731	Smelter man	6	0,2
732	Hardener	1	0,0
733	Roller	0	0,0
735	Smith	2	0,1

736	Foundry man	4	0,1
737	Wire maker	2	0,1
741	Precision-tool maker	8	0,2
742	Watchmaker	1	0,0
743	Optician	3	0,1
744	Dental technician	2	0,1
745	Gold-, silversmith	3	0,1
750	Mechanic	75	2,1
751	Machine fitter	80	2,3
753	Plater	28	0,8
754	Plumber	19	0,5
755	Welder	10	0,3
757	Metalizer	1	0,0
761	Electrician	49	1,4
764	Telephone fitter	28	0,8
765	Recording technician	2	0,1
766	Telephone repairman	4	0,1
769	Glazier	0	0,0
771	Wood builder	35	1,0
772	Carpenter	39	1,1
773	Layered wood panel worker	2	0,1
774	Sawyer	7	0,2
778	Other woodwork	1	0,0
781	Painter	12	0,3
791	Bricklayer	11	0,3
793	Concrete worker	19	0,5
794	Insulation worker	1	0,0
795	Glazier	0	0,0
797	Pipe fitter	3	0,1
801	Typographer	12	0,3
806	Bookbinder	4	0,1
808	Other graphic work	0	0,0
811	Glassworks worker	0	0,0
812	Moulder	0	0,0
813	Furnace worker (glass, ceramics)	1	0,0
814	Decorator	0	0,0
819	Not specified moulding work	0	0,0
821	Mill worker	2	0,1
822	Baker	15	0,4
824	Brewery worker	1	0,0
825	Canned goods worker	0	0,0
826	Slaughterhouse worker	9	0,3
827	Dairy worker	1	0,0
828	Other food and beverage work	4	0,1
831	Chemical processing work	3	0,1
834	Paper pulp worker	1	0,0
836	Paper worker	7	0,2
838	Other chem. tech. work	6	0,2
839	Not specified chem. work	3	0,1
841	Tobacco worker	0	0,0
850	Basket-maker	0	0,0
851	Rubber worker	5	0,1
852	Plastic worker	3	0,1
853	Tanner	0	0,0

854	Photo lab worker	2	0,1
856	Stonemason	2	0,1
857	Paper products worker	2	0,1
858	Other manufacturing work	8	0,2
861	Unskilled labourer	6	0,2
871	Engine operator	5	0,1
872	Crane operator	1	0,0
874	Machine operator	4	0,1
875	Truck operator	9	0,3
876	Greaser	0	0,0
881	Packer	13	0,4
882	Stevedore	2	0,1
883	Store man	36	1,0
888	Mover	1	0,0
901	Fireman	2	0,1
902	Policeman	16	0,5
903	Customs officer	0	0,0
904	Prison guard	4	0,1
908	Other guards (civil duties)	13	0,4
911	Catering supervisor	21	0,6
912	Cook	33	0,9
913	Kitchen assistant	33	0,9
914	Child minder	36	1,0
915	Domestic help	85	2,4
916	Hotel receptionist	2	0,1
917	Purser	8	0,2
918	Other housekeeping work	4	0,1
921	Head waiter	27	0,8
931	Building caretaker	30	0,9
932	Cleaner	71	2,0
933	Chimney-sweeper	0	0,0
941	Hairdresser	17	0,5
942	Bath attendant	1	0,0
943	Laundry worker	2	0,1
944	Pressing worker	0	0,0
945	Coach	7	0,2
946	Photographer	7	0,2
947	Burial service worker	0	0,0
948	Other service work	4	0,1
981	Military work	7	0,2
	Total	3527	
999	No answer	13	
993	Not gainfully employed at interview	1602	
		5142	

X414

NYK85 CURRENT JOB

Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for respondent's current job. A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.

99999	No answer	13
99993	Not gainfully employed at interview	1602

X415	EGP CURRENT JOB			Y253
	Class (EGP) for respondent's current job.			
	1 Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	13	0,4	
	2 Ib Higher-grade professionals	579	16,4	
	3 II Lower-grade professionals	703	19,9	
	4 IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	505	14,3	
	5 IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	322	9,1	
	6 IVa Small proprietors with employees	151	4,3	
	7 IVb Small proprietors without employees	158	4,5	
	8 IVc Farmers	21	0,6	
	9 IVd Smallholders	8	0,2	
	10 Vs Supervisors	82	2,3	
	11 Vj Supervisors in primary production	5	0,1	
	12 VIs Skilled manual workers	354	10,0	
	13 VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	5	0,1	
	14 VIIs Unskilled manual workers	610	17,3	
	15 VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	11	0,3	
	Total	3527		
	99 No answer	13		
	93 Not gainfully employed at interview	1602		
		5142		
X416	SNI CURRENT JOB			Y254, jfr U349, jfr V399, jfr W228
	Industry for respondent's current workplace, according to Swedish Standard of Industrial Classification (SNI). A list of codes was published by SCB:s Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor 1977:9, Svensk standard för näringsgrensindelning (Reports on Statistical Coordination 1977:9, Swedish Standard of Industrial Classification), second edition of standard for 1969.			
	991 Self-employed	348		
	992 Farmer	41		
	993 Not gainfully employed at interview	1602		
	999 No answer	195		
X417	WORKPLACE SIZE, CURRENT JOB			jfr Y255
	Number of employees at respondent's current workplace. The table is valid for employees.			
	1 Only respondent (works alone)	51	1,7	
	2 2-9 employees	533	17,3	
	3 10-19	419	13,6	
	4 20 -49	607	19,7	
	5 50-99	391	12,7	
	6 100-499	563	18,2	
	7 500-999	187	6,1	
	8 1000 or more employees	338	10,9	
	Total	3089		
	99 No answer	62		
	91 Self-employed	348		
	92 Farmer	41		
	93 Not gainfully employed at interview	1602		
		5142		

X418	SECTOR, CURRENT JOB			Y256
	Sector (private/public) for respondent's current job. The table is valid for employees.			
	1 Public	1264	40,6	
	2 Private	1850	59,4	
	Total	3114		
	99 No answer	37		
	91 Self-employed	348		
	92 Farmer	41		
	93 Not gainfully employed at interview	1602		
		5142		
X419	PERMANENTLY EMPLOYED, CURRENT JOB			
	Form of employment at current job. The table is valid for employees.			
	1 Permanently employed	2388	76,7	
	2 Time-limited employment contract	461	14,8	
	3 First time-limited, then permanent employment	264	8,5	
	Total	3113		
	91 Self-employed	348		
	92 Farmer	41		
	93 Not gainfully employed at interview	1602		
	99 No answer	38		
		5142		
X420	REGULAR EMPLOYMENT			
	Regular time-limited employment contract, or employment measure (AMS-åtgärd). The table is valid for persons with a time-limited employment contract.			
	1 Regular time-limited employment	675	95,9	
	2 Employment measure	29	4,1	
	Total			
	90 Permanent employees	2388		
	91 Self-employed	348		
	92 Farmer	41		
	93 Not gainfully employed at interview	1602		
	99 No answer	59		
X435	GENERAL HEALTH			
	How do you judge your general state of health? Is it...			
	1 Good	3766	73,4	
	2 Bad	278	5,4	
	3 Something in-between	1090	21,2	
	Total	5134		
	9 No answer	8		
		5142		

X436	WALK 100 M		Y258, U160, V235, W101
	Can you walk 100 meters relatively quickly without trouble?		
	1 Yes	4749	92,5
	2 No	386	7,5
	Total	5135	
	9 No answer	7	
		5142	
X437	RUN 100 M		Y259, U161, V236, W102
	Can you run 100 meters without much trouble?		
	1 Yes	4142	80,7
	2 No	990	19,3
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X438	WALK STAIRS		Y260, U162, V237, W103
	Can you walk up and down stairs without trouble?		
	1 Yes	4613	89,9
	2 No	521	10,1
	Total	5134	
	9 No answer	8	
		5142	
X439	TURN TAP		Y261
	Can you turn the tap off and on without trouble?		
	1 Yes	4939	96,3
	2 No	190	3,7
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X440	LENGTH IN CM		Y262
	How tall are you?		
	140	1	0,0
	143	1	0,0
	144	1	0,0
	145	1	0,0
	147	2	0,0
	148	2	0,0
	149	2	0,0
	150	19	0,4
	151	2	0,0
	152	16	0,3
	153	14	0,3

154	26	0,5
155	33	0,6
156	52	1,0
157	42	0,8
158	100	2,0
159	55	1,1
160	189	3,7
161	82	1,6
162	167	3,3
163	173	3,4
164	156	3,0
165	209	4,1
166	104	2,0
167	238	4,6
168	248	4,8
169	118	2,3
170	275	5,4
171	85	1,7
172	196	3,8
173	168	3,3
174	169	3,3
175	195	3,8
176	208	4,1
177	93	1,8
178	234	4,6
179	103	2,0
180	282	5,5
181	92	1,8
182	177	3,5
183	144	2,8
184	93	1,8
185	103	2,0
186	96	1,9
187	81	1,6
188	49	1,0
189	49	1,0
190	59	1,2
191	18	0,4
192	19	0,4
193	30	0,6
194	9	0,2
195	12	0,2
196	9	0,2
197	8	0,2
198	3	0,1
199	5	0,1
200	3	0,1
201	2	0,0
204	1	0,0
210	1	0,0
Total	5124	

999 No answer	18	
	5142	
Mean value		172,49
Standard deviation		9,45

X441	WEIGHT IN KG		Y263
	What is your weight?		
	37	1	0,0
	40	4	0,1
	41	1	0,0
	42	1	0,0
	43	1	0,0
	44	1	0,0
	45	9	0,2
	46	3	0,1
	47	8	0,2
	48	15	0,3
	49	16	0,3
	50	50	1,0
	51	14	0,3
	52	49	1,0
	53	55	1,1
	54	48	0,9
	55	98	1,9
	56	58	1,1
	57	75	1,5
	58	96	1,9
	59	60	1,2
	60	217	4,3
	61	64	1,3
	62	116	2,3
	63	123	2,4
	64	96	1,9
	65	228	4,5
	66	65	1,3
	67	124	2,4
	68	153	3,0
	69	72	1,4
	70	256	5,1
	71	55	1,1
	72	163	3,2
	73	114	2,3
	74	111	2,2
	75	260	5,1
	76	91	1,8
	77	90	1,8
	78	150	3,0
	79	85	1,7
	80	285	5,6
	81	44	0,9

82	124	2,4
83	98	1,9
84	74	1,5
85	179	3,5
86	59	1,2
87	64	1,3
88	58	1,1
89	46	0,9
90	155	3,1
91	16	0,3
92	53	1,0
93	48	0,9
94	36	0,7
95	70	1,4
96	23	0,5
97	33	0,7
98	33	0,7
99	6	0,1
100	96	1,9
101	5	0,1
102	14	0,3
103	12	0,2
104	14	0,3
105	25	0,5
106	7	0,1
107	4	0,1
108	6	0,1
109	4	0,1
110	30	0,6
111	1	0,0
112	4	0,1
113	2	0,0
114	1	0,0
115	8	0,2
116	1	0,0
118	4	0,1
119	1	0,0
120	9	0,2
121	1	0,0
122	2	0,0
125	2	0,0
127	1	0,0
128	1	0,0
129	1	0,0
130	2	0,0
132	2	0,0
135	2	0,0
140	1	0,0
142	1	0,0
143	1	0,0
Total	5065	

	999 No answer	77		
		5142		
	Mean value		74,42	
	Standard deviation		13,89	
X442	DIGITALIS OR OTHER CARDIOVASCULAR MEDICATIONS			jfr Y271/Y272, jfr U174/U175, jfr V941/V942, jfr W977/W978
	Have you used digitalis or other cardiovascular medications in the last 14 days?			
	1 Yes	274	5,3	
	2 No	4860	94,7	
	Total	5134		
	9 No answer	8		
		5142		
X443	MEDICINE TO REDUCE BLOOD PRESSURE			Y274
	Have you used medicine to reduce blood pressure in the last 14 days?			
	1 Yes	520	10,1	
	2 No	4615	89,9	
	Total	5135		
	9 No answer	7		
		5142		
X444	LOSEC OR OTHER GASTRIC ULCER MEDICATIONS			
	Have you used Losec or other gastric ulcer medications in the last 14 days?			
	1 Yes	277	5,4	
	2 No	4856	94,6	
	Total	5133		
	9 No answer	9		
		5142		
X445	TRANQUILIZERS			jfr Y268, jfr U171, jfr V246, jfr W112
	Have you used tranquilizers such as Stesolid, Sobril, Temesta, Xanor or the like in the last 14 days?			
	1 Yes	170	3,3	
	2 No	4964	96,7	
	Total	5134		
	9 No answer	8		
		5142		
X446	ANTIDEPRESSANTS			
	Have you used anti-depressive agents such as Cipramil, Fontex or the like in the last 14 days?			
	1 Yes	171	3,3	
	2 No	4960	96,7	
	Total	5131		
	9 No answer	11		
		5142		

X447	SLEEPING PILLS	Y269, U172, V247, W113
	Have you used sleeping pills in the last 14 days?	
	1 Yes	210 4,1
	2 No	4924 95,9
	Total	5134
	9 No answer	8
		5142
X448	MEDICINE FOR DIABETES	Y270, U173, V945, W981
	Have you used medicine for diabetes in the last 14 days?	
	1 Yes	144 2,8
	2 No	4974 97,2
	Total	5118
	9 No answer	24
		5142
X449	HORMONE REPLACEMENT THERAPY	
	<i>To women over 50 years:</i> Have you used hormone replacement preparation (hormone treatment) in the last 14 days?	
	1 Yes	292 29,5
	2 No	698 70,5
	Total	990
	9 No answer	48
	Not applicable	4104
		5142
X450	CONTRACEPTIVE PILLS	Y275, U176, V248, W114
	<i>To women under 60 years:</i> Have you used contraceptive pills in the last 14 days?	
	1 Yes	333 17,6
	2 No	1556 82,4
	Total	1889
	9 No answer	158
	Not applicable	3095
		5142
X451	USED OTHER MEDICINES	Jfr Y276, jfr U177, jfr V249, jfr W115
	Have you used other medicines in the last 14 days?	
	1 Yes	1467 29,0
	2 No	3585 71,0
	Total	5052
	9 No answer	90
		5142
X452	HEADACHE	Y277, U190,

	Have you in the last 12 months had headaches, migraine?		V257, W120
	1 No	2447	47,7
	2 Yes, mild	2051	40,0
	3 Yes, severe	629	12,3
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X453	COLD		Y278, U191, V258, W121
	Have you in the last 12 months had colds or influenza?		
	1 No	1742	33,9
	2 Yes, mild	2568	50,0
	3 Yes, severe	824	16,0
	Total	5134	
	9 No answer	8	
		5142	
X454	POOR VISION		Y279, U192, V259, W122
	Have you in the last 12 months had poor vision/disease of the eyes that were not helped by eyeglasses?		
	1 No	4754	92,9
	2 Yes, mild	235	4,6
	3 Yes, severe	128	2,5
	Total	5117	
	9 No answer	25	
		5142	
X455	IMPAIRED HEARING		Y280, U193, V260, W123
	Have you in the last 12 months had impaired hearing?		
	1 No	4375	85,3
	2 Yes, mild	572	11,2
	3 Yes, severe	181	3,5
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	
X456	CHEST PAIN		Y281, U194, V261, W124
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches or pain in the chest?		
	1 No	4716	91,9
	2 Yes, mild	301	5,9
	3 Yes, severe	113	2,2
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	

X457	BRONCHITIS		Y282, U195, V262, W125
	Have you in the last 12 months had chronic bronchitis (asthma)?		
	1 No	4830	94,2
	2 Yes, mild	219	4,3
	3 Yes, severe	81	1,6
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X458	GOITRE		Y283, U196, V263, W126
	Have you in the last 12 months had enlargement of the thyroid (goitre)?		
	1 No	5008	97,6
	2 Yes, mild	92	1,8
	3 Yes, severe	29	0,6
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X459	TUBERCULOSIS		Y284, U197, V264, W127
	Have you in the last 12 months had tuberculosis (all forms)?		
	1 No	5116	99,8
	2 Yes, mild	7	0,1
	3 Yes, severe	4	0,1
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X460	ACHES IN SHOULDERS/SHOULDER BLADES		Y285, U198, V265, W128
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches in shoulders or shoulder blades?		
	1 No	3316	64,7
	2 Yes, mild	1163	22,7
	3 Yes, severe	649	12,7
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	
X461	HEART ATTACK		Y286, U199, V266, W129
	Have you in the last 12 months had coronary thrombosis, heart attack?		
	1 No	5079	99,0
	2 Yes, mild	29	0,6
	3 Yes, severe	22	0,4
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	

X462	STROKE		
	Have you in the last 12 months had cerebral thrombosis, stroke?		
	1 No	5083	99,1
	2 Yes, mild	26	0,5
	3 Yes, severe	18	0,4
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X463	CARDIAC WEAKNESS		Y287, U200, V267, W130
	Have you in the last 12 months had a weak heart?		
	1 No	4996	97,4
	2 Yes, mild	98	1,9
	3 Yes, severe	35	0,7
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X464	HIGH BLOOD PRESSURE		Y288, U201, V268, W131
	Have you in the last 12 months had high blood pressure?		
	1 No	4610	89,9
	2 Yes, mild	405	7,9
	3 Yes, severe	114	2,2
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X465	STOMACH PAINS		Y289, U202, V269, W132
	Have you in the last 12 months had stomach pains?		
	1 No	3927	76,5
	2 Yes, mild	854	16,6
	3 Yes, severe	352	6,9
	Total	5133	
	9 No answer	9	
		5142	
X466	GASTRIC ULCER		Y290, U203, V270, W133
	Have you in the last 12 months had a gastric ulcer?		
	1 No	4983	97,2
	2 Yes, mild	80	1,6
	3 Yes, severe	63	1,2
	Total	5126	
	9 No answer	16	
		5142	

X467	PAIN IN BACK/HIPS	Y291, U204, V271, W134	
Have you in the last 12 months had backache, pain in back or hips or sciatica?			
1	No	3133	61,1
2	Yes, mild	1232	24,0
3	Yes, severe	766	14,9
Total		5131	
9	No answer	11	
		5142	
X468	BILIARY TROUBLE	Y292, U205, V272, W135	
Have you in the last 12 months had biliary/gall trouble or gall stones?			
1	No	5005	97,6
2	Yes, mild	77	1,5
3	Yes, severe	46	0,9
Total		5128	
9	No answer	14	
		5142	
X469	KIDNEY TROUBLE	Y293, U206, V273, W136	
Have you in the last 12 months had kidney trouble or kidney stones?			
1	No	5032	98,1
2	Yes, mild	48	0,9
3	Yes, severe	51	1,0
Total		5131	
9	No answer	11	
		5142	
X470	HAEMORRHOIDS	Y294, U207, V274, W137	
Have you in the last 12 months had haemorrhoids or anal discomfort?			
1	No	4857	94,7
2	Yes, mild	210	4,1
3	Yes, severe	61	1,2
Total		5128	
9	No answer	14	
		5142	
X471	TROUBLE WITH URINATION	Y295, U208, V275, W138	
Have you in the last 12 months had cystitis, trouble with urination? <i>For men:</i> prostate trouble?			
1	No	4864	94,9
2	Yes, mild	191	3,7
3	Yes, severe	71	1,4
Total		5126	
9	No answer	16	
		5142	

X472	MENSTRUATION TROUBLE	Y296, jfr U209, jfr V276, jfr W139
	<i>To women born in 1940 or later:</i> Have you in the last 12 months had menstruation trouble?	
	1 No	1644 80,5
	2 Yes, mild	251 12,3
	3 Yes, severe	146 7,2
	Total	2041
	9 No answer	69
	Not applicable	3032
		5142
X473	PREGNANCY COMPLICATIONS	Y297, jfr U210, jfr V278, jfr W141
	<i>To women born in 1940 or later:</i> Have you in the last 12 months had pregnancy complications?	
	1 No	1956 96,7
	2 Yes, mild	23 1,1
	3 Yes, severe	43 2,1
	Total	2022
	9 No answer	88
	Not applicable	3032
		5142
X474	VAGINAL TROUBLE	Y298, U211, V277, W140
	<i>To all women:</i> Have you in the last 12 months had other vaginal trouble (discharges, pains, prolaps of uterus, etc.)?	
	1 No	2320 93,0
	2 Yes, mild	119 4,8
	3 Yes, severe	56 2,2
	Total	2495
	9 No answer	45
	Not applicable	2602
		5142
X475	INGUINAL HERNIA	Y299, U212, V279, W142
	Have you in the last 12 months had inguinal hernia?	
	1 No	5054 98,7
	2 Yes, mild	44 0,9
	2 Yes, severe	25 0,5
	Total	5123
	9 No answer	19
		5142
X476	VARICOSE VEINS	Y300, U213, V280, W143
	Have you in the last 12 months had varicose veins, varicose ulcers?	
	1 No	4845 94,5
	2 Yes, mild	220 4,3
	3 Yes, severe	62 1,2

	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X477	SWOLLEN LEGS		Y301, U214, V281, W144
	Have you in the last 12 months had swollen legs?		
	1 No	4721	92,0
	2 Yes, mild	321	6,3
	3 Yes, severe	87	1,7
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X478	ACHES IN JOINTS		Y302, U215, V282, W145
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches or pain in hands, elbows, legs or knees?		
	1 No	3651	71,2
	2 Yes, mild	933	18,2
	3 Yes, severe	545	10,6
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X479	GENERAL TIREDNESS		Y303, U216, V283, W146
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from general tiredness?		
	1 No	3516	68,6
	2 Yes, mild	1234	24,1
	3 Yes, severe	372	7,3
	Total	5122	
	9 No answer	20	
		5142	
X480	INSOMNIA		Y304, U217, V284, W147
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from insomnia?		
	1 No	4152	81,0
	2 Yes, mild	699	13,6
	3 Yes, severe	278	5,4
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X481	NERVOUS TROUBLE		Y305, U218, V285, W148
	Have you in the last 12 months had nervous trouble (anxiety, uneasiness, anguish)?		
	1 No	4433	86,4
	2 Yes, mild	480	9,4
	3 Yes, severe	216	4,2

	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X482	DEPRESSIONS		Y306, U219, V286, W149
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from depressions or deep dejection?		
	1 No	4658	90,8
	2 Yes, mild	300	5,8
	3 Yes, severe	174	3,4
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X483	MENTAL ILLNESS		Y307, U220, V287, W150
	Have you in the last 12 months had a mental illness?		
	1 No	5054	98,5
	2 Yes, mild	35	0,7
	3 Yes, severe	41	0,8
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X484	SWEATING		Y308, U221, V288, W151
	Have you in the last 12 months had flushing (hot flashes) or copious sweating?		
	1 No	4787	93,4
	2 Yes, mild	269	5,2
	3 Yes, severe	71	1,4
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X485	COUGH		Y309, U222, V289, W152
	Have you in the last 12 months had a cough?		
	1 No	4024	78,4
	2 Yes, mild	904	17,6
	3 Yes, severe	204	4,0
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X486	DIFFICULTY IN BREATHING		Y310, U223, V290, W153
	Have you in the last 12 months had difficulty in breathing or breathlessness?		
	1 No	4738	92,3
	2 Yes, mild	279	5,4
	3 Yes, severe	114	2,2

	Total	5131	
	9 No answer	11	
		5142	
X487	DIZZINESS		Y311, U224, V291, W154
	Have you in the last 12 months had giddiness?		
	1 No	4551	88,7
	2 Yes, mild	457	8,9
	3 Yes, severe	124	2,4
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X488	NAUSEA		Y312, U225, V292, W155
	Have you in the last 12 months had a feeling of being unwell, out of sorts?		
	1 No	4521	88,1
	2 Yes, mild	512	10,0
	3 Yes, severe	99	1,9
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X489	WEIGHT LOSS		Y313, U226, V293, W156
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from weight loss?		
	1 No	5016	97,8
	2 Yes, mild	77	1,5
	3 Yes, severe	35	0,7
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	
X490	VOMITING		Y314, U227, V294, W157
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from vomiting?		
	1 No	4803	93,6
	2 Yes, mild	261	5,1
	3 Yes, severe	67	1,3
	Total	5131	
	9 No answer	11	
		5142	
X491	DIARRHOEA		Y315, U228, V295, W158
	Have you in the last 12 months had diarrhoea?		
	1 No	4586	89,4
	2 Yes, mild	447	8,7
	3 Yes, severe	99	1,9

	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X492	CONSTIPATION		Y316, U229, V296, W159
	Have you in the last 12 months had constipation?		
	1 No	4810	93,8
	2 Yes, mild	252	4,9
	3 Yes, severe	68	1,3
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X493	OVEREXERTION		Y317, U230, V297, W160
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from overexertion?		
	1 No	4545	88,6
	2 Yes, mild	438	8,5
	3 Yes, severe	146	2,8
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X494	RASHES		Y318, U231, V298, W161
	Have you in the last 12 months had rashes, eczema or psoriasis?		
	1 No	4468	87,1
	2 Yes, mild	548	10,7
	3 Yes, severe	116	2,3
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X495	CANCER		Y319, U232, V299, W162
	Have you in the last 12 months had a malignant tumour, cancer?		
	1 No	5074	98,9
	2 Yes, mild	30	0,6
	3 Yes, severe	28	0,5
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X496	ANAEMIA		Y320, U233, V300, W163
	Have you in the last 12 months had anaemia?		
	1 No	5015	97,7
	2 Yes, mild	88	1,7
	3 Yes, severe	28	0,5

	Total	5131	
	9 No answer	11	
		5142	
X497	DIABETES		Y321, U234, V301, W164
	Have you in the last 12 months had diabetes, blood sugar?		
	1 No	4967	96,8
	2 Yes, mild	107	2,1
	3 Yes, severe	56	1,1
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X498	OVERWEIGHT		Y322, U235, V302, W165
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from overweight, obesity?		
	1 No	4358	85,0
	2 Yes, mild	627	12,2
	3 Yes, severe	143	2,8
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	
X499	ORGANIC NERVE DISORDER		Y323, U236, V303, W166
	Have you in the last 12 months had an organic nerve disorder (CP, MS, Polio etc.)?		
	1 No	5069	98,8
	2 Yes, mild	27	0,5
	3 Yes, severe	32	0,6
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	
X500	DISCOMFORT AFTER INJURY		Y324, jfr U189
	Have you in the last 12 months had lasting disability/discomfort after an accident or injury?		
	1 No	4646	90,6
	2 Yes, mild	266	5,2
	3 Yes, severe	215	4,2
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X501	ALLERGY		Y325
	Have you in the last 12 months had an allergy?		
	1 No	4151	80,9
	2 Yes, mild	786	15,3
	3 Yes, severe	191	3,7
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	

		5142	
X502	URINARY TRACT INFECTION		Y326
	Have you in the last 12 months had infection of the urinary tract?		
	1 No	4907	95,7
	2 Yes, mild	147	2,9
	3 Yes, severe	73	1,4
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X503	OTHER INFECTION		jfr Y327, jfr U237, jfr V304
	Have you in the last 12 months had any other infection that is not on the list?		
	1 No	5089	99,1
	2 Yes, mild	23	0,4
	3 Yes, severe	25	0,5
	Total	5137	
	9 No answer	5	
		5142	
X504	OTHER INFLAMMATIONS		jfr Y328, jfr U238, jfr V305
	Have you in the last 12 months had any other inflammation that is not on the list?		
	1 No	5092	99,0
	2 Yes, mild	10	0,2
	3 Yes, severe	40	0,8
		5142	
X505	DENTAL TROUBLE		
	Have you in the last 12 months had any dental trouble that is not on the list?		
	1 No	5131	99,9
	2 Yes, mild	1	0,0
	3 Yes, severe	6	0,1
	Total	5138	
	9 No answer	4	
		5142	
X506	METABOLISM TROUBLE		
	Have you in the last 12 months had any metabolism trouble that is not on the list?		
	1 No	5119	99,6
	2 Yes, mild	12	0,2
	3 Yes, severe	10	0,2
	Total	5141	
	9 No answer	1	
		5142	
X507	CIRCULATORY TROUBLE		
	Have you in the last 12 months had any circulatory trouble that is not on the list?		
	1 No	5122	99,6
	2 Yes, mild	13	0,3
	3 Yes, severe	6	0,1
	Total	5141	

	9 No answer	1	
		5142	
X508	OTHER ILLNESSES		
	Have you in the last 12 months had any other illness that is not on the list?		
	1 No	5127	99,7
	2 Yes, mild	6	0,1
	3 Yes, severe	9	0,2
		5142	
X509	HOSPITALIZED		Y329, U253, V310, jfr W172
	Have you admitted to a hospital, nursing home or similar institution in the last 12 months?		
	1 Yes	517	10,1
	2 No	4619	89,9
	Total	5136	
	9 No answer	6	
		5142	
X510	DAYS IN HOSPITAL		jfr Y330, jfr U254, jfr V311, jfr W173
	If yes, how many days altogether? The table is valid for X509 NE 2. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1-5	322	62,4
	6-10	98	19,0
	11-15	36	7,0
	16-20	11	2,1
	21-25	10	1,9
	26-30	13	2,5
	31-35	4	0,8
	36-40	2	0,4
	41-45	2	0,4
	46-50	1	0,2
	56-60	3	0,6
	76-80	1	0,2
	86-90	2	0,4
	100-199	8	1,6
	200-299	1	0,2
	300-399	2	0,4
	Total	516	
	999 No answer	7	
	Not been in hospital	4619	
		5142	
	Mean value		10,75
	Standard deviation		30,50
X511	BEEEN TO A DOCTOR		Y331, U255, V321, jfr W176
	Have you at any time in the last 12 months been to a doctor for some illness or complaint on your own account? (Getting a doctor's certificate for a driver's licence or similar should not be counted. Neither should contact with a doctor while in hospital.)		
	1 Yes	3151	61,4
	2 No	1984	38,6
	Total	5135	
	9 No answer	7	
		5142	

X512**NUMBER OF VISITS TO A DOCTOR****Y332, U256,
V322, W176**

If yes, about how many times have you visited/spoken to a doctor in the last 12 months? The table is valid for X511 EQ 1. This variable is divided into categories.

1	1113	35,5
2	780	24,9
3	403	12,9
4	265	8,5
5	137	4,4
6	95	3,0
7	34	1,1
8	44	1,4
9	16	0,5
10-19	182	5,8
20-29	35	1,1
30-39	16	0,5
40-49	6	0,2
50-59	6	0,2
Total	3132	
99 No answer	26	
Not visited a doctor	1984	
	5142	

X513**REFRAINED MEDICAL CARE**

Have you at any time during the last 12 months refrained from seeing a doctor, even though you felt the need to seek help?

1 Yes	872	17
2 No	4262	83
Total	5134	
9 No answer	8	
	5142	

X514**NUMBER OF TIMES REFRAINED FROM MEDICAL CARE DUE TO PATIENT FEE**

If yes, about how many times during the last 12 months have you refrained from seeking medical care on account of difficulties in paying the patient fee? The table is valid for X514 NE 2.

0	436	51,2
1	163	19,1
2	138	16,2
3	53	6,2
4	18	2,1
5	15	1,8
6	5	0,6
7	1	0,1
8	2	0,2
9	1	0,1
10	14	1,6
12	2	0,2
20	1	0,1
40	1	0,1
77	2	0,2
Total	852	
99 No answer	28	
Not refrained from seeking medical care	4262	
	5142	

	Mean value for all	1,39	
	Standard deviation	4,36	
	Mean value for >0	2,85	
	Standard deviation	5,90	
X515	VISITED A NURSE		Y333, U257, V323, W177
	Have you in the last 12 months spoken with, visited or been visited by a district nurse, school nurse or equivalent? (The consultation or visit should be for your own problems, not e.g. your children's.)		
	1 Yes	1179	23
	2 No	3954	77
	Total	5133	
	9 No answer	9	
		5142	
X516	VISITED A DENTIST		Y334, U261, jfr V328, W182
	Have you been to a dentist in the last 12 months? (The visit should be for your own needs, not e.g. your children's.)		
	1 Yes	3722	72,6
	2 No	1407	27,4
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X517	REFRAINED FROM SEEING A DENTIST		
	Have you at any time during the last 12 months refrained from seeing a dentist, even though you felt the need to seek help?		
	1 Yes	579	11,3
	2 No	4553	88,7
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X518	NUMBER OF TIMES REFRAINED FROM DENTAL CARE DUE TO PATIENT FEE		
	If yes, about how many times during the last 12 months have you refrained from seeking dental care on account of difficulties in paying the patient fee? The table is valid for X517 NE 2.		
	0	171	30,2
	1	240	42,4
	2	83	14,7
	3	36	6,4
	4	12	2,1
	5	9	1,6
	6	5	0,9
	10	5	0,9
	12	1	0,2
	15	1	0,2
	20	1	0,2
	50	1	0,2
	77	1	0,2
	Total	566	
	99 No answer	23	
	Not refrained from care	4553	
		5142	

	Mean value for all	1,52	
	Standard deviation	4,18	
	Mean value for >0	2,18	
	Standard deviation	4,86	
X519	CONDITION OF TEETH		Y336, jfr U269, jfr V336, jfr W185
	Which of the following alternatives best describes the conditions of your teeth?		
	1 No teeth	14	0,3
	2 Dentures, whole or part	260	5,1
	3 Own teeth but in bad condition	118	2,3
	4 Many fillings	2402	46,8
	5 Own teeth in good condition	2337	45,5
	Total	5131	
	9 No answer	11	
		5142	
X520	DENTURES GOOD		Y337, U270, V337, W186
	If respondent has dentures: Do your dentures fit well or do you have trouble with them? The table is valid for X519 EQ 1 or 2.		
	1 Fit well	218	83,5
	2 Give trouble	43	16,5
	Total	261	
	9 No answer	24	
	No dentures	4857	
		5142	
X521	FRESH VEGETABLES		Y339, jfr U276, jfr W198
	How often do you include fresh vegetables in your meals?		
	1 Every meal	715	13,9
	2 At least once a day	2412	47,0
	3 Almost every day	1064	20,7
	4 Once or twice a week	755	14,7
	5 Almost never	188	3,7
	Total	5134	
	9 No answer	8	
		5142	
X522	SMOKING		Y340, jfr U278, jfr V340, jfr W202, W203
	Do you smoke?		
	1 Yes, <10 cigarettes/day	516	10,1
	2 Yes, >10 cigarettes/day	661	12,9
	3 No, have given up	1440	28,1
	4 No, have never smoked	2516	49,0
	Total	5133	
	9 No answer	9	
		5142	
X523	SMOKING NUMBER OF YEARS		Y341, U279
	How many years have you been smoking altogether? The table is valid for X522 NE 4. This variable is divided into categories.		

	0	20	0,8	
	1-9	736	28,3	
	10-19	653	25,1	
	20-29	513	19,7	
	30-39	405	15,5	
	40-49	203	7,8	
	50-59	71	2,7	
	60-69	3	0,1	
	70-79	1	0,0	
	Total	2605		
	99 No answer	21		
	Not smoked	2516		
		5142		
	Mean value for all		18,91	
	Standard deviation		13,58	
	Mean value for >0		19,05	
	Standard deviation		13,53	
X524	SMOKING INDOORS			
	Does anyone smoke regularly in your home?			
	1 Yes	697	13,7	
	2 No	4393	86,3	
	Total	5090		
	9 No answer	52		
		5142		
X525	DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR ETC			Y343, U280, jfr V341, jfr W204
	Do you at any time drink wine, strong beer or liquor?			
	1 Yes	4612	89,8	
	2 No	521	10,2	
	Total	5133		
	9 No answer	9		
		5142		
X526	NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC			
	If yes: During the last 12 months, about how often have you consumed some amount of alcoholic beverage, that is: wine, strong beer or liquor? The table is valid for X525 EQ 1.			
	1 Daily or almost daily (at least 5 days a week)	70	1,5	
	2 2-4 times a week	568	12,3	
	3 Once a week	1215	26,4	
	4 2-3 times a month	1209	26,2	
	5 Once a month	609	13,2	
	6 6-11 times a year	386	8,4	
	7 Less often	522	11,3	
	8 Never	29	0,6	
	Total	4608	100	
	9 No answer	13		
	Doesn't drink alcohol	521		
		5142		
X527	NUMBER OF GLASSES			
	If yes: On such occasions, how many glasses do you usually drink? One glass can be 1 glass of wine, 1 bottle or			

can of beer, or 1 schnapps or drink. The table is valid for X525 EQ 1 and X526 NE 8.

1	987	21,7
2	1679	37,0
3	865	19,0
4	382	8,4
5	262	5,8
6	118	2,6
7	60	1,3
8	71	1,6
9	13	0,3
10	76	1,7
11	2	0,0
12	7	0,2
13	1	0,0
14	1	0,0
15	13	0,3
19	1	0,0
20	1	0,0
24	1	0,0
26	1	0,0
37	1	0,0
Total	4542	
99 No answer	50	
Does not drink alcohol	550	
	5142	
Mean value	2,82	
Standard deviation	2,12	

X528

AGILITY

**Y346, U239,
V734, W559**

Index based on the questions about agility (X436 walk meter, X437 run 100 meter and X438 walk stairs). Any variable non-response equals value 9.

1 Normal agility	4091	79,7
2 Reduced agility	495	9,6
3 Hampered agility	236	4,6
4 Greatly hampered agility	309	6,0
Total	5131	
9 No answer	11	
	5142	

X529

INDEX FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

**Y347, U241,
V736**

Logical index based on dichotomisation of the answers on the questions about psychological well-being (X479 general tiredness, X480 insomnia, X481 nervous trouble and X482 depressions) where No="No" and Yes="Yes, mild" and "Yes, severe". Any variable non-response equals value 99.

1	2973	58,1
2	753	14,7
3	96	1,9
4	262	5,1
5	49	1,0
6	93	1,8
7	275	5,4
8	62	1,2
9	49	1,0

	10	38	0,7
	11	18	0,4
	12	144	2,8
	13	83	1,6
	14	33	0,6
	15	29	0,6
	16	160	3,1
	Total	5117	
	99 No answer	25	
		5142	
X530	PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING		Y348, U242, V737, W573
	Scale based on the logical index X529, where X529=1, 4, 5 gives the value 1, X529=2, 9 gives the value 2, X529=3, 6, 10, 13 gives the value 3, X529=7, 8, 12 gives the value 4 and X529=11, 14, 15, 16 gives the value 5. Any variable non-response equals value 9.		
	1 Normal	3284	64,2
	2 Tiredness	802	15,7
	3 Nervous	310	6,1
	4 Insomnia	481	9,4
	5 Depressions	240	4,7
	Total	5117	
	9 No answer	25	
		5142	
X531	OLLE'S PSYCHOLOGICAL INDEX		Y349
	Added index based on the questions about psychological well-being (X479 general tiredness + X480 insomnia + X481 nervous trouble + X482 depressions + X493 overextension), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 3. Any variable non-response equals value 9.		
	0 No trouble	2854	55,8
	1 1 mild trouble	957	18,7
	2 2 mild trouble	411	8,0
	3 1 severe, 3 mild	302	5,9
	4 1 severe + 1 mild, 4 mild	164	3,2
	5 1 severe + 2 mild, 5 mild	79	1,5
	6 2 severe, 1 severe + 3 mild	100	2,0
	7 2 severe + 1 mild, 1 severe + 4 mild	71	1,4
	8 2 severe + 2 mild	39	0,8
	9 3 severe, 2 severe + 3 mild	45	0,9
	10 3 severe + 1 mild	20	0,4
	11 3 severe + 2 mild	14	0,3
	12 4 severe	30	0,6
	13 4 severe + 1 mild	13	0,3
	15 5 severe	15	0,3
	Total	5114	
	99 No answer	28	
		5142	
X532	ACHE IN THE LOCOMOTOR SYSTEM		Y350, U243, V739, W567
	Added index based on the questions about ache in the locomotor system (X460 aches in shoulders/shoulder blades + X467 pain in back/hips + X478 aches in joints), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 2. Any variable non-response equals value 9.		
	0 No trouble	2096	40,9

1 1 mild trouble	1077	21,0
2 2 mild, 1 severe	879	17,2
3 1 severe + 1 mild, 3 mild	448	8,7
4 1 severe + 2 mild, 2 severe	310	6,0
5 2 severe + 1 mild	159	3,1
6 3 severe	156	3,0
Total	5125	
9 No answer	17	
	5142	

X533	OLLE'S INDEX FOR ACHE	Y351
<p>Added index based on the questions about ache in the locomotor system (X460 aches in shoulders/shoulder blades + X467 pain in back/hips + X478 aches in joints), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 3. Any variable non-response equals value 99.</p>		
0 No trouble	2096	40,9
1 1 mild trouble	1077	21,0
2 2 mild trouble	497	9,7
3 1 severe, 3 mild	552	10,8
4 1 severe + 1 mild	278	5,4
5 1 severe + 2 mild	143	2,8
6 2 severe	167	3,3
7 2 severe + 1 mild	159	3,1
9 3 severe	156	3,0
Total	5125	
99 No answer	17	
	5142	

X534	CIRCULATORY SYSTEM	Y352, U244, V740, W566
<p>Added index based on the questions about the circulatory system (X456 pain in the chest + X463 weak heart + X464 high blood pressure + X476 varicose veins + X477 swollen legs + X486 difficulty in breathing + X487 giddiness), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 2. Any variable non-response equals value 99.</p>		
0 No trouble	3520	68,8
1 1 mild trouble	810	15,8
2 2 mild, 1 severe	367	7,2
3 3 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	178	3,5
4 4 mild, 2 severe etc.	110	2,2
5 5 mild, 1 severe + 3 mild etc.	65	1,3
6 6 mild, 3 severe etc..	28	0,5
7 7 mild, 3 severe + 1 mild etc.	19	0,4
8 4 severe, 3 severe + 2 mild etc.	6	0,1
9 4 severe + 1 mild, etc.	3	0,1
10 10	6	0,1
11 5 severe + 1 mild, 4 severe + 3 mild	1	0,0
12 12	1	0,0
13 13	1	0,0
Total	5115	
99 No answer	27	
	5142	

X535	OLLE'S CIRCULATORY INDEX	Y353
<p>Added index based on the questions about the circulatory system (X456 pain in the chest + X463 weak heart +</p>		

X464 high blood pressure + X487 giddiness), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 3. Any variable non-response equals value 99.

0 No trouble	3909	76,3
1 1 mild trouble	735	14,3
2 2 mild trouble	128	2,5
3 3 mild, 1 severe	201	3,9
4 4 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	75	1,5
5 1 severe + 2 mild	21	0,4
6 2 severe, 1 severe + 3 mild	24	0,5
7 2 severe + 1 mild	14	0,3
8 2 severe + 2 mild	3	0,1
9 3 severe	10	0,2
10 3 severe + 1 mild	2	0,0
12 12	2	0,0
Total	5124	
99 No answer	18	
	5142	

X536

STOMACH TROUBLE

**Y354, U245,
V741, W568**

Added index based on the questions about stomach trouble (X465 stomach pains + X468 gall trouble + X488 being unwell + X490 vomiting + X491 diarrhoea), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 2. Any variable non-response equals value 99.

0 No trouble	3435	67,0
1 1 mild trouble	765	14,9
2 2 mild, 1 severe	493	9,6
3 3 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	208	4,1
4 4 mild, 2 severe, 1 severe + 2 mild	133	2,6
5 5 mild, 2 severe + 1 mild etc.	39	0,8
6 3 severe, 2 severe + 2 mild	31	0,6
7 3 severe + 1 mild, 2 severe + 3 mild	10	0,2
8 4 severe, 3 severe + 2 mild	10	0,2
Total	5124	
99 No answer	18	
	5142	

X537

OLLE'S STOMACH INDEX

Y355

Added index based on the questions about stomach trouble (X465 stomach pains + X488 being unwell + X490 vomiting + X491 diarrhoea), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 3. Any variable non-response equals value 99.

0 No trouble	3491	68,1
1 1 mild trouble	760	14,8
2 2 mild trouble	262	5,1
3 3 mild, 1 severe	333	6,5
4 4 mild, 1 severe + 1 mild	117	2,3
5 1 severe + 2 mild	44	0,9
6 1 severe + 3 mild	58	1,1
7 2 severe + 1 mild	21	0,4
8 2 severe + 2 mild	10	0,2
9 3 severe	17	0,3
10 3 severe + 1 mild	8	0,2
12 4 severe	8	0,2
Total	5129	

	99 No answer	13	
		5142	
X538	DEFECATION TROUBLE		Y356, U246, V742, W569
	Added index based on the questions about defecation trouble (X470 haemorrhoids + X492 constipation), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 2. Any variable non-response equals value 9.		
	0 No trouble	4621	90,1
	1 1 mild trouble	347	6,8
	2 2 mild, 1 severe	120	2,3
	3 1 mild + 1 severe	24	0,5
	4 2 severe	15	0,3
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X539	ACCUMULATED SYMPTOM SCALE		Y357, U247, V743, jfr W637
	Added index (44 item) based on X452 – X471 (but not X462, stroke) and X475 – X499, where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 2. Any variable non-response equals value 99.		
	0	233	4,6
	1	420	8,4
	2	563	11,2
	3	572	11,4
	4	469	9,3
	5	433	8,6
	6	394	7,9
	7	337	6,7
	8	276	5,5
	9	197	3,9
	10	162	3,2
	11	147	2,9
	12	130	2,6
	13	104	2,1
	14	87	1,7
	15	71	1,4
	16	79	1,6
	17	55	1,1
	18	41	0,8
	19	31	0,6
	20	30	0,6
	21	34	0,7
	22	21	0,4
	23	24	0,5
	24	19	0,4
	25	16	0,3
	26	14	0,3
	27	5	0,1
	28	13	0,3
	29	8	0,2
	30	4	0,1
	31	7	0,1
	32	4	0,1

33	3	0,1
34	3	0,1
35	4	0,1
37	2	0,0
38	1	0,0
39	1	0,0
41	1	0,0
46	2	0,0
48	1	0,0
70	1	0,0
Total	5019	
99 No answer	123	
	5142	
Mean value for all		6,67
Standard deviation		5,94
Mean value for >0		6,99
Standard deviation		5,89

X540

ACCUMULATED SYMPTOM SCALE 2

Y358

Added index (47 item) based on X452 – X471 (but not X462, stroke) and X475 – X502, where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 2. Any variable non-response equals value 99.

0	205	4,1
1	381	7,6
2	527	10,5
3	535	10,7
4	471	9,4
5	437	8,7
6	377	7,5
7	335	6,7
8	289	5,8
9	222	4,4
10	180	3,6
11	160	3,2
12	134	2,7
13	98	2,0
14	103	2,1
15	84	1,7
16	77	1,5
17	50	1,0
18	56	1,1
19	42	0,8
20	36	0,7
21	31	0,6
22	25	0,5
23	20	0,4
24	23	0,5
25	20	0,4
26	12	0,2
27	13	0,3
28	10	0,2
29	11	0,2

30	6	0,1
31	9	0,2
32	7	0,1
33	4	0,1
34	3	0,1
35	5	0,1
36	2	0,0
37	2	0,0
38	2	0,0
41	2	0,0
43	1	0,0
50	2	0,0
52	1	0,0
75	1	0,0
Total	5011	
99 No answer	131	
	5142	
Mean value for all		7,07
Standard deviation		6,23
Mean value for >0		7,37
Standard deviation		6,19

X542

NUMBER OF YES ON SYMPTOM

Added index (44 item) based on X452 – X471 (but not X462, stroke) and X475 – X499, where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" and "Yes, severe" is coded 1. Any variable non-response equals value 99.

**Y359, U248,
V744, jfr
W638**

0	233	4,6
1	524	10,4
2	669	13,3
3	664	13,2
4	544	10,8
5	472	9,4
6	416	8,3
7	340	6,8
8	252	5,0
9	179	3,6
10	160	3,2
11	120	2,4
12	114	2,3
13	91	1,8
14	59	1,2
15	46	0,9
16	34	0,7
17	26	0,5
18	18	0,4
19	21	0,4
20	7	0,1
21	10	0,2
22	9	0,2
23	4	0,1
24	4	0,1
25	1	0,0

26	1	0,0
40	1	0,0
Total	5019	
99 No answer	123	
	5142	
Mean value for all		5,26
Standard deviation		4,13
Mean value for >0		5,52
Standard deviation		4,06
X543	NUMBER OF YES ON SYMPTOM 2	
Added index (47 item) based on X452 – X471 (but not X462, stroke) and X475 – X502, where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" and "Yes, severe" is coded 1. Any variable non-response equals value 99.		
0	205	4,1
1	477	9,5
2	624	12,5
3	632	12,6
4	536	10,7
5	495	9,9
6	407	8,1
7	341	6,8
8	281	5,6
9	203	4,1
10	163	3,3
11	147	2,9
12	101	2,0
13	103	2,1
14	81	1,6
15	49	1,0
16	44	0,9
17	26	0,5
18	16	0,3
19	20	0,4
20	19	0,4
21	11	0,2
22	11	0,2
23	4	0,1
24	7	0,1
25	3	0,1
26	2	0,0
27	1	0,0
28	1	0,0
43	1	0,0
Total	5011	
99 No answer	131	
	5142	
Mean value for all		5,58
Standard deviation		4,33
Mean value for >0		5,82
Standard deviation		4,26
X544	TOTAL HOURS WORKED 1999	Y360, U283,

Total number of hours worked in gainful employment during 1999. The sum of full-time, part-time, farm work, assisting on farm, work in own firm, assisting in firm and freelance occupation. This variable is divided into categories.

V789, W940

0	1307	25,9
1-99	27	0,5
100-199	48	1,0
200-299	69	1,4
300-399	77	1,5
400-499	68	1,3
500-599	37	0,7
600-699	48	1,0
700-799	28	0,6
800-899	45	0,9
900-999	38	0,8
1000-1099	173	3,4
1100-1199	36	0,7
1200-1299	55	1,1
1300-1399	55	1,1
1400-1499	61	1,2
1500-1599	176	3,5
1600-1699	98	1,9
1700-1799	56	1,1
1800-1899	158	3,1
1900-1999	217	4,3
2000-2099	1562	31,0
2100-2199	59	1,2
2200-2299	40	0,8
2300-2399	138	2,7
2400-2499	31	0,6
2500-2599	11	0,2
2600-2699	130	2,6
2700-2799	10	0,2
2800-2899	46	0,9
2900-2999	13	0,3
3000-3099	2	0,0
3100-3199	76	1,5
3300-3399	12	0,2
3400-3499	1	0,0
3600-3699	15	0,3
3700-3799	1	0,0
3900-3999	6	0,1
4100-4199	2	0,0
4200-4299	1	0,0
4300-4399	1	0,0
4500-4599	3	0,1
4800-4899	1	0,0
5200-5299	1	0,0
6100-6199	1	0,0
6500-6599	1	0,0
6600-6699	4	0,1
Total	5045	
9999 No answer	97	
	5142	

Mean value for all

1347,53

	Standard deviation		1003,66
	Mean value for >0		1818,70
	Standard deviation		708,87
X545	EMPLOYED FULL-TIME 1999		Y361, U284, V342, jfr W205, W206
	Were you employed full-time (including vacation and sick-leave) during 1999?		
	1 Yes	2744	53,4
	2 No	2390	46,6
	Total	5134	
	9 No answer	8	
		5142	
X546	WEEKS FULL-TIME 1999		Y362, U285, V343, jfr W205, W206
	Number of weeks during 1999: employed full-time.		
	1	1	0,0
	2	5	0,2
	3	5	0,2
	4	18	0,7
	5	6	0,2
	6	15	0,5
	7	7	0,3
	8	44	1,6
	9	11	0,4
	10	22	0,8
	11	3	0,1
	12	31	1,1
	13	7	0,3
	14	7	0,3
	15	2	0,1
	16	25	0,9
	17	11	0,4
	18	11	0,4
	19	1	0,0
	20	25	0,9
	21	7	0,3
	22	8	0,3
	23	3	0,1
	24	11	0,4
	25	16	0,6
	26	59	2,2
	27	2	0,1
	28	14	0,5
	29	4	0,1
	30	20	0,7
	32	21	0,8
	33	3	0,1
	34	10	0,4
	35	10	0,4
	36	15	0,5
	37	1	0,0
	38	5	0,2
	39	7	0,3
	40	20	0,7

42		8	0,3
43		7	0,3
44		12	0,4
45		1	0,0
46		8	0,3
47		2	0,1
48		18	0,7
49		2	0,1
50		7	0,3
51		1	0,0
52		2171	79,5
	Total	2730	
99	No answer	22	
	Not employed full-time 1999	2390	
		5142	
	Mean value		46,10
	Standard deviation		13,06
X547	HOURS PER WEEK FULL-TIME 1999		Y363, U286, V344, jfr W205, W206
	Numbers of hours on average per week during 1999: full-time employed. This variable is divided into categories.		
	10-19	3	0,1
	20-29	12	0,4
	30-39	430	15,9
	40-49	2105	78,0
	50-59	116	4,3
	60-69	28	1,0
	70-79	6	0,2
	Total	2700	
	99 No answer	52	
	Not employed full-time 1999	2390	
		5142	
	Mean value		40,47
	Standard deviation		4,14
X548	EMPLOYED PART-TIME 1999		Y364, U288, V346, jfr W207, W208
	Were you employed part-time (including vacation and sick-leave) during 1999?		
	1 Yes	761	14,8
	2 No	4373	85,2
	Total	5134	
	9 No answer	8	
		5142	
X549	WEEKS PART-TIME 1999		Y365, U289, V347, jfr W207, W208
	Number of weeks during 1999: employed part-time.		
	1	1	0,1
	2	4	0,5
	3	8	1,1
	4	5	0,7
	5	6	0,8
	6	6	0,8
	7	2	0,3
	8	21	2,8
	9	3	0,4

10	4	0,5
11	1	0,1
12	20	2,7
13	1	0,1
14	2	0,3
15	3	0,4
16	10	1,3
17	2	0,3
18	2	0,3
19	1	0,1
20	14	1,9
21	1	0,1
22	5	0,7
23	1	0,1
24	3	0,4
25	7	0,9
26	24	3,2
27	3	0,4
28	3	0,4
29	2	0,3
30	14	1,9
31	3	0,4
32	10	1,3
33	2	0,3
34	2	0,3
35	4	0,5
36	6	0,8
37	2	0,3
38	3	0,4
39	1	0,1
40	16	2,1
41	1	0,1
42	1	0,1
43	1	0,1
44	9	1,2
45	2	0,3
46	1	0,1
48	5	0,7
49	1	0,1
50	5	0,7
51	2	0,3
52	498	66,0
Total	754	
99 No answer	15	
Not employed part-time 1999	4373	
	5142	
Mean value		42,26
Standard deviation		15,71

X550

HOURS PER WEEK PART-TIME 1999

Numbers of hours on average per week during 1999: part-time employed. This variable is divided into categories.

**Y366, U290,
V348, jfr
W207,
W208**

1-9	31	4,2
10-19	79	10,7
20-29	280	38,0

	30-39		342	46,4	
	40-49		3	0,4	
	50-59		1	0,1	
	60-69		1	0,1	
	Total		737		
	99 No answer		32		
	Not employed part-time 1999		4373		
			5142		
	Mean value			25,37	
	Standard deviation			7,96	
X551	FARM WORK 1999				Y369, U296, V356, jfr W210, W211
	Did you do farm work during 1999?				
	1 Yes		63	1,2	
	2 No		5071	98,8	
	Total		5134		
	9 No answer		8		
			5142		
X552	FARM WORK WEEKS 1999				Y370, U297, V357, jfr W210, W211
	Number of weeks during 1999: farm work.				
	4		1	1,6	
	7		1	1,6	
	10		1	1,6	
	40		1	1,6	
	52		59	93,7	
	Total		63		
	99 No answer		8		
	Did not do farm work		5071		
			5142		
	Mean value			49,67	
	Standard deviation			9,75	
X553	HOURS PER WEEK FARM WORK 1999				Y371, U298, V358, jfr W210, W211
	Numbers of hours per week during 1999: farm work. This variable is divided into categories.				
	1-9		14	23,0	
	10-19		12	19,7	
	20-29		6	9,8	
	30-39		7	11,5	
	40-49		7	11,5	
	50-59		6	9,8	
	60-69		4	6,6	
	70-79		4	6,6	
	90-98		1	1,6	
	Total		61		
	99 No answer		10		
	Did not do farm work		5071		
			5142		
	Mean value			29,02	
	Standard deviation			23,27	
X554	ASSISTED ON FARM 1999				Y372, U300, V360, jfr W212,
	Did you assist on family member's farm at least 1 hour/day during 1999?				

				W213
	1	Yes	27	0,5
	2	No	5107	99,5
		Total	5134	
	9	No answer	8	
			5142	
X555		WEEKS ASSISTED ON FARM 1999		Y373, U301, V361, jfr W212, W213
		Number of weeks during 1999: assisted on family member's farm.		
	3		2	8
	10		1	4
	15		1	4
	44		1	4
	49		1	4
	52		19	76
		Total	25	
	99	No answer	10	
		Did not do farm work	5107	
			5142	
		Mean value		44,48
		Standard deviation		16,58
X556		HOURS PER WEEK ASSISTED ON FARM 1999		Y374, U302, V362, jfr W212, W213
		Numbers of hours per week during 1999: assisted on family member's farm.		
	1		3	12,5
	2		2	8,3
	3		3	12,5
	5		3	12,5
	7		3	12,5
	8		1	4,2
	10		2	8,3
	12		1	4,2
	15		2	8,3
	20		2	8,3
	25		1	4,2
	50		1	4,2
		Total	24	
	99	No answer	11	
		Did not do farm work	5107	
			5142	
		Mean value		9,88
		Standard deviation		10,84
X557		WORK IN OWN FIRM 1999		Y375, U304, V364, jfr W214, W215
		Did you work in your own or in partnership firm, during 1999?		
	1	Yes	398	7,8
	2	No	4736	92,2
		Total	5134	
	9	No answer	8	
			5142	
X558		WEEKS IN OWN FIRM		Y376, U305, V365, jfr W214, W215
		Number of weeks during 1999: work in own or in partnership firm.		

4	3	0,8
5	1	0,3
8	1	0,3
10	1	0,3
12	3	0,8
15	1	0,3
16	3	0,8
20	9	2,3
22	2	0,5
25	1	0,3
26	2	0,5
28	3	0,8
30	3	0,8
31	1	0,3
32	4	1,0
35	2	0,5
36	1	0,3
37	1	0,3
38	3	0,8
39	1	0,3
40	4	1,0
44	5	1,3
48	3	0,8
49	3	0,8
50	2	0,5
51	2	0,5
52	326	83,4
Total	391	
99 No answer	15	
Did not work in own firm	4736	
	5142	
Mean value		48,31
Standard deviation		9,96

X559

HOURS PER WEEK IN OWN FIRM 1999

**Y377, U306,
V366, jfr
W214,
W215**

Numbers of hours per week during 1999: work in own or in partnership firm. This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	37	9,6
10-19	18	4,7
20-29	31	8,0
30-39	35	9,0
40-49	108	27,9
50-59	84	21,7
60-69	56	14,5
70-79	14	3,6
80-89	3	0,8
90-98	1	0,3
Total	387	
99 No answer	19	
Did not work in own firm	4736	
	5142	
Mean value		48,31
Standard deviation		9,96

X560	ASSISTANT IN FIRM 1999		Y378, U308, V368, jfr W216, W217
	Did you assist in family member's firm at least 1 hour per day during 1999?		
	1 Yes	39	0,8
	2 No	5095	99,2
	Total	5134	
	9 No answer	8	
		5142	
X561	WEEKS ASSISTANT IN FIRM 1999		Y379, U309, V369, jfr W216, W217
	Number of weeks during 1999: assist in family member's firm.		
	7	1	2,7
	8	2	5,4
	10	2	5,4
	12	1	2,7
	16	3	8,1
	20	1	2,7
	26	3	8,1
	40	1	2,7
	42	1	2,7
	51	1	2,7
	52	21	56,8
	Total	37	
	99 No answer	10	
	Did not assist in family member's firm	5095	
		5142	
	Mean value		38,54
	Standard deviation		17,88
X562	HOURS PER WEEK ASSISTANT IN FIRM 1999		Y380, U310, V370, jfr W216, W217
	Numbers of hours per week during 1999: assist in family member's firm.		
	1	1	2,6
	2	1	2,6
	3	2	5,3
	4	5	13,2
	5	5	13,2
	7	2	5,3
	8	1	2,6
	10	4	10,5
	20	6	15,8
	25	2	5,3
	30	2	5,3
	32	1	2,6
	40	4	10,5
	45	1	2,6
	60	1	2,6
	Total	38	
	No answer	9	
	Did not assist in family member's firm	5095	
		5142	
	Mean value		16,92
	Standard deviation		15,08

X563	FREELANCE PROFESSION 1999			Y381, U312, V372, jfr W218, W219
	Did you work in a freelance occupation or did you have a side-line/extra job during 1999?			
	1 Yes	202	3,9	
	2 No	4932	96,1	
	Total	5134		
	9 No answer	8		
		5142		
X564	WEEKS IN FREELANCE OCCUPATION 1999			Y382, U313, V373, jfr W218, W219
	Number of weeks during 1999: work in freelance occupation/side-line job. The table is valid for X563 NE 2.			
	1	6	3,0	
	2	9	4,5	
	3	4	2,0	
	4	10	5,1	
	5	6	3,0	
	6	9	4,5	
	7	1	0,5	
	8	6	3,0	
	9	1	0,5	
	10	6	3,0	
	11	1	0,5	
	12	8	4,0	
	13	1	0,5	
	15	5	2,5	
	16	3	1,5	
	17	1	0,5	
	18	1	0,5	
	20	10	5,1	
	21	1	0,5	
	22	2	1,0	
	24	2	1,0	
	25	3	1,5	
	26	3	1,5	
	32	2	1,0	
	35	2	1,0	
	36	2	1,0	
	39	1	0,5	
	40	4	2,0	
	42	1	0,5	
	43	1	0,5	
	45	1	0,5	
	46	1	0,5	
	48	4	2,0	
	50	1	0,5	
	52	79	39,9	
	Total	198		
	99 No answer	12		
	No freelance profession	4932		
		5142		
	Mean value		30,10	
	Standard deviation		20,77	

X565	HOURS PER WEEK IN FREELANCE OCCUPATION 1999		Y383, U314, V374, jfr W218, W219
	Numbers of hours per week during 1999: work in freelance occupation/side-line job. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1-9	80	42,3
	10-19	42	22,2
	20-29	25	13,2
	30-39	11	5,8
	40-49	29	15,3
	60-69	2	1,1
	Total	189	
	99 No answer	21	
	No freelance profession	4932	
		5142	
	Mean value		16,04
	Standard deviation		13,83
X566	UNEMPLOYED DURING 1999		Y384, U316, V376, jfr W220
	Were you seeking or waiting for employment, unemployed or laid off during 1999?		
	1 Yes	456	8,9
	2 No	4674	91,1
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X567	WEEKS UNEMPLOYED 1999		Y385, U317, V377, jfr W220
	Number of weeks during 1999: waiting for employment/unemployed/laid off. The table is valid for X566 NE 2. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1-9	95	21,7
	10-19	84	19,2
	20-29	67	15,3
	30-39	33	7,5
	40-49	20	4,6
	50-52	139	31,7
	Total	438	
	99 No answer	30	
	Not unemployed	4674	
		5142	
	Mean value		28,62
	Standard deviation		18,76
X568	HOUSEHOLD WORK 1999		jfr Y367, jfr U292, jfr V350, jfr W238
	Did you take care of your own household during 1999?		
	1 Yes	3019	58,8
	2 No	2111	41,2
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X569	WEEKS HOUSEHOLD WORK 1999		jfr Y368, jfr U293, jfr V351, jfr W238
	Number of weeks during 1999: take care of own household. The table is valid for X568 NE 2. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1-9	13	0,5

	10-19	30	1,1
	20-29	28	1,1
	30-39	6	0,2
	40-49	17	0,6
	50-52	2559	96,5
	Total	2653	
99	No answer	378	
	Not applicable	2111	
		5142	
	Mean value		50,95
	Standard deviation		5,98
X570	LAST WEEK: FULL-TIME		Y398, jfr U332, jfr V345
	Were you employed full-time (also vacation, sick leave, parental leave, studies etc.) last week?		
	1 Yes	2457	47,8
	2 No	2680	52,2
	Total	5137	
	9 No answer	5	
		5142	
X571	LAST WEEK: PART-TIME		Y399, jfr U333, jfr V349
	Were you employed part-time (also vacation, sick leave, parental leave, studies etc.) last week?		
	1 Yes	668	13
	2 No	4469	87
	Total	5137	
	9 No answer	5	
		5142	
X572	LAST WEEK: FARM WORK		Y400, U336, V359
	Did you work on a farm last week?		
	1 Yes	68	1,3
	2 No	5069	98,7
	Total	5137	
	9 No answer	5	
		5142	
X573	LAST WEEK: ASSIST ON FARM		Y401, U337, V363
	Did you assist on a family member's farm at least 1 hour/day last week?		
	1 Yes	19	0,4
	2 No	5116	99,6
	Total	5135	
	9 No answer	7	
		5142	
X574	LAST WEEK: OWN FIRM		Y402, U338, V367
	Did you work in own or part-owned firm last week?		
	1 Yes	378	7,4
	2 No	4759	92,6
	Total	5137	
	9 No answer	5	
		5142	

X575	LAST WEEK: ASSISTANT IN FIRM	Y403, U339, V371
	Did you assist in a family member's firm at least 1 hour per day last week?	
	1 Yes	30 0,6
	2 No	5107 99,4
	Total	5137
	9 No answer	5
		5142
X576	LAST WEEK: FREELANCE OCCUPATION	Y404, U340, V375
	Did you work in a freelance occupation or a side-line/extra job last week?	
	1 Yes	152 3
	2 No	4985 97
	Total	5137
	9 No answer	5
		5142
X577	LAST WEEK: LOOKING FOR WORK	Y405, U341, V378
	Were you looking or waiting for work, unemployed or laid off last week?	
	1 Yes	317 6,2
	2 No	4820 93,8
	Total	5137
	9 No answer	5
		5142
X578	LAST WEEK: PENSION	Y406, U344, V387
	Were you pensioned (also disability pension or partial pension) last week?	
	1 Yes	968 18,8
	2 No	4169 81,2
	Total	5137
	9 No answer	5
		5142
X579	LAST WEEK: MILITARY SERVICE	Y407, U345, V390
	Were you in military service last week?	
	1 Yes	15 0,3
	2 No	5122 99,7
	Total	5137
	9 No answer	5
		5142
X580	LAST WEEK: STUDYING	Y408, U346, V393
	Were you studying (incl. adult education and labour market training) last week?	
	1 Yes	510 9,9
	2 No	4627 90,1
	Total	5137
	9 No answer	5
		5142
X581	LAST WEEK: HOUSEHOLD	Y409, U334, V352
	Did you take care of your own household last week?	

	1	Yes	2938	57,2
	2	No	2199	42,8
		Total	5137	
	9	No answer	5	
			5142	
X582	LAST WEEK: OTHER			Y410, U347, V396
	Did you have any other occupation last week?			
	1	Yes	147	2,9
	2	No	4987	97,1
		Total	5134	
	9	No answer	8	
			5142	
X583	SEI EMPLOYEES			Y411, jfr U355, jfr V712
	What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Coded according to socio-economic classification (SEI). The table is valid for employees last week.			
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	204	6,6
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	561	18,0
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	358	11,5
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	216	6,9
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	164	5,3
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	58	1,9
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	283	9,1
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	53	1,7
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	678	21,8
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	451	14,5
	57	Professional, upper-level executive**	88	2,8
		Total	3114	
	99	Unclassified	10	
		Not employed last week	2018	
			5142	
X584	NYK80 EMPLOYEES			Y412, jfr U356
	What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Profession according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.			
X585	NYK85 EMPLOYEES			
	What is your position in the workplace? Can you describe your assignments briefly? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.			
X586	PERFORM WORK ASSIGNMENTS: WHERE			
	Where do you usually perform your work assignments?			
	0	At employer's address	2460	78,9
	1	At a (permanent) workplace belonging to employer	206	6,6
	2	At several different workplaces belonging to employer	135	4,3
	3	At a (permanent) workplace belonging to other employer	29	0,9
	4	At several different workplaces belonging to other employer	92	3,0
	5	At a moving workplace (car, bus or the like)	96	3,1

	6	In own home	24	0,8	
	7	In other people's homes	52	1,7	
	8	Other location	22	0,7	
		Total	3116		
	9	No answer	8		
		Not employed last week	2018		
			5142		
X587		ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, CURRENT JOB			
		How good are the opportunities for advancement in a job like yours?			
	1	Very good	303	9,8	
	2	Fairly good	756	24,4	
	3	Fairly poor	1229	39,7	
	4	Very poor	807	26,1	
		Total	3095		
	9	No answer	29		
		Not employed last week	2018		
			5142		
X588		ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES, DIFFERENT EMPLOYERS			
		Are the opportunities for advancement good where you work now, at other workplaces or both?			
	1	Good opportunities at respondent's current workplace	284	27,2	
	2	Good opportunities at other workplaces	132	12,6	
	3	Both	630	60,2	
		Total	1046		
	9	No answer	46		
		Not employed last week/Not applicable	4050		
			5142		
X590		NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES			Y414, jfr U357, jfr V404, jfr W233
		How many persons do you supervise? This variable is divided into categories.			
	0		2344	75,4	
	1-9		493	15,9	
	10-19		113	3,6	
	20-29		58	1,9	
	30-39		31	1,0	
	40-49		19	0,6	
	50-59		11	0,4	
	60-69		8	0,3	
	70-79		7	0,2	
	80-89		2	0,1	
	100-199		9	0,3	
	200-299		8	0,3	
	300-399		2	0,1	
	400-499		1	0,0	
	600-699		1	0,0	
		Total	3107		
	999	No answer	17		
		Not employed last week	2018		
			5142		
		Mean value for all		4,13	
		Standard deviation		21,81	
		Mean value for >0		16,83	

Standard deviation		41,52	
X591	EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS		Y415, U358, V405, jfr W234
	Is any schooling or vocational training above elementary schooling necessary for your job?		
	1 Yes	2319	74,5
	2 No	793	25,5
	Total	3112	
	9 No answer	12	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X592	SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL		Y416, U359, V406, jfr W234
	About how many years of education above elementary school are necessary? The table is valid for employees last week and X591 EQ 1.		
	0	55	2,4
	1	139	6,1
	2	234	10,2
	3	824	36,0
	4	239	10,4
	5	164	7,2
	6	291	12,7
	7	180	7,9
	8	95	4,2
	9	13	0,6
	10	14	0,6
	11	6	0,3
	12	7	0,3
	13	2	0,1
	14	3	0,1
	15	9	0,4
	16	9	0,4
	17	2	0,1
	18	1	0,0
	22	1	0,0
	Total	2288	
	99 No answer	43	
	Not employed last week/Not applicable	2811	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		4,13
	Standard deviation		2,44
	Mean value for >0		4,23
	Standard deviation		2,38
X593	LEARNING TIME		Y417
	Apart from the competence necessary to get a job such as yours, how long does it take to learn to do the job reasonably well?		
	1 1 day or less	51	1,6
	2 2-5 days	156	5,0
	3 1-4 weeks	385	12,5
	4 1-3 months	490	15,9
	5 3 months - 1 year	775	25,1
	6 1 to 2 years	563	18,2
	7 More than 2 years	671	21,7

	Total	3091	
	9 No answer	33	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X594	USE OF PREVIOUS KNOWLEDGE		Y418
	To what extent can you in your daily work make use of what you've learnt through your education or previous job experience?		
	1 To a very large extent	1092	35,1
	2 To a large extent	825	26,5
	3 To a certain extent	677	21,8
	4 To a small extent	278	8,9
	5 Not at all	237	7,6
	Total	3109	
	9 No answer	15	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X595	KNOWLEDGE CORRESPONDS TO WORK REQUIREMENTS		
	How well do you think your skills and knowledge correspond to the requirements of your work? Do you think that you ...		
	1 ... are very overqualified	132	4,2
	2 ... are somewhat overqualified	452	14,5
	3 ... are suitably qualified	1867	60,0
	4 ... need certain additional skills	594	19,1
	5 ... need a good many additional skills	67	2,2
	Total	3112	
	9 No answer	12	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X596	SPECIFIC COMPETENCE		Y419
	Do you know of any other employers where you would have good use for what you've learnt in your current job?		
	1 Yes, many	1082	34,9
	2 Yes, some	1037	33,4
	3 Yes, one or two	354	11,4
	4 No	631	20,3
	Total	3104	
	9 No answer	20	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X597	ON-THE-JOB TRAINING		Y420
	Have you in the last 12 months received any kind of education on paid work-time?		
	1 Yes	1513	48,5
	2 No	1604	51,5
	Total	3117	
	9 No answer	7	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X598	NUMBER OF DAYS, ON-THE-JOB TRAINING		Y421
	How many whole days altogether was this education? The table is valid for X597 EQ 1. This variable is divided		

into categories.

1-4	629	41,8
5-9	446	29,6
10-19	285	18,9
20-29	80	5,3
30-39	28	1,9
40-49	8	0,5
50-59	11	0,7
60-69	6	0,4
70-79	1	0,1
90-99	3	0,2
120-129	1	0,1
150-159	2	0,1
190-199	1	0,1
240-249	2	0,1
290-299	1	0,1
360-365	2	0,1
Total	1506	
999 No answer	14	
Not employed last week/Did not receive education	3622	
	5142	
Mean value		9,29
Standard deviation		20,81

X599

ON-THE-JOB TRAINING: HELP TO ADVANCE

Could the education help you to advance at your workplace? The table is valid for respondent whose education lasted more than 4 days.

1 Yes	411	47,1
2 No	429	49,1
8 Doesn't know	33	3,8
Total	873	
No answer	18	
Not employed last week/Did not receive education	4251	
	5142	

X600

ON-THE-JOB TRAINING: SPECIFIC/GENERAL

Could this education be useful at another workplace? The table is valid for respondent whose education lasted more than 4 days.

1 Yes	761	87,1
2 No	84	9,6
8 Doesn't know	29	3,3
Total	874	
No answer	17	
Not employed last week/Did not receive education	4251	
	5142	

X601

WORKING HOURS OR SHIFT

**Y422, jfr
U360**

What are your normal working hours or what shift do you work?

1 Daytime	2395	76,9
2 Evening/night/morning	123	3,9
3 2-shifts	159	5,1
4 3-shifts	62	2,0
5 Irregular passes	376	12,1

	Total	3115	
	9 No answer	9	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X602	REGULAR WORKTIME PER WEEK		Y460, U418, V459, W251
	How many hours are your regular weekly work hours? This variable is divided into categories.		
	1-5	9	0,3
	6-10	30	1,0
	11-15	13	0,4
	16-20	157	5,1
	21-25	73	2,3
	26-30	222	7,1
	31-35	198	6,4
	36-40	2218	71,4
	41-45	124	4,0
	46-50	32	1,0
	51-55	16	0,5
	56-60	12	0,4
	66-70	1	0,0
	76-80	1	0,0
	81-85	1	0,0
	Total	3107	
	99 No answer	17	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
	Mean value		37,38
	Standard deviation		8,53
X603	SUITABLE WORK TIME		Y461, U420, V468
	Is your normal work-time what suits you best or would you prefer shorter or longer working hours? (Take into account that your wages would diminish or increase accordingly.)		
	1 Present best	2352	75,7
	2 Shorter better	543	17,5
	3 Longer better	210	6,8
	Total	3105	
	9 No answer	19	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X604	HOW OFTEN OVERTIME		
	How often do you work overtime? Is it ... (concerns respondent's current job).		
	1 By and large never	811	26,2
	2 A few times a year	440	14,2
	3 A couple times a month	724	23,3
	4 A couple of times a week	564	18,2
	5 Several times a week	557	18,0
	6 Not applicable	5	0,2
	Total	3101	
	9 No answer	23	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	

X605**OVERTIME PER YEAR**

About how many hours of overtime does this amount to during one year? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	36	8,7
10-19	102	24,8
20-29	113	27,4
30-39	43	10,4
40-49	45	10,9
50-59	37	9,0
60-69	11	2,7
70-79	3	0,7
80-89	2	0,5
90-99	1	0,2
100-199	16	3,9
200-299	2	0,5
300-399	1	0,2
Total	412	
999 No answer	28	
Not employed last week/No overtime	4702	
	5142	
Mean value		30,16
Standard deviation		29,65

X606**OVERTIME PER MONTH**

About how many hours of overtime does this amount to during one month?

1-9	455	64,0
10-19	186	26,2
20-29	52	7,3
30-39	4	0,6
40-49	8	1,1
50-59	4	0,6
70-79	1	0,1
100-109	1	0,1
Total	711	
999 No answer	13	
Not employed last week/No overtime	4418	
	5142	
Mean value		8,80
Standard deviation		8,31

X607**OVERTIME PER WEEK**

About how many hours of overtime does this amount to during one week?

1-9	830	75,6
10-19	230	20,9
20-29	31	2,8
30-39	6	0,5
40-49	1	0,1
Total	1098	
99 No answer	23	
Not employed last week/No overtime	4021	
	5142	
Mean value		6,13
Standard deviation		4,87

X608	OVERTIME HOURS		jfr Y439, jfr U385, jfr V764, jfr W243
	Total number of hours of overtime during one week? (Valid for X604, X605, X606, X607). This variable is divided into categories.		
	>1	529	23,8
	1-9	1417	63,8
	10-19	236	10,6
	20-29	32	1,4
	30-39	6	0,3
	40-49	1	0,0
	Total	2221	
	9999 No answer	64	
	Not employed last week/No overtime	2857	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		3,80
	Standard deviation		4,30
	Mean value for >0		4,83
	Standard deviation		4,46
X609	COMPENSATION FOR OVERTIME		
	Are you entitled to financial compensation for the overtime you work?		
	1 Yes	2347	75,9
	2 No	741	24,0
	3 Not applicable	5	0,2
	Total	3093	
	9 No answer	31	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X610	WORKED WHEN SICK		
	During the last 12 months, have you – in order to avoid salary reductions – worked instead of taking sick leave?		
	1 Yes, several times	361	11,6
	2 Yes, once or twice	533	17,2
	3 No, never	2210	71,2
	Total	3104	
	9 No answer	20	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X611	FIXED MONTHLY SALARY BEFORE TAX		Y464, U434, V720, jfr W272, W275
	Salary in SEK per month before tax: fixed monthly salary. This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	481	15,8
	1-999	1	0,0
	2000-2999	1	0,0
	3000-3999	5	0,2
	4000-4999	5	0,2
	5000-5999	6	0,2
	6000-6999	16	0,5
	7000-7999	33	1,1
	8000-8999	43	1,4
	9000-9999	38	1,2
	10000-10999	65	2,1
	11000-11999	62	2,0

12000-12999	92	3,0
13000-13999	119	3,9
14000-14999	202	6,6
15000-15999	246	8,1
16000-16999	264	8,7
17000-17999	220	7,2
18000-18999	182	6,0
19000-19999	132	4,3
20000-29999	632	20,7
30000-39999	131	4,3
40000-49999	46	1,5
50000-59999	18	0,6
60000-69999	8	0,3
70000-79999	1	0,0
150000-159999	1	0,0
300000-399999	2	0,1
Total	3052	
999999 No answer	72	
Not employed last week	2018	
	5142	
Mean value for all		16145,93
Standard deviation		12623,48
Mean value for >0		19166,62
Standard deviation		11456,77

X612

WEEKLY WAGE BEFORE TAX

**Y465, U435,
V721, jfr
W272,
W275**

Salary in SEK per week before tax: fixed weekly wage.

0	3111	99,8
2253	1	0,0
3615	1	0,0
4000	1	0,0
4800	1	0,0
5000	1	0,0
Total	3116	
999999 No answer	8	
Not employed last week	2018	
	5142	
Mean value for all		6,31
Standard deviation		162,28
Mean value for >0		3933,60
Standard deviation		1097,52

X613

FIXED HOURLY WAGE

**Y466, U436,
V722, jfr
W272,
W275**

Salary in SEK per hour before tax: flat rate per hour. This variable is divided into categories.

0	2729	87,8
50-59	5	0,2
60-69	29	0,9
70-79	72	2,3
80-89	102	3,3
90-99	66	2,1
100-109	51	1,6
110-119	27	0,9
120-129	12	0,4

130-139	5	0,2
140-149	3	0,1
150-159	2	0,1
180-189	1	0,0
190-199	1	0,0
200-209	1	0,0
250-259	1	0,0
270-279	1	0,0
Total	3108	
999 No answer	16	
Not employed last week	2018	
	5142	
Mean value for all		11,13
Standard deviation		30,92
Mean value for >0		91,25
Standard deviation		22,96

X614

INDIVIDUAL PIECE-RATE

**Y467, U437,
jfr V723,
V724, jfr
W272,
W275**

Average earnings in SEK per hour before tax: individual piece-rate. This variable is divided into categories.

0	3095	99,3
1-9	1	0,0
10-19	2	0,1
20-29	2	0,1
30-39	1	0,0
70-79	1	0,0
80-89	3	0,1
90-99	2	0,1
100-109	2	0,1
110-119	4	0,1
120-129	1	0,0
140-149	1	0,0
400-409	1	0,0
Total	3116	
999 No answer	8	
Not employed last week	2018	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,62
Standard deviation		10,03
Mean value for >0		92,67
Standard deviation		81,85

X615

GROUP PIECE-RATE

**Y468, U438,
V725, jfr
W272,
W275**

Average earnings in SEK per hour before tax: group piece-rate. This variable is divided into categories.

0	3087	99,1
1-9	2	0,1
10-19	2	0,1
20-29	2	0,1
30-39	1	0,0
50-59	1	0,0
100-109	1	0,0
110-119	3	0,1
120-129	10	0,3
130-139	5	0,2

140-149	1	0,0
160-169	1	0,0
Total	3116	
999 No answer	8	
Not employed last week	2018	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,90
Standard deviation		10,45
Mean value for >0		96,93
Standard deviation		50,08

X616

MONTHLY SALARY W BONUS/COMMISSION

**jfr Y469, jfr
U439, jfr
V726, jfr
W272,
W275**

Average monthly salary before tax: fixed salary with bonus or commission, not included in any alternative above.
This variable is divided into categories.

0	2869	92,7
1-999	49	1,6
1000-1999	57	1,8
2000-2999	28	0,9
3000-3999	19	0,6
4000-4999	9	0,3
5000-5999	5	0,2
6000-6999	6	0,2
7000-7999	6	0,2
8000-8999	4	0,1
9000-9999	1	0,0
10000-10999	7	0,2
11000-11999	3	0,1
12000-12999	2	0,1
13000-13999	1	0,0
14000-14999	1	0,0
15000-15999	6	0,2
16000-16999	1	0,0
17000-17999	2	0,1
18000-18999	1	0,0
19000-19999	2	0,1
20000-29999	11	0,4
30000-39999	2	0,1
40000-49999	3	0,1
Total	3095	
999999 No answer	29	
Not employed last week	2018	
	5142	
Mean value for all		385,82
Standard deviation		2530,36
Mean value for >0		5283,67
Standard deviation		7877,26

X617

COMP. FOR INCONVENIENT WORKING HOURS

**Y470, U441,
V729, jfr
W272**

Special compensation for uncomfortable working hours not included above, in SEK per month. This variable is divided into categories.

0	89,4
1-99	0,2
100-199	0,1

200-299			0,1
300-399			0,3
400-499			0,1
500-599			0,4
600-699			0,3
700-799			0,2
800-899			0,3
900-999			0,2
1000-1999			4,3
2000-2999			2,1
3000-3999			0,8
4000-4999			0,4
5000-5999			0,3
6000-6999			0,2
7000-7999			0,1
8000-8999			0,1
9000-9999			0,0
10000-10999			0,1
12000-12999			0,0
Total		3072	
99999 No answer		52	
Not employed last week		2018	
		5142	
Mean value for all			211,21
Standard deviation			841,23
Mean value for >0			1996,41
Standard deviation			1769,93

X618

OTHER WAGE FORM SEK/MONTH

**Y471, U442,
V730, jfr
W272**

Salary in SEK per month: other wage form. This variable is divided into categories.

0		2985	96,4
1-999		19	0,6
1000-1999		16	0,5
2000-2999		13	0,4
3000-3999		12	0,4
4000-4999		5	0,2
5000-5999		4	0,1
6000-6999		4	0,1
7000-7999		4	0,1
8000-8999		4	0,1
9000-9999		1	0,0
10000-19999		24	0,8
20000-29999		2	0,1
30000-39999		2	0,1
40000-49999		1	0,0
Total		3096	
999999 No answer		28	
Not employed last week		2018	
		5142	
Mean value for all			238,148
Standard deviation			1911,280
Mean value for >0			6642,396
Standard deviation			7736,642

X619**GROSS SALARY PER HOUR**jfr Y472, jfr
U443, jfr
V727, jfr
W650Gross salary in SEK per hour, calculated by adding X611 - X618 converted into hourly wage by using X602.
This variable is divided into categories.

30-39	3	0,1
40-49	5	0,2
50-59	14	0,5
60-69	62	2,1
70-79	192	6,4
80-89	477	15,9
90-99	525	17,6
100-199	1572	52,6
200-299	108	3,6
300-399	24	0,8
400-499	5	0,2
500-599	2	0,1
800-899	1	0,0
1000-1999	1	0,0
Total	2991	
9999 No answer	133	
Not employed last week	2018	
	5142	
Mean value		116,46
Standard deviation		55,37

X620**MONTHLY SALARY AFTER TAX**Y473, U433,
V490, jfr
W276

How much is your take-home pay (after tax) from your regular job each month? This variable is divided into categories.

200-299	1	0,0
700-799	3	0,1
1000-1999	10	0,3
2000-2999	13	0,4
3000-3999	18	0,6
4000-4999	53	1,8
5000-5999	57	2,0
6000-6999	75	2,6
7000-7999	137	4,7
8000-8999	195	6,7
9000-9999	285	9,8
10000-10999	434	14,9
11000-11999	360	12,4
12000-12999	309	10,6
13000-13999	263	9,0
14000-14999	196	6,7
15000-15999	131	4,5
16000-16999	89	3,1
17000-17999	59	2,0
18000-18999	44	1,5
19000-19999	24	0,8
20000-29999	136	4,7
30000-39999	17	0,6
40000-49999	1	0,0
60000-69999	1	0,0
70000-79999	1	0,0

	150000-159999	1	0,0
	Total	2913	
	999999 No answer	211	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		11833,74
	Standard deviation		5219,81
X621	PROFIT SHARE		Y474
	Benefit: A share in company profits?		
	1 No	2794	90,1
	2 Yes, included in the wages	97	3,1
	3 Yes, not included in the wages	193	6,2
	4 Yes benefit, no info on emolument or not	17	0,5
	Total	3101	
	9 No answer	23	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X622	COMPANY CAR		Y476
	Benefit: A company car for private use?		
	1 No	2983	96,1
	2 Yes, included in the wages	22	0,7
	3 Yes, not included in the wages	87	2,8
	4 Yes benefit, no info on emolument or not	12	0,4
	Total	3104	
	9 No answer	20	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X623	FREE CELLPHONE		jfr Y477
	Benefit: Free cell phone or telephone in your home?		
	1 No	2707	87,24
	2 Yes, included in the wages	40	1,29
	3 Yes, not included in the wages	303	9,76
	4 Yes benefit, no info on emolument or not	53	1,71
	Total	3103	
	9 No answer	21	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X624	FREE CLEANING ETC		
	Benefit: Domestic services (cleaning, child-minding etc.)?		
	1 No	3090	99,6
	2 Yes, included in the wages	3	0,1
	3 Yes, not included in the wages	9	0,3
	4 Yes benefit, no info on emolument or not	1	0,0
	Total	3103	
	9 No answer	21	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	

X625	HOLIDAY HOUSE	Y478
	Benefit: Holiday house (free or for a nominal sum)?	
	1 No	2966 95,6
	2 Yes, included in the wages	4 0,1
	3 Yes, not included in the wages	123 4,0
	4 Yes benefit, no info on emolument or not	10 0,3
	Total	3103
	9 No answer	21
	Not employed last week	2018
		5142
X626	SHAREHOLDER BENEFITS	Y480
	Benefit: Shares, options, etc. at favourable rates?	
	1 No	2922 94,1
	2 Yes, included in the wages	12 0,4
	3 Yes, not included in the wages	154 5,0
	4 Yes benefit, no info on emolument or not	16 0,5
	Total	3104
	9 No answer	20
	Not employed last week	2018
		5142
X627	NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK/YEAR	
	Do you ever stay overnight away from home because of your work, e.g., on a business trip? About how many nights are you away altogether during one year's time? This variable is divided into categories.	
	0	2019 65,1
	1-9	528 17,0
	10-19	237 7,6
	20-29	97 3,1
	30-39	54 1,7
	40-49	26 0,8
	50-59	33 1,1
	60-69	12 0,4
	70-79	13 0,4
	80-89	9 0,3
	90-99	4 0,1
	100-109	15 0,5
	110-119	6 0,2
	120-129	8 0,3
	130-139	4 0,1
	140-149	1 0,0
	150-159	11 0,4
	160-169	3 0,1
	170-179	5 0,2
	180-189	6 0,2
	200-209	5 0,2
	220-229	1 0,0
	230-239	2 0,1
	240-249	2 0,1
	250-259	1 0,0
	Total	3102
	999 No answer	22

	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		7,91
	Standard deviation		24,91
	Mean value for >0		22,65
	Standard deviation		37,99
X628	PUNCTUALITY DEMANDED		Y482, U422, V470, W254
	Is punctuality demanded at your workplace?		
	1 Yes	2120	68,1
	2 No	993	31,9
	Total	3113	
	9 No answer	11	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X629	PUNCH CLOCK		Y483, U423, V471, W255
	Is there a punch clock you must use?		
	1 Yes	882	28,3
	2 No	2233	71,7
	Total	3115	
	9 No answer	9	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X630	FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS		Y484, U424
	Do you have any kind of flexible working hours, i.e. can you within certain limits decide yourself when you want to begin and end work?		
	1 Yes	1816	58,3
	2 No	1298	41,7
	Total	3114	
	9 No answer	10	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X631	CAN GO ON AN ERRAND		Y485, U427, V474, W258
	If you need to go on a private errand, can you leave your workplace for about half an hour without informing a supervisor?		
	1 Yes	1809	58,1
	2 No	1303	41,9
	Total	3112	
	9 No answer	12	
	Not employed last week	2018	
		5142	
X632	CAN BE VISITED		Y486, U428, V475, W259
	Can you receive a private visit at your workplace for say 10 minutes during regular working hours?		
	1 Yes	2658	85,4
	2 No	454	14,6
	Total	3112	
	9 No answer	12	
	Not employed last week	2018	

			5142	
X633	CAN DETERMINE PACE OF WORK			Y487, U429
	Can you yourself determine your pace of work?			
	1 Yes	2077	66,8	
	2 No	1033	33,2	
	Total	3110		
	9 No answer	14		
	Not employed last week	2018		
		5142		
X634	INFLUENCE WHAT TASKS			Y489
	To what extent do you have influence over what tasks you carry out?			
	1 To a very large extent	700	22,6	
	2 To a large extent	826	26,6	
	3 To a certain extent	934	30,1	
	4 To a small extent	412	13,3	
	5 Not at all	232	7,5	
	Total	3104		
	9 No answer	20		
	Not employed last week	2018		
		5142		
X635	INFLUENCE WORKING METHODS			Y490
	To what extent do you have influence over how you carry out your tasks?			
	1 To a very large extent	1114	35,9	
	2 To a large extent	1066	34,4	
	3 To a certain extent	592	19,1	
	4 To a small extent	201	6,5	
	5 Not at all	128	4,1	
	Total	3101		
	9 No answer	23		
	Not employed last week	2018		
		5142		
X636	LEARN NEW THINGS			Y491
	To what extent does your work mean that you learn new things?			
	1 To a very large extent	563	18,1	
	2 To a large extent	898	28,9	
	3 To a certain extent	1082	34,9	
	4 To a small extent	392	12,6	
	5 Not at all	168	5,4	
	Total	3103		
	9 No answer	21		
	Not employed last week	2018		
		5142		
X637	MUST BE CREATIVE			Y492
	To what extent does your work mean that you have to be creative (innovative, inventive)?			
	1 To a very large extent	883	28,5	
	2 To a large extent	1057	34,1	
	3 To a certain extent	775	25,0	

	4	To a small extent	253	8,2
	5	Not at all	131	4,2
		Total	3099	
	9	No answer	25	
		Not employed last week	2018	
			5142	
X638	GETS SUPPORT FROM WORKMATES			Y494
	To what extent does your work mean that you can get support and help from workmates when needed?			
	1	To a very large extent	895	28,9
	2	To a large extent	1208	39,0
	3	To a certain extent	716	23,1
	4	To a small extent	190	6,1
	5	Not at all	92	3,0
		Total	3101	
	9	No answer	23	
		Not employed last week	2018	
			5142	
X639	DIRECT SUPERVISION			Y495
	To what extent does your work mean that your closest superiors keep an eye on you while you're carrying out your tasks?			
	1	To a very large extent	92	3,0
	2	To a large extent	182	5,9
	3	To a certain extent	527	17,0
	4	To a small extent	975	31,5
	5	Not at all	1321	42,7
		Total	3097	
	9	No answer	27	
		Not employed last week	2018	
			5142	
X640	MUST FOLLOW RULES			Y497
	To what extent does your work mean that you must follow clearly stated rules or routines when you carry out your tasks?			
	1	To a very large extent	649	20,9
	2	To a large extent	779	25,1
	3	To a certain extent	894	28,8
	4	To a small extent	423	13,6
	5	Not at all	355	11,5
		Total	3100	
	9	No answer	24	
		Not employed last week	2018	
			5142	
X641	GROUP RESPONSIBILITY			Y498
	To what extent does your work mean that you work in a group with collective responsibility for the results?			
	1	To a very large extent	750	24,2
	2	To a large extent	936	30,2
	3	To a certain extent	616	19,9
	4	To a small extent	307	9,9
	5	Not at all	489	15,8
		Total	3098	

	9	No answer		26	
		Not employed last week		2018	
				5142	
X642		PACE OF WORK DETERMINED BY MACHINES			Y499
		To what extent does your work mean that your pace of work is determined by machines or other equipment?			
	1	To a very large extent		208	6,7
	2	To a large extent		243	7,8
	3	To a certain extent		330	10,7
	4	To a small extent		342	11,0
	5	Not at all		1975	63,8
		Total		3098	
	9	No answer		26	
		Not employed last week		2018	
				5142	
X643		PACE OF WORK DETERMINED BY FELLOW WORKERS			Y500
		To what extent does your work mean that your pace of work is determined by that of your fellow workers?			
	1	To a very large extent		172	5,6
	2	To a large extent		419	13,5
	3	To a certain extent		992	32,0
	4	To a small extent		550	17,7
	5	Not at all		966	31,2
		Total		3099	
	9	No answer		25	
		Not employed last week		2018	
				5142	
X644		PACE OF WORK DETERMINED BY CUSTOMERS			Y501
		To what extent does your work mean that your pace of work must be adapted to external persons (e.g. customers, passengers, patients, pupils or the like)?			
	1	To a very large extent		1028	33,2
	2	To a large extent		828	26,7
	3	To a certain extent		656	21,2
	4	To a small extent		214	6,9
	5	Not at all		374	12,1
		Total		3100	
	9	No answer		24	
		Not employed last week		2018	
				5142	
X645		BOSS' NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES			
		How many persons are placed directly under your immediate supervisor/boss?			
	1	Have no boss		63	2,0
	2	1-3 persons		351	11,3
	3	4-9 persons		688	22,1
	4	10-19 persons		677	21,7
	5	20-49 persons		815	26,2
	6	50-99 persons		253	8,1
	7	100 or more persons		174	5,6
	8	Do not know how many are directly under boss		89	2,9
	9	Do not know who boss is		6	0,2
		Total		3116	

	99	No answer		8	
		Not employed last week		2018	
				5142	
X646		SEX OF BOSS			
		Is your immediate supervisor/boss a man or a woman?			
	1	Man	2057	67,5	
	2	Woman	976	32,0	
	3	Two supervisors, a man and a woman	14	0,5	
		Total	3047		
	9	No answer	8		
		Not employed last week/Have no boss	2087		
				5142	
X647		BOSS BORN IN ANOTHER COUNTRY			
		Was your immediate supervisor/boss born in Sweden or another country?			
	1	Born in Sweden	2802	92,0	
	2	Born in another country	202	6,6	
	3	Two supervisors, one man one woman, one born in another country	4	0,1	
	8	Doesn't know	39	1,3	
		Total	3047		
	9	No answer	8		
		Not employed last week/Have no boss	2087		
				5142	
X648		DIFFICULT TO REPLACE RESPONDENT			
		In your opinion, how difficult would it be for your employer to replace you if you quit?			
	1	Very difficult	415	13,4	
	2	Fairly difficult	1236	39,9	
	3	Not particularly difficult	955	30,8	
	4	Fairly easy	323	10,4	
	5	Very easy	168	5,4	
		Total	3097		
	9	No answer	27		
		Not employed last week	2018		
				5142	
X649		DIFFICULT TO GET NEW JOB			
		If you for some reason had to leave your present employer, how difficult do you think it would be for you to find a new job as good as your current one?			
	1	Very difficult	472	15,2	
	2	Fairly difficult	904	29,1	
	3	Not particularly difficult	721	23,2	
	4	Fairly easy	674	21,7	
	5	Very easy	331	10,7	
		Total	3102		
	9	No answer	22		
		Not employed last week	2018		
				5142	
X651		TRAVEL TIME MINUTES PER DAY			
		Number of minutes of total travel time to and from work during last week. This variable is divided into			
					jfr Y441, jfr U387, jfr V765, jfr W244,

categories. The table is valid for gainfully employed last week.

W636

1	No commute/live at workplace	171	5,1
2-9		139	4,2
10-19		541	16,2
20-29		578	17,3
30-39		521	15,6
40-49		398	11,9
50-59		128	3,8
60-69		371	11,1
70-79		64	1,9
80-89		78	2,3
90-99		129	3,9
100-109		28	0,8
110-119		12	0,4
120-129		113	3,4
130-139		8	0,2
140-149		8	0,2
150-159		16	0,5
160-169		4	0,1
170-179		1	0,0
180-189		32	1,0
190-199		1	0,0
200-209		1	0,0
220-229		1	0,0
230-239		1	0,0
240-249		4	0,1
480-489		1	0,0
	Total	3349	
997	Have no permanent workplace	184	
999	No answer	13	
	Not gainfully employed	1596	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		39,73
	Standard deviation		35,53
	Mean value for >1		41,81
	Standard deviation		35,28

X652

WORKLOAD

How great is your workload on a normal workday? Do you usually have ...

1	Much too much to do	580	16,5
2	A bit too much to do	1273	36,1
3	About the right amount to do	1607	45,6
4	A bit too little to do	49	1,4
5	Much too little to do	14	0,4
	Total	3523	
9	No answer	23	
	Not gainfully employed	1596	
		5142	

X653

HEAVY LIFTING

Do you have to be able to lift 60 kilos in order to manage your job? If yes: Do you need such physical strength daily in your work, a few times per week or less often?

**Y507, U447,
V492, jfr
W277**

11	Less often	197	5,6
----	------------	-----	-----

	12	A few times per week	277	7,8
	13	Daily	310	8,8
	20	No	2750	77,8
		Total	3534	
	9	No answer	12	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X654		PHYSICALLY DEMANDING		Y508, U448, V493, W278
		Is your type of work physically demanding in any other way?		
	1	Yes	1591	45
	2	No	1944	55
		Total	3535	
	9	No answer	11	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X655		DAILY SWEATING		Y509, U449, V494, W279
		Does your work make you sweaty from physical exertion every day?		
	1	Yes	845	23,9
	2	No	2687	76,1
		Total	3532	
	9	No answer	14	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X656		MENTALLY TAXING		Y510, U451, V496, W281
		Is your work mentally taxing?		
	1	Yes	1786	50,5
	2	No	1748	49,5
		Total	3534	
	9	No answer	12	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X657		STRESSFUL WORK		Y511, U452, V497, W282
		Is your work stressful?		
	1	Yes	2494	70,6
	2	No	1040	29,4
		Total	3534	
	9	No answer	12	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X658		MONOTONOUS WORK		Y512, U453, V498, W283
		Is your work monotonous?		
	1	Yes	643	18,2
	2	No	2890	81,8
		Total	3533	
	9	No answer	13	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	

X659	PSYCHOLOGICAL PRESSURE	Y513
<p>Index for psychological pressure was created by combining information about DEMAND and DISCRETION at work. If X656=1 (mentally taxing work) and X657=1 (stressful work) DEMAND is coded 1. For other combinations DEMAND is coded 0. If X633=1 (can determine pace of work) and X658=2 (not monotonous work) DISCRETION is coded 1. For other combinations DISCRETION is coded 0.</p>		
	1 Discretion and not demand	1057 34,0
	2 Other	1375 44,3
	3 Not discretion but demand	674 21,7
	Total	3106
	9 No answer	18
	Not employed last week	2018
		5142
X660	PSYCHOLOGICAL ACTIVITY	Y514
<p>Index for psychological activity was created by combining information about DEMAND and DISCRETION at work (see X659).</p>		
	1 Not discretion and not demand	705 22,7
	2 Other	1731 55,7
	3 Both discretion and demand	670 21,6
	Total	3106
	9 No answer	18
	Not employed last week	2018
		5142
X661	PHYSICALLY EXHAUSTED	jfr U450, jfr V495, jfr W280
<p>Are you physically exhausted after work?</p>		
	1 Yes, always	85 2,4
	2 Yes, most of the time	291 8,2
	3 Yes, sometimes	994 28,1
	4 No, seldom	937 26,5
	5 No, never	1226 34,7
	Total	3533
	9 No answer	13
	Not gainfully employed	1596
		5142
X662	MENTALLY EXHAUSTED	jfr U454, jfr V499, jfr W284
<p>Are you mentally exhausted after work?</p>		
	1 Yes, always	68 1,9
	2 Yes, most of the time	356 10,1
	3 Yes, sometimes	1374 38,9
	4 No, seldom	839 23,7
	5 No, never	897 25,4
	Total	3534
	9 No answer	12
	Not gainfully employed	1596
		5142
X663	NOISE	Y515, U456, V501, W286
<p>Is it noisy where you work? If yes: Is it noisy all the time or just sometimes? Is the noise deafening?</p>		
	111 Sometimes deafening	315 8,9
	112 Sometimes, not deafening	389 11,0

	121	Always deafening	281	8,0
	122	Always, not deafening	282	8,0
	200	No	2264	64,1
		Total	3531	
	999	No answer	15	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X664	MONOTONOUS MOVEMENTS			Y517, U465, V511
	Do you in your work have to perform many repetitive and monotonous movements?			
	1	Yes	1615	45,7
	2	No	1919	54,3
		Total	3534	
	9	No answer	12	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X665	UNSUITABLE WORK POSITIONS			Y518, U466, V512
	Does your work force you to take bent, twisted or in other ways unsuitable work positions?			
	1	Yes	1486	42,1
	2	No	2045	57,9
		Total	3531	
	9	No answer	15	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X666	GAS, DUST, SMOKE			Y519, U468, V514, jfr W290
	Are you in your work exposed to gas, dust or smoke? If yes: Is this so all the time, often or only sometimes?			
	11	All the time	306	8,7
	12	Often	276	7,8
	13	Sometimes	442	12,5
	20	No	2507	71,0
		Total	3531	
	99	No answer	15	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X667	DIRTY WORK			jfr U455, jfr V500, jfr W285
	Do you get dirty in your work? If yes: Do you get just a little dirty or very dirty?			
	11	A little dirty	1054	29,8
	12	Very dirty	291	8,2
	20	No	2187	61,9
		Total	3532	
	99	No answer	14	
		Not gainfully employed	1596	
			5142	
X668	TOXIC SUBSTANCES, ACIDS, EXPLOSIVES			Y521, U470, V516, jfr W291
	Do you come into contact with toxic substances, corroding acids or explosives? If yes: Does this happen all the time, often or only sometimes?			
	11	All the time	116	3,3
	12	Often	146	4,1

13	Sometimes	433	12,3
20	No	2838	80,3
	Total	3533	
99	No answer	13	
	Not gainfully employed	1596	
		5142	

X669

ABSENCE DUE TO ILLNESS

During the last 12 months, about how many days have you been absent from work due to own illness? This variable is divided into categories.

0		1623	46,2
1-9		1253	35,6
10-19		288	8,2
20-29		82	2,3
30-39		64	1,8
40-49		31	0,9
50-59		7	0,2
60-69		33	0,9
70-79		13	0,4
80-89		7	0,2
90-99		15	0,4
100-199		48	1,4
200-299		13	0,4
300-365		39	1,1
	Total	3516	
999	No answer	30	
	Not gainfully employed	1596	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		12,04
	Standard deviation		44,28
	Mean value for >0		22,36
	Standard deviation		58,41

X670

SATISFACTION WITH JOB

Y522

So now we've asked a lot of questions about your working conditions. On the whole, how satisfied are you with your current job?

1	Very satisfied	1176	33,3
2	Rather satisfied	1738	49,2
3	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	400	11,3
4	Rather dissatisfied	162	4,6
5	Very dissatisfied	53	1,5
	Total	3529	
9	No answer	17	
	Not gainfully employed	1596	
		5142	

X671

SATISFACTION WITH WAGES

Y523

How satisfied are you with your current wages (income from work)?

1	Very satisfied	318	9,0
2	Rather satisfied	1330	37,8
3	Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	769	21,8
4	Rather dissatisfied	739	21,0
5	Very dissatisfied	365	10,4

	Total	3521	
9	No answer	25	
	Not gainfully employed	1596	
		5142	
X672	ARABLE LAND		Y524, U482, V526, W300
	How large is the farm (hectares arable land)? This variable is divided into categories. The table is valid for farmers last week.		
	0	5	6,0
	2	2	2,4
	3	1	1,2
	4	1	1,2
	5	8	9,5
	6	3	3,6
	7	2	2,4
	8	1	1,2
	9	1	1,2
	10-19	14	16,7
	20-29	13	15,5
	30-39	5	6,0
	40-49	5	6,0
	50-59	4	4,8
	60-69	3	3,6
	70-79	3	3,6
	80-89	4	4,8
	100-109	3	3,6
	110-119	1	1,2
	120-129	1	1,2
	130-139	1	1,2
	170-179	1	1,2
	220-229	1	1,2
	270-279	1	1,2
	Total	84	
999	No answer	7	
	Not farmer	5051	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		38,46
	Standard deviation		48,36
	Mean value for >0		40,90
	Standard deviation		48,87
X673	WOODLAND		Y525, U483, V527, W301
	How large is the farm (hectares of woodland)? This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	8	9,6
	2	1	1,2
	3	1	1,2
	5	4	4,8
	6	1	1,2
	7	1	1,2
	9	1	1,2
	10-19	14	16,9
	20-29	8	9,6
	30-39	7	8,4
	40-49	10	12,0

50-59		5	6,0
60-69		6	7,2
70-79		1	1,2
80-89		2	2,4
90-99		1	1,2
100-109		2	2,4
110-119		1	1,2
120-129		2	2,4
150-159		2	2,4
200-209		1	1,2
290-299		1	1,2
350-359		1	1,2
370-379		1	1,2
997	Over 1000 hectares of woodland	1	1,2
	Total	83	
999	No answer	8	
	Not farmer	5051	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		61,37
	Standard deviation		125,00
	Mean value for >0		67,92
	Standard deviation		129,86

X674

PERMANENT EMPLOYEES ON FARM

**Y526, jfr
U484**

Are there any permanent employees on the farm? (Assisting family members should not be counted).

1		6	7,1
88	No employees	78	92,9
	Total	84	
99	No answer	7	
	Not farmer	5051	
		5142	

X675

HOURS DURING BUSIEST PERIOD

**Y528, U487,
V530, W308**

How many working hours per week is usual on the farm during the busiest period? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9		8	9,5
10-19		14	16,7
20-29		11	13,1
30-39		5	6,0
40-49		8	9,5
50-59		7	8,3
60-69		9	10,7
70-79		5	6,0
80-89		5	6,0
90-99		3	3,6
100-109		5	6,0
110-119		4	4,8
	Total	84	
999	No answer	7	
	Not farmer	5051	
		5142	
	Mean value		45,49
	Standard deviation		32,60

X676

HOURS DURING QUIETEST PERIODY529, U488,
V531, W309

How many working hours per week is usual on the farm during the least busy period? This variable is divided into categories.

0	18	21,4
1-9	20	23,8
10-19	13	15,5
20-29	6	7,1
30-39	9	10,7
40-49	11	13,1
50-59	3	3,6
70-79	3	3,6
90-98	1	1,2
Total	84	
99 No answer	7	
Not farmer	5051	
	5142	
Mean value		18,73
Standard deviation		20,98
Mean value for >0		23,83
Standard deviation		20,94

X677

NUMBER OF BUSY WEEKSY530, U489,
V532, W310

How many weeks per year are very busy on the farm?

0	5	6,2
1	3	3,7
2	7	8,6
3	4	4,9
4	13	16,0
5	6	7,4
6	6	7,4
7	4	4,9
8	10	12,3
10	4	4,9
12	3	3,7
15	2	2,5
16	1	1,2
20	4	4,9
24	2	2,5
26	1	1,2
30	1	1,2
35	1	1,2
39	1	1,2
51	1	1,2
52	2	2,5
Total	81	
99 No answer	10	
Not farmer	5051	
	5142	
Mean value for all		9,75
Standard deviation		11,40
Mean value for >0		10,39
Standard deviation		11,48

X678	VACATION POSSIBILITY	Y531, U490, V533, W311
	Can you take vacation from the farm any part of the year?	
	1 Yes	77 91,7
	2 No	7 8,3
	Total	84
	9 No answer	7
	Not farmer	5051
		5142
X679	VACATION 1999	Y532, U491, V534, jfr W312
	Did you take any vacation from the farm in 1999?	
	1 Yes	63 75
	2 No	21 25
	Total	84
	9 No answer	7
	Not farmer	5051
		5142
X680	VACATION WEEKS 1999	Y533, U492, V535, jfr W312
	How many weeks of vacation did you take from the farm in 1999?	
	0	6 10
	1	25 41,7
	2	13 21,7
	3	4 6,7
	4	5 8,3
	5	2 3,3
	6	2 3,3
	10	2 3,3
	45	1 1,7
	Total	60
	99 No answer	10
	Not farmer/Farmer no vacation	5072
		5142
	Mean value for all	2,83
	Standard deviation	5,91
	Mean value for >0	3,15
	Standard deviation	6,15
X681	SNI (INDUSTRY) SELF EMPLOYED	Y534, jfr U494, jfr V537, jfr W314
	To what industry does your company belong or what does it produce? Coded according to Swedish Standard Industrial Classification (<i>Svensk näringsgrensindelning, SNI</i>). A list of codes is published by Statistics Sweden in <i>SCB, Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor 1992:5, SE-SIC92, Swedish Standard Industrial Classification 1992</i>	
X684	NUMBER OF EMPLOYEES IN FIRM	Y537, U499, V538, jfr W315
	How many employees are there in the firm? (Assisting family members should not be counted as employee). This variable is divided into categories. The table is valid for self-employed last week.	
	1	34 18,1
	2	26 13,8
	3	25 13,3
	4	22 11,7
	5	11 5,9
	6	6 3,2

7		7	3,7
8		5	2,7
9		5	2,7
10-19		18	9,6
20-29		10	5,3
30-39		1	0,5
40-49		3	1,6
60-69		3	1,6
70-79		1	0,5
80-89		1	0,5
90-99		7	3,7
110-119		2	1,1
990-997		1	0,5
Total		188	
888	No employees	220	
	Not self-employed	4734	
		5142	
	Mean value		14,48
	Standard deviation		32,95

X685

AVERAGE WORKING HOURS

**Y542, U501,
V540, W317**

How many hours do you normally work in the firm per week seen on average over a whole year? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9		48	12,0
10-19		23	5,8
20-29		33	8,3
30-39		36	9,0
40-49		100	25,0
50-59		84	21,0
60-69		58	14,5
70-79		14	3,5
80-89		1	0,3
90-98		3	0,8
Total		400	
99	No answer	8	
	Not self-employed	4734	
		5142	
	Mean value		39,30
	Standard deviation		19,85

X686

HOURS BUSY WEEKS

How many hours per week do you usually work in the company during busy weeks? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9		31	7,9
10-19		15	3,8
20-29		26	6,6
30-39		18	4,6
40-49		45	11,5
50-59		73	18,6
60-69		80	20,4
70-79		60	15,3
80-89		28	7,1
90-99		5	1,3
100-109		8	2,0

110-119		1	0,3
120-129		2	0,5
140-149		1	0,3
	Total	393	
999	No answer	15	
	Not self-employed	4734	
		5142	
	Mean value		51,30
	Standard deviation		24,16

X687

HOURS QUIET WEEKS

How many hours per week do you usually work in the company during quiet weeks? This variable is divided into categories.

0		23	5,8
1-9		45	11,4
10-19		18	4,6
20-29		53	13,5
30-39		72	18,3
40-49		104	26,4
50-59		45	11,4
60-69		25	6,3
70-79		6	1,5
80-89		1	0,3
90-98		2	0,5
	Total	394	
99	No answer	14	
	Not self-employed	4734	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		31,94
	Standard deviation		18,91
	Mean value for >0		33,92
	Standard deviation		17,68

X688

NUMBER OF BUSY WEEKS

About how many busy weeks do you have during a one-year period?

0		53	14,1
1		5	1,3
2		5	1,3
3		10	2,7
4		27	7,2
5		19	5,1
6		14	3,7
7		8	2,1
8		19	5,1
9		2	0,5
10		40	10,6
12		25	6,6
13		1	0,3
14		3	0,8
15		9	2,4
16		15	4,0
17		4	1,1
20		32	8,5
23		2	0,5

24		6	1,6
25		9	2,4
26		12	3,2
28		1	0,3
29		1	0,3
30		9	2,4
32		1	0,3
35		4	1,1
36		1	0,3
38		1	0,3
39		1	0,3
40		12	3,2
42		1	0,3
44		1	0,3
45		2	0,5
46		1	0,3
48		3	0,8
50		4	1,1
51		1	0,3
52		12	3,2
	Total	376	
99	No answer	32	
	Not self-employed	4734	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		14,51
	Standard deviation		13,81
	Mean value for >0		16,89
	Standard deviation		13,48
X689	VACATION 1999		Y543, U503, V542, jfr W319
	Did you take any vacation from the firm in 1999?		
1	Yes	295	74,3
2	No	102	25,7
	Total	397	
9	No answer	11	
	Not self-employed	4734	
		5142	
X690	VACATION WEEKS 1999		Y544, U504, V543, jfr W319
	How many weeks of vacation did you take from your firm in 1999?		
0		3	1,0
1		38	12,9
2		64	21,9
3		56	19,1
4		48	16,4
5		35	11,9
6		24	8,2
7		9	3,1
8		8	2,7
12		4	1,3
13		1	0,34
14		1	0,3
16		2	0,7

	Total	293	
99	No answer	13	
	Not self-employed/Self-employed no vacation	4836	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		3,68
	Standard deviation		2,44
	Mean value for >0		3,72
	Standard deviation		2,42
X691	SEI FREELANCE OCCUPATION		Y545, jfr U508
	What is your occupation/side-line? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system (SEI).		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	3	2,1
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	60	41,1
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	3	2,1
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	8	5,5
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	9	6,2
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	14	9,6
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	26	17,8
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	11	7,5
	57 Professional, upper-level executive	4	2,7
	60 Self-employed professional	8	5,5
	Total	146	
	99 Unclassified	11	
	Not freelance occupation/Not employed last week	4985	
		5142	
X692	NYK80 FREELANCE OCCUPATION		Y546, jfr U509
	What is your occupation/side-line? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for freelance occupation. See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.		
X693	NYK85 FREELANCE OCCUPATION		
	What is your occupation/side-line? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for freelance occupation. A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.		
X694	AVERAGE WORKING HOURS		Y548, U511, V547, jfr W323
	How many hours a week do you work with your occupation/side-line on average, seen over a year? This variable is divided into categories.		
	1	7	4,9
	2	11	7,7
	3	11	7,7
	4	12	8,5
	5	16	11,3
	6	9	6,3
	7	7	4,9
	8	11	7,7
	10-19	42	29,6
	20-29	9	6,3
	30-39	2	1,4
	40-49	4	2,8
	80-89	1	0,7
	Total	142	

	999	No answer	15	
		Not freelance occupation/Not employed last week	4985	
			5142	
		Mean value		9,95
		Standard deviation		10,45
X695	SEI UNEMPLOYED			Y549, jfr U516
	What is your occupation, i.e. what job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system (SEI).			
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	39	13,2
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	70	23,6
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	54	18,2
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	28	9,5
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	13	4,4
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	2	0,7
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	17	5,7
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	3	1,0
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	42	14,2
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	25	8,4
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	1	0,3
	89	Farmer, area unknown	2	0,7
		Total	296	
	99	Unclassified	26	
		Not unemployed/Not employed last week	4820	
			5142	
X696	NYK80 UNEMPLOYED			Y550, jfr U517
	What is your occupation, i.e. what job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Coded according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK") for unemployed. See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.			
X697	NYK85 UNEMPLOYED			
	What is your occupation, i.e. what job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.			
X698	WEEKS UNEMPLOYED			Y551, U525, V559, jfr W345
	How long have you now been looking/waiting for work/been unemployed/laid off? This variable is divided into categories.			
	1-9		69	23,0
	10-19		55	18,3
	20-29		28	9,3
	30-39		16	5,3
	40-49		17	5,7
	50-59		10	3,3
	60-69		5	1,7
	70-79		7	2,3
	80-89		3	1,0
	90-99		3	1,0
	100-109		13	4,3
	110-119		3	1,0
	120-129		1	0,3

130-139	3	1,0
140-149	3	1,0
150-159	9	3,0
160-169	2	0,7
170-179	1	0,3
180-189	2	0,7
190-199	1	0,3
200-299	23	7,7
300-399	15	5,0
400-499	5	1,7
500-599	4	1,3
700-799	1	0,3
800-899	1	0,3
Total	300	
999 No answer	22	
Not unemployed/Not employed last week	4820	
	5142	
Mean value		88,15
Standard deviation		130,47

X700

SEI PENSIONERS

**Y553, jfr
U555**

What was your main profession or occupation during your working life? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system (SEI).

11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	88	9,48
12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	200	21,55
21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	116	12,50
22	Skilled manual worker, service production	51	5,50
33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	73	7,87
35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	13	1,40
36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	77	8,30
45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	15	1,62
46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	160	17,24
56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	52	5,60
57	Professional, upper-level executive**	20	2,16
60	Self-employed professional	17	1,83
79	Self employed, unknown number of employees	16	1,72
89	Farmer, area unknown	30	3,23
Total		928	
99	Unclassified	42	
Not pensioner		4172	
		5142	

X701

NYK80 PENSIONERS

Y554

What was your main profession or occupation during your working life? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.

X702

NYK85 PENSIONERS

What was your main profession or occupation during your working life? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.

X703**FORMER FARMER – ARABLE LAND****Y555, U556**

Retired farmer: How many hectares of arable land did you have? This variable is divided into categories.

0	1	2,5
1-9	7	17,5
10-19	13	32,5
20-29	4	10
30-39	3	7,5
40-49	5	12,5
50-59	3	7,5
60-69	1	2,5
80-89	1	2,5
90-99	1	2,5
250-259	1	2,5
Total	40	
999 No answer	4	
Not former farmer	5098	
	5142	
Mean value for all		31,45
Standard deviation		41,15
Mean value for >0		32,26
Standard deviation		41,36

X704**FORMER FARMER – WOODLAND****Y556, U557**

Retired farmer: How many hectares of woodland did you have? This variable is divided into categories.

0	3	8,1
1-9	4	10,8
10-19	6	16,2
20-29	1	2,7
30-39	1	2,7
40-49	3	8,1
50-59	4	10,8
60-69	2	5,4
70-79	1	2,7
80-89	1	2,7
90-99	2	5,4
100-109	2	5,4
110-119	1	2,7
120-129	2	5,4
170-179	1	2,7
290-299	1	2,7
390-399	1	2,7
500-509	1	2,7
Total	37	
999 No answer	7	
Not former farmer	5098	
	5142	
Mean value for all		77,62
Standard deviation		107,16
Mean value for >0		84,47
Standard deviation		109,23

X705**FORMERLY SELF-EMPLOYED – EMPLOYEES****Y557, U558**

Formerly self-employed: How many employees did you have?

0	24	36,4
1	4	6,1
2	8	12,1
3	3	4,5
4	6	9,1
5	2	3,0
6	1	1,5
9	2	3,0
10	3	4,5
11	2	3,0
12	2	3,0
13	1	1,5
19	2	3,0
20	3	4,5
30	1	1,5
50	1	1,5
70	1	1,5
Total	66	
999 No answer	15	
Not formerly self-employed	5061	
	5142	
Mean value for all		6,42
Standard deviation		11,70
Mean value for >0		10,10
Standard deviation		13,39

X706

WANTS TO WORK

**Y558, U559,
V586, W363**

Would you like to have a job now if you could find something suitable? The table is valid for pensioners not working last week.

1 Yes	89	11,3
2 No	696	88,7
Total	785	
9 No answer	65	
Not pensioner/Respondent pensioner but works	4292	
	5142	

X707

WANTED WORKING HOURS PER WEEK

**Y559, jfr
U560-U562**

How many hours per week would you like to work?

0	1	1,15
2	2	2,30
4	3	3,45
8	3	3,45
10	11	12,64
15	8	9,20
16	3	3,45
20	39	44,83
24	1	1,15
25	3	3,45
30	3	3,45
32	1	1,15
40	9	10,34
Total	87	

	99	No answer	67	
		Not pensioner/Does not want to work	4988	
			5142	
		Mean value for all		19,30
		Standard deviation		9,46
		Mean value for >0		19,52
		Standard deviation		9,27
X708		DOES NOT MANAGE TO WORK		Y560, U563, V591
		Is that because you feel could not manage work right now?		
	1	Question not asked	98	14,2
	2	Yes, feel unable to work at present	314	45,6
	3	No	276	40,1
		Total	688	
	9	No answer	18	
		Not pensioner/Does not want to work	4436	
			5142	
X709		NOT PROFITABLE		Y562, U565, V593
		Financially speaking, do you think it doesn't pay to be gainfully employed?		
	1	Yes	79	31,3
	2	No	173	68,7
		Total	252	
	9	No answer	42	
		Not pensioner/Doesn't want to work	4848	
			5142	
X710		SEI OTHER		Y565
		What is your occupation, i.e. what type of job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system (SEI). The table is valid for neither gainfully employed, unemployed nor pensioned.		
	11	Unskilled manual worker, goods production	46	8,2
	12	Unskilled manual worker, service production	115	20,6
	21	Skilled manual worker, goods production	44	7,9
	22	Skilled manual worker, service production	74	13,3
	33	Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	35	6,3
	35	Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	6	1,1
	36	Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	50	9,0
	45	Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	7	1,3
	46	Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	118	21,1
	56	Professional, higher non-manual worker	24	4,3
	57	Professional, upper-level executive	2	0,4
	60	Self-employed professional	33	5,9
	89	Farmer, area unknown	4	0,7
		Total	558	
	99	Unclassified	205	
		Not applicable	4379	
			5142	
X711		NYK80 OTHER		Y566
		What is your occupation, i.e. what type of job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.		

X712**NYK85 OTHER**

What is your occupation, i.e. what type of job do you consider to be your occupation based on your education and/or job experience? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.

X713**HOURS – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES****Y567, jfr
U542, jfr
V576**

Approximate number of hours per week that are spent on buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in respondent's household. This variable is divided into categories.

0	10	0,2
1-5	813	16,3
6-10	1814	36,4
11-15	1323	26,6
16-20	548	11,0
21-25	293	5,9
26-30	115	2,3
31-35	35	0,7
36-40	13	0,3
41-45	4	0,1
46-50	5	0,1
56-60	5	0,1
66-70	1	0,0
Total	4979	
99 No answer	163	
	5142	
Mean value for all		11,85
Standard deviation		6,89
Mean value for >0		11,87
Standard deviation		6,87

X714**HOURS RESPONDENT – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES****Y568, jfr
U543, jfr
V577**

Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent spends on buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes. This variable is divided into categories.

0	200	5,0
1-5	1893	47,4
6-10	1222	30,6
11-15	408	10,2
16-20	149	3,7
21-25	71	1,8
26-30	28	0,7
31-35	10	0,3
36-40	5	0,1
46-50	2	0,1
56-60	1	0,0
66-70	1	0,0
Total	3990	
99 No answer	103	
Lives alone	1049	
	5142	
Mean value for all		6,82
Standard deviation		5,85
Mean value for >0		7,18
Standard deviation		5,78

X715**HOURS – CARE OF CLOTHING****Y569, jfr
U536, U538,
jfr V570,
V572**

Approximate number of hours per week that are spent on care of clothing (laundry, ironing, etc.) in respondent's household. This variable is divided into categories.

0	45	0,9
1-5	3736	75,7
6-10	984	19,9
11-15	130	2,6
16-20	26	0,5
21-25	6	0,1
26-30	7	0,1
31-35	2	0,0
Total	4936	
99 No answer	206	
	5142	
Mean value for all		4,39
Standard deviation		3,26
Mean value for >0		4,43
Standard deviation		3,24

X716**HOURS RESPONDENT – CARE OF CLOTHING****Y570, jfr
U537, U539,
jfr
V571, V573**

Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent spends on care of clothing (laundry, ironing, etc.). This variable is divided into categories.

0	1082	27,1
1-5	2566	64,3
6-10	301	7,5
11-15	33	0,8
16-20	5	0,1
21-25	4	0,1
26-30	2	0,1
Total	3993	
99 No answer	100	
Lives alone	1049	
	5142	
Mean value for all		2,34
Standard deviation		2,66
Mean value for >0		3,21
Standard deviation		2,63

X717**HOURS – CLEANING****Y571, jfr
U540, jfr
V574**

Approximate number of hours per week that are spent on cleaning in respondent's household. This variable is divided into categories.

0	24	0,5
1-5	3977	79,8
6-10	835	16,8
11-15	111	2,2
16-20	18	0,4
21-25	8	0,2
26-30	5	0,1
31-35	2	0,0
36-40	1	0,0
66-70	1	0,0
71-75	1	0,0
Total	4983	

	99	No answer	159	
			5142	
		Mean value for all		3,99
		Standard deviation		3,45
		Mean value for >0		4,01
		Standard deviation		3,45
X718	HOURS RESPONDENT - CLEANING			Y572, jfr U541, jfr V575
	Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent spends on cleaning. This variable is divided into categories.			
	0		552	13,8
	1-5		3119	78,1
	6-10		282	7,1
	11-15		33	0,8
	16-20		5	0,1
	21-25		3	0,1
	26-30		1	0,0
	66-70		1	0,0
	Total		3996	
	99	No answer	97	
		Lives alone	1049	
			5142	
		Mean value for all		2,33
		Standard deviation		2,64
		Mean value for >0		2,70
		Standard deviation		2,66
X719	HOURS – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE			
	Approximate number of hours per week that are spent on repair and maintenance (of residence, motor vehicle and other property) in respondent's household. This variable is divided into categories.			
	0		1576	31,6
	1-5		2806	56,3
	6-10		378	7,6
	11-15		105	2,1
	16-20		71	1,4
	21-25		19	0,4
	26-30		14	0,3
	31-35		2	0,0
	36-40		6	0,1
	41-45		4	0,1
	46-50		1	0,0
	66-70		1	0,0
	Total		4983	
	99	No answer	159	
			5142	
		Mean value for all		2,68
		Standard deviation		4,65
		Mean value for >0		3,91
		Standard deviation		5,18
X720	HOURS RESPONDENT – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE			
	Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent spends on repair and maintenance (of residence, motor vehicle and other property). This variable is divided into categories.			
	0		1827	46,1

1-5	1812	45,7
6-10	211	5,3
11-15	56	1,4
16-20	37	0,9
21-25	8	0,2
26-30	9	0,2
31-35	4	0,1
36-40	1	0,0
41-45	1	0,0
Total	3966	
99 No answer	127	
Lives alone	1049	
	5142	
Mean value for all		1,87
Standard deviation		3,76
Mean value for >0		3,47
Standard deviation		4,55

X721

HOURS – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE

Approximate number of hours per week that the respondent helps a family member or relative outside the household with personal care or housework. This variable is divided into categories.

0	49	4,4
1-5	955	86,1
6-10	76	6,9
11-15	13	1,2
16-20	10	0,9
21-25	2	0,2
26-30	4	0,4
Total	1109	
99 No answer	37	
Does not help anyone else	3996	
	5142	
Mean value for all		2,51
Standard deviation		3,43
Mean value for >0		2,62
Standard deviation		3,46

X722

HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OWN CHILDREN

Approximate number of hours per week that respondent's own children (not living in household) do housework in the respondent's home.

0	175	87,1
1	12	6,0
2	8	4,0
3	2	1,0
4	2	1,0
5	2	1,0
Total	201	
99 No answer	11	
Does not receive any help	4930	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,26
Standard deviation		0,81
Mean value for >0		2,00
Standard deviation		1,26

X723

HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PARENTS

Approximate number of hours per week that respondent's parents (not living in household) do housework in respondent's home.

0	162	80,6
1	19	9,5
2	12	6,0
3	4	2,0
5	1	0,5
10	2	1,0
14	1	0,5
Total	201	
99 No answer	11	
Does not receive any help	4930	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,47
Standard deviation		1,55
Mean value for >0		2,41
Standard deviation		2,80

X724

HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER FAMILY MEMBER/RELATIVE

Approximate number of hours per week that family member/relative of the respondent does housework in respondent's home.

0	160	79,6
1	18	9,0
2	10	5,0
3	4	2,0
4	4	2,0
5	2	1,0
7	1	0,5
10	1	0,5
20	1	0,5
Total	201	
99 No answer	11	
Does not receive any help	4930	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,56
Standard deviation		1,86
Mean value for >0		2,76
Standard deviation		3,34

X725

HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM MUNICIPAL HOME-HELP SERVICE

Approximate number of hours per week that municipal home-help service does housework in respondent's home.

0	184	91,5
1	2	1,0
2	2	1,0
3	2	1,0
5	1	0,5
7	1	0,5
10	1	0,5
14	4	2,0
15	1	0,5
28	1	0,5

	30	1	0,5
	35	1	0,5
	Total	201	
99	No answer	11	
	Does not receive any help	4930	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,99
	Standard deviation		4,43
	Mean value for >0		11,65
	Standard deviation		10,65
X726	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PRIVATELY PAID HOME-HELP SERVICE		
	Approximate number of hours per week that a privately paid home-help service does housework in respondent's home.		
	0	174	86,6
	1	6	3,0
	2	13	6,5
	3	5	2,5
	4	2	1,0
	8	1	0,5
	Total	201	
99	No answer	11	
	Does not receive any help	4930	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,31
	Standard deviation		0,95
	Mean value for >0		2,33
	Standard deviation		1,41
X727	HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER		
	Approximate number of hours per week that other than above does housework in respondent's home.		
	0	137	70,3
	1	20	10,3
	2	13	6,7
	3	5	2,6
	4	6	3,1
	5	9	4,6
	8	2	1,0
	10	1	0,5
	19	1	0,5
	25	1	0,5
	Total	195	
99	No answer	17	
	Does not receive any help	4930	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		1,03
	Standard deviation		2,73
	Mean value for >0		3,45
	Standard deviation		4,11
X728	DISTRIBUTION OF HOUSEHOLD'S MONEY		
	How do you and your partner distribute your money?		
	1 All money is common	2302	66,5

	2	We have a common portion and a portion to each of us	883	25,5
	3	We have entirely separate economies	268	7,7
	4	Other	3	0,1
	5	Doesn't know	4	0,1
		Total	3460	
	9	No answer	42	
		Not cohabiting	1640	
			5142	
X729		DIFFERENT OPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK		
		How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to division of housework?		
	1	Often	219	6,3
	2	Sometimes	919	26,5
	3	Seldom	1258	36,3
	4	Never	1054	30,4
	5	Not applicable	18	0,5
		Total	3468	
	9	No answer	34	
		Not cohabiting	1640	
			5142	
X730		DIFFERENT OPINIONS USE OF MONEY		
		How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to use of money?		
	1	Often	68	2,0
	2	Sometimes	537	15,5
	3	Seldom	1298	37,5
	4	Never	1547	44,6
	5	Not applicable	15	0,4
		Total	3465	
	9	No answer	37	
		Not cohabiting	1640	
			5142	
X731		DIFFERENT OPINIONS WHO YOU KEEP COMPANY WITH		
		How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to who you keep company with as a couple?		
	1	Often	26	0,8
	2	Sometimes	287	8,3
	3	Seldom	1022	29,5
	4	Never	2115	61,0
	5	Not applicable	15	0,4
		Total	3465	
	9	No answer	37	
		Not cohabiting	1640	
			5142	
X732		DIFFERENT OPINIONS CHILD RAISING		
		How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to child raising?		
	1	Often	53	1,5
	2	Sometimes	412	12,0
	3	Seldom	685	19,9
	4	Never	621	18,0

5	Not applicable	1676	48,6
	Total	3447	
9	No answer	55	
	Not cohabiting	1640	
		5142	

X733

DIFFERENT OPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS

How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to how much your spouse/partner works?

1	Often	86	2,5
2	Sometimes	360	10,4
3	Seldom	543	15,7
4	Never	1721	49,7
5	Not applicable	756	21,8
	Total	3466	
9	No answer	36	
	Not cohabiting	1640	
		5142	

X734

DIFFERENT OPINIONS HOW MUCH RESPONDENT WORKS

How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to how much you work?

1	Often	97	2,8
2	Sometimes	435	12,5
3	Seldom	607	17,5
4	Never	1558	44,9
5	Not applicable	771	22,2
	Total	3468	
9	No answer	34	
	Not cohabiting	1640	
		5142	

X735

NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT DROPS CHILDREN OFF

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days do you drop children off at day-care/recreation centre, school?

0		656	49,8
1		69	5,2
2		94	7,1
3		125	9,5
4		81	6,2
5		283	21,5
7		9	0,7
	Total	1317	
9	No answer	52	
	No children in household born >1988	3773	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		1,85
	Standard deviation		2,11
	Mean value for >0		3,68
	Standard deviation		1,47

X736

NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER DROPS CHILDREN OFF

ES

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does respondent's spouse/partner drop children off at day-care/recreation centre, school?

0	748	60,5
1	64	5,2
2	98	7,9
3	82	6,6
4	74	6,0
5	166	13,4
7	5	0,4
Total	1237	
9 No answer	132	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	
Mean value for all		1,35
Standard deviation		1,91
Mean value for >0		3,41
Standard deviation		1,49
X737	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE DROPS CHILDREN OFF	
	During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does someone else drop children off at day-care/recreation centre, school?	
0	964	95,4
1	17	1,7
2	13	1,3
3	5	0,5
4	2	0,2
5	9	0,9
7	1	0,1
Total	1011	
9 No answer	358	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,12
Standard deviation		0,63
Mean value for >0		2,51
Standard deviation		1,64
X738	NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PICKS CHILDREN UP	
	During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days do you pick children up from day-care/recreation centre, school?	
0	669	50,8
1	87	6,6
2	125	9,5
3	127	9,6
4	90	6,8
5	212	16,1
7	7	0,5
Total	1317	
9 No answer	52	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	
Mean value for all		1,66
Standard deviation		1,98
Mean value for >0		3,38
Standard deviation		1,49

X739**NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PICKS CHILDREN UP**

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does respondent's spouse/partner pick children up from day-care/recreation centre, school?

0	701	56,58
1	93	7,51
2	109	8,80
3	112	9,04
4	70	5,65
5	150	12,11
7	4	0,32
Total	1239	
9 No answer	130	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	
Mean value for all		1,38
Standard deviation		1,85
Mean value for >0		3,17
Standard deviation		1,49

X740**NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PICKS CHILDREN UP**

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does someone else pick children up from day-care/recreation centre, school?

0	928	91,0
1	43	4,2
2	21	2,1
3	11	1,1
4	6	0,6
5	10	1,0
7	1	0,1
Total	1020	
9 No answer	349	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	

X741**NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT COOKS DINNER**

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days do you cook dinner?

0	151	11,2
1	136	10,1
2	140	10,4
3	177	13,2
4	159	11,8
5	167	12,4
6	82	6,1
7	333	24,8
Total	1345	
9 No answer	24	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	
Mean value for all		3,90
Standard deviation		2,42
Mean value for >0		4,39
Standard deviation		2,10

X742

NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER COOKS DINNER

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does respondent's spouse/partner cook dinner?

0	289	22,6
1	99	7,8
2	177	13,9
3	167	13,1
4	163	12,8
5	128	10,0
6	108	8,5
7	146	11,4
Total	1277	
9 No answer	92	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	
Mean value for all		3,07
Standard deviation		2,37
Mean value for >0		3,96
Standard deviation		1,92

X743

NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE COOKS DINNER

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does someone else cook dinner?

0	926	93,5
1	26	2,6
2	18	1,8
3	8	0,8
4	2	0,2
5	2	0,2
6	1	0,1
7	7	0,7
Total	990	
9 No answer	379	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,16
Standard deviation		0,78
Mean value for >0		2,48
Standard deviation		1,94

X744

NUMBER OF DAYS RESPONDENT PUTS CHILDREN TO BED

During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days do you put children to bed?

0	254	18,9
1	38	2,8
2	82	6,1
3	214	15,9
4	210	15,6
5	98	7,3
6	40	3,0
7	408	30,4
Total	1344	
9 No answer	25	
No children in household born >1988	3773	
	5142	

	Mean value for all	3,12	
	Standard deviation	2,57	
	Mean value for >0	4,43	
	Standard deviation	1,89	
X745	NUMBER OF DAYS SPOUSE/PARTNER PUTS CHILDREN TO BED		
	During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does respondent's spouse/partner put children to bed?		
	0	376	29,6
	1	43	3,4
	2	86	6,8
	3	196	15,4
	4	210	16,5
	5	76	6,0
	6	38	3,0
	7	244	19,2
	Total	1269	
	9 No answer	100	
	No children in household born >1988	3773	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		3,12
	Standard deviation		2,57
	Mean value for >0		4,43
	Standard deviation		1,89
X746	NUMBER OF DAYS SOMEONE ELSE PUTS CHILDREN TO BED		
	During a normal week (Monday-Sunday), how many days does someone else put children to bed?		
	0	945	97,3
	1	6	0,6
	2	8	0,8
	3	5	0,5
	4	3	0,3
	6	1	0,1
	7	3	0,3
	Total	971	
	9 No answer	398	
	No children in household born >1988	3773	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,08
	Standard deviation		0,56
	Mean value for >0		2,92
	Standard deviation		1,92
X747	GRANDPARENTS BABY-SITTERS		
	How often do the child's/children's grandparents take care of or baby-sit your child/children?		
	1 Several times a week	89	6,6
	2 About once a week	146	10,8
	3 1-3 times a month	312	23,1
	4 Less often	455	33,8
	5 Never	310	23,0
	6 Doesn't have grandparents	36	2,7
	Total	1348	
	9 No answer	21	
	No children in household born >1988	3773	

		5142	
X748	CASH MARGIN		
	If a situation suddenly arose where you had to come up with 12 000 kronor in a week, could you manage it?		
	1 Yes	4514	88,1
	2 No	607	11,9
	Total	5121	
	9 No answer	21	
		5142	
X749	ACQUIRING CASH		
	If yes: How would you manage to come up with 12 000 kronor in a week?		
	1 Withdrawal from own bank account	3075	68,2
	2 Sale of stocks, fund shares or the like	411	9,1
	3 Loan from family member	352	7,8
	4 Loan from other relatives or friends	396	8,8
	5 Bank loan or equivalent	234	5,2
	6 Other way	40	0,9
	Total	4508	
	9 No answer	27	
	Could not acquire money	607	
		5142	
X750	CAR OWNER		
	Do you (or your spouse/partner) own a car?		
	1 Yes	4022	78,4
	2 No	1109	21,6
	Total	5131	
	9 No answer	11	
		5142	
X751	BOAT OWNER		
	Do you (or your spouse/partner) own a boat		
	1 Yes	1054	20,5
	2 No	4075	79,5
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X752	SUMMER COTTAGE OWNER		
	Do you (or your spouse/partner) own a summer cottage?		
	1 Yes	1010	19,7
	2 No	4120	80,3
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X753	CARAVAN OWNER		
	Do you (or your spouse/partner) own a caravan/trailer?		
	1 Yes	369	7,2
	2 No	4760	92,8

	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X754	ECONOMIC DIFFICULTIES		Y584
	Have you at any time in the last 12 months had difficulty managing your current expenses for food, rent, bills, etc?		
	1 Yes	809	15,8
	2 No	4311	84,2
	Total	5120	
	9 No answer	22	
		5142	
X755	RECEIVES MAINTENANCE PER MONTH		
	Do you receive maintenance for a child born 1982 or later? If yes: What is the total payment per month (SEK per month)? The table is valid for respondent with children under 18 who has separated from the other parent. This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	275	64,1
	100-199	2	0,5
	300-399	1	0,2
	400-499	1	0,2
	500-599	1	0,2
	700-799	1	0,2
	800-899	1	0,2
	1000-1099	6	1,4
	1100-1199	69	16,1
	1200-1299	6	1,4
	1300-1399	2	0,5
	1500-1599	2	0,5
	1600-1699	1	0,2
	1700-1799	2	0,5
	2000-2999	44	10,3
	3000-3999	11	2,6
	4000-4999	1	0,2
	5000-5999	3	0,7
	Total	429	
	99999 No answer	45	
	Not separated from parent/Does not receive maintenance	4668	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		623,97
	Standard deviation		1006,94
	Mean value for >0		1738,19
	Standard deviation		941,78
X756	PAYS MAINTENANCE PER MONTH		
	Do you pay maintenance for a child born 1982 or later? If yes: What is the total payment per month (SEK per month)? The table is valid for respondent with children under 18 who has separated from the other parent. This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	279	66,7
	100-199	2	0,5
	200-299	1	0,2
	300-399	1	0,2
	400-499	2	0,5
	500-599	4	1,0
	600-699	5	1,2

700-799	4	1,0
800-899	4	1,0
900-999	1	0,2
1000-1099	8	1,9
1100-1199	38	9,1
1200-1299	8	1,9
1300-1399	1	0,2
1400-1499	1	0,2
1500-1599	9	2,2
1600-1699	1	0,2
1700-1799	2	0,5
1800-1899	4	1,0
1900-1999	1	0,2
2000-2999	25	6,0
3000-3999	12	2,9
4000-4999	1	0,2
5000-5999	3	0,7
11000-11999	1	0,2
Total	418	
99999 No answer	43	
Not separated from parent/Does not pay maintenance	4681	
	5142	
Mean value for all		558,91
Standard deviation		1070,43
Mean value for >0		1680,76
Standard deviation		1250,27

X757

INHERITANCE

jfr U580, jfr
V605, jfr
W377

Have you ever received an inheritance of at least 25 000 kronor or something of equivalent value?

1 Yes	1490	29,1
2 No	3627	70,9
Total	5117	
9 No answer	25	
	5142	

X758

SIZE OF INHERITANCE

jfr U581, jfr
V606, jfr
W378

If you have ever received an inheritance of at least 25 000 kronor: How much did you inherit altogether? (Approx. amount in thousands of SEK at the time of inheritance.) This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	8	0,6
20-29	170	12,6
30-39	128	9,5
40-49	86	6,4
50-59	176	13,0
60-69	64	4,7
70-79	94	7,0
80-89	43	3,2
90-99	24	1,8
100-199	273	20,2
200-299	143	10,6
300-399	54	4,0
400-499	25	1,9
500-599	25	1,9
600-699	10	0,7

700-799	6	0,4
800-899	1	0,1
900-999	2	0,1
1000-1999	13	1,0
2000-2999	5	0,4
Total	1350	
9999 No answer	165	
Not received inheritance	3627	
	5142	
Mean value		133,56
Standard deviation		199,16

X759

INHERITANCE, YEAR

jfr U582, jfr
V607, jfr
W379

If you have ever received an inheritance of at least 25 000 SEK: When (during approx. what year) did you receive your inheritance? (If several inheritances, give year corresponding to the largest.)

1932	1	0,1
1941	1	0,1
1946	1	0,1
1948	1	0,1
1949	2	0,1
1950	1	0,1
1955	1	0,1
1956	1	0,1
1957	1	0,1
1958	2	0,1
1960	7	0,5
1961	2	0,1
1962	1	0,1
1963	6	0,4
1964	1	0,1
1965	4	0,3
1966	4	0,3
1967	6	0,4
1968	3	0,2
1969	7	0,5
1970	11	0,8
1971	8	0,6
1972	9	0,6
1973	8	0,6
1974	7	0,5
1975	9	0,6
1976	13	0,9
1977	20	1,4
1978	20	1,4
1979	24	1,7
1980	41	2,9
1981	17	1,2
1982	30	2,1
1983	31	2,2
1984	39	2,8
1985	50	3,5
1986	52	3,7
1987	53	3,7
1988	55	3,9

1989	52	3,7
1990	69	4,9
1991	65	4,6
1992	62	4,4
1993	48	3,4
1994	69	4,9
1995	85	6,0
1996	76	5,4
1997	86	6,1
1998	96	6,8
1999	100	7,1
2000	59	4,2
Total	1417	
9999 No answer	98	
Not received inheritance	3627	
	5142	

X760

TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT GIVEN

During the last 12 months, have you given financial support or gifts to a person/persons outside your household?
If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	348	41,7
10-19	230	27,5
20-29	112	13,4
30-39	45	5,4
40-49	24	2,9
50-59	24	2,9
60-69	10	1,2
70-79	2	0,2
80-89	5	0,6
90-99	5	0,6
100-109	8	1,0
110-119	1	0,1
120-129	4	0,5
140-149	2	0,2
150-159	4	0,5
160-169	1	0,1
190-199	1	0,1
200-299	4	0,5
300-399	2	0,2
500-599	2	0,2
700-799	1	0,1
Total	835	
9998 Has given, no amount	22	
9999 No answer	43	
Has not given gifts/support	4242	
	5142	
Mean value		277,86
Standard deviation		1579,32

X761

FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you given financial support or gifts to parents? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0	794	92,8
1-5	32	3,7
6-10	17	2,0

11-15		3	0,4
16-20		7	0,8
21-25		2	0,2
31-35		1	0,1
Total		856	
9998	Has given, no amount	1	
9999	No answer	43	
	Has not given gifts/support	4242	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,61
	Standard deviation		2,84
	Mean value for >0		8,40
	Standard deviation		6,80

X762

FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you given financial support or gifts to grandparents? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0		852	99,2
1-5		4	0,5
6-10		2	0,2
21-25		1	0,1
Total		859	
9999	No answer	41	
	Has not given gifts/support	4242	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		0,07
	Standard deviation		1,00
	Mean value for >0		8,57
	Standard deviation		7,68

X763

FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you given financial support or gifts to children? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0		301	35,7
1-9		194	23,0
10-19		167	19,8
20-29		76	9,0
30-39		36	4,3
40-49		17	2,0
50-59		12	1,4
60-69		9	1,1
70-79		3	0,4
80-89		2	0,2
90-99		2	0,2
100-199		16	1,9
200-299		5	0,6
300-399		1	0,1
400-499		1	0,1
Total		842	
9998	Has given, no amount	17	
9999	No answer	41	
	Has not given gifts/support	4242	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		13,93

	Standard deviation		30,98
	Mean value for >0		21,68
	Standard deviation		36,41
X764	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK		
	During the last 12 months, have you given financial support or gifts to grandchildren? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	716	83,6
	1-9	80	9,3
	10-19	27	3,2
	20-29	10	1,2
	30-39	6	0,7
	40-49	6	0,7
	50-59	5	0,6
	60-69	1	0,1
	80-89	2	0,2
	90-99	1	0,1
	100-199	2	0,2
	Total	856	
	9998 Has given, no amount	3	
	9999 No answer	41	
	Has not given gifts/support	4242	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		2,46
	Standard deviation		9,81
	Mean value for >0		15,02
	Standard deviation		20,05
X765	FINANCIAL SUPPORT TO OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK		
	During the last 12 months, have you given financial support or gifts to another person? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	621	72,7
	1-9	150	17,6
	10-19	47	5,5
	20-29	20	2,3
	30-39	6	0,7
	40-49	3	0,4
	50-59	1	0,1
	70-79	1	0,1
	80-89	1	0,1
	100-199	2	0,2
	500-599	1	0,1
	700-799	1	0,1
	Total	854	
	9998 Has given, no amount	5	
	9999 No answer	41	
	Has not given gifts/support	4242	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		4,40
	Standard deviation		30,94
	Mean value for >0		16,13
	Standard deviation		57,71
X766	TOTAL FINANCIAL SUPPORT RECEIVED		

During the last 12 months, have you received financial support or gifts from a person/persons outside your household? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9		251	38,4
10-19		246	37,6
20-29		73	11,2
30-39		25	3,8
40-49		8	1,2
50-59		16	2,4
60-69		3	0,5
70-79		4	0,6
80-89		3	0,5
90-99		2	0,3
100-199		13	2,0
200-299		8	1,2
500-599		1	0,2
700-799		1	0,2
Total		654	
9998	Has received, no amount	25	
9999	No answer	25	
	Has not received gifts/support	4438	
		5142	
	Mean value		20,01
	Standard deviation		45,03

X767

FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM PARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you received financial support or gifts from parents? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0		219	33,2
1-9		184	27,9
10-19		156	23,6
20-29		51	7,7
30-39		19	2,9
40-49		4	0,6
50-59		9	1,4
60-69		1	0,2
70-79		1	0,2
80-89		2	0,3
90-99		1	0,2
100-199		6	0,9
200-299		6	0,9
500-599		1	0,2
Total		660	
9998	Has received, no amount	19	
9999	No answer	25	
	Has not received gifts/support	4438	
		5142	
	Mean value for all		12,06
	Standard deviation		32,77
	Mean value for >0		18,05
	Standard deviation		38,73

X768

FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDPARENTS, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you received financial support or gifts from grandparents? If yes: What is the

total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0	544	80,5
1-9	67	9,9
10-19	47	7,0
20-29	8	1,2
30-39	1	0,1
40-49	2	0,3
50-59	2	0,3
70-79	1	0,1
80-89	1	0,1
100-199	1	0,1
200-299	2	0,3
Total	676	
9998 Has received, no amount	3	
9999 No answer	25	
Has not received gifts/support	4438	
	5142	
Mean value for all		2,85
Standard deviation		14,96
Mean value for >0		14,59
Standard deviation		31,31

X769

FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM CHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you received financial support or gifts from children? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)?

0	673	99,3
2	1	0,1
6	1	0,1
10	1	0,1
12	2	0,3
Total	678	
9998 Has received, no amount	1	
9999 No answer	25	
Has not received gifts/support	4438	
	5142	
Mean value for all		0,06
Standard deviation		0,79
Mean value for >0		8,40
Standard deviation		4,34

X770

FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM GRANDCHILDREN, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you received financial support or gifts from grandchildren? If yes: What is the total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)?

0	679	100
9999 No answer	25	
Has not received gifts/support	4438	
Total	4463	
	5142	
Mean value		0
Standard deviation		0

X771

FINANCIAL SUPPORT FROM OTHER PERSON, THOUSANDS SEK

During the last 12 months, have you received financial support or gifts from another person? If yes: What is the

total approximate value (amount in thousands SEK)? This variable is divided into categories.

0	528	78,2
1-9	66	9,8
10-19	46	6,8
20-29	15	2,2
30-39	3	0,4
40-49	1	0,1
50-59	5	0,7
60-69	2	0,3
70-79	1	0,1
80-89	1	0,1
90-99	1	0,1
100-199	5	0,7
700-799	1	0,1
Total	675	
9998 Has received, no amount	4	
9999 No answer	25	
Has not received gifts/support	4438	
	5142	
Mean value for all		4,68
Standard deviation		29,76
Mean value for >0		21,50
Standard deviation		61,02

X772

HELP WITH REPAIRS/MAINTENANCE/WORKMANSHIP

Do you have a friend or acquaintance that can help you with repairs, maintenance or workmanship?

1 Yes	3857	75,4
2 No	1261	24,6
Total	5118	
9 No answer	24	
	5142	

X773

HELP WITH MEDICAL EXPERTISE

Do you have a friend or acquaintance that can help you with medical expertise?

1 Yes	2543	49,7
2 No	2577	50,3
Total	5120	
9 No answer	22	
	5142	

X774

HELP WITH FINANCIAL OR LEGAL EXPERTISE

Do you have a friend or acquaintance that can help you with financial or legal expertise, i.e. tax declaration?

1 Yes	2863	55,9
2 No	2255	44,1
Total	5118	
9 No answer	24	
	5142	

X775

CLOSE FRIEND WHEN ILL

Y614, U699

Do you have a family member or close friend who helps out if you become ill?

1 Yes	4912	96,0
2 No	203	4,0

	Total	5115	
	9 No answer	27	
		5142	
X776	CLOSE FRIEND AS COMPANY		Y615, U700
	Do you have a family member or close friend who helps out if you want company?		
	1 Yes	4950	96,7
	2 No	167	3,3
	Total	5117	
	9 No answer	25	
		5142	
X777	SOMEONE TO TALK TO		Y616, U701
	Do you have a family member or close friend who helps out if you need to talk to someone about personal problems?		
	1 Yes	4900	95,8
	2 No	214	4,2
	Total	5114	
	9 No answer	28	
		5142	
X778	SOMEONE TO BORROW MONEY FROM		
	Do you have a family member or close friend who helps out if you need a loan of 12 000 kronor?		
	1 Yes	4061	80,0
	2 No	1015	20,0
	Total	5076	
	9 No answer	66	
		5142	
X779	SUFFERED FROM THEFT		Y585, U593, jfr V618
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from any form of theft?		
	1 Yes	804	15,7
	2 No	4328	84,3
	Total	5132	
	9 No answer	10	
		5142	
X780	SUFFERED FROM DAMAGE		Y586, U596, V621
	Has it happened in the last 12 months that someone has damaged or destroyed any property of yours?		
	1 Yes	631	12,3
	2 No	4493	87,7
	Total	5124	
	9 No answer	18	
		5142	
X781	VIOLENCE LEADING TO BODILY HARM		Y587, U601, V626
	Have you in the last 12 months been a victim of violence leading to visible marks or bodily harm?		
	1 Yes	77	1,5
	2 No	5051	98,5
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	

X782	VIOLENCE WITHOUT BODILY HARM	Y588, U602, V627
	Have you in the last 12 months been a victim of violence which did not lead to visible marks or bodily harm?	
	1 Yes	114 2,2
	2 No	5007 97,8
	Total	5121
	9 No answer	21
		5142
X783	SERIOUS THREATS	Y589, U603, V628
	Have you in the last 12 months been a victim of threat or threats dangerous or serious enough to frighten you?	
	1 Yes	235 4,6
	2 No	4892 95,4
	Total	5127
	9 No answer	15
		5142
X784	VACATION TRIP 1999	Y590, U611, V636, jfr W614
	Did you go on a vacation trip (or other leisure trip) in 1999?	
	1 Yes	3595 70,1
	2 No	1536 29,9
	Total	5131
	9 No answer	11
		5142
X785	COTTAGE STAY 1999	Y594, U618, V643, W469
	Did you in 1999 spend any time in a summer cottage, allotment-garden cottage or other leisure dwelling?	
	1 Yes	2494 48,7
	2 No	2630 51,3
	Total	5124
	9 No answer	18
		5142
X786	FISHING OR HUNTING IN SPARE TIME	jfr Y596- 597, jfr U621-622, jfr V646- 647, jfr W472-473
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go fishing or hunting?	
	1 No	3284 64,1
	2 Yes, sometimes	1359 26,5
	3 Yes, often	479 9,4
	Total	5122
	9 No answer	20
		5142
X787	GARDENING	Y598, U623, V648, W474
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: gardening?	
	1 No	1785 34,8
	2 Yes, sometimes	1465 28,6
	3 Yes, often	1875 36,6
	Total	5125
	9 No answer	17
		5142

X788	GO TO THE CINEMA		Y599, U624, V649, W475
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go to the cinema?		
	1 No	1948	38,0
	2 Yes, sometimes	2788	54,4
	3 Yes, often	390	7,6
	Total	5126	
	9 No answer	16	
		5142	
X789	GO TO THE THEATRE		Y600, U625, V650, W476
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go to the theatre, concerts, museums, exhibitions?		
	1 No	1799	35,1
	2 Yes, sometimes	2954	57,6
	3 Yes, often	373	7,3
	Total	5126	
	9 No answer	16	
		5142	
X790	GO TO A RESTAURANT		Y601, U626, V651, W477
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go to a restaurant?		
	1 No	850	16,6
	2 Yes, sometimes	3454	67,3
	3 Yes, often	825	16,1
	Total	5129	
	9 No answer	13	
		5142	
X791	DANCING		Y602, U627, V652, W478
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: go dancing?		
	1 No	2820	55,0
	2 Yes, sometimes	1838	35,9
	3 Yes, often	466	9,1
	Total	5124	
	9 No answer	18	
		5142	
X792	VISIT RELATIVES		Y604, U632, V657, W483
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: visit relatives?		
	1 No	305	6,0
	2 Yes, sometimes	2829	55,2
	3 Yes, often	1992	38,9
	Total	5126	
	9 No answer	16	
		5142	
X793	HAVE RELATIVES VISIT		Y605, U633, V658, W485
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: have relatives visit?		
	1 No	501	9,8
	2 Yes, sometimes	3109	60,7
	3 Yes, often	1514	29,5

	Total	5124	
	9 No answer	18	
		5142	
X794	VISIT FRIENDS AND ACQUAINTANCES		Y606, U634, V659, W484
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: visit friends and acquaintances?		
	1 No	141	2,8
	2 Yes, sometimes	2432	47,4
	3 Yes, often	2554	49,8
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X795	HAVE FRIENDS VISIT		Y607, U635, V660, W486
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: have friends and acquaintances visit?		
	1 No	188	3,7
	2 Yes, sometimes	2645	51,6
	3 Yes, often	2290	44,7
	Total	5123	
	9 No answer	19	
		5142	
X796	READ BOOKS		Y603, U628, V653, W479
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: read books?		
	1 No	1258	24,5
	2 Yes, sometimes	1812	35,3
	3 Yes, often	2057	40,1
	Total	5127	
	9 No answer	15	
		5142	
X797	STUDY CIRCLE		Y608, U636, V661, W487
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: take part in study groups or courses?		
	1 No	3830	74,8
	2 Yes, sometimes	924	18,0
	3 Yes, often	369	7,2
	Total	5123	
	9 No answer	19	
		5142	
X798	PLAY MUSIC OR SING IN A CHOIR		jfr Y610- 611, jfr U638, jfr V663, jfr W488
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: play a musical instrument or sing in a choir?		
	1 No	4311	84,0
	2 Yes, sometimes	389	7,6
	3 Yes, often	430	8,4
	Total	5130	
	9 No answer	12	
		5142	
X799	HOBBY ACTIVITY		Y612, U640, V665, W490
	Do you engage in any of the following leisure activities: pursuit a hobby (knit, sew, do woodwork, paint, collect		

stamps and the like)?			
1	No	2364	46,1
2	Yes, sometimes	1098	21,4
3	Yes, often	1662	32,4
	Total	5124	
9	No answer	18	
		5142	
X800	SPORTS ACTIVITY		Y613
Do you pursue any sports, outdoor or exercise activities, e.g. long walks? If yes: How often?			
1	Yes, several times/week	2407	46,9
2	Yes, about once/week	1162	22,7
3	Yes, 1-3 times/month	399	7,8
4	Yes, but less often	440	8,6
5	No	721	14,1
	Total	5129	
9	No answer	13	
		5142	
X801	MEMBER OF TRADE UNION		Y617, U648,V666, jfr W491
Are you a member of a trade union or association?			
1	Yes	3245	63,3
2	No	1885	36,7
	Total	5130	
9	No answer	12	
		5142	
X802	UNION		Y618, U649, V667, jfr W491
What union (or equivalent) do you belong to?			
-1	Arbetsgivar- och företagarorganisationer (Employers' associations)	25	0,8
1	Beklädnads arb.förbundet/Industrifacket (Clothing/Industry union)	58	1,8
2	Bleck- och plåtslagare (Tinsmiths and platers)	3	0,1
4	Byggnadsarb. Förbundet (Building Workers' Union)	104	3,2
5	Elektriker förbundet (Electricians' Union)	24	0,7
6	Fabriksarb. förbundet (Factory Workers' Union)	9	0,3
7	Fastighetsanst. Förbund (Building Maintenance Workers' Union)	37	1,1
9	Försäkringsanst. Förbund (Insurance Employees' Union)	14	0,4
11	Handelsanst. Förbund (Commercial Employees' Union)	123	3,8
12	Hotell och rest. anst. Förbund (Hotel and Restaurant Workers' Union)	42	1,3
13	Kommunalarb. Förbundet (Trade Union for municipality workers)	548	16,9
14	Lantarb. Förbundet (Farm Workers' Trade Union)	7	0,2
16	Livsmedelsarb. Förbundet (Food Workers' Union)	51	1,6
17	Metallind. arb. Förbundet (Metal Workers' Union)	284	8,8
18	Musikerförbundet (Musicians' Union)	4	0,1
19	Målareförbundet (Painters' Union)	10	0,3
20	Pappersindustriarb. Förbundet (Paper Workers' Union)	21	0,6
21	Sjöfolksförbundet (Seamen's Union)	5	0,2
23	Skogsarb. förbud/Skogs- träfacket/Träind förbundet (Forest and Wood Workers' Union)	66	2,0
24	Statsanst förb/Fack för service och kom. (SEKO) (Union for Service and Communications Employees)	121	3,7

25	Transportarb förbundet (Transport Workers' Union)	70	2,2
27	Grafiska fackförbundet/Typograf förbundet (Graphic Workers' Union)	34	1,1
28	Ospec LO (Swedish Trade Union Confederation, not specified)	18	0,6
29	Sveriges arb. central org. (SAC) (Central Organization of the Workers of Sweden)	3	0,1
30	Farmaciförb/Apotekstjm förbundet (Pharmacists' Union)	1	0,0
31	Ledarna/Arbetsledar förbundet (Organization for Managers)	57	1,8
32	Finansförb/Bankmannas förbundet (Financial Sector Union of Sweden)	45	1,4
33	Läraryrb/Facklärar förbundet (Teachers' Union)	176	5,4
35	Folkhögsk läraryrb förbundet (Union for Folk High School Teachers)	4	0,1
36	Försvarets civila tjm förbundet (Union of Civilian Salaried Employees in Defence Establishments)	7	0,2
37	Försäkrings tjm förbundet (Union of Insurance Employees)	20	0,6
38	Handels tjm förb (HTF) (Salaried Employees' Union)	137	4,2
39	Vårdförb/Hälso- och sjukv. Tjmförbundet (Association of Health Professionals)	86	2,7
40	Industritjm förbundet (Industrial Workers' Union)	325	10,0
41	Journalist förbundet (Union of Journalists)	10	0,3
42	Kommunaltjm förbundet (Union of Local Government Officers)	151	4,7
43	Officerarnas riksförbund (National Association of Officers)	2	0,1
46	Yrkesmusiker förbundet (Professional musicians' union)	3	0,1
47	Polisförbundet (Police Union)	20	0,6
48	Skogs- och lantbruks tjm (Association of Forestal and Agricultural Employees)	1	0,0
49	Stats tjm förbundet (Union of Civil Servants)	68	2,1
50	Teater förbundet (Union for Theatre, Artists and Media)	6	0,2
51	Tull- kust/Tulltjm förbundet (Customs union)	2	0,1
52	Ospec TCO (Swedish Confederation of Professional Employees, not specified)	8	0,2
53	Järnvägars tjmförbund (Transport and Railway Association)	1	0,0
54	Agrifack (Association of Graduates in Agricultural and Horticultural Sciences)	7	0,2
55	Civilek riksförbund (Association of Graduates in Business Administration)	19	0,6
56	Dik- förb, dokum, info, kultur (Association of Graduates in Documentation, Information and Culture)	7	0,2
57	Ingenjörers förbundet (Association of Graduate Engineers)	10	0,3
58	JUSEK (Union of University Graduates of Law)	45	1,4
59	Sjukgymn riksförbund (Swedish Association of Registered Physiotherapists)	9	0,3
60	Läraernas riksförbund (National Union of Teachers)	60	1,9
62	SACO: s allm. tjm förbund (Swedish Confederation of Professional Associations)	4	0,1
63	Skolledar förbundet (Association of School Principals and Directors of Education)	5	0,2
64	Arkitekt förbundet (Union of Architects)	11	0,3
65	Officersförbundet (Military Officers' Association)	3	0,1
67	Civilingenjör förbundet (Association of Graduate Engineers)	70	2,2
68	Farmaceutv förbundet (Pharmaceutical Association)	7	0,2
70	Läkar förbundet (Medical Association)	20	0,6
71	Naturvetare förbundet (Association of Scientists)	7	0,2
72	Psykologförbundet (Association of Psychologists)	5	0,2
73	Akademikerförb/Socionom riksförbund, SSR (Association of Graduates Social Work)	24	0,7
74	Tandläkar förbundet (Dental Association)	9	0,3
75	Arbetsterapeuters förbund (Occupational Therapy Association)	9	0,3

	76 Veterinärförbundet (Veterinary Association)	1	0,0
	77 Universitetslärare (Association of University Teachers)	15	0,5
	78 Ospec SACO (Swedish Confederation of Professional Associations, not specified)	21	0,6
	79 Lantbrukarnas riksförbund (Federation of Swedish Farmers)	35	1,1
	81 Other	1	0,0
	82 Unknown union	15	0,5
	84 Self-employed, not specified	1	0,0
	86 Hamnarbetarförbundet (Dockworkers' Union)	1	0,0
	87 Handelsrepres/Säljarnas riksförbund (National Union of Sales People)	6	0,2
	Total	3238	
	88 Doesn't know	2	
	99 No answer	17	
	Not member	1885	
		5142	
X803	VISITED TRADE UNION MEETING		jfr Y620, jfr U650, jfr V668, jfr W492
	Have you been to any trade union meeting during the last year?		
	1 Yes	839	16,5
	2 No	4254	83,5
	Total	5093	
	9 No answer	49	
		5142	
X804	UNION REPRESENTATIVE		Y621, U652, V670, W493
	Do you now hold or have you at any time held a position of trust in a trade union (committee member and like)?		
	1 Holds position of trust	307	6,0
	2 Has held position of trust	702	13,7
	3 No	4109	80,3
	Total	5118	
	9 No answer	24	
		5142	
X805	UNION ACTIVITY		Y622, U653, V749, W579
	Index of union activity based on the answers from the questions in X801, X803 and X804.		
	Construction of index:		
	X805 = 1 Not member of trade union		
	= 2 Member + neither holds nor has held position of trust + not been to trade union meeting last year		
	= 3 Member + neither holds nor has held position of trust + has been to trade union meeting last year		
	= 4 Member + holds or has held position of trust		
	1 Not member	1885	36,8
	2 Passive member	2017	39,3
	3 Active member	387	7,5
	4 Representative	839	16,4
	Total	5128	
	9 No answer	14	
		5142	
X806	PARTY MEMBERSHIP		Y623, U654, V671, W494
	Do you belong to a political party or a political association? If yes: Do you now hold or have you at any time held a position of trust in a political association or organization (committee member and the like)?		
	11 Holds position of trust	89	1,7
	12 Has held position of trust	79	1,5

	13	No	176	3,4	
	20	Not member	4782	93,3	
		Total	5126		
	99	No answer	16		
			5142		
X807	VISITED POLITICAL MEETING				jfr Y624, jfr U656, jfr V672, jfr W495
	Have you been to a political meeting or gathering in the last year?				
	1	Yes	273	5,3	
	2	No	4846	94,7	
		Total	5119		
	9	No answer	23		
			5142		
X808	POLITICAL ACTIVITY				
	Index of political activity based on the answers from the questions in X806, X807 and X808.				
	Construction of index:				
	X808 = 1 Not member of political association + not been to political meeting last year				
	= 2 Member not position of trust + not been to political meeting last year				
	= 3 (Member or not member) + does not hold or has held position of trust + has been to political meeting last year				
	= 4 Member + (has held position of trust) or (holds position of trust) + has been to political meeting last year				
	1	Not member	4664	91,1	
	2	Passive member	172	3,4	
	3	Active member	151	3,0	
	4	Representative	130	2,5	
		Total	5117		
	9	No answer	25		
			5142		
X809	PARTICIPATION IN ELECTION 1998				Y627, U659, V673, jfr W523
	Did you vote in the 1998 elections?				
	1	Yes	4291	83,8	
	2	No	564	11,0	
	3	Not eligible to vote	266	5,2	
		Total	5121		
	9	No answer	21		
			5142		
X810	OTHER ASSOCIATIONS				Y629, jfr U670, jfr V683, jfr W500
	Do you belong to any other kind of association or organization than the ones above?				
	1	Yes	3183	62	
	2	No	1948	38	
		Total	5131		
	9	No answer	11		
			5142		
X811	ASSOCIATION ACTIVITIES				Y630
	How often, roughly, do you take part in organization activities? The table is valid for X810 NE 2.				
	1	Never or almost never	734	23,1	

	2	Once or twice a year	911	28,7	
	3	Once or twice a month	646	20,3	
	4	Once or twice a week	504	15,9	
	5	Several times a week	381	12,0	
		Total	3176		
	9	No answer	18		
		Not applicable	1948		
			5142		
X812		SERVICE LAST YEAR			Y631, U668, V681, jfr W499
		Have you been to a service in church at any time in the last year?			
	1	Yes	2336	45,6	
	2	No	2791	54,4	
		Total	5127		
	9	No answer	15		
			5142		
X813		SERVICE ACTIVITY			Y632, U669, V682, jfr W499
		How often do you attend services? The table is valid for X812 NE 2.			
	1	Maybe once a year	1278	54,8	
	2	A few times a year	639	27,4	
	3	About once a month	142	6,1	
	4	About twice a month	126	5,4	
	5	Once a week or more	147	6,3	
		Total	2332		
	9	No answer	19		
		Not applicable	2791		
			5142		
X814		TOOK PART IN DEMONSTRATION			jfr Y633, jfr U671, jfr V684, jfr W501
		Have you ever taken part in a public demonstration?			
	1	Yes	1371	26,8	
	2	No	3748	73,2	
		Total	5119		
	9	No answer	23		
			5142		
X815		PERSONAL CONTACT			Y634, U672, V685, W502
		Have you at any time contacted any person in responsible office in order to influence a decision on a public matter?			
	1	Yes	1079	21,1	
	2	No	4044	78,9	
		Total	5123		
	9	No answer	19		
			5142		
X816		SPOKEN IN MEETING			Y635, U673, V686, W503
		Have you ever addressed a meeting of an association or organization?			
	1	Yes, held a speech	1509	29,5	
	2	Yes, took part in a debate	713	13,9	
	3	No, never	2897	56,6	
		Total	5119		

	9 No answer	23	
		5142	
X817	WRITTEN IN NEWSPAPER		Y636, U674, V687, W504
	Have you ever written an article or letter to the editor of a newspaper or magazine?		
	1 Yes, article	527	10,3
	2 Yes, letter	650	12,7
	3 No, never	3945	77,0
	Total	5122	
	9 No answer	20	
		5142	
X818	POLITICAL PARTICIPATION		Y637, U675, V751, jfr W580, W599
	Index of political participation based on the questions in X814, X815, X816, X817 and index X805 and X808.		
	Index construction:		
	X818 = 9 if any of 6 variables has value 9		
	= 1 if no on all 6 variables		
	= 2 in other cases		
	1 Outsider	798	16
	2 Not outsider	4177	84
	Total	4975	
	9 No answer	167	
		5142	
X819	CAN COMPLAIN		Y638, U678, V689, W506
	Could you take it upon yourself to write a letter appealing against a decision made by a public authority? If no: Do you know anyone from whom you could get help in such a case?		
	10 Can do it	3528	68,9
	21 Can get help	1240	24,2
	22 No	350	6,8
	Total	5118	
	99 No answer	24	
		5142	
X820	HELP WHEN COMPLAINING		Y639
	Do you know where to turn to get help in a situation like this? The table is valid for X819 NE 10 or 21.		
	1 Yes	99	28,1
	2 No	253	71,9
	Total	352	
	9 No answer	22	
	Not applicable	4768	
		5142	
X821	AFFINITY TO THE WORKING CLASS		Y640
	People sometimes refer to the different social groups or classes in society, e.g. working class, middle class and upper middle class. Do you feel any affinity to the working class?		
	1 Very great affinity	1089	21,4
	2 Quite a lot of affinity	1817	35,7
	3 Not much affinity	891	17,5
	4 No affinity at all	378	7,4
	5 Doesn't feel that social classes exist	474	9,3
	8 Doesn't know	441	8,7
	Total	5090	

	9 No answer	52	
		5142	
X822	AFFINITY TO THE MIDDLE CLASS		Y641
	People sometimes refer to the different social groups or classes in society, e.g. working class, middle class and upper middle class. Do you feel any affinity to the middle class?		
	1 Very great affinity	672	13,2
	2 Quite a lot of affinity	2318	45,6
	3 Not much affinity	791	15,5
	4 No affinity at all	336	6,6
	5 Doesn't feel that social classes exist	487	9,6
	8 Doesn't know	483	9,5
	Total	5087	
	9 No answer	55	
		5142	
X823	AFFINITY TO THE UPPER MIDDLE CLASS		Y642
	People sometimes refer to the different social groups or classes in society, e.g. working class, middle class and upper middle class. Do you feel any affinity to the upper middle class?		
	1 Very great affinity	202	4,0
	2 Quite a lot of affinity	675	13,3
	3 Not much affinity	1268	25,0
	4 No affinity at all	1896	37,3
	5 Doesn't feel that social classes exist	487	9,6
	8 Doesn't know	553	10,9
	Total	5081	
	9 No answer	61	
		5142	
X824	SOCIETY WITH MORE PRIVATE ALTERNATIVES		jfr Y643
	I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go for in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society with more private alternatives within school, nursing and care?		
	1 Very good idea	718	14,1
	2 Rather good idea	1482	29,0
	3 Neither good nor bad	850	16,7
	4 Rather bad idea	1100	21,5
	5 Very bad idea	633	12,4
	8 Doesn't know	322	6,3
	Total	5105	
	9 No answer	37	
		5142	
X825	SOCIETY WITH SMALL INCOME DIFFERENCES		Y645
	I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go for in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society where income differences are small?		
	1 Very good idea	1008	19,7
	2 Rather good idea	1628	31,9
	3 Neither good nor bad	828	16,2
	4 Rather bad idea	1037	20,3
	5 Very bad idea	352	6,9
	8 Doesn't know	251	4,9
	Total	5104	

	9 No answer	38	
		5142	
X826	SOCIETY WITH MORE CARE WITHIN THE FAMILY		
	I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go or in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society where care for children and the elderly occurs to a greater extent within the family?		
	1 Very good idea	475	9,3
	2 Rather good idea	1090	21,4
	3 Neither good nor bad	1106	21,7
	4 Rather bad idea	1413	27,7
	5 Very bad idea	709	13,9
	8 Doesn't know	308	6,0
	Total	5101	
	9 No answer	41	
		5142	
X827	SOCIETY WITH GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FAMILY		
	I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go for in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society where men take as much responsibility for children and the household as women do?		
	1 Very good idea	2744	53,8
	2 Rather good idea	1530	30,0
	3 Neither good nor bad	413	8,1
	4 Rather bad idea	187	3,7
	5 Very bad idea	75	1,5
	8 Doesn't know	152	3,0
	Total	5101	
	9 No answer	41	
		5142	
X828	TROUBLESHOOTER		Y649
	Do you usually see a solution to problems and difficulties that other people find hopeless?		
	1 Yes, most often	1860	36,9
	2 Yes, sometimes	2821	56,0
	3 No	358	7,1
	Total	5039	
	9 No answer	103	
		5142	
X829	LIFE SATISFACTION		Y650
	Do you usually feel that your daily life is a source of personal satisfaction?		
	1 Yes, most often	2921	58,0
	2 Yes, sometimes	1757	34,9
	3 No	357	7,1
	Total	5035	
	9 No answer	107	
		5142	
X830	HARD TO UNDERSTAND		Y651
	Do you usually feel that things that happen to you in your daily life are hard to understand?		
	1 Yes, most often	181	3,6
	2 Yes, sometimes	1404	27,8

	3	No	3469	68,6
		Total	5054	
	9	No answer	88	
			5142	
X831	CONTROL OF OWN LIFE			Y652
	Do you usually feel that you are in control of your own life?			
	1	Yes, most often	3825	75,6
	2	Yes, sometimes	981	19,4
	3	No	253	5,0
		Total	5059	
	9	No answer	83	
			5142	
X832	RESPONDENT'S VALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION			Y647, U702
	We have now been through a lot of questions about your living conditions in different areas. How do you yourself view your own conditions? By and large, do you think that your situation is very good, rather good, rather bad, or very bad?			
	1	Very good	2186	42,8
	2	Rather good	2619	51,2
	3	Neither good nor bad	198	3,9
	4	Rather bad	81	1,6
	5	Very bad	28	0,5
		Total	5112	
	9	No answer	30	
			5142	
X833	HAS RESPONDENT'S CONDITIONS IMPROVED OR DETERIORATED			Y648, U703
	If you look back over the last ten years, do you think that your living conditions during this time have deteriorated, improved, or remained more or less the same?			
	1	Deteriorated	699	13,7
	2	Improved	2688	52,8
	3	Remained more or less the same	1708	33,5
		Total	5095	
	9	No answer	47	
			5142	
X835	NATIONALITY			Y654, U705
	Citizenship or year when respondent became a Swedish citizen			
X837	COUNTY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION			Y656, U707
	County according to current parish registration.			
	1		998	19,4
	3		160	3,1
	4		155	3,0
	5		231	4,5
	6		190	3,7
	7		117	2,3
	8		137	2,7
	9		30	0,6
	10		80	1,6
	12		614	11,9
	13		146	2,8

	14	897	17,4
	17	158	3,1
	18	183	3,6
	19	141	2,7
	20	173	3,4
	21	187	3,6
	22	146	2,8
	23	83	1,6
	24	161	3,1
	25	155	3,0
		5142	
X838	MUNICIPALITY FOR PARISH REGISTRATION		Y657, U708
	Municipality according to current parish registration. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1-9	108	2,1
	10-19	159	3,1
	20-29	252	4,9
	30-39	166	3,2
	40-49	78	1,5
	50-59	24	0,5
	60-69	497	9,7
	70-79	83	1,6
	80-89	3434	66,8
	90-99	341	6,6
		5142	
X839	DISTRICT/PARISH FOR PARISH REGISTRATION		Y658, U709
	District/parish according to current parish registration. This variable is divided into categories		
	1-9	3857	75,0
	10-19	624	12,1
	20-29	336	6,5
	30-39	228	4,4
	40-49	88	1,7
	50-59	4	0,1
	60-69	2	0,0
	70-79	1	0,0
	80-89	2	0,0
		5142	
X840	TYPE OF LOCALITY		Y659, U710, V820, W610
	Place of residence according to LKF, coded according to the municipal division 1967 using to the Metropolitan-Area-Criteria for the metropolitan areas.		
	1 Larger Stockholm area	879	17,1
	2 Larger Gothenburg area	375	7,3
	3 Larger Malmö area	218	4,2
	4 Towns > 30000	1107	21,5
	5 Urban districts	982	19,1
	6 Countryside	1581	30,7
		5142	
X841	H-REGION		Y660, jfr U728
	H-region, scope.		

	1 Sthlm, Södertälje	970	18,9	
	3 Medium sized cities	1909	37,1	
	4 Southern Sweden	927	18	
	5 Densely populated northern Sweden	288	5,6	
	6 Sparsely populated northern Sweden	276	5,4	
	8 Gothenburg	491	9,5	
	9 Malmö/Lund	281	5,5	
		5142		
X842	CIVIL STATUS			Y661, U715, V814, W704
	Civil status according to RTB.			
	1 Unmarried	1928	37,5	
	2 Married man, cohabitant	1224	23,8	
	3 Married woman, not cohabitant	26	0,5	
	4 Divorced	551	10,7	
	5 Widower, widow	171	3,3	
	6 Married man, not cohabitant	21	0,4	
	7 Married woman, cohabitant	1221	23,7	
		5142		
X843	SPOUSE YEAR OF BIRTH			Y663, U716
	Year of birth for respondent's spouse/partner according to RTB. This variable is divided into categories.			
	10-19	9	0,3	
	20-29	192	5,8	
	30-39	458	13,9	
	40-49	741	22,4	
	50-59	735	22,2	
	60-69	691	20,9	
	70-79	463	14,0	
	80-89	17	0,5	
	Total	3306		
	Not spouse	1836		
		5142		
X844	SPOUSE YEAR OF BIRTH FROM INTERVIEW			Y664
	Year of birth for respondent's spouse according to the interview. The variable is identical with X153. This variable is divided into categories.			
	10-19	8	0,2	
	20-29	194	5,5	
	30-39	457	13,1	
	40-49	759	21,7	
	50-59	777	22,2	
	60-69	764	21,8	
	70-79	524	15	
	80-89	17	0,5	
	Total	3500		
	99 No answer	2		
	Not cohabiting	1640		
		5142		
X845	RESPONDENT GROUP WEIGHT			jmf Y666, jfr U727, jfr V797, jfr W942
	This weight system gives the total selection 2000 adjusted to population with correction for dropout rates by sex, age, civil status, H-region. The table refers to the whole selection. The weight system does not make corrections			

for differences in sub-samples

800-899	208	4,0
900-999	328	6,4
1000-1099	599	11,6
1100-1199	1998	38,9
1200-1299	919	17,9
1300-1399	684	13,3
1400-1499	280	5,4
1500-1599	61	1,2
1700-1799	65	1,3
	5142	

X846

RESPONDENT GROUP WEIGHT B

**jmf Y666,
jfr U727, jfr
V797, jfr
W942**

Modification of X845. This weight system gives the total selection 2000 adjusted to population with correction for dropout rates by sex, age, civil status, H-region and salary. The table refers to the whole selection. The weight system does not make corrections for differences in sub-samples.

700-799	31	0,6
800-899	197	3,8
900-999	240	4,7
1000-1099	1321	25,7
1100-1199	1697	33,0
1200-1299	623	12,1
1300-1399	476	9,3
1400-1499	306	6,0
1500-1599	157	3,1
1600-1699	18	0,4
1700-1799	23	0,4
2000-2099	42	0,8
2500-2599	11	0,2
	5142	

X847

RESPONDENT GROUP WEIGHT C

**jmf Y666,
jfr U727, jfr
V797, jfr
W942**

Modification of X845. This weight system gives the total selection 2000 adjusted to population with correction for dropout rates by sex, age, civil status, H-region and salary classes. The table refers to the whole selection. The weight system does not make corrections for differences in sub-samples.

700-799	99	1,9
800-899	82	1,6
900-999	503	9,8
1000-1099	998	19,4
1100-1199	1430	27,8
1200-1299	1071	20,8
1300-1399	276	5,4
1400-1499	380	7,4
1500-1599	174	3,4
1600-1699	18	0,4
1700-1799	23	0,4
1800-1899	9	0,2
1900-1999	26	0,5
2000-2099	42	0,8
2500-2599	11	0,2
	5142	

X848

FATHER'S EGP

Y670

Father's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).

1	Ia Self-employed, higher grade professionals	14	0,3
2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	620	12,2
3	II Lower-grade professionals	480	9,5
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	301	5,9
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	147	2,9
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	368	7,3
7	IVb Small proprietors without employees	274	5,4
8	IVc Farmers	334	6,6
9	IVd Smallholders	238	4,7
10	Vs Supervisors	171	3,4
11	Vj Supervisors in primary production	23	0,5
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	901	17,8
13	VIj Skilled manual workers in primary production	3	0,1
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	1001	19,8
15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	191	3,8
	Total	5066	
99	Unclassified	76	
		5142	

X849

MOTHER'S EGP

Y671

Mother's profession/occupation according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).

2	Ib Higher-grade professionals	191	3,8
3	II Lower-grade professionals	448	8,8
4	IIIa Routine non-manual employees, higher grade	325	6,4
5	IIIb Routine non-manual employees, lower grade	678	13,3
6	IVa Small proprietors with employees	66	1,3
7	IVb Small proprietors without employees	63	1,2
8	IVc Farmers	156	3,1
9	IVd Smallholders	116	2,3
10	Vs Supervisors	20	0,4
12	VIs Skilled manual workers	75	1,5
14	VIIs Unskilled manual workers	882	17,4
15	VIIj Unskilled manual workers in primary production	42	0,8
92	Homemaker	201	39,7
		9	
	Total	508	
		1	
99	Unclassified	61	
		5142	

X1001

P – YEAR OF BIRTH

What year were you born?

15	1	0,0
17	2	0,1
18	2	0,1
20	1	0,0
21	6	0,2
22	8	0,3
23	5	0,2
24	17	0,6
25	16	0,6

26	16	0,6
27	24	0,9
28	22	0,8
29	29	1,1
30	18	0,7
31	37	1,4
32	35	1,3
33	26	0,9
34	48	1,8
35	39	1,4
36	43	1,6
37	42	1,5
38	41	1,5
39	37	1,4
40	36	1,3
41	61	2,2
42	60	2,2
43	57	2,1
44	70	2,6
45	67	2,4
46	67	2,4
47	69	2,5
48	53	1,9
49	67	2,4
50	67	2,4
51	58	2,1
52	50	1,8
53	59	2,2
54	67	2,4
55	75	2,7
56	64	2,3
57	60	2,2
58	64	2,3
59	54	2,0
60	46	1,7
61	60	2,2
62	61	2,2
63	55	2,0
64	55	2,0
65	73	2,7
66	62	2,3
67	59	2,2
68	69	2,5
69	34	1,2
70	51	1,9
71	66	2,4
72	64	2,3
73	40	1,5
74	51	1,9
75	36	1,3
76	33	1,2
77	28	1,0
78	24	0,9
79	16	0,6

	80	10	0,4
	81	3	0,1
	82	1	0,0
		2737	
X1002	P – SEX		
	Are you a man or a woman?		
	1 Man	1283	46,9
	2 Woman	1454	53,1
		2737	
X1003	P – NUMBER OF SIBLINGS, TOTAL		
	Do you have or have you had siblings?		
	1	871	34,7
	2	676	26,9
	3	400	15,9
	4	211	8,4
	5	118	4,7
	6	76	3,0
	7	67	2,7
	8	37	1,5
	9	23	0,9
	10	9	0,4
	11	9	0,4
	12	9	0,4
	13	2	0,1
	15	1	0,0
	Total	2509	
	99 No answer	17	
	Doesn't have siblings	211	
		2737	
X1004	P – BOTH PARENTS BORN IN SWEDEN		
	Were both of your parents born in Sweden?		
	1 No	457	16,8
	2 Yes	2269	83,2
	Total	2726	
	9 No answer	11	
		2737	
X1005	P – BIRTH COUNTRY – FATHER		
	What is the birth country of your father?		
	1 Sweden	2327	85,9
	2 Denmark, Norway	46	1,7
	3 Finland	101	3,7
	4 Former Yugoslavia (when defining Yug.)	43	1,6
	5 Other Eastern Europe, incl. former East Germany	31	1,1
	6 Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	42	1,5
	7 Spain, Italy, Greece	11	0,4
	8 Other nationalities	109	4,0
	Total	2710	

	9	Unknown	27	
			2737	
X1006	P – BIRTH COUNTRY – MOTHER			
	What is the birth country of your mother?			
	1	Sweden	2310	85,1
	2	Denmark, Norway	51	1,9
	3	Finland	118	4,3
	4	Former Yugoslavia (when defining Yug.)	42	1,5
	5	Other Eastern Europe, incl. former East Germany	28	1,0
	6	Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	50	1,8
	7	Spain, Italy, Greece	10	0,4
	8	Other nationalities	107	3,9
		Total	2716	
	9	Unknown	21	
			2737	
X1007	P – HOME LANGUAGE			
	During your childhood and adolescence, i.e., up to your 16th birthday, what language was spoken most in your home? The table is valid for X1004 EQ 1.			
	1	Swedish	148	32,5
	2	Danish, Norwegian	29	6,4
	3	Finnish	56	12,3
	4	Serbo-Croatian, Serbian, Croatian, Yugoslavian Other Eastern European languages, incl.	9	2,0
	5	Hungarian	18	4,0
	6	German	17	3,7
	7	English	9	2,0
	8	French, Spanish, Italian	16	3,5
	9	Other	119	26,2
	12		1	0,2
	13		9	2,0
	16		6	1,3
	19		2	0,4
	22		1	0,2
	56		1	0,2
	69		1	0,2
	78		2	0,4
	79		3	0,7
	99		8	1,8
		Total	455	
	11	No answer	13	
		Both parents born in Sweden	2269	
			2737	
		Two digits = a combination of two languages		
X1008	P – COUNTRY OF ORIGIN			
	Where were you born?			
	1	Sweden	2434	89,1
	2	Denmark, Norway	31	1,1
	3	Finland	64	2,3
	4	Former Yugoslavia (when defining Yug.)	42	1,5
	5	Other Eastern Europe, incl. former East Germany	19	0,7
	6	Germany, Austria and rest of Western Europe	27	1,0

7	Spain, Italy, Greece	9	0,3
8	Other nationalities	107	3,9
	Total	2733	
9	Unknown	4	
		2737	

X1009
P – AGE AT IMMIGRATION

How old were you when you came to Sweden? The table is valid for X1008 NE 1. This variable is divided into categories.

0		1	0,3
1-5		18	6,1
6-10		10	3,4
11-15		16	5,4
16-20		54	18,4
21-25		79	26,9
26-30		50	17,0
31-35		31	10,5
36-40		17	5,8
41-45		7	2,4
46-50		4	1,4
51-55		1	0,3
56-60		1	0,3
61-65		4	1,4
71-75		1	0,3
		294	
99	No answer	9	
	Born in Sweden	2434	
		2737	

X1010
P – FATHER - MOTHER LIVING

Are your mother and father still alive?

1	Yes, both are living	1162	42,6
2	Only my mother is living	589	21,6
3	Only my father is living	143	5,2
4	No, neither is living	836	30,6
	Total	2730	
9	No answer	7	
		2737	

X1011
P – INTACT CHILDHOOD FAMILY

Did you live with both your (biological) parents during your whole childhood?

10	Yes	2251	82,4
21	No, divorce/separation	293	10,7
22	No, parents never lived together	54	2,0
23	No, both parents deceased	8	0,3
24	No, father deceased	49	1,8
25	No, mother deceased	26	1,0
26	No, lived with foster parents	22	0,8
27	No, lived with adoptive parents	25	0,9
28	No, no information on reason	5	0,2
	Total	2733	
99	No answer	4	
		2737	

X1013	P – SEI FATHER		
	Father's main profession or occupation. Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	516	19,8
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	276	10,6
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	484	18,6
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	37	1,4
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	70	2,7
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	183	7,0
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	103	4,0
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	48	1,8
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	276	10,6
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	119	4,6
	57 Professional, upper-level executive	56	2,2
	60 Self-employed professional	65	2,5
	79 Self-employed, unknown number of employees	81	3,1
	86 Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	287	11,0
	Total	2601	
	99 Unclassified	136	
		2737	
X1014	P – NYK80 FATHER		
	Father's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.		
X1015	P – NYK85 FATHER		
	Father's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.		
X1017	P – SEI MOTHER		
	Mother's main profession or occupation. Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".		
	11 Unskilled manual worker, goods production	119	4,6
	12 Unskilled manual worker, service production	422	16,2
	21 Skilled manual worker, goods production	12	0,5
	22 Skilled manual worker, service production	92	3,5
	33 Low level, non-manual worker with routine tasks	148	5,7
	35 Low level, non-manual worker, supervisor of manual workers	22	0,8
	36 Low level, non-manual worker, without subordinates	91	3,5
	45 Intermediate level, non-manual worker, supervisors	14	0,5
	46 Intermediate non-manual worker, without subordinates	183	7,0
	56 Professional, higher non-manual worker	51	2,0
	57 Professional, upper-level executive	6	0,2
	60 Self-employed professional	20	0,8
	79 Self-employed, unknown number of employees	17	0,7
	89 Farmer, -20 hectares arable land	78	3,0
	92 Homemaker	1338	51,2
	Total	2613	
	99 Unclassified	124	
		2737	

X1018	P – NYK80 MOTHER		
		Mother's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.	
X1019	P – NYK85 MOTHER		
		Mother's main profession or occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.	
X1022	P – CONFLICTS IN CHILDHOOD FAMILY		
		Was there any serious friction in your family while you were growing up?	
	1	Yes	407 15,0
	2	No	2064 76,0
	3	Uncertain	246 9,1
		Total	2717
	9	No answer	20
			2737
X1023	P – PARTNER'S EDUCATION IN YEARS		
		How many years altogether have you been to school or a vocational training full-time?	
	0		6 0,2
	1		1 0,0
	3		1 0,0
	4		4 0,1
	5		10 0,4
	6		63 2,4
	7		199 7,4
	8		152 5,7
	9		193 7,2
	10		203 7,6
	11		358 13,4
	12		368 13,7
	13		263 9,8
	14		207 7,7
	15		201 7,5
	16		177 6,6
	17		131 4,9
	18		70 2,6
	19		29 1,1
	20		16 0,6
	21		8 0,3
	22		6 0,2
	23		3 0,1
	24		1 0,0
	25		2 0,1
	29		1 0,0
	30		1 0,0
	33		1 0,0
	39		2 0,1
	41		1 0,0
	44		1 0,0

	Total	2679	
	99 No answer	58	
		2737	
X1024	P – HIGHEST EDUCATION		jfr Y80, jfr V82, jfr W39
	Which of the following educational levels have you passed?		
	0 No education	22	0,8
	1 Elementary school	394	14,4
	2 Compulsory school	265	9,7
	3 Vocational and academic 2-year upper secondary school	1019	37,2
	4 3- to 4-year academic upper secondary program	219	8,0
	5 Post-secondary education	452	16,5
	6 University	349	12,8
	7 Postgraduate education	17	0,6
		2737	
X1025	P – NUMBER OF YEARS IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT		
	About how many years altogether have you spent in gainful employment? This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	3	0,1
	1-5	233	8,9
	6-10	265	10,1
	11-15	320	12,2
	16-20	310	11,9
	21-25	335	12,8
	26-30	325	12,4
	31-35	238	9,1
	36-40	250	9,6
	41-45	166	6,3
	46-50	133	5,1
	51-55	23	0,9
	56-60	10	0,4
	61-65	4	0,2
	Total	2615	
	99 No answer	70	
	Has never been gainfully employed	52	
		2737	
X1026	P – BEGAN WORKING: YEAR		
	What year and month did you begin the first job you had that lasted at least 6 months? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.		
	30-39	32	1,2
	40-49	199	7,6
	50-59	381	14,5
	60-69	487	18,5
	70-79	617	23,5
	80-89	562	21,4
	90-99	343	13,1
	2000	6	0,2
	Total	2627	
	9999 No answer	40	
	Has never been gainfully employed/Never had a job that lasted at least 6 months	70	
		2737	

X1031	P – OCCUPATION AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION																																																
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner?																																																
	<table> <tr><td>1</td><td>Employed, full-time</td><td>1899</td><td>71,1</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Employed, part-time</td><td>180</td><td>6,7</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Self-employed</td><td>126</td><td>4,7</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Unemployed</td><td>83</td><td>3,1</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Studying</td><td>306</td><td>11,5</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Working in the home</td><td>30</td><td>1,1</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Pensioner</td><td>9</td><td>0,3</td></tr> <tr><td>8</td><td>Other</td><td>38</td><td>1,4</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Total</td><td>2671</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9</td><td>No answer</td><td>66</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td>2737</td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	Employed, full-time	1899	71,1	2	Employed, part-time	180	6,7	3	Self-employed	126	4,7	4	Unemployed	83	3,1	5	Studying	306	11,5	6	Working in the home	30	1,1	7	Pensioner	9	0,3	8	Other	38	1,4		Total	2671		9	No answer	66				2737					
1	Employed, full-time	1899	71,1																																														
2	Employed, part-time	180	6,7																																														
3	Self-employed	126	4,7																																														
4	Unemployed	83	3,1																																														
5	Studying	306	11,5																																														
6	Working in the home	30	1,1																																														
7	Pensioner	9	0,3																																														
8	Other	38	1,4																																														
	Total	2671																																															
9	No answer	66																																															
		2737																																															
X1032	P – SEI AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION																																																
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".																																																
X1033	P – NYK80 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION																																																
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.																																																
X1034	P – NYK85 AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION																																																
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.																																																
X1035	P – EGP AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION																																																
	What was your main activity and occupation when you moved in with your present spouse/partner? Coded according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).																																																
X1036	P – YEAR/MONTH STARTED OCCUPATION HELD AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION																																																
	Can you specify approximately when you began the occupation you had when you began cohabiting? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.																																																
	<table> <tr><td>30-39</td><td></td><td>8</td><td>0,3</td></tr> <tr><td>40-49</td><td></td><td>106</td><td>4,6</td></tr> <tr><td>50-59</td><td></td><td>289</td><td>12,5</td></tr> <tr><td>60-69</td><td></td><td>472</td><td>20,5</td></tr> <tr><td>70-79</td><td></td><td>462</td><td>20,0</td></tr> <tr><td>80-89</td><td></td><td>565</td><td>24,5</td></tr> <tr><td>90-99</td><td></td><td>394</td><td>17,1</td></tr> <tr><td>2000</td><td></td><td>9</td><td>0,4</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Total</td><td>2305</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td>9999</td><td>No answer</td><td>178</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td>Had no profession</td><td>254</td><td></td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td><td>2737</td><td></td></tr> </table>	30-39		8	0,3	40-49		106	4,6	50-59		289	12,5	60-69		472	20,5	70-79		462	20,0	80-89		565	24,5	90-99		394	17,1	2000		9	0,4		Total	2305		9999	No answer	178			Had no profession	254				2737	
30-39		8	0,3																																														
40-49		106	4,6																																														
50-59		289	12,5																																														
60-69		472	20,5																																														
70-79		462	20,0																																														
80-89		565	24,5																																														
90-99		394	17,1																																														
2000		9	0,4																																														
	Total	2305																																															
9999	No answer	178																																															
	Had no profession	254																																															
		2737																																															
X1037	P – YEAR/MONTH LEFT OCCUPATION HELD AT START OF PRESENT COHABITATION																																																
	Can you specify approximately when you left the occupation you had when you began cohabiting? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.																																																

	40-49	5	0,4
	50-59	89	6,4
	60-69	198	14,3
	70-79	240	17,4
	80-89	291	21,1
	90-99	510	36,9
	2000	49	3,5
	Total	1382	
	9999 No answer	162	
	Had no profession/Partner has not quit profession	1193	
		2737	
X1038	P – SEI AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION		
	What occupation (or other activity) did you change to then? Coded according to the socio-economic classification system "Socioekonomisk indelning, SEI".		
X1039	P – NYK80 AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION		
	What occupation (or other activity) did you change to then? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1980 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). See x413 where there is a list of different occupations.		
X1040	P – NYK85 AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION		
	What occupation (or other activity) did you change to then? Occupation according to Nordic Occupational Classification from 1985 ("Nordisk yrkesklassificering, NYK"). A list of codes was published by SCB's Meddelanden i samordningsfrågor (Reports on Statistical Coordination) MIS 1989:5.		
X1041	P – EGP AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION		
	What profession (or other occupation) did you change to then? Coded according to Erikson, Goldthorpe and Portocarero (EGP).		
X1042	P – NUMBER OF TIMES CHANGED OCCUPATION AFTER START OF PRESENT COHABITATION		
	Have you changed occupation since then? If yes: How many times?		
	0	938	37,9
	1	655	26,5
	2	643	26,0
	5	236	9,5
	Total	2472	
	9 No answer	265	
		2737	
X1044	P – PRESENT OCCUPATION		jfr Y74, jfr U118, jfr V710
	What is your main occupation at present?		
	1 Employed, full-time	1348	49,7
	2 Employed, part-time	403	14,9
	3 Self-employed	237	8,7
	4 Unemployed	113	4,2
	5 Studying	121	4,5
	6 Working at home	30	1,1
	7 Pensioner	443	16,3
	8 Other	15	0,6
	Total	2710	
	9 No answer	27	

X1049**P – YEAR/MONTH BEGAN PRESENT OCCUPATION**

When did you begin this occupation? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.

30-39	2	0,2
40-49	11	0,8
50-59	36	2,7
60-69	117	8,8
70-79	176	13,3
80-89	331	25,0
90-99	549	41,4
2000	104	7,8
Total	1326	
-1 Has no profession	157	
9999 No answer	284	
Has no profession/Question not asked	970	
	2737	

X1050**P – IN GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT LAST WHEN**

When did you last engage in gainful employment lasting at least 6 months? Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.

40-49	1
50-59	2
60-69	8
70-79	9
80-89	47
90-99	354
2000	36
Total	457
9999 No answer	234
Is employed full- or part-time or self-employed	2046
	2737

X1051**P – EMPLOYED: PERMANENT EMPLOYMENT**

Are you permanently or temporarily employed?

1 Permanently	1576	90,3
2 Temporarily	170	9,7
Total	1746	
9 No answer	32	
Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
	2737	

X1052**P – WORKING HOURS OR SHIFT**

What are your normal working hours or what shift do you work?

1 Daytime, weekdays	1353	77,0
2 Evening, night, morning or Saturday/Sunday	147	8,4
3 2- or 3-shifts	93	5,3
4 Irregular passes per 24 hours and week	164	9,3
Total	1757	
9 No answer	21	
Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
	2737	

X1053

P – REGULAR WEEKLY WORKING TIME

jfr Y77, jfr
U111

How many hours do you usually work per week?

4	1	0,1
5	1	0,1
6	1	0,1
8	7	0,4
10	11	0,6
13	1	0,1
14	2	0,1
15	5	0,3
16	4	0,2
17	1	0,1
18	4	0,2
19	1	0,1
20	55	3,2
21	2	0,1
22	5	0,3
23	5	0,3
24	18	1,0
25	28	1,6
26	11	0,6
27	16	0,9
28	15	0,9
29	7	0,4
30	113	6,5
31	7	0,4
32	60	3,5
33	11	0,6
34	18	1,0
35	34	2,0
36	27	1,6
37	56	3,2
38	92	5,3
39	48	2,8
40	939	54,3
41	6	0,3
42	7	0,4
43	4	0,2
44	2	0,1
45	61	3,5
46	2	0,1
47	4	0,2
48	5	0,3
50	15	0,9
51	1	0,1
52	1	0,1
55	4	0,2
58	1	0,1
60	5	0,3
65	1	0,1
70	3	0,2
80	1	0,1
90	1	0,1

	Total	1730	
99	No answer	48	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
		2737	
	Mean value		36,94
	Standard deviation		7,35
X1054	P – SUITABLE WORKING TIME		
	Is your normal working time what suits you best or would you prefer shorter or longer working hours?		
	1 Present working hours best	1163	66,7
	2 Shorter hours better	501	28,7
	3 Longer hours better	80	4,6
	Total	1744	
9	No answer	34	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
		2737	
X1055	P – HOW OFTEN OVERTIME		
	How often do you work overtime in your present job? Is it...		
	1 Never	446	25,6
	2 A few times a year	286	16,4
	3 A few times a month	484	27,8
	4 A couple of times a week	280	16,1
	5 Several times a week	243	14,0
	Total	1739	
9	No answer	39	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
		2737	
X1056	P – OVERTIME PER YEAR		
	About how many hours overtime is that altogether in a year? The table is valid for X1055 EQ 2. This variable is divided into categories.		
	1-9	10	3,9
	10-19	54	20,9
	20-29	65	25,2
	30-39	31	12,0
	40-49	29	11,2
	50-59	31	12,0
	60-69	10	3,9
	70-79	2	0,8
	80-89	4	1,6
	90-99	2	0,8
	100-109	10	3,9
	110-119	2	0,8
	120-129	3	1,2
	200-209	5	1,9
	Total	258	
999	No answer	66	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present /Doesn't work overtime	2413	
		2737	
	Mean value		37,10

Standard deviation		33,91	
X1057	P – OVERTIME PER MONTH		
About how many hours overtime is that altogether in a month? The table is valid for X1055 EQ 3. This variable is divided into categories.			
1-9		273	59,1
10-19		152	32,9
20-29		32	6,9
30-39		1	0,2
40-49		1	0,2
50-59		1	0,2
60-69		2	0,4
	Total	462	
999	No answer	61	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present		
	/Doesn't work overtime	2214	
		2737	
	Mean value		8,27
	Standard deviation		6,77
X1058	P – OVERTIME PER WEEK		
About how many hours overtime is that altogether in a week? The table is valid for X1055 EQ 4,5. This variable is divided into categories.			
1-9		387	78,2
10-19		89	18,0
20-29		14	2,8
30-39		2	0,4
50-59		3	0,6
	Total	495	
99	No answer	67	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present		
	/Doesn't work overtime	2175	
		2737	
	Mean value		6,09
	Standard deviation		5,79
X1059	P – ON-THE-JOB TRAINING		
Have you in the last 12 months had any kind of education on paid work-time?			
1	Yes	817	46,7
2	No	933	53,3
	Total	1750	
9	No answer	28	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
		2737	
X1060	P – NUMBER OF DAYS ON-THE-JOB TRAINING		
If yes: How many working days altogether was this education? (One whole day is 8 hours.) The table is valid for X1059 EQ 1. This variable is divided into categories.			
0		2	0,3
1-9		596	75,2
10-19		131	16,5
20-29		25	3,2
30-39		10	1,3
40-49		7	0,9

	50-59	5	0,6
	60-69	2	0,3
	70-79	1	0,1
	80-89	1	0,1
	90-99	2	0,3
	100-109	3	0,4
	120-129	2	0,3
	150-159	1	0,1
	200-209	2	0,3
	240-249	1	0,1
	250-259	1	0,1
	360-365	1	0,1
	Total	793	
	999 No answer	52	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present/ Did not receive education	1892	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		9,49
	Standard deviation		23,94
	Mean value >0		9,51
	Standard deviation		23,96
X1061	P – OPPORTUNITIES FOR ADVANCEMENT IN CURRENT JOB		
	How good are the opportunities for advancement in a job like yours?		
	1 Very good	123	7,1
	2 Fairly good	458	26,3
	3 Fairly poor	722	41,5
	4 Very poor	438	25,2
	Total	1741	
	9 No answer	37	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
		2737	
X1062	P – FLEXIBLE WORKING HOURS		
	Do you have any kind of flexible working hours?		
	1 Yes	981	56,7
	2 No	750	43,3
	Total	1731	
	9 No answer	47	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
		2737	
X1063	P – CAN DETERMINE PACE OF WORK		
	Can you yourself determine your pace of work?		
	1 Yes	1019	59,8
	2 No	685	40,2
	Total	1704	
	9 No answer	74	
	Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
		2737	
X1064	P – MENTALLY TAXING		
	Is your work mentally taxing?		

	1	Yes	921	55,6
	2	No	734	44,4
		Total	1655	
	9	No answer	123	
		Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
			2737	
X1065		P – STRESSFUL WORK		
		Is your work stressful?		
	1	Yes	1217	73,3
	2	No	443	26,7
		Total	1660	
	9	No answer	118	
		Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
			2737	
X1066		P – MONOTONOUS WORK		
		Is your work monotonous?		
	1	Yes	227	13,8
	2	No	1413	86,2
		Total	1640	
	9	No answer	138	
		Self-employed/Doesn't have a job at present	959	
			2737	
1067		P – TRAVEL TIME MINUTES		
		How long does it usually take you to commute to and from work on a normal workday? This variable is divided into categories.		
	0	No commute/live at workplace	74	3,9
	1-9		87	4,6
	10-19		314	16,7
	20-29		300	16,0
	30-39		313	16,7
	40-49		212	11,3
	50-59		76	4,0
	60-69		214	11,4
	70-79		32	1,7
	80-89		45	2,4
	90-99		54	2,9
	100-109		34	1,8
	110-119		6	0,3
	120-129		71	3,8
	130-139		6	0,3
	140-149		6	0,3
	150-159		10	0,5
	160-169		5	0,3
	170-179		2	0,1
	180-189		15	0,8
	200-209		1	0,1
	210-219		1	0,1
		Total	1879	
	997	Have no permanent workplace	105	
	999	No answer	32	

Doesn't have a job at present	722	
	2737	
Mean value for all		40,56
Standard deviation		34,92
Mean value >0		42,23
Standard deviation		34,63

1068

P – NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME BECAUSE OF WORK: NUMBER OF NIGHTS/YEAR

Do you ever stay away from home overnight because of your work, e.g., on a business trip? If yes: About how many nights are you away altogether during one year's time? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	296	45,3
10-19	152	23,3
20-29	65	10,0
30-39	46	7,0
40-49	19	2,9
50-59	16	2,5
60-69	11	1,7
70-79	12	1,8
80-89	6	0,9
90-99	3	0,5
100-109	7	1,1
120-129	2	0,3
140-149	1	0,2
150-159	6	0,9
160-169	1	0,2
170-179	1	0,2
180-189	4	0,6
200-209	2	0,3
240-249	2	0,3
250-259	1	0,2
Total	653	
999 No answer	41	
Doesn't have a job at present/No nights away from home	2043	
	2737	
Mean value for all		21,33
Standard deviation		34,55

X1069

P – EDUCATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Is any schooling or vocational training above elementary schooling necessary for your job?

1 Yes	1430	72,7
2 No	537	27,3
Total	1967	
9 No answer	48	
Doesn't have a job at present	722	
	2737	

X1070

P – SCHOOL YEARS ABOVE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

If yes: About how many years of education above elementary school are necessary for your job?

1	85	6,5
2	173	13,2
3	452	34,6
4	157	12,0
5	85	6,5

6	155	11,9
7	81	6,2
8	67	5,1
9	11	0,8
10	25	1,9
11	3	0,2
12	3	0,2
13	2	0,2
14	1	0,1
15	5	0,4
16	1	0,1
Total	1306	
99 No answer	172	
Doesn't have a job at present /No education above elementary school	1259	
	2737	

X1071

P – SUPERVISORY TASKS

Do you have any supervisory tasks?

1 Yes	525	26,6
2 No	1447	73,4
Total	1972	
9 No answer	43	
Doesn't have a job at present	722	
	2737	

X1072

P – NUMBER OF SUBORDINATES

If yes: How many persons do you supervise? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	42	9,0
10-19	141	30,1
20-29	96	20,5
30-39	51	10,9
40-49	46	9,8
50-59	26	5,6
60-69	19	4,1
70-79	22	4,7
80-89	11	2,4
90-99	2	0,4
100-109	2	0,4
110-119	2	0,4
140-149	1	0,2
190-199	1	0,2
260-269	1	0,2
300-309	3	0,6
400-409	1	0,2
>900	1	0,2
Total	468	
999 No answer	100	
Doesn't have a job at present/No supervisory tasks	2169	
	2737	

X1073

P – GROSS MONTHLY SALARY

What is your usual monthly salary from your regular employment? (Gross salary) The table is valid for no answer on X1074. This variable is divided into categories.

1-999	1	0,1
1000-1999	1	0,1
2000-2999	2	0,1
3000-3999	8	0,5
4000-4999	3	0,2
5000-5999	6	0,4
6000-6999	6	0,4
7000-7999	21	1,3
8000-8999	25	1,5
9000-9999	28	1,7
10000-10999	48	2,9
11000-11999	50	3,0
12000-12999	53	3,2
13000-13999	59	3,6
14000-14999	109	6,6
15000-15999	125	7,6
16000-16999	134	8,1
17000-17999	117	7,1
18000-18999	120	7,3
19000-19999	92	5,6
20000-29999	449	27,1
30000-39999	125	7,6
40000-49999	34	2,1
50000-59999	16	1,0
60000-69999	9	0,5
70000-79999	3	0,2
80000-89999	2	0,1
90000-99999	1	0,1
100000-199999	4	0,2
200000-299999	2	0,1
500000-599999	1	0,1
Total	1654	
999999 No answer	153	
Doesn't have a job at present	930	
	2737	
Mean value		20674,54
Standard deviation		17627,92

X1074

P – NET MONTHLY SALARY

What is your usual monthly salary from your regular employment? (Net salary). The table is valid for no answer on X1073. This variable is divided into categories.

1000-1999	2	1,0
2000-2999	2	1,0
3000-3999	3	1,4
4000-4999	5	2,4
5000-5999	7	3,4
6000-6999	12	5,8
7000-7999	16	7,7
8000-8999	21	10,1
9000-9999	18	8,7
10000-10999	37	17,8
11000-11999	14	6,7
12000-12999	27	13,0
13000-13999	12	5,8

14000-14999	8	3,8	
15000-15999	8	3,8	
16000-16999	4	1,9	
17000-17999	1	0,5	
18000-18999	1	0,5	
19000-19999	2	1,0	
20000-29999	5	2,4	
50000-59999	1	0,5	
70000-79999	1	0,5	
80000-89999	1	0,5	
Total	208		
Doesn't have a job at present	2529		
	2737		
Mean value		11152,46	
Standard deviation		7913,95	
X1075	P –PHYSICALLY EXHAUSTED		
	Are you physically exhausted after work?		
1 Yes, always	76	3,9	
2 Yes, most of the time	197	10,0	
3 Yes, sometimes	792	40,3	
4 No, seldom	596	30,3	
5 No, never	304	15,5	
Total	1965		
9 No answer	50		
Doesn't have a job at present	722		
	2737		
X1076	P – MENTALLY EXHAUSTED		
	Are you mentally exhausted after work?		
1 Yes, always	67	3,4	
2 Yes, most of the time	274	14,0	
3 Yes, sometimes	985	50,4	
4 No, seldom	417	21,3	
5 No, never	213	10,9	
Total	1956		
9 No answer	59		
Doesn't have a job at present	722		
	2737		
X1077	P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 1999: NUMBER OF WEEKS		jfr Y78, jfr U112, jfr V71 jfr W41-43
	Were you gainfully employed during calendar year 1999? If yes: How many weeks during 1999?		
2	3	0,2	
3	4	0,2	
4	14	0,8	
5	9	0,5	
6	8	0,4	
7	5	0,3	
8	15	0,8	
9	4	0,2	
10	24	1,3	
11	6	0,3	
12	15	0,8	

13	5	0,3
14	5	0,3
15	6	0,3
16	14	0,8
17	4	0,2
18	3	0,2
19	1	0,1
20	45	2,5
22	10	0,6
24	14	0,8
25	19	1,1
26	13	0,7
27	1	0,1
28	9	0,5
29	1	0,1
30	22	1,2
31	1	0,1
32	9	0,5
34	6	0,3
35	18	1,0
36	15	0,8
37	3	0,2
38	18	1,0
39	6	0,3
40	98	5,4
41	6	0,3
42	38	2,1
43	7	0,4
44	29	1,6
45	93	5,2
46	103	5,7
47	224	12,5
48	212	11,8
49	37	2,1
50	72	4,0
51	15	0,8
52	510	28,3
Total	1799	
99 No answer	370	
Not gainfully employed during 1999	568	
	2737	
Mean value		42,83
Standard deviation		12,33

X1078

P – GAINFUL EMPLOYMENT 1999: HOURS/WEEK

Were you gainfully employed during calendar year 1999? If yes: Number of hours/week on average? This variable is divided into categories.

1-9	26	2,0
10-19	39	3,1
20-29	124	9,8
30-39	279	22,0
40-49	672	52,9
50-59	88	6,9
60-69	27	2,1

	70-79	14	1,1
	80-89	2	0,2
	Total	1271	
99	No answer	898	
	Not gainfully employed during 1999	568	
		2737	
	Mean value		37,8
	Standard deviation		10,6
X1079	P – PREVIOUSLY COHABITING		
	Have you previously been married or cohabiting for at least 6 months?		
	1 No	1985	73,1
	2 Yes	730	26,9
	Total	2715	
	9 No answer	22	
		2737	
X1080	P – NUMBER OF PREVIOUS COHABITATIONS		
	If yes: How many times have you previously been married or cohabiting for at least 6 months? The table is valid for X1079 EQ 2.		
	1	560	79,4
	2	116	16,5
	3	16	2,3
	4	9	1,3
	5	1	0,1
	7	1	0,1
	8	2	0,3
	Total	705	
	9 No answer	47	
	Not been cohabiting previously	1985	
		2737	
X1081	P – YEAR/MONTH LAST COHABITATION ENDED		
	If yes: When did your most recent marriage/cohabitation of at least 6 months end, i.e. when did you split up? The table is valid for X1079 EQ 2. Only year is shown. This variable is divided into categories.		
	40-49	1	0,1
	50-59	10	1,5
	60-69	30	4,4
	70-79	113	16,5
	80-89	226	33,0
	90-99	302	44,1
	2000	3	0,4
	Total	685	
	9999 No answer	67	
	Not been cohabiting previously	1985	
		2737	
X1082	P – CHILDREN NOT IN HOME		
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children?		
	1	139	42,4
	2	129	39,3
	3	38	11,6
	4	15	4,6

	5	5	1,5
	6	2	0,6
	Total	328	
9	No answer	144	
	No absent children with previous partner	2265	
		2737	
	Mean value		1,85
	Standard deviation		0,97
X1083	P – NUMBER OF YOUNG CHILDREN NOT LIVING IN THE HOUSEHOLD		
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children born 1994 or later?		
	0	314	95,7
	1	14	4,3
	Total	328	
9	No answer	144	
	No absent children with previous partner	2265	
		2737	
X1084	P – NUMBER OF SCHOOLCHILDREN NOT LIVING IN THE HOUSEHOLD		
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children born between 1982 and 1993?		
	0	268	81,7
	1	41	12,5
	2	16	4,9
	3	1	0,3
	4	2	0,6
	Total	328	
9	No answer	144	
	No absent children with previous partner	2265	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		0,26
	Standard deviation		0,62
	Mean value for >0		1,40
	Standard deviation		0,69
X1085	P – NUMBER OF ADULT CHILDREN NOT LIVING IN THE HOUSEHOLD		
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: How many children born between 1974 and 1981?		
	0	53	16,2
	1	119	36,3
	2	105	32,0
	3	35	10,7
	4	11	3,4
	5	4	1,2
	6	1	0,3
	Total	328	
9	No answer	144	
	No absent children with previous partner	2265	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		1,54
	Standard deviation		1,09
	Mean value for >0		1,83
	Standard deviation		0,94

X1086	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 1 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 1 not living in your household born? This variable is divided into categories.	
	40-49	14 4,4
	50-59	44 13,8
	60-69	99 31,1
	70-79	97 30,5
	80-89	38 11,9
	90-99	26 8,2
	Total	318
	Not applicable	2419
		2737
X1087	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 2 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 2 not living in your household born? This variable is divided into categories.	
	40-49	6 3,2
	50-59	16 8,5
	60-69	66 35,1
	70-79	65 34,6
	80-89	22 11,7
	90-99	13 6,9
	Total	188
	Not applicable	2549
		2737
X1088	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 3 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 3 not living in your household born? This variable is divided into categories.	
	40-49	2 3,4
	50-59	7 11,9
	60-69	20 33,9
	70-79	20 33,9
	80-89	9 15,3
	90-99	1 1,7
	Total	59
	Not applicable	2678
		2737
X1089	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 4 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 4 not living in your household born? This variable is divided into categories.	
	40-49	1 4,8
	60-69	7 33,3
	70-79	7 33,3
	80-89	5 23,8
	90-99	1 4,8
	Total	21
	Not applicable	2716
		2737
X1090	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 5 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD	
	Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child	

5 not living in your household born?			
47		1	16,7
62		1	16,7
64		1	16,7
72		1	16,7
73		1	16,7
82		1	16,7
Total		6	
Not applicable		2731	
		2737	
X1091	P – YEAR OF BIRTH CHILD 6 NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD		
Do you have children with a previous partner, children who do not live with you now? If yes: What year is child 6 not living in your household born?			
50		1	100,0
Not applicable		2736	
		2737	
X1092	P – RELATIONS CHILDREN NOT IN THE HOUSEHOLD		
About how often do you see this child/any of these children? The table is valid for value on X1082.			
1	Several times a week	59	18,3
2	About once a week	65	20,2
3	1-3 times a month	106	32,9
4	Less often	67	20,8
5	Never	25	7,8
Total		322	
9	No answer	150	
No absent children with previous partner		2265	
		2737	
X1093	P – PAYS MAINTENANCE PER MONTH		
Do you pay maintenance for this child/any of these children? If yes: How much do you pay altogether per month? (Kronor per month.)			
100-499		5	10,2
500-999		6	12,2
1000-1499		20	40,8
1500-1999		7	14,3
2000-2499		7	14,3
2500-2999		4	8,2
Total		49	
9999	No answer	140	
No absent children with previous partner/Doesn't pay maintenance		2548	
		2737	
Mean value			1367,78
Standard deviation			658,96
X1094	P – RECEIVES MAINTENANCE PER MONTH		
Do you receive any maintenance for children in your household, children you have with a previous partner? If yes: How much do you receive altogether per month? (SEK per month.)			
100-499		1	1,9
500-999		1	1,9
1000-1499		29	54,7

1500-1999		1	1,9
2000-2499		17	32,1
2500-2999		2	3,8
3500-3999		2	3,8
	Total	53	
99999	No answer	4	
	No absent children with previous partner/Doesn't receive maintenance	2680	
		2737	
	Mean value		1644,25
	Standard deviation		689,86

X1095

P – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE

Do you normally help a family member or relative outside your household with personal care and housework?

1	Yes	419	16,1
2	No	2183	83,9
	Total	2602	
9	No answer	135	
		2737	

X1096

P – HOURS – HELPS FAMILY MEMBER OR RELATIVE

If yes: On average, about how many hours per week altogether do you spend doing this? This variable is divided into categories. The table is valid for X1095 EQ 1.

1-4		301	74,9
5-9		72	17,9
10-14		18	4,5
15-19		3	0,7
20-24		4	1,0
25-29		1	0,2
30-34		2	0,5
>90		1	0,2
	Total	402	
99	No answer	152	
	Doesn't help family member/relative	2183	
	Total	2335	
		2737	
	Mean value		3,83
	Standard deviation	6,05	

X1097

P – HOURS P – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES

About how many hours on average are spent buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in your household? Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.

0		163	6,2
1-4		944	36,1
5-9		719	27,5
10-14		493	18,9
15-19		143	5,5
20-24		105	4,0
25-29		24	0,9
30-34		9	0,3
35-39		7	0,3
40-44		4	0,2
45-49		1	0,0

50-54		2	0,1
	Total	2614	
99	No answer	123	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		6,94
	Standard deviation		6,14
	Mean value for >0		7,40
	Standard deviation		6,06

X1098

P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES

About how many hours on average are spent buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.

0		380	14,6
1-4		1070	41,1
5-9		655	25,2
10-14		335	12,9
15-19		69	2,7
20-24		67	2,6
25-29		12	0,5
30-34		7	0,3
35-39		6	0,2
60-64		1	0,0
	Total	2602	
99	No answer	135	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		5,22
	Standard deviation		5,42
	Mean value for >0		6,11
	Standard deviation		5,37

X1099

P – HOURS CHILDREN – BUYING GROCERIES, COOKING, WASHING DISHES

About how many hours on average are spent buying groceries, cooking and washing dishes in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours possible children (in the household) spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0		1011	76,8
1		165	12,5
2		79	6,0
3		18	1,4
4		9	0,7
5		20	1,5
6		3	0,2
7		2	0,2
8		1	0,1
10		8	0,6
	Total	1316	
	No answer	48	
	No children in the household	1373	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		0,48
	Standard deviation		1,25
	Mean value for >0		2,08
	Standard deviation		1,85

X1100**P – HOURS P – CARE OF CLOTHING**

About how many hours on average are spent on laundry, ironing and other care of clothing in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.

0	644	24,6
1-4	1418	54,2
5-9	438	16,7
10-14	94	3,6
15-19	11	0,4
20-24	8	0,3
25-29	1	0,0
50-54	1	0,0
Total	2615	
99 No answer	122	
	2737	
Mean value for all		2,74
Standard deviation		3,07
Mean value for >0		3,63
Standard deviation		3,04

X1101**P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CARE OF CLOTHING**

About how many hours on average are spent on laundry, ironing and other care of clothing in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.

0	963	37,0
1-4	1130	43,4
5-9	372	14,3
10-14	115	4,4
15-19	6	0,2
20-24	14	0,5
30-34	2	0,1
60-64	1	0,0
Total	2603	
99 No answer	134	
	2737	
Mean value for all		2,43
Standard deviation		3,37
Mean value for >0		3,86
Standard deviation		3,54

1102**P – HOURS CHILDREN – CARE OF CLOTHING**

About how many hours on average are spent on laundry, ironing and other care of clothing in your household?
Can you indicate about how many hours possible children (in the household) spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)

0	1153	87,6
1	112	8,5
2	27	2,1
3	8	0,6
4	5	0,4
5	8	0,6
6	1	0,1
7	1	0,1
10	1	0,1
Total	1316	

	99	No answer	48	
		No children in the household	1373	
			2737	
		Mean value for all		0,21
		Standard deviation		0,73
		Mean value for >0		1,67
		Standard deviation		1,36
X1103		P – HOURS P – CLEANING		
		About how many hours on average are spent on cleaning in your household? Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.		
		0	308	11,8
		1-4	1767	67,6
		5-9	413	15,8
		10-14	97	3,7
		15-19	11	0,4
		20-24	10	0,4
		25-29	3	0,1
		30-34	2	0,1
		35-39	1	0,0
		40-44	2	0,1
		50-54	1	0,0
		Total	2615	
	99	No answer	122	
			2737	
		Mean value for all		3,02
		Standard deviation		3,37
		Mean value for >0		3,43
		Standard deviation		3,39
X1104		P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – CLEANING		
		About how many hours on average are spent on cleaning in your household? Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.		
		0	625	24,0
		1-4	1566	60,2
		5-9	315	12,1
		10-14	78	3,0
		15-19	8	0,3
		20-24	7	0,3
		25-29	2	0,1
		30-34	1	0,0
		60-64	1	0,0
		Total	2603	
	99	No answer	134	
			2737	
		Mean value for all		2,41
		Standard deviation		3,01
		Mean value for >0		3,17
		Standard deviation		3,08
X1105		P – HOURS CHILDREN – CLEANING		
		About how many hours on average are spent on cleaning in your household? Can you indicate about how many hours possible children spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)		
		0	886	67,3

1	311	23,6
2	78	5,9
3	18	1,4
4	7	0,5
5	9	0,7
6	1	0,1
7	1	0,1
10	4	0,3
33	1	0,1
Total	1316	
99 No answer	48	
No children in the household	1373	
	2737	
Mean value for all		0,52
Standard deviation		1,34
Mean value for >0		1,58
Standard deviation		1,94

X1106

P – HOURS P – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE

About how many hours on average are spent on repair and maintenance of your residence, motor vehicle and other property belonging to the household? Can you indicate about how many hours you spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.

0	1050	40,2
1-4	1168	44,7
5-9	218	8,3
10-14	109	4,2
15-19	25	1,0
20-24	28	1,1
25-29	7	0,3
30-34	5	0,2
40-44	2	0,1
Total	2612	
99 No answer	125	
	2737	
Mean value for all		2,25
Standard deviation		3,93
Mean value for >0		3,76
Standard deviation		4,49

X1107

P – HOURS SPOUSE/PARTNER – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE

About how many hours on average are spent on repair and maintenance of your residence, motor vehicle and other property belonging to the household? Can you indicate about how many hours your spouse/partner spends? (Approx. number of hours per week.) This variable is divided into categories.

0	1057	40,7
1-4	1170	45,0
5-9	232	8,9
10-14	88	3,4
15-19	24	0,9
20-24	20	0,8
25-29	3	0,1
30-34	4	0,2
40-44	2	0,1
Total	2600	
99 No answer	137	

		2737	
	Mean value for all		2,09
	Standard deviation		3,65
	Mean value for >0		3,51
	Standard deviation		4,18
X1108	P – HOURS CHILDREN – REPAIR AND MAINTENANCE		
	About how many hours on average are spent on repair and maintenance of your residence, motor vehicle and other property belonging to the household? Can you indicate about how many hours possible children (in the household) spend? (Approx. number of hours per week.)		
	0	1241	94,3
	1	53	4,0
	2	14	1,1
	3	2	0,2
	4	1	0,1
	5	3	0,2
	6	1	0,1
	10	1	0,1
	Total	1316	
	99 No answer	48	
	No children in the household	1373	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		0,09
	Standard deviation		0,51
	Mean value for >0		1,63
	Standard deviation		1,45
X1109	P – RECEIVES HELP WITH HOUSEWORK		
	Does someone living outside your household do housework in your home?		
	1 No	2552	94,6
	2 Yes	147	5,4
	Total	2699	
	9 No answer	38	
		2737	
X1110	P – HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OWN CHILDREN NOT LIVING AT HOME		
	If yes: approximate number of hours per week that respondent's own children (not living in household) do housework in respondent's home. The table is valid for X1109 NE 1.		
	0	134	91,8
	1	5	3,4
	2	1	0,7
	3	1	0,7
	4	1	0,7
	5	2	1,4
	10	1	0,7
	30	1	0,7
	Total	146	
	99 No answer	39	
	Doesn't get help	2552	
	Total	2591	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		0,44
	Standard deviation		2,70
	Mean value for >0		5,33

Standard deviation		8,22	
X1111	P – HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PARENTS		
Approximate number of hours per week that respondent's parents do housework in respondent's home. The table is valid for X1109 NE 1.			
0	87	59,6	
1	24	16,4	
2	14	9,6	
3	4	2,7	
4	6	4,1	
5	3	2,1	
7	1	0,7	
9	1	0,7	
10	2	1,4	
14	1	0,7	
18	1	0,7	
20	1	0,7	
25	1	0,7	
Total	146		
99 No answer	39		
Doesn't get help	2552		
	2737		
Mean value for all		1,48	
Standard deviation		3,56	
Mean value for>0		3,66	
Standard deviation		4,86	
X1112	P – HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER FAMILY MEMBER/RELATIVE		
Approximate number of hours per week that respondent's family member/relative does housework in respondent's home. The table is valid for X1109 NE 1.			
0	128	87,7	
1	5	3,4	
2	9	6,2	
3	1	0,7	
4	1	0,7	
5	1	0,7	
6	1	0,7	
Total	146		
99 No answer	39		
Doesn't get help	2552		
	2737		
Mean value for all		0,28	
Standard deviation		0,89	
Mean value for>0		2,28	
Standard deviation		1,41	
X1113	P – HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM MUNICIPAL HOME-HELP SERVICE		
Approximate number of hours per week that a municipal home-help service does housework in respondent's home The table is valid for X1109 NE 1.			
0	144	98,6	
1	1	0,7	
2	1	0,7	
Total	146		
9 No answer	39		

	Doesn't get help	2552	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		0,02
	Standard deviation		0,18
	Mean value for>0		1,50
	Standard deviation		0,71
X1114	P – HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM PRIVATELY PAID HOME-HELP SERVICE		
	Approximate number of hours per week that a privately paid home-help service does housework in respondent's home. The table is valid for X1109 NE 1.		
	0	89	61,0
	1	5	3,4
	2	22	15,1
	3	14	9,6
	4	10	6,8
	5	2	1,4
	6	2	1,4
	8	1	0,7
	10	1	0,7
	Total	146	
99	No answer	39	
	Doesn't get help	2552	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		1,17
	Standard deviation		1,79
	Mean value for>0		3,00
	Standard deviation		1,65
X1115	P – HOURS – HOUSEHOLD HELP FROM OTHER		
	Approximate number of hours per week that someone other than above does housework in respondent's home. The table is valid for X1109 NE 1.		
	0	142	97,9
	2	2	1,4
	3	1	0,7
	Total	145	
99	No answer	40	
	Doesn't get help	2552	
		2737	
	Mean value for all		0,05
	Standard deviation		0,34
	Mean value for>0		2,33
	Standard deviation		0,58
X1116	P – DIFFERENT OPINIONS DIVISION OF HOUSEWORK		
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to division of housework?		
	1 Often	200	7,6
	2 Sometimes	709	26,8
	3 Seldom	1041	39,3
	4 Never	699	26,4
	Total	2649	
9	No answer	88	
		2737	

X1117	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS USE OF MONEY		
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to the use of money?		
	1 Often	99	3,7
	2 Sometimes	504	19,1
	3 Seldom	1103	41,7
	4 Never	939	35,5
	Total	2645	
	9 No answer	92	
		2737	
X1118	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS WHO YOU KEEP COMPANY WITH		
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to who you keep company with as a couple?		
	1 Often	30	1,1
	2 Sometimes	212	8,0
	3 Seldom	943	35,8
	4 Never	1452	55,1
	Total	2637	
	9 No answer	100	
		2737	
X1119	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS CHILD RAISING		
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to child raising?		
	1 Often	60	2,3
	2 Sometimes	391	15,1
	3 Seldom	843	32,7
	4 Never	624	24,2
	5 Not applicable	663	25,7
	Total	2581	
	9 No answer	156	
		2737	
X1120	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH SPOUSE/PARTNER WORKS		
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to how much your spouse/partner works?		
	1 Often	103	3,9
	2 Sometimes	362	13,8
	3 Seldom	755	28,7
	4 Never	1158	44,1
	5 Not applicable	250	9,5
	Total	2628	
	9 No answer	109	
		2737	
X1121	P – DIFFERENT OPPINIONS HOW MUCH P WORKS		
	How often do your opinions and those of your spouse/partner differ with respect to how much you work?		
	1 Often	112	4,3
	2 Sometimes	415	15,8
	3 Seldom	701	26,6
	4 Never	1138	43,2
	5 Not applicable	267	10,1

	Total	2633	
	9 No answer	104	
		2737	
X1122	P – CASH MARGIN		
	If a situation suddenly arose where you had to come up with 12 000 kronor, could you manage it?		
	1 No	239	8,8
	2 Yes	2479	91,2
	Total	2718	
	9 No answer	19	
		2737	
X1123	P – ACQUIRING CASH		
	If yes: How would you manage to come up with 12 000 kronor in a week? The table is valid for X1122 NE 1.		
	1 Withdrawal from own bank account	1498	61,0
	2 Sale of stocks, fund shares or the like	404	16,4
	3 Loan from family member	211	8,6
	4 Loan from other relatives or friends	182	7,4
	5 Bank loan or equivalent	159	6,5
	6 Other way	2	0,1
	Total	2456	
	9 No answer	42	
	Could not acquire money	239	
		2737	
X1124	P – GENERAL HEALTH		
	How do you judge your general state of health?		
	1 Good	1927	71,3
	2 Bad	81	3,0
	3 Something in-between	695	25,7
	Total	2703	
	9 No answer	34	
		2737	
X1125	P – HEADACHE		
	Have you in the last 12 months had headaches?		
	1 No	1004	37,5
	2 Yes, mild	1478	55,1
	3 Yes, severe	198	7,4
	Total	2680	
	9 No answer	57	
		2737	
X1126	P – GENERAL TIREDNESS		
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from general tiredness?		
	1 No	919	34,1
	2 Yes, mild	1554	57,6
	3 Yes, severe	224	8,3
	Total	2697	
	9 No answer	40	
		2737	

X1127	P – INSOMNIA		
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from insomnia?		
	1 No	1807	67,0
	2 Yes, mild	766	28,4
	3 Yes, severe	123	4,6
	Total	2696	
	9 No answer	41	
		2737	
X1128	P – POOR VISION		
	Have you in the last 12 months had poor vision/disease of the eyes not helped by eyeglasses?		
	1 No	2439	91,1
	2 Yes, mild	198	7,4
	3 Yes, severe	41	1,5
	Total	2678	
	9 No answer	59	
		2737	
X1129	P – IMPAIRED HEARING		
	Have you in the last 12 months had impaired hearing?		
	1 No	2201	81,7
	2 Yes, mild	408	15,1
	3 Yes, severe	85	3,2
	Total	2694	
	9 No answer	43	
		2737	
X1130	P – ACHEs IN SHOULDERS/SHOULDER BLADES		
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches in shoulders or shoulder blades?		
	1 No	1309	48,5
	2 Yes, mild	1043	38,7
	3 Yes, severe	345	12,8
	Total	2697	
	9 No answer	40	
		2737	
X1131	P – STOMACH PAINS		
	Have you in the last 12 months had stomach pains?		
	1 No	1842	68,5
	2 Yes, mild	719	26,7
	3 Yes, severe	130	4,8
	Total	2691	
	9 No answer	46	
		2737	
X1132	P – PAIN IN BACK/HIPS		
	Have you in the last 12 months had backache, pain in back or hips, sciatica?		
	1 No	1354	50,2
	2 Yes, mild	1010	37,4
	3 Yes, severe	334	12,4

	Total	2698	
	9 No answer	39	
		2737	
X1133	P – OVEREXERTION		
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from overexertion?		
	1 No	1980	74,1
	2 Yes, mild	584	21,9
	3 Yes, severe	107	4,0
	Total	2671	
	9 No answer	66	
		2737	
X1134	P – ACHEs IN JOINTS		
	Have you in the last 12 months had aches/pain in hands, elbows, legs or knees?		
	1 No	1597	59,3
	2 Yes, mild	834	30,9
	3 Yes, severe	264	9,8
	Total	2695	
	9 No answer	42	
		2737	
X1135	P – NERVOUS TROUBLE		
	Have you in the last 12 months had nervous trouble (anxiety, uneasiness, anguish)?		
	1 No	2058	76,4
	2 Yes, mild	547	20,3
	3 Yes, severe	90	3,3
	Total	2695	
	9 No answer	42	
		2737	
X1136	P – DEPRESSIONS		
	Have you in the last 12 months suffered from depressions or deep dejection?		
	1 No	2399	89,0
	2 Yes, mild	228	8,5
	3 Yes, severe	68	2,5
	Total	2695	
	9 No answer	42	
		2737	
X1137	P – MENTAL ILLNESS		
	Have you in the last 12 months had a mental illness?		
	1 No	2652	98,5
	2 Yes, mild	25	0,9
	3 Yes, severe	15	0,6
	Total	2692	
	9 No answer	45	
		2737	
X1138	P – INDEX FOR PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING		
	Logical index based on dichotomisation of the answers on the questions about psychological well-being (X1126 general tiredness, X1127 insomnia, X1135 nervous trouble and X1136 depressions) where No="No" and		

Yes="Yes, mild" and "Yes, severe". Any variable non-response equals value 99.

1	718	26,9
2	2	0,1
3	39	1,5
4	122	4,6
5	770	28,8
6	4	0,1
7	1	0,0
8	25	0,9
9	22	0,8
10	161	6,0
11	371	13,9
12	6	0,2
13	77	2,9
14	35	1,3
15	177	6,6
16	140	5,2
Total	2670	
99 No answer	67	
	2737	

X1139

P – PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING

Scale based on the logical index X1138, where X1138=1, 4, 5 gives the value 1, X1138=2, 9 gives the value 2, X1138=3, 6, 10, 13 gives the value 3, X1138=7, 8, 12 gives the value 4 and X1138=11, 14, 15, 16 gives the value 5. Any variable non-response equals value 9.

1 Normal	1610	60,3
2 Tiredness	24	0,9
3 Nervous	281	10,5
4 Insomnia	32	1,2
5 Depressions	723	27,1
Total	2670	
9 No answer	67	
	2737	

X1140

P – OLLE'S PSYCHOLOGICAL INDEX

Added index based on the questions about psychological well-being (X1126 general tiredness + X1127 insomnia + X1135 nervous trouble + X1136 depressions + X1133 overextension), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 3. Any variable non-response equals value 99.

0 No trouble	665	25,2
1 1 mild trouble	741	28,0
2 2 mild trouble	493	18,7
3 1 severe, 3 mild	283	10,7
4 1 severe + 1 mild, 4 mild	178	6,7
5 1 severe + 2 mild, 5 mild	85	3,2
6 2 severe, 1 severe + 3 mild	49	1,9
7 2 severe + 1 mild, 1 severe + 4 mild	48	1,8
8 2 severe + 2 mild	22	0,8
9 3 severe, 2 severe + 3 mild	25	0,9
10 3 severe + 1 mild	17	0,6
11 3 severe + 2 mild	16	0,6
12 4 severe	5	0,2
13 4 severe + 1 mild	8	0,3
15 5 severe	7	0,3
Total	2642	

	99 No answer	95	
		2737	
X1141	P – ACHE IN THE LOCOMOTOR SYSTEM		
	Added index based on the questions about ache in the locomotor system (X1130 aches in shoulders/shoulder blades + X1132 pain in back/hips + X1134 aches in joints), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 2. Any variable non-response equals value 9.		
	0 No trouble	690	25,8
	1 1 mild trouble	635	23,7
	2 2 mild, 1 severe	582	21,7
	3 1 severe + 1 mild, 3 mild	416	15,5
	4 1 severe + 2 mild, 2 severe	180	6,7
	5 2 severe + 1 mild	89	3,3
	6 3 severe	85	3,2
	Total	2677	
	9 No answer	60	
		2737	
X1142	P – OLLE'S INDEX FOR ACHE		
	Added index based on the questions about ache in the locomotor system (X1130 aches in shoulders/shoulder blades + X1132 pain in back/hips + X1134 aches in joints), where "No" is coded 0, "Yes, mild" is coded 1 and "Yes, severe" is coded 3. Any variable non-response equals value 10.		
	0 No trouble	690	25,8
	1 1 mild trouble	635	23,7
	2 2 mild trouble	471	17,6
	3 1 severe, 3 mild	380	14,2
	4 1 severe + 1 mild	147	5,5
	5 1 severe + 2 mild	120	4,5
	6 2 severe	60	2,2
	7 2 severe + 1 mild	89	3,3
	9 3 severe	85	3,2
	Total	2677	
	10 No answer	60	
		2737	
X1143	P – DRINKS WINE, LIQUOR ETC		
	Do you at any time drink wine, strong beer or liquor?		
	1 Yes	2475	90,9
	2 No	247	9,1
	Total	2722	
	9 No answer	15	
		2737	
X1144	P – NUMBER OF TIMES DRINKS WINE LIQUOR ETC		
	If yes: during the last 12 months, about how often have you consumed wine, strong beer or liquor? The table is valid for X1143 EQ 1.		
	1 Daily	48	2,0
	2 2-4 times a week	385	15,7
	3 Once a week	619	25,2
	4 2-3 times a month	627	25,6
	5 Once a month	307	12,5
	6 6-11 times a year	186	7,6
	7 Less often	270	11,0
	8 Never	12	0,5
	Total	2454	

	9	No answer		36	
		Doesn't drink alcohol		247	
				2737	
X1145		P – NUMBER OF GLASSES			
		If yes: On such occasions, how many glasses do you usually drink? The table is valid for X1143 EQ 1 and X1144 NE 8.			
		0	2	0,1	
		1	487	20,1	
		2	1010	41,7	
		3	461	19,0	
		4	200	8,3	
		5	121	5,0	
		6	61	2,5	
		7	14	0,6	
		8	33	1,4	
		10	24	1,0	
		12	1	0,0	
		14	1	0,0	
		15	3	0,1	
		16	1	0,0	
		20	2	0,1	
		Total	2421		
	99	No answer	57		
		Doesn't drink alcohol	259		
			2737		
		Mean value for all		2,64	
		Standard deviation		1,76	
		Mean value >0		2,64	
		Standard deviation		1,76	
X1146		P – SOCIETY WITH MORE PRIVATE ALTERNATIVES			
		I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go for in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society with more private alternatives within school, nursing and care?			
		1	Very good idea	372	13,8
		2	Rather good idea	689	25,6
		3	Neither good nor bad	509	18,9
		4	Rather bad idea	507	18,9
		5	Very bad idea	430	16,0
		6	Doesn't know	181	6,7
		Total		2688	
		9	No answer	49	
				2737	
X1147		P – SOCIETY WITH SMALL INCOME DIFFERENCES			
		I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go for in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society where income differences are small?			
		1	Very good idea	505	18,8
		2	Rather good idea	759	28,2
		3	Neither good nor bad	504	18,8
		4	Rather bad idea	517	19,2
		5	Very bad idea	248	9,2
		6	Doesn't know	154	5,7

	Total	2687	
9	No answer	50	
		2737	
X1148	P - SOCIETY WITH MORE CARE WITHIN THE FAMILY		
	I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go for in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society where care for children and the elderly occurs to a greater extent within the family?		
	1	Very good idea	210 7,8
	2	Rather good idea	519 19,3
	3	Neither good nor bad	683 25,5
	4	Rather bad idea	681 25,4
	5	Very bad idea	428 16,0
	6	Doesn't know	162 6,0
	Total	2683	
	9	No answer	54
		2737	
X1149	P – SOCIETY WITH GENDER EQUALITY IN THE FAMILY		
	I am now going to present four ideas about different kinds of societies, which some people think we should go for in Sweden in the future. I would like to know what you think about these ideas. What do you think of the idea of going for a society where men take as much responsibility for children and the household as women do?		
	1	Very good idea	1139 42,3
	2	Rather good idea	944 35,1
	3	Neither good nor bad	392 14,6
	4	Rather bad idea	95 3,5
	5	Very bad idea	44 1,6
	6	Doesn't know	79 2,9
	Total	2693	
	9	No answer	44
		2737	
X1150	P – AFFINITY TO THE WORKING CLASS		
	People sometimes refer to the different social groups or classes in society, e.g. working class, middle class and upper middle class. Do you feel any affinity to the working class?		
	1	Very great affinity	697 26,9
	2	Quite a lot of affinity	902 34,8
	3	Not much affinity	454 17,5
	4	No affinity at all	175 6,8
	5	Doesn't feel that social classes exist	172 6,6
	6	Doesn't know	192 7,4
	Total	2592	
	9	No answer	145
		2737	
X1151	P – AFFINITY TO THE MIDDLE CLASS		
	People sometimes refer to the different social groups or classes in society, e.g. working class, middle class and upper middle class. Do you feel any affinity to the middle class?		
	1	Very great affinity	427 16,6
	2	Quite a lot of affinity	1286 50,0
	3	Not much affinity	386 15,0
	4	No affinity at all	92 3,6
	5	Doesn't feel that social classes exist	173 6,7
	6	Doesn't know	207 8,1

	Total	2571	
	9 No answer	166	
		2737	
X1152	P – AFFINITY TO THE UPPER MIDDLE CLASS		
	People sometimes refer to the different social groups or classes in society, e.g. working class, middle class and upper middle class. Do you feel any affinity to the upper middle class?		
	1 Very great affinity	104	4,2
	2 Quite a lot of affinity	340	13,9
	3 Not much affinity	695	28,4
	4 No affinity at all	899	36,7
	5 Doesn't feel that social classes exist	162	6,6
	6 Doesn't know	251	10,2
	Total	2451	
	9 No answer	286	
		2737	
X1153	P –P:S VALUATION OF HIS/HER SITUATION		
	How do you yourself view your own living conditions? By and large what do you think about your situation?		
	1 Very good	1108	40,9
	2 Rather good	1389	51,2
	3 Neither good nor bad	177	6,5
	4 Rather bad	33	1,2
	5 Very bad	4	0,1
	6 Doesn't know	2711	
	Total	26	
	9 No answer	2737	
X1154	P – TODAY'S DATE		
	Date – year, month and day – when the interview was carried out. Only months is shown. For interviews carried out 2000 year is also shown.		
	1	1	0,0
	2	1	0,0
	3	183	6,7
	4	443	16,3
	5	476	17,5
	6	360	13,2
	7	91	3,3
	8	97	3,6
	9	276	10,2
	10	454	16,7
	11	179	6,6
	12	36	1,3
	101	63	2,3
	0002	47	1,7
	0003	9	0,3
	0004	1	0,0
	Total	2717	
	999 No answer	20	
		2737	